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Adoption of Maize (*Zea mays L*) Production Technologies in Karimnagar District of Telangana

N Venkateshwar Rao¹, P K Jain², N Kishor Kumar³ and M Jagan Mohan Reddy⁴

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ABSTRACT

The present paper highlights the adoption levels of farmers of maize production technologies in Karimnagar (Telangana). Total 90 farmers were selected for study. High extent of adoption of maize production technologies was observed among the Krishi Vigyan Kendra adopted farmers compared to the non adopted farmers.

Key Words: Adoption, Farmers, Maize, Production technologies.

INTRODUCTION

The full scale application of technologies is considered as adoption. A farmer is to understand, analyze and satisfy before implement of technologies. Technology adoption is a graded process in which a farmer has to pass through different stages like awareness, interest, evaluation, training and adoption. Adoption is a holistic process where in farmer has to understand the intrinsic as well as extrinsic factors effecting the technology adoption. Maize being one of the important crops of Karimnagar district, the study was undertaken to know the adoption level of production technologies of maize by the farmers in KVK adopted villages.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ex-post facto research design combined with exploratory type of research design was used as

the selected phenomena have already occurred and the researcher had no control over the same. Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Jammikunta (Telangana) along with its 15 adopted villages was selected for the study. A sample of 60 maize growing farmers who were adopting recommended technologies and 30 maize farmers who did adopt production technologies were selected from the KVK adopted villages.

A schedule was developed to know the adoption level of the maize production technologies by the farmers which was measured on 3 point continuum i.e. fully adopted, partially adopted and non adopted with the scores of 3, 2, 1 respectively. Accordingly the respondents were grouped on the basis of percentage.

Table 1. Extent of adoption level of maize production technologies.

Category	KVK adopted farmers (n=60)			Non adopted farmers (n=30)		
	Low (33-55)	Medium (56-78)	High (79-100)	Low (33-55)	Medium (56-78)	High (79-100)
Frequency	18	20	22	16	6	8
Percentage	30.0	33.3	36.7	53.3	20.0	26.7

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It was observed from (Table1) that majority (36.7%) of the KVK adopted farmers had high extent of adoption whereas, majority (53.3%) of the KVK non-adopted farmers had low extent of adoption. The results were in tune with finding of Kharatmol (2006).

The data (Table 2 & 3) indicated that ranks were assigned to all the technologies based on

the total score obtained on each technology. The technologies on which the respondents had high extent of adoption were zero tillage, weed management with recommended herbicides, stem borer management with carbofuron granules were ranked 1st followed by providing irrigation at critical stages and stem borer control (2nd), selection of suitable cultivar, optimum time of sowing, optimum seed rate and management of

Table 2. Extent of adoption of maize production technologies by adopted farmers.

Sr. No.	Production technology	Extent of adoption (%)			Mean score	Rank
		Fully adopted	Partially adopted	Not adopted		
1	Proper weeding in the early stages of crop growth, Spraying of atrazine 2.5kg/ha in 500l of water as pre emergence immediately after sowing, application of 5kg carbofuron granules at knee high stage, In zero tillage timely sowing, higher returns due to lesser cost of cultivation, spraying of atrazine @ 2.5kg and paraquat @ 2.5l per hectare after sowing, less water is required as compared with normal maize cultivation and paddy stubbles will be harvested closer to the ground.	100.0	0.0	0.0	3.00	I
2	Providing irrigation at critical stages, spraying of endosulfan @ 2 ml/l of water at 12th and 19th day after sowing.	96.6	0.0	3.4	2.93	II
3	Selection of suitable cultivar, optimum seed rate, timely sowing, application of zinc sulphate.	83.4	16.6	0.0	2.83	III
4	Wilt management with <i>Trichoderma viridi</i> 5kg/ha with 250kg FYM at the time of sowing, hybrid seed production.	75.0	16.7	8.3	2.66	IV
5	Soil samples collected up to 15-20cm depth for soil testing, soil test based fertilizer application, Sowing of DHM 117 hybrid developed by ANGRAU.	50.0	25.0	25.0	2.25	V

Maize Production Technologies in Karimnagar

Table 3. Extent of adoption of maize production technologies by non-adopted farmers.

Sr. No.	Production technology	Extent of adoption			Mean score	Rank
		Fully adopted	Partially adopted	Not adopted		
1	Proper weeding, spraying of atrazine 2.5kg/ha in 500l of water as pre emergence immediately after sowing.	93.3	0.0	6.7	2.86	I
2	Timely sowing.	83.4	16.6	0.0	2.80	II
3	Sowing of DHM 117 maize hybrid developed by ANGRAU, Application of 5kg carbofuron granules at knee high stage, in zero tillage timely sowing, higher returns due to lesser cost of cultivation, spraying of atrazine @ 2.5kg and paraquat @ 2.5l per hectare after sowing, less water is required as compared with normal maize cultivation and paddy stubbles will be harvested closer to the ground.	83.4	8.3	8.3	2.50	III
4	Providing irrigation at critical stages, application of zinc sulphate 50 kg/ha/year.	66.7	33.3	0.0	2.33	IV
5	Hybrid seed production.	66.7	0.0	33.3	2.30	V
6	Selection of suitable cultivar, spraying of endosulfan @ 2 ml/l of water at 12th and 19th day after sowing, optimum seed rate, wilt management with application of <i>Trichoderma viridi</i> 5kg/ha with 250kg FYM at the time of sowing.	50.0	0.0	50.0	2.00	VI
7	Soil samples collected up to 15-20cm depth for soil testing, Soil test based fertilizer application.	0.0	50.0	50.0	1.50	VII

zinc deficiency (3rd), hybrid seed production, wilt management (4th), soil sample collection, soil test based fertilizer application, usage of DHM 117 hybrid (5th), respectively, whereas, most of the non adopted KVK farmers opt for practices like weed management with recommended herbicides are ranked 1st followed by timely sowing to reduce pest incidence (2nd), stem borer management with

carbofuran granules, practicing of zero tillage (3rd), providing irrigations at critical stages, management of zinc deficiency (4th), hybrid seed production (5th), selection of suitable cultivar, optimum seed rate, wilt management (6th), respectively.

KVK adopted farmers in maize crop had high adoption on zero tillage, weed management with herbicides, stem borer management with

carbofuron granules, providing irrigation at critical stages, practicing selection of suitable cultivar, optimum time of sowing, usage of optimum seed rate, management of zinc deficiency, hybrid seed production, wilt management etc. The reasons for high extent of adoption on the above technologies is KVK scientists envisaged the maize farmers by conducting series of trainings, demonstrations by practically involving the adopted farmers. KVK scientists also conducted farmer–scientist interactions, field days and group discussions which facilitated high extent of adoption of the above technologies. In zero tillage, KVK assessed this technology for 2 years and demonstrated in farmers fields with farmer field school approach. Given wide publicity through electronic and print media, publishing booklets, using local cable net work which helped the farmers for high extent of adoption in zero tillage.

Most of the non adopted farmers had high extent of adoption on weed management with herbicides, timely sowing to reduce pest incidence, stem borer management with carbofuron granules, providing irrigation at critical stages, management of zinc deficiency, hybrid seed production etc. The reasons for high extent of adoption on above technologies might be that fellow adopted farmers influenced and motivated the non adopted farmers. Some of the non adopted farmers were also participated in extension activities, electronic and print media also

facilitated the non adopted farmers to adopt the above technologies. The non adopted farmers had lowest extent of adoption on soil test based fertilizer application due to lack of awareness, motivation and inspiration.

CONCLUSION

High extent of adoption of maize production technologies was seen among the farmers adopted by the KVK Jammikunta compared to the non adopted farmers. This could be due to the multiplicity of the transfer of technology mechanisms followed by the KVK scientists in the adopted villages especially for the benefit of farmers adopted by the KVK.

REFERENCES

- Anonymous(2002). Comparison of cost and returns per hectare maize, wheat, mustard and cotton. *Agricultural Situation in India* **24**(2): 73-78.
- Kharatmol (2006). *Impact of trainings conducted on vermicompost by Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Bijapur*. M. Sc. (Ag.) Thesis, Univ. Agric. Sci., Dharwad.
- Sharma M L, Chauhan M S and Sharma P N (1997). Impact of Krishi Vigya Kendra on Maize Growers. *Maharashtra J Extn Edu* **16**: 335-336.
- Sharma A and Sharma B M (1999). Association between knowledge of farmers about important extension programme of KVK and selected independent variable. *Rural India* 279-281.

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Assessment of Infestation by *Sesamia inferens* on Wheat Varieties under different Tillage Conditions

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ABSTRACT

Field trials were conducted at farmers' field (Bahircap, Balupur Barnapara and Pulbanda villages) of Ratua 1 block, Malda, West Bengal, India (25°13'1.51"N latitude and 87°55'29.02"E latitude) during rabi season of 2013-2014 to assess the infestation of pink stem borer and varietal performance of wheat under different tillage condition. Among the eleven varieties, DBW17 (0.75% and 1.06%), DBW39 (1% and 1.94%) and CBW 38 (1.75% and 0.94%) and K307 (2% and 1%) showed better tolerance against stem borer infestation in both conventional and zero tillage condition, respectively. The infestation was comparatively more at maturity under zero tillage condition.

Key Words: Pink Stem Borer, Wheat, Varieties, Tillage.

INTRODUCTION

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) is the second most important cereal crop next to rice according to acreage however it is at third position next to rice and maize according to production. The system of wheat cultivation i.e. zero tillage has the immediate advantage of reduced cost of tillage. The pest scenario of wheat cultivation is also undergoing change with the change in tillage system. Though pink stem borer (*Sesamia inferens* Walker) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) originally a pest of rice (Pathak and Khan, 1994), is an established pest of wheat due to adoption of this tillage system of sowing of wheat crop in North-Western plains of India and causes major damage by feeding inside the stem causing dead hearts at tillering stage and empty white heads at ripening stage and ultimately reduced yield by more than 11 per cent in India (Saxena *et al*, 1972). Signs of damage in wheat were similar to those recorded in rice and damage caused by larvae of this insect is expressed as "dead hearts" at seedling stage and "white ears" at ear-head stage (Deol, 2002).

It occasionally causes heavy losses in restricted areas. From an estimate, it was found that every one

per cent increase in stem borers' incidence at the vegetative phase resulted in a loss of 0.28 per cent yield in rice (Jaipal *et al*, 2005). In Rajasthan, 5.7 to 11.1 per cent infestation has been recorded in wheat varietal trials (Singh, 1986). A lot of work on the effect of tillage conditions on agronomic parameters is available in literature (Azam *et al*, 2008) but very little information is available regarding their effect on insect pests. Thus survey were carried out on wheat grown under different tillage conditions during the last years which indicated medium to high damage caused by pink stem borer in sporadic early sown zero tilled wheat fields in north-western plains of India (Anonymous, 2008).

Indiscriminate use of synthetic pesticide for controlling a pest resulted in problems including pest resistance, pest outbreak, pest resurgence, environmental pollution and finally health hazard to consumers. To overcome these problems, resistant varieties are now being used in many developed and developing countries for combating the pest infestations with the aim of increasing cereal production because the use of resistant varieties in pest management is considered to be commercial and safer as compared to the chemical insecticides.

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Very few sources of resistance (BAW 743 and BAW 769) are available in literature against this pest (Ahad *et al*, 2002). The present study was under taken to assess infestation by pink stem borer on different wheat Varieties grown under different tillage conditions

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The field experiment was conducted at farmers' field of Bahircap, Balupur Barnapara and Pulbanda villages of Ratua 1 block, Malda, West Bengal, India (25°13'1.51"N latitude and 87°55'29.02"E latitude) during rabi season of 2013-14 and 2014-15. Eleven varieties of wheat were evaluated against stem borer in correlation with the stage of the crop and different tillage condition. The eleven varieties were DBW 39, DBW 17, PBW 621, CBW 38, Sonalika, K 307, HD 2687, HD 2827, Francolin, Gautam and PBW 343. The seeds were sown during last week of November, 2013 and 3rd week of November, 2014 with recommended dose of fertilizer at the time of land preparation. The varieties were treated as treatments and locations as replications. Two methods of tillage operations were done in this experiment i.e. conventional and zero tillage. In conventional tillage the plot area was 0.27 ha to 0.47 ha with 20 cm row to row spacing, while in zero tillage sowing was done by 11 tyne seed drill with the plot size 50 sq.m. Three irrigations were given at 21, 42 and 75 DAS in both the tillage systems. Here, the infestation at later stage of the crop was recorded because infestation of pink stem borer was gradually increased in mature stage compared to early stage as reported by Shawkhatuzzama *et al* (2013). The infestation was recorded just after 1st flowering and before 50 per cent flowering stage of the crop i.e. 84-90 DAS and after that the observation was taken at weekly interval up to the harvest of the crop by direct counting the white ear-head per plant per square meter area. The percentage of infestation was calculated by the formula:

$$\text{Percentage of infestation} = \frac{\text{Number of white ear-head}}{\text{Number of total plants counted}} \times 100$$

No pesticides were applied during the course of study and for these fields only regular management tactics (cultural, prophylactic, etc.) were used. Percentage of infestation was compared by using correlation coefficient (IBM SPSS Statistics Data Editor software, version 19.0; SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA) in both tillage conditions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Per cent of infestation by pink stem borer in respect to stage of the crop

Considering the pooled mean, it was evident that mean per cent infestation of pink stem borer was higher at maturity stage than the early stage in all eleven varieties in both the years. Ahad *et al*. (1995) reported the similar results that the pink borer infested wheat field only at the later stage of plants resulting in white head symptoms.

Per cent of infestation by pink stem borer in different tillage conditions

The mean per cent infestation of pink stem borer was comparatively more in zero tillage plots as compared to conventional tillage plots as shown in (Table 1). Higher incidence of pink stem borer in zero tillage was also reported by Razzaq *et al* (1997) and Singh (2012). It may be due to incomplete destruction of the rice stubbles that have remained in the field even after ploughing several times as described by Inayatullah *et al* (1989). Literature also proved that medium to high damage caused by pink stem borer in sporadic early sown zero tilled wheat fields in north-western plains of India (Anonymous, 2008).

It was observed that under conventional tillage condition, amongst the eleven varieties of wheat, pooled mean per cent of stem borer infestation was highest in HD2687 (5%) followed by HD2827 (4.75%). The lowest mean per cent of stem borer infestation was noticed in DBW17 as depicted in Table 1. Likewise, under zero tillage condition, the highest pooled mean per cent of stem borer infestation was observed in PBW343 (7.19%) among the eleven varieties of wheat followed by PBW621 (4%). The mean per cent of stem borer infestation was lowest in CBW 38 (0.94%).

Infestation of *Sesamia inferens* in Wheat

Table 1. Pooled data of the effect of infestation of stem borer under conventional and zero tillage conditions.

Sr. No.	Variety	Conventional tillage condition		Zero tillage condition	
		Mean per cent infestation by Stem Borer	Yield (q/ha)	Mean per cent infestation by Stem Borer	Yield (q/ha)
1.	DBW 39	1.0	23.6	1.94	25.1
2.	DBW 17	0.75	23.4	1.06	27.3
3.	PBW 621	1.5	14.2	4.0	18.5
4.	CBW 38	1.75	12.0	0.94	30.7
5.	Sonalika	2.0	9.0	3.31	24.0
6.	K 307	2.0	22.0	1.00	30.0
7.	HD 2687	5.0	17.2	1.75	14.6
8.	HD 2827	4.75	12.8	2.00	29.9
9.	Francolin	4.0	15.2	1.00	23.1
10.	Gautam	1.0	16.4	1.75	12.9
11.	PBW 343	2.5	15.4	7.19	14.7

CONCLUSION

Among the eleven wheat varieties/lines, in general, none of them was found to be resistant to pink stem borer. However, DBW17 showed better tolerance followed by DBW39, CBW38 and K307 at later stage irrespective of tillage condition. From the experiment, it can be inferred that DBW17, DBW39, CBW 38 and K307 were found comparatively promising against pink stem borer infestation.

REFERENCES

- Ahad M A, Talukder F A and Shahjahan M (1995). Influence of wheat varieties and sowing times on the infestation rate of *Sesamia inferens* W. *Bangladesh J Trg and Dev* **8**: 73-76.
- Anonymous (2008). Wheat crop health newsletter. Directorate of Wheat Research, Karnal. 14(2): pp 1. www. dwr.in
- Anonymous (2011). Project Director's Report. All India Coordinated Wheat and Barley Improvement Project, pp 3.
- Azam M G, Zoebisch Micheal A and Wickramarachchi Kanchana S (2008). Effects of cropping systems on selected soil structural properties and crop yields in the Lam Phra Phloeng watershed-Northeast Thailand. *J Agron* **7**: 56-62.
- Deol G S (2002). Latest trends for insect-pest management in wheat. Proceedings of Specialized Workshop on Identification and Management of Weeds, Insect-Pests and Diseases in Wheat. February 20-22, 2002, CETWPT, P.A.U., Ludhiana.
- Inayatullah C, Ehasan-ul-Haq, Ata-ul-Mohsin and Rehman A and Hobbs P R (1989). *Management of Rice Stem borers and the Feasibility of adopting Zero-tillage in Wheat*. Pak-Agric. Res. Council, Islamabad, Pakistan.
- Jaipal S, Malik R K, Yadav A and Gupta R (2005). *IPM issues in zero-tillage system in rice-wheat cropping sequence*. Technical Bulletin (8), CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar-125 004, India, pp: 5.
- Pathak M D and Khan Z R (1994). *Insect Pest of Rice*. International Rice Research Institute, Manila, Philippines, ISBN: 9789712200281, pp: 5-6.
- Razzaq A, Zafar M A and Sabir B A (1997). Control of insect pests on rice using tillage practices. *Mech Asia Africa Latin America* **28**: 29-30.
- Saxena R C, Mathur Y K and Sharma S K (1972). Varietal susceptibility of wheat against pink borer, *Sesamia inferens* Walker (*Lepidoptera: Noctuidae*). *Labdev J Sci and Tech* **10**: 52.
- Singh B (2012). Incidence of the Pink Noctuid Stem Borer, *Sesamia inferens* (Walker), on Wheat under Two Tillage Conditions and Three Sowing Dates in North-western Plains of India.

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Assessment of Phenotypic Divergence and Association Studies in Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.)

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ABSTRACT

Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L., 2n=34), one of the important oilseed crops of the world, is a rich source of edible oil and is considered good from cardiac health point of view. In this study, a total of 67 sunflower inbred lines comprising 55 restorer lines and 12 maintainer lines belonging to different geographical origins were evaluated for phenotypic divergence on the basis of eight agro morphological traits and oil content. Among the evaluated traits, days taken to initiation of disk floret opening, days taken to complete anthesis, days taken to physiological maturity, head diameter, plant height, autogamy per cent, 1000 seed weight, seed yield per plant and oil content revealed significant variation in the material under study. The data pertaining to these traits was subjected to D2 analysis which allowed grouping of the genotypes into nine clusters indicating genetic diversity in the material. The distribution patterns of the genotypes into different clusters indicated that grouping was not according to the source of genotypes. Cluster I has maximum number of genotypes (49). Inter cluster distance were higher than the intra cluster distances supporting the grouping of the genotypes. 1000 seed weight, plant height, initiation of flowering, autogamy per cent and oil content had greater contribution towards the observed genetic divergence. Selection of three CMS lines viz. 207A, 10A, 7-1A and five restorer lines viz. P83R, P81R, PISF-1R, LTRR-341 and R-17 from different clusters based on inter cluster distance and cluster mean values for hybridization is suggested.

Key Words: Sunflower, Genetic divergence, Correlations.

INTRODUCTION

Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L. 2n=34) is one of the important oilseed crops of the world and it accounts for nearly 14 per cent of the global production of 9 major vegetable oilseed crops. It is a rich source of edible oil and is considered good from cardiac health point of view due to high concentration of unsaturated fatty acids. Sunflower oil is generally considered premium oil because of its light colour, high level of unsaturated fatty acids and lack of linolenic acid, and high smoke point. Knowledge of genetic parameters is essential for understanding and their manipulations in any crop improvement programme. Seed yield in sunflower being is a quantitative character and dependent on its own component characters. Such interdependence of contributory characters as well

as the characters of economic importance often misleads and thus makes correlation coefficient by and large unreliable during selection (Dewey and Lu, 1959), particularly in crop like sunflower, which is highly cross pollinated and heterozygous and envisages enormous variability in succeeding generations. Many researchers (Arshad *et al*, 2004 & 2006; Ghafoor and Ahmed, 2005) have used these techniques along with diversity study for investigating genetic parameters. In a quest to develop hybrids revealing higher magnitude of standard heterosis, greater adaptation with desirable attributes like oil content, tolerance to biotic and abiotic stresses, there is a need to evaluate parental lines for the extent of genetic variability prevailing so that it facilitates to develop desired hybrid in a reasonably short time. In this context breeder would

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choose genetically distinct parents for hybridization since heterotic crosses are expected to arise as a result of hybridization between divergent parental lines (Singh and Sharma, 1989). The D2 analysis has been successfully utilized in sunflower to classify genotypes and determine their inter relationships by many workers (Sankarpandian *et al*, 1996). Therefore, an attempt has been made to study the genetic diversity among parental lines of sunflower comprising mainly CMS A and R lines for further use in hybridization programme.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present investigation was carried out at the research fields of the oilseeds Section, Department of Plant Breeding and Genetics, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, India. The material for present study consisted of 67 parental lines comprising 55 were restorer lines and 12 maintainer lines. The material was raised in two rows each row of 4.5m length with 60 cm and 30 cm inter and intra row spacing respectively, in the randomized block design. All the agronomic practices recommended for the region were followed to raise a good crop.

The data for morpho physiological traits i.e. days taken to initiation of disk floret opening, complete anthesis and physiological maturity were recorded on the basis of total plants per genotype whereas other characters *viz.*, head diameter, plant height, autogamy per cent, 1000 seed weight, seed yield per plant were recorded for five random plants in the field. From each genotype, five plants were randomly selected and covered with cloth bags on the day the first ray florets opened. These remained covered until harvest to observe seed set, that was used later to calculate per cent autogamy. All other traits were recorded from other five plants left uncovered for open pollination.

The observations on oil content were recorded from the random sample of open pollinated seed using NMR. The mean data of two years with respect to all the traits was subjected to statistical analysis following standard methods to calculate correlations

among seed yield and its component traits. The D2 statistic for yield and yield attributes was computed using INDOSTAT, version 7.5 software programme. The D2 values of all the combinations were arranged in descending order. Treating D2 as a generalized statistics, all the genotypes used were clustered into different groups following the method as described by Rao (1952). The intra and inter cluster distances and contribution of individual traits towards divergence were computed following Singh and Chaudhary (1996).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Univariate analysis of variance for each of the nine traits *viz.* Initiation of disk floret opening, complete anthesis, physiological maturity, head diameter, plant height, autogamy, 1000 seed weight, seed yield and oil content revealed highly significant differences among genotypes. The simultaneous testing of significance of difference in mean values between genotypes based on Wilk's criterion revealed highly significant differences ($X^2=4763.84$ with 594 degree of freedom) among genotypes for the aggregate of the nine traits considered. Previous studies conducted by Teklewold *et al* (2000) have also reported significant differences among genotypes in univariate and multivariate analysis of variance.

D2 analysis assigned the test genotypes into nine clusters (Table 1) indicating presence of enough genetic diversity in the material. Cluster I contained maximum number of genotypes (49). Cluster II, IV and VII had seven, four and two genotypes respectively. The cluster III, V, VI, VIII and IX comprised of one genotype each. The cluster 1 which included maximum no. of genotypes (42 R lines and 7 B lines) indicated that the divergence among these lines was rather limited and hence fell in the same cluster. Out of the twelve B lines included in this study, seven B lines developed at different research centres in India fell in group I and, thus may have common ancestors. Maximum number of R lines (43) also fell in group I suggesting

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some commonness shared among parents of these forty-three lines.

Intra and inter cluster distance

Intra and inter-cluster distance for 67 lines are given in table 2. Among the 9 clusters formed, inter-cluster D2 values varied from 8.94 (between cluster III and VIII) to 21.07 (between cluster IV and IX). The genotypes falling in these clusters are more diverse from each other. Among the 9 clusters formed cluster I, II, IV and cluster VII had 8.06, 8.41 and 5.34 intra-cluster D2 values, respectively. Intra cluster distances were absent in cluster III, V, VI, VIII and IX because these included only one genotype each. Genotypes grouped in the same cluster presumably diverge little from one another as the aggregate traits were measured. In this context, as the inter-cluster distance was high between cluster IV and IX followed by VII and IX, the genotypes falling in these clusters could be selected for the hybridization programme as these are expected to produce, high heterosis. However, earlier studies by Arunachalam (1981) indicate that too high divergence does not always produce the high heterosis because of internal cancellation of dominance effect at various loci. Environmental variation can also affect the expression of divergence values (Yadav *et al*, 1988). Therefore, assessment of heritable and non-heritable component of variation in total variability is of immense value in choice of the breeding programme.

Cluster mean values and contribution of each trait towards genetic divergence

The Cluster means and contribution of each trait towards genetic divergence is given in table 3. It can be seen from cluster means that each cluster has its own uniqueness that separated it from other clusters. For example cluster I with largest number of genotypes has mean values near to the population mean for all the traits. Cluster II is characterized as having low 1000 seed weight (28.0g). Cluster III has only one genotype, R-17 characterized as having largest head diameter (19.0cm) and high value for autogamy per cent (95.70), this indirectly

indicates that large head size produces more number of filled seeds. Cluster IV is characterized as having genotypes with minimum number of days taken for initiation to flowering (53.17) and days to complete anthesis (59.83). Cluster V which has only one genotype 10 B that has maximum seed yield per plant (31.73g). The genotype PISF 13 R falling in cluster VI took maximum number of days to physiological maturity (92.33) and had lowest autogamy per cent of 74.37. The cluster VII comprising of two genotypes is characterized as having highest 1000 seed weight (89.27g). High oil content (41.57%) is the characteristic feature of the genotype 7-1 B falling in cluster VIII. Cluster IX also having one genotype is taking maximum number of days to initiation to flowering (69.97), days to complete anthesis (73.00) but minimum no of days to physiological maturity (82.33), minimum head diameter (8.53cm), lowest 1000 seed weight (23.33g) and minimum seed yield per plant (13.33g).

The per cent contribution of each character to total divergence varied between 1.22 and 35.19 for complete anthesis and 1000 seed weight, respectively. The highest degree of contribution towards genetic divergence was by 1000 seed weight (35.19%) followed by plant height (22.52%), initiation of flowering (15.56%), autogamy (9.45%) and oil content (6.6%). These five traits contributed 89.02% towards divergence. The least contribution to genetic divergence is by days taken to complete anthesis (1.22%). Major contribution of plant height, oil content and day to flowering (Mohan and Seetharam, 2005) oil content and plant height (Manjula *et al* (2001), head diameter and seed yield (Mupidathi *et al* (1995) and Sankarapandian *et al* (1996) towards genetic divergence in sunflower, have earlier been reported.

Genetic diversity is the main consideration for selecting parents to be used in a hybridization programme in crop plants. In this study the highest inter cluster distance was observed between cluster IV and IX followed by cluster VII and IX. Hence the parental lines falling in these clusters could be selected for developing better hybrids in sunflower.

It is common experience of the breeder that variation from diverse origin with reasonable range, when crossed, give maximum heterosis, specific combining ability and transgressive segregants in segregating generations. On the basis of inter cluster distance and cluster mean the crosses viz. 207 A X P83R, 207A X P81R, 207A X PISF1R, 207A X LTRR-341, 10A X R-17, 7-1 A X P83R, 7-1A X P81R, 7-1 A X PISF-1R and 7-1A X LTRR-341 are expected to perform better.

Character association studies

In all breeding programmes, yield is the ultimate objective, which has highly variable expression as it is influenced by several other components. These yield components are related among themselves and with yield either favorably or unfavourably. In general, in most of the crops the association among yield components are reported to be undesirable thereby hindering the rapid progress that could be made. Thus the knowledge of association of various characters with yield and among themselves would provide best criteria for indirect selection through component traits for improvement in yield.

In the present work the character association studies indicated that days to initiation of disk floret opening had strong positive correlation (0.75**) with days to complete anthesis. Head diameter was observed to be highly positively associated with days to physiological maturity (0.38**) which in turn was positively associated with seed weight (0.35**) and seed yield (0.28**). This is an indication that as the no. of days taken for physiological maturity increase the head diameter increases, seed filling becomes better which improves seed weight and ultimately affecting the seed yield in a positive side. This has been strongly supported by the highly positive association of head diameter with seed weight (0.51**) and seed yield (0.49**) in the present study. Autogamy per cent has been observed to be positively correlated with seed weight (0.21*) which in turn has shown significant positive association with seed yield (0.36**). These results were supported by the previous findings by Morinkovi *et al* (1992) and Taklewold *et al* (2000). Efforts were made to correlate seed yield and its component traits with oil content and quality because improving the oil yield and quality is prime

Table 1. Cluster composition with their respective inbred lines/genotypes.

Cluster No.	No. of Genotypes	Name of Genotypes
I	49	PISF-9R, RGA-856, R-272-1-P9, P72R, PISF-12R, P71R, P395R, RHA 271, P87R, 18B, P88R, P35R, P63R, P68R, 243A, 1147-4, P65R, P86R, P70R, PISF-18R, P62R, P78R, RHA-296, P74R, RHA-859, RCR-8297, P66R, P67R, SF-1R, NDR-2, 853B, P73R, P82R, RHA-83R6, 304B, P84R, RHA-297, P75R, RHA-17, 179-2RP2, 31B, P64R, MR-6, P61R, 44-B, RHA-214, PISF-3R, RR-1, RHA-274,
II	7	32-B, 12-B, SF-7R, LTR-1822, RHA-265, P69R, SF-4R
III	1	R-17
IV	4	P83R, P81R, PISF-1R, LTRR-341
V	1	10B
VI	1	PISF-13R
VII	2	R-273, R-801
VIII	1	7-1B
IX	1	207B

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Table 2. Inter and intra-cluster distance values.

Cluster	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX
I	8.06	10.59	10.59	13.20	10.10	10.03	11.19	11.13	15.32
II		8.41	11.08	12.30	11.16	12.46	16.9	11.59	13.53
III			0.00	11.52	14.79	14.79	14.12	8.94	16.16
IV				8.41	15.84	15.64	16.08	12.69	21.07
V					0.00	11.20	16.90	15.33	16.12
VI						0.00	10.68	14.24	15.66
VII							5.34	13.90	20.47
VIII								0.00	13.56
IX									0.00

Diagonal and above diagonal values indicated intra-cluster and inter cluster distance respectively.

objective in sunflower breeding. Oil content in the present study did not show any association with the morphological and seed yield components however, it has been reported to correlate negatively with days to flowering, plant height and seed yield per plant, whereas, positive association of oil content with these traits have been reported by Khan *et al* (2003) and Kaya *et al* (2007).

It was observed that palmitic acid showed significant positive correlations with seed weight (0.26*). Oleic acid correlated positively (0.24*) and linoleic acid was associated negatively (-0.24*) with head diameter and this association can be attributed mainly to genotypic effect as the influence of environment on this association was negligible (genotypic correlation almost equal to

Table 3. Cluster means and contribution of traits towards genetic divergence .

Cluster No	Initiation of disk floret opening (days)	Complete anthesis (days)	Physiological maturity (days)	Head diameter (cm)	Plant Height (cm)	Autogamy (%)	1000 seed weight (g)	Seed yield (g/pl)	Oil content (%)
I	61.56	66.69	92.07	14.18	117.22	92.28	52.17	22.32	33.38
II	60.33	66.57	90.67	11.27	110.80	87.27	28.00	17.90	33.96
III	60.33	67.00	90.00	19.00	82.67	95.70	41.07	25.73	28.07
IV	53.17	59.83	89.92	14.26	69.38	91.83	45.12	17.46	35.06
V	61.33	66.67	92.00	15.97	157.27	88.23	37.93	31.73	33.27
VI	62.33	68.33	92.33	12.00	125.13	74.37	62.27	16.47	34.43
VII	60.83	66.50	91.33	14.52	101.20	89.98	89.27	19.30	32.52
VIII	61.67	67.67	83.00	15.70	88.67	95.90	44.87	24.47	41.57
IX	69.67	73.00	82.33	8.53	108.07	83.53	23.33	13.33	31.55
Population Mean	61.1± 0.53	66.9 ± 0.63	90.6 ± 0.85	13.7 ± 0.79	117.8 ± 3.13	91.7 ± 1.44	46.7 ± 2.29	21.4 ± 4.28	33.01 ± 1.20
per cent Contribution of traits towards genetic divergence	15.56	1.22	2.76	5.16	22.52	9.45	35.19	1.54	6.60

Table 4. Genotypic and phenotypic correlations of 13 quantitative characters for 67 inbred lines.

Sr.No.	Characters	IDF	CA	PM	HD	PH	AP	SW	SY	OC	PA	SA	OA	LA
1	IDF	1	0.85	0.18	-0.18	0.37	-0.04	-0.08	-0.02	0.04	-0.04	0.01	0.07	-0.07
2	CA	0.75**	1	0.34	-0.03	0.38	-0.21	-0.07	-0.04	-0.15	0.05	-0.04	-0.03	0.02
3	PM	0.04	0.12	1	0.51	0.13	-0.17	0.48	0.38	-0.14	0.21	-0.01	-0.01	-0.01
4	HD	-0.11	-0.1	0.38**	1	0.35	0.23	0.75	0.67	-0.06	-0.08	-0.03	0.29	-0.28
5	PH	0.3	0.26*	0.06	0.18	1	0.59	0.16	0.37	0.16	-0.14	-0.19	0.13	-0.12
6	AP	-0.05	-0.09	-0.02	0.2	0.15	1	0.38	0.19	-0.15	0.24	-0.33	-0.03	0.04
7	SW	-0.12	-0.14	0.35**	0.51**	0.11	0.21*	1	0.42	-0.15	0.3	-0.15	-0.01	-0.01
8	SY	-0.04	-0.04	0.28**	0.49**	0.23	0.09	0.36**	1	0.32	-0.1	-0.24	0.1	-0.07
9	OC	-0.05	-0.06	-0.02	-0.04	0.07	0.09	-0.1	0.12	1	-0.2	0.26	-0.02	0.02
10	PA	0	0.04	0.15	-0.08	-0.12	0.06	0.26*	-0.12	-0.17	1	-0.2	-0.62	0.56
11	SA	0.01	0	0.02	-0.02	-0.1	-0.18	-0.14	-0.09	0.1	-0.27*	1	0.33	-0.42
12	OA	0.04	-0.04	0.01	0.24*	0.1	-0.01	0.03	0.12	-0.1	-0.57**	0.26*	1	-0.99
13	LA	-0.04	0.03	-0.02	-0.24*	-0.09	0.02	-0.05	-0.1	0.02	0.53**	-0.34**	-0.99**	1

Above diagonal values indicate genotypic correlation and below diagonal values indicate phenotypic correlation

IDF= Initiation of disk floret opening (days); **CA**= Complete anthesis (days); **PM**= Physiological maturity (days); **HD**= Head diameter (cm); **PH**= Plant height (cm); **AP**= Autogamy percent; **SW**= 1000 Seed weight; **SY**= Seed yield (g/pl); **OC**= Oil Content (%); **PA**= Palmitic acid; **SA**= Stearic acid; **OA**= Oleic acid; **LA**= Linoleic acid.

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phenotypic correlation). Similarly for other fatty acids i.e. stearic acid showed negative association with palmitic acid (-0.27*). Oleic acid was strongly and negatively associated with palmitic acid (-0.57**) while showed +ve correlation with stearic acid (0.26*). Linoleic acid was observed to have highly significant +ve association with palmitic acid (0.53**) while highly significant -ve correlation with stearic acid (-0.34**) and oleic acid (-0.99**).

CONCLUSION

Diversity analysis indicates enormous quantum of diversity present in the germ plasm which can be exploited and put to use in hybrid breeding programme. The maximum genetic divergence was observed between cluster IV and cluster IX, which represents a good cross combination and may lead to desirable recombinants in the segregating generations. Restorer lines namely, R-17, P83R, P81R, PISF1R and LTRR-341 can be used in hybridization with CMS A lines present in cluster I to synthesize high yielding and good quality hybrids.

REFERENCES

- Arshad M, Bakhsh A and Ghafoor A (2004). Path coefficient analysis in chickpea (*Cicer arictinum* L.) under rainfed condition. *Pak J Bot* **36** (1): 75-81
- Arshad. M, Ali N and Ghafoor A (2006). Character correlation and Path coefficient in soybean (*Glycine Max* L.). *Pak J Bot* **38** (1): 121-130
- Arunachalam V (1981). Genetic distance in plant breeding. *Indian J Genet* **41**: 226-236
- Dewey J R and Lu K H (1959). A correlation and Path coefficient analysis of components of crested wheat seed production. *Agron J* **51**: 515-518
- Ghafoor A and Ahmed Z (2005). *Diversity of agronomic traits and total seed protein in Black gram (Vigna mungo L.)* Hepper. Acta Biologica Cracoviensia, Series Botanica, Poland, 47 (2): 69-75
- Kaya Y, Evic G, Durak S, Pekcan V and Gucer T (2007). Determining the relationships between yield and yield attributes in sunflower. *Turk J Agri* **31**: 237-44
- Khan A, Ullah I, Murtaza S B and Khan M Y (2003). Variation and correlation study in different newly developed sunflower hybrids. *Asian J of Plant Sci* **212**: 887-90
- Manjula K, Nadaf H L and Giriraj (2001). Genetics diversity in non-oil seed sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) genotypes. *Helia* **24**: 17-24
- Mohan G S and Seetharam A (2005). Genetic divergence in lines of sunflower derived from interspecific hybridization. *SABRO J Breeding and Gen* **34** (2): 77-84
- Morinkovi C R, Mihaljeevic M and Joksimovic J (1992). *Genetic Diversity of sunflower (Helianthus annuus L.). Varietal population assessed by cluster analysis.* Proc. Of the 13th Int. sunflower conf., Pisa, Italy, 7-11, September 1992. 2: 1135-1140
- Muppudathi N, Sandkarapandian R and Rajarathinam S (1995). Genetic divergence, correlation and Path analysis in Sunflower. *Crop Improv* **22**: 221-224
- Rao C R (1952). *Advanced Statistical Methods in Biometrical Research.* John Wiley and Sons, New York, USA. Pp 357-363.
- Sankarapandian R, Muppudathim N, Rajarathinam S, Chidambaram A R S and Kovilpathi (1996). Genetics divergence in Sunflower. *Madras Agric J* **83**: 367-39
- Singh R K and Chaudhary B D (1996). *Biometrical Methods in Quantitative Genetics Analysis.* Kalyani Publishers, New Delhi, India. P 318
- Singh S P and Sharma J R (1989). Genetic improvement of Pyrethrum-IV. Selection divergence, heterosis and potential hybrid clones. *Theor Appl Genet* **78**: 841-846
- Teklewold A, Jayaramaiah H and Gowda J (2000). Genetics divergence study in sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) *Helia* **23** (32): 93-134
- Yadava R K, Behl R K and Yadava T P (1988). Assessment of diversity among sunflower collections. *Crop Improv* **15**: 160-62

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Comparative Evaluation of Different Attributes of the Existing Extruded Snacks

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ABSTRACT

The different brands of extruded products consumed as snacks were surveyed in the local market and were compared for their listed nutritional status along with textural and functional properties. The snacks were constituted mainly of wheat and maize as well as rice, potato, and grams, soy and pulses. The price of the snacks varied from Rs. 147/- to Rs. 2000/-kg. The average content of energy, carbohydrates, protein and fat for extruded snacks were 489.34kcal/100g, 22.73, 46.53 and 6.97 percent, respectively. The bulk density varied between 107.69 to 763.64kg/m³. This information will help to guide the entrepreneurs for product development which is nutritious and made with cheaper source, according to the need and preference of the consumers.

Key Words: Extrusion, Extruded Snack, Physical, Functional properties.

INTRODUCTION

Extrusion cooking is a high temperature and shear process that is characterized by forming a melt from the starchy ingredient, at high temperature (140–180°C), low moisture content (12%) and low mean residence time of 15–30s. Cereal grains mainly rice, wheat and corn with different physico-chemical characteristics are used as major raw materials in extruded snack foods and breakfast cereals due to their good expansion characteristics. Starch is the main constituent responsible for the structural attributes of the extruded products. A large variety of extruded Ready-to-eat (RTE) snacks are available in the market. Direct-puffed snacks made by extrusion process are classified as a second-generation snack. They are usually low in bulk density and are often marketed as high-fiber, low-calorie, high-protein and nutritional product (Liu *et al*, 2000). Crisp extruded snacks are widely consumed convenience food products. These snacks are dense in energy but are nutritionally poor and it is possible to add beneficial nutrients. Although the nutritional properties are important, the consumer acceptability of the snacks depends mainly on the physical and organoleptic properties

of the snacks. Physical characteristics of extruded products such as expansion, hardness and density are important parameters along with its functional properties (Jamora *et al*, 2002) whereas texture is also considered as one of the most important factors (Mazumder *et al*, 2007). There is an increasing consumer demand for more complex and natural seasonings in snack foods. The acceptance of snacks is critical because of the specific quality attributes that attract people. Hence, this study was undertaken with an objective to know the availability of different extruded snacks in the local market and make a comparative evaluation of different attributes of these snacks.

Moreover, there is no concise information available regarding the various attributes of existing snacks, the study will act as a guideline for an entrepreneur in selection and combination of raw material for healthy extruded snacks.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Twelve samples of RTE snacks available in the market were bought from local grocery stores. The information as reported by the manufacturer on the package was compared and tabulated to study the

compositional status and price of these extruded snacks (Table 1). The nutritional information as derived from the labels was also tabulated for comparative study. Extruded samples were further analyzed for the parameters not given by the manufacturer on the label as follows.

Chemical Composition

Samples were ground in a laboratory mill (Model No.3303, Perten Instruments AB, Huddings, Sweden) to pass through an 80-mesh sieve. The moisture content of the ground products was determined using (AACC, 2000). The ash content was determined from the percentage of combusted material following heating in a furnace at 550° C (AACC, 2000).

Physical Properties: A 50ml graduated measuring cylinder was tared and gently filled with extruded sample. The bottom of the cylinder was repeatedly tapped gently on a laboratory bench until there was no further reduction of sample volume. Bulk density was calculated as weight of the sample/volume (Hwang and Hayakawa,1980). All measurements were done in triplicate and results reported as kg/m³.

$$\rho = W_p / V_c$$

W_p =Weight of sample (kg)

V_c =Volume of cylinder (m³)

ρ =Density (kg/m³)

Color

Color of extruded samples was measured using a Hunter Laboratory Instrument Model CIE 1996 (Hunter Associates Laboratory, Inc., Reston, Virginia, U.S.A.) and expressed in terms of the 'L' (lightness (100) or darkness (0)), 'a' (redness (+) or greenness (-)), and 'b' (yellowness (+) or blueness (-)). A white calibration plate (L = 91.08, a = -1.25 and b = 1.43) was used as a standard for the measurements (Altanet al,2008). Ground and sieved samples (sieve #48 mesh) were taken. For each sample, three measurements were taken and

averaged. ΔE signifies the total color difference which was calculated as Matthey and Hanna (1997).

$$\Delta E = (\Delta L^2 + \Delta a^2 + \Delta b^2)^{1/2}$$

Where $\Delta L = L_{\text{sample}} - L_{\text{standard}}$

$\Delta a = a_{\text{sample}} - a_{\text{standard}}$

$\Delta b = b_{\text{sample}} - b_{\text{standard}}$

Gas analysis

The gas analysis was done by a Gas Analyzer, Systech Instruments (Model GS3) and percentage of oxygen, carbon dioxide and nitrogen present in the pack were recorded.

Texture analysis: The texture of the snacks is an important parameter for consumer acceptability. The hardness of samples was measured using Stable Microsystems TA-HD Texture Analyzer (Texture Technologies Corp., Scarsdale, NY, USA) fitted with a 250 kg load cell. The probe (P 75) was moved at the test speed of 0.5mm/sec for a distance of 50 mm. Maximum force needed to break the samples was recorded and analyzed by Texture Exponent software associated with the texture analyzer and reported as Hardness (N) giving an average of three to four replicates (Kaur *et al*, 2014).

Functional Properties:

A 2.0 g \pm 0.005 g sample was placed in a tared centrifuge tube and 20 ml distilled water added. After standing for 15 min (with intermittent shaking every 5 min), the sample was centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 15 min. The supernatant was decanted into a tared aluminum pan and weight gain in the gel was noted (Rehal *et al*, 2015). Water absorption index (WAI) was calculated as the increase in weight of sediment obtained after decanting the supernatant as:

$WAI = \text{Weight of wet sediment (g)} / \text{weight of dried sediment (g)}$

The supernatant was evaporated to dryness at 105°C until constant weight. Water solubility index (WSI) was determined as Nyombaire *et al* (2011).

$WSI = [(\text{weight of dried supernatant}) / (\text{weight of dry sample}) \times 100]$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chemical Composition

The major ingredients of extruded snacks as listed on the labels were rice meal, corn meal, gram meal, soy flour, potato flour, spices and condiments (onion powder, red chili powder, garlic powder, tomato powder, milk solids, cheese blends), flavor enhancers, citric acid, anti caking agents, coloring compounds and anti-oxidants. All the manufactures had listed only the ingredients without listing their proportion/percentage (Table 1). Price variation fell in the range of Rs 147/kg- Rs 555/kg with an exception of sample 11 for Rs 1416/kg and sample 12 for Rs 2000/kg since they were not indigenous. The average weight of the pack varied between 25-68g as shown in table 1.

All the snacks except for sample 1 listed the composition of protein, carbohydrate and fat as given in table 2. The fat content was highest for sample 10 with a value of 35.6 per cent and minimum for sample 9 with 3.15 per cent. The carbohydrates varied from 4.0 to 70.9 per cent. Sample 9 extruded from rice reported minimum protein content of 2.8 per cent. Wheat semolina and corn have higher protein content in comparison to rice (Dehghan-Shoar *et al*, 2010). The energy obtained from the snacks ranged from 137-607 kcal where sample 9 reported the minimum calorific value due to minimum amount of fat, protein and carbohydrates. Sample 12 had the highest amount of fat 42.9 per cent hence delivering maximum energy. The mineral content was reported by few manufactures only with sample 12 showing the highest sodium content of 1.71 per cent while sample 6 showed the highest calcium content of 668.5 mg (Table 2).

Moisture content is the most important factor in both processing of the snack as well as the storage. All the extruded snacks reported moisture content in the range of 3.71 to 9.24. Moisture content below 10 per cent is considered safe to prevent any microbial growth. The sample 1 had the maximum moisture content of 9.24 per cent. Since the mineral percentage was not listed for all

the snacks hence it was determined by following the standard procedures (Table 3). It indicated the amount of minerals present varied between 1.36 to 4.12 per cent. The snacks studied reported lack of micronutrients. Only 2 samples listed the presence of micronutrients on their nutritional label.

Physical Properties

Bulk Density

The bulk density of the extruded snacks varied from 107.69 to 763.64 kg/m³ and is tabulated in table 3. The bulk density of 763.64 kg/m³ implied minimum expansion. The expansion was inversely proportional to the bulk density and was greatest for low protein. A 3-dimensional protein network by gluten proteins and water decreases the starch swelling (Champenois *et al*, 1998). This is contrary to the previous results that addition of protein to starchy extrudate reduced the expansion of product by reducing the extensibility of starch polymer during its expansion at the die exit (Derby *et al*, 1975). The high protein content in sample 3 to 8 did not increase the bulk density of the extruded snack as the protein was not incorporated in the premix but rather coated over the extruded product. The coated protein had no role in altering the gelatinization of starch or the structure of protein, hence did not affect bulk density.

Color

The L values varied in the range 52.19 to 79.76 as given in table 3. Sample 1 was the lightest having maximum value of L as its ingredients were potato powder, starch and refined oil secondly, higher L values were due to rise in the number of air cells. The minimum L value of 52.19 was recorded for Sample 2 due to presence of corn meal, grain meal and wheat bran making it darker in color. The value of 'a' (redness) and 'b' (yellowness) were maximum for sample 11 and 12 due to the presence of tomato powder and added color. Samples with higher 'a' values were darker and had lower 'L' values (Altan *et al*, 2008).

The packaging of ten out of twelve samples were in laminated pouches and the remaining two were

Table 1. Details of the extruded snacks as available on the labels

Sample No. and name		Ingredients	Manufacturer	Wt. (g)	Price (Rs)
1.	Sai Lite-N-Fit	Potato powder, starch, vegetable refined oil and starch	Sai Gram Udyog, Paschim Vihar, Delhi	35	80
2.	Bingo TedheMedhe	Rice meal, edible oil, corn meal, gram meal, spices and condiments (onion powder 2.8%, red chili powder 1.1%, Coriander powder 0.2%), Salt (2.1%), maltodextrin, Acidity regulators (296, 330, 334), Tomato powder, sugar, hydrolysed vegetable protein, anti-caking agent 551, flavor enhancers 627 & 631.	ITC Ltd, Foods division, snacks unit, Bhel, Haridwar	68	10
3.	Bingo Mad Angles	Rice meal, edible oil, corn meal, gram meal, sugar, salt, spices and condiments (red chili powder 0.2%) milk solids, hydrolysed vegetable protein, malto dextrin, acidity regulators (296, 330) emulsifier (414), anti-caking agent (551), wheat fiber, anti-oxidant (320)	ITC Ltd, Bhel, Haridwar	50	10
4.	Peppy Tomato Discs	Wheat flour, edible starch, edible vegetable oil, flour of soya and corn, sugar, tomato powder, onion powder, chili powder, malto dextrin, black pepper, acid (E 296, E 330), salt, baking powder, ground spices, Color (E 150) and condiments.	Venkataramana Food Specialities Ltd (VFSL), Bhind, M.P.	25	10
5.	Peppy Cheese Balls	Whole corn, vegetable oil, blend of whey, malto dextrin. Cheese powder, salt, sodium phosphate, flavor enhancer (E621) acid (E 270, E 330) Color (E 160 C) and yeast extract.	Venkataramana Food Specialities Ltd (VFSL), Bhind, M.P.	27	15
6.	Crax Corn Rings-masala	Corn meal, edible vegetable oil, spices and condiments, sugar, salt, acidifying agents and starch.	DFM Foods Ltd, Rohan Hara Road, Delhi.	45	10
7.	Crax Corn Rings-Chatpata	Corn meal, hydrogenated vegetable oil, spices, salt, permitted flavors and citric acid.	DFM Foods Ltd, Rohan Hara Road, Delhi.	45	10
8.	Pik-Nik Classic	Wheat flour, edible starch, edible vegetable oil, flour of soya, corn and potato, salt, sugar, tomato powder, onion powder, garlic powder, chili powder, malto dextrin, acid (E 296, E 330), baking powder, ground spices, Color (E 150) and condiments.	Venkataramana Food Specialities Ltd. (VFSL) Bhind, M.P	25	10
9.	Fun Flips Rice Puffs	Rice, Pulse, maize, edible vegetable oil, spices, edible salt and citric acid.	Fun choice, Shadara, Delhi	30	5
10.	Kurkure	Rice meal, edible vegetable oil, corn meal, gram meal, spices and condiments (onion powder, chili powder, amchur, coriander powder, ginger powder, garlic powder, black pepper powder, turmeric powder, fenugreek powder) salt, black salt, tomato powder, sugar, citric acid, tartaric acid.	Pepsico India holding Pvt Ltd (Frito lay division) Gurgaon, Haryana.	55	10

Different Attributes of the Existing Extruded Snacks

11.	Fisher Cheez Curlz	Degerminated yellow corn meal, soya bean and/or canola oil, dried cheese blend (whey, sunflower oil, semi soft cheese {pasteurized milk,cheese culture, salt, enzymes},lactose, food starch – modified, malto dextrin, whey protein concentrate, salt,sodium phosphate, natural flavor, citric acid, Yellow6, yellow 5,lactic acid)	America's best canister snacks, Boonton, NJ 07005	120	170
12.	Fisher Pizza Ballz	Degerminated yellow corn meal, sun flower seed and / or soya bean and / or canola oil , dried cheese blend (whey, sunflower oil, semi soft cheese{pasteurized milk ,cheese culture, salt, enzymes},lactose, food starch – modified, malto dextrin, whey protein concentrate, salt, sodium phosphate, natural flavor, citric acid, Yellow 6, yellow 5,lactic acid), Tomato powder, monosodium glutamate, sugar, whey protein concentrate, spices, lactose, onion and garlic powder, disodiuminosinate and guanylate, salt , citric acid	America's best canister snacks, Boonton, NJ 07005	85	170

Table 2. Nutritional information available on the labels of extruded snacks.

Sam-ple No.	Product	En-ergy (kcal)	Total Fat	Total CHO	Protein	Na (g)	Vit C (mg)	Fe (mg)	Ca (mg)	Sugar (%)
1.	Sai Lite-N-Fit	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A
2.	Bingo Tedhemedhe	558	35.6	51.9	7.5	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	2.6
3.	Bingo mad Angels	534	30.8	55.9	8.3	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	3.4
4.	Peppy Tomato Discs	505.2	26.3	59.2	8.0	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	6.2
5.	Peppy Cheese Balls	473	17	70.9	9.2	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	1.0
6.	Crax Corn Rings-masala	502.6	25.2	63.9	5.2	0.001	N.A	25.74	668.5	N.A
7.	Crax Corn Rings-Chatpata	463.9	18.7	67.6	6.4	0.013	N.A	30.50	291.6	N.A
8.	Pik-nik Classic	513	27.6	57.6	8.7	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A	5.6
9.	Fun Flips Rice Puffs	137	3.15	22.18	2.8	0.23	N.A	N.A	N.A	N.A
10.	Kurkure	561	35.7	53.6	6.4		N.A	N.A	N.A	3
11.	Fisher Cheez Curlz	635	18.0	4.0	7.1	17.1	N.A	N.A	400	7.14
12.	Fisher Pizza Ballz	500	12.0	5.0	7.1	4.5	20	200	0	7.14

N.A means 'Information Not Printed'

Table 3. Estimated parameters of the extruded snacks

Sample No.	Sample Name	Moisture Content (%)	Ash (%)	Bulk density (kg/m ³)	L	a	b	ΔE O ₂	Gas analysis(%)			Max. Force (N)
									CO ₂	N ₂		
1.	Bingo tedhemedhe	4.72	2.09	763.64	55.10	14.52	25.12	45.95	2.54	0.3	97.2	16.66
2.	Bingo mad angels	4.24	2.04	753.20	52.19	11.47	23.32	46.40	11.7	0.8	87.5	35.37
3.	Peppy Tomato discs	5.51	2.98	148.88	52.63	10.27	20.22	44.31	19.3	0.6	80.1	5.09
4.	Peppy cheese balls	6.55	1.36	130.29	58.92	22.40	29.64	48.88	20.9	0.2	78.9	14.50
5.	Crax masala	5.39	2.85	188.39	61.24	7.71	30.64	42.70	20.9	0.3	78.8	25.57
6.	Craxchatpata	3.71	4.12	157.54	61.27	4.93	28.58	40.79	20.9	0.4	78.7	22.73
7.	Piknik tomato chilli	5.85	2.86	139.25	52.20	14.02	22.47	46.77	20.9	0.4	78.7	12.15
8.	Funflips	4.56	2.47	107.69	57.55	19.57	25.55	46.26	15.8	0.3	83.9	15.09
9.	Kurkure	3.41	2.55	522.46	53.87	15.58	24.95	47.12	20.9	0.2	78.9	14.50
10.	Fisher cheese curlz	8.13	2.68	436.47	55.79	32.58	30.10	56.67	19	0.4	80.6	12.44
11.	Fisher pizza ballz	8.11	2.53	170.81	54.91	30.47	29.19	55.43	20.9	0.4	78.7	11.66
12.	Lite n fit potato extrudates	9.24	2.82	269.82	79.76	0.39	13.68	16.75	21.8	0.0	78.2	48.71

packed in laminated card boards. The gas analysis of the laminated pouches revealed the presence of nitrogen gas in the range of 78.2-97.2 per cent. Nitrogen being an inert gas helps to prevent the oxidation of oil which leads to rancidity.

Texture analysis

The hardness is the maximum force required for a probe to penetrate the extrudates. The feed moisture was the main factor affecting the density and expansion. The high density and low expansion produces a harder extrudate (Liu *et al*, 2000). Maximum force of 48.71 N was recorded for sample 1 (Table 3). It could be due to high carbohydrate content i.e. potato starch, and secondly due to its moisture content (9.24 %). Increase in moisture increases the bulk density of the extruded products making it more dense and hard. The sample 3 had more force of 35.38 N as its carbohydrate (55.9%) and protein (8.3%) was comparatively higher when compared to other samples. Wheat has a higher protein and lower starch content compared to rice and corn, therefore extruded wheat products are harder and less expanded (Riaz, 2006). They are often described as crunchy because of a complex failure mechanism that involves the repetitive

deformation and fracturing of the cell structure. These products exhibit a classical brittle failure mechanism as a consequence of their cellularity and lack of structural resiliency.

Functional Properties

Water absorption and solubility index:

Water absorption index is an important functional characteristic in extruded products as high water absorption index assures cohesiveness of the product. It gives an indication of the amount of water needed to form gruel. Water solubility index describes the rate and extent to which the component of powdered extruded material is dissolved in water which depends on its chemical composition and physical state. It is used as an indicator of degradation of molecular components, measures the degree of starch conversion during extrusion which is the amount of soluble polysaccharides released from the starch components after extrusion. The water absorption index of the snacks varied from 3.77 to 5.31 whereas the water solubility ranged from 19.8 to 34. The difference observed could be attributed to the nature of the raw materials and the extrusion conditions like moisture content, screw speed, extrusion temperature etc.

Different Attributes of the Existing Extruded Snacks

CONCLUSION

The market demand of RTE snacks is likely to increase exponentially in the coming years due to the convenience attached with them. Economically, from the entrepreneur point of view RTE have a huge potential as a profitable venture. The RTE snacks available in the market right now are costly as well as nutritionally inadequate. A competitive product with better nutritional quality should be made available to the consumers which can be achieved by exploring cheaper but nutritional alternatives with an aim of lowering the cost and enhancing the nutritional composition of the product. For a manufacturing entrant, the study will be very useful as it provides the values for different parameters such as moisture, hardness, water solubility index, water absorption index and color. These parameters play an important role in selection of ingredient during the designing of a new product, but are not listed on the label of these products. There is a void in the snack market for meeting specific needs of target customers with specific health issues which can be explored by the entrepreneurs.

REFERENCES

- AACC (2000). *Approved methods of American Association of Cereal Chemists* (10th ed.). St. Paul, MN: The Association.
- Altan A, McCarthy L, Kathryn M M (2008). Extrusion cooking of barley flour and process parameter optimization by using response surface methodology. *J Sci. Food Agri* **88**(9):1648–1659.
- Champenois Y M, Rao A and Walker L P (1998). Influence of α -amylase on the viscoelastic properties of starch-gluten pastes and gels. *J Sci Food Agri* **78**: 127-133.
- Dehghan-Shoar Z, Hardacre A K and Brennan C S (2010). The physico-chemical characteristics of extruded snacks enriched with tomatolycopene. *Food Chem* **123** (4): 1117-1122.
- Derby R I, Miller B S, Miller B F and Trimbo H B (1975). Visual observation of wheat-starch gelatinization in limited water systems. *Cereal Chem* **52**: 702-713.
- Hwang M P and Hayakawa K I (1980). Bulk densities of cookies undergoing commercial baking processes. *J Food Sci* **45**: 1400–1402.
- Jamora J J, Rhee K S and Rhee K C (2002). Chemical and sensory properties of expanded extrudates from pork meat-defatted soy flour blends with onion, carrot and oat. *J Food Sci and Nutr* **6**:158–162.
- Kaur G J, Rehal J, Singh A K, Singh B and Kaur A (2014). Optimization of extrusion parameters for development of ready-to-eat breakfast cereal using RSM. *Asian J Dairy and Food Res* **33** (2): 77-86.
- Rehal J, Kaur G J, Kaur A and Singh A K (2015). Evaluation of Physicochemical and Functional Properties of Cereal Based Porridges Available in Indian Market. *Intl J Sci Adv Res Technol* **1**(6):90-98.
- Liu Y, Hsieh F, Heymann H and Huff H E (2000). Effect of process conditions on the physical and sensory properties of extruded oat-corn puff. *J Food Sci* **65**:1253-1259.
- Matthey F P and Hanna M A (1997). Physical and functional properties of twin-screw extruded whey protein concentrate–corn starch blends. *LWT - Food Sci and Technol* **30**: 359–366.
- Mazumder P, Roopa B S and Bhattacharya S (2007). Textural attributes of a model snack food at different moisture contents. *J Food Engg* **79**(2): 511-516.
- Nyombaire G, Siddiq M and Dolan K D (2011). Physico-chemical and sensory quality of extruded light red kidney bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) porridge. *LWT - Food Sci Technol* **44**:1597-1602.
- Riaz M N (2006). “*Extruded snacks*”. In: *Handbook of Food Science Technology and Engineering*. (eds Y H Hui) Vol. 4. Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press.

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Crop Residue in Punjab Agriculture- Status and Constraints

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ABSTRACT

With 70 per cent of net sown area under paddy in kharif season and 84.6 percent of it under wheat crop in rabi season , the crop residue is generated in huge quantities. Out of this 95 per cent of paddy straw and 25 per cent of wheat straw is burnt each year. The hazardous practice has affected health, air ,road safety, soil etc. leading to massive physical as well as monetary losses. The present study has been based on primary data collected from three agri-economic zones of the state to highlight the constraints pertaining to the issue. For the state as a whole, 67.47 per cent of the total sampled farmers reported not burning the residue of the crops. Lack of buyers, shortage of time for next crop, lack of assistance by the state government and labour shortage emerged as the major reasons for the ongoing practice. Measures like utilizing it as animal feed, subsidy on machines like 'Happy seeder' generating lesser amount of straw during harvesting, use in cardboard factories, power generation, compost making, new crop varieties producing lesser residue as well as lower wages to carry on manual harvesting were suggested by the sampled farmers to deal with the issue. Creating awareness among farmers about eco-loss and significance of the problem itself at various fora along with strict implementation of the law prohibiting the burning of crop residue can be of further help in handing the major concern of the state.

Key Words: Crop Residue, Agriculture, Status, Constraints, Suggestions.

INTRODUCTION

There is a large variability in production of crop residue, and their use depends on the crops grown, cropping intensity, and productivity in different regions of India (Singh and Sidhu, 2014). Cereal crops (rice, wheat, maize, millets) contribute 70 per cent of the total crop residue (352 Mt) comprising 34 per cent by rice and 22 per cent by wheat crops. The rice-wheat system accounts for nearly one-fourth of the total residue produced in India. The surplus residue of crops (total residues produced minus the amount used for various purposes) is traditionally burnt on-farm. The amount of surplus crop residue available in India is estimated between 84 and 141 Mt per annum where cereals crops contribute 58 per cent. Of the 82 Mt of surplus of it nearly 70 MTs (44.5 Mt rice straws and 24.5 Mt wheat straws) are burnt annually.

Punjab is predominately an agrarian state and largest contributor of food grains to the central

pool. With 28 lakh hectares under wheat and paddy cultivation in the state, a total of 47.2 lakh tones of straw is generated every year. This included 25 lakh tones of wheat straw and 22 lakh tones of paddy straw. Out of this 95 per cent of paddy straw and 25 per cent of wheat straw is burnt each year. The mechanized harvesting of these crops has further added to the quantity of residue. At the time of manual harvesting, the straw was chopped into small pieces and ploughed back into the soil to improve its content. Though, a ban was imposed on stubble burning by the state government way back in 2005, but the practice is still going on due non- implementation of the ban. The problem has been highlighted by the United States National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) and Supreme Court of India has also taken a serious note of it, but of no avail. Impact is manifold i.e. air as well as soil pollution, health hazards, road safety etc. Air pollution caused by the residue burning

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especially with paddy stubble is increasing every year. The air quality deteriorates during that time. The carbon dioxide level in air shoots up by 70 per cent, while concentration of carbon monoxide and nitrogen dioxide rises by 7 percent and 2.1 percent, thus causing respiratory and cardio vascular problems.

According to study conducted by centre for sustainable agriculture, Hyderabad, the burning of a tonne of straw releases 3 kg particulate matter, 60 kg. carbon monoxide, 1460 kg. carbon dioxide, 199 kg ash and 2 kg sulphur oxide in the air. Apart from this, the practice causes massive loss to the soil, both in terms of nutrients and micronutrients. As per the study conducted by Department of Soils, PAU, Ludhiana in 2010, the soil loses 6-7 kg nitrogen per tonne, 1-1.7 kg phosphorus, 14-25 kg potassium and 1.2-1.5 kg sulphur due to stubble burning. This leads to an additional expenditure of Rs. 150 crore per year to replenish the soil. Preservation of organic carbons is must as these boost the water holding capacity of the soil. About 38 lakh tones of organic carbon is lost every year due to burning of soil and 32 kg of urea, 5.5 kg diammonium phosphate and 51 kg of potash per acre is lost.

The loss of fertility leads to loss of one quintal extra yield of wheat crop and that could be obtained if the farmer ploughs back the paddy straw into the fields. So, the monetary losses attributed to this practice have been estimated at around Rs. 500 crore per annum in terms of loss of fertility, additional nutrients and loss of yield due to stubble burning. Burning of wheat/paddy straw raises the temperature of the soil in the top 3 inches to such high degree that the equilibrium of carbon: Nitrogen ratio (11:1), the percent bacteria (4:1), and the percent fungi (9:1) are rapidly changed. Keeping in view the above mentioned facts, the present study was undertaken to highlight the quantity of crop residue generated in two cropping seasons as well as constraints related to its management in Punjab.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study has been based on primary data collected from farm households of different

categories in Punjab and was devised on randomly selected 10 blocks from three agri-economic zones viz. sub- mountainous zone, central plain zone and south western zone of the state. At second stage of sampling, two villages were selected from each selected block and 25 farm households were selected from each village based on size of their operational holding and were divided into three categories i.e. small(up to 2 ha), medium(>2-4 ha) and large(> 4 ha). Thus, the ultimate sample consisted of 495 farm households in proportion to the size holding structure existing in that particular village. To find out the extent of generation of crop residue at farm level, its disposal pattern as well as the constraints faced by the farmers in its management, primary data were collected from selected sample of farm households across the state through especially structured and pre-tested questionnaire through personal interview method. Suggestions were also sought from the respondents to deal with the issue. The primary data were supplemented with secondary data on some parameters. Statistical techniques like percentage, average etc. were worked out for the variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Punjab has witnessed high cropping intensity with emergence of rice-wheat system since the inception of green revolution. With 70 per cent of net sown area under paddy in kharif season and 84.6 per cent of it under wheat crop in rabi season, the crop residue is generated in huge quantities under this cropping system.

Wheat is the main Rabi crop in sub-mountainous zone of the state (Zone I). The study found that in this zone on an average 11.21 q/farm of wheat straw was generated. In kharif season, residue of paddy here was 7.43q/farm, maximum being on medium farms i.e.13 q/farm and of maize was 12q/farm. The respondent farmers when questioned about disposing pattern of the straw, majority denied burning the residue. In I zone, wheat and maize being the main crops 95.65 percent of the farmers reported not burning the stubble. Here, only one

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small and one medium farmer cultivating paddy have reported burning of crop residue in kharif season.

Central plain zone of the state (Zone II) is the wheat-paddy zone. The residue generated in this zone was estimated to be 14.96q/farm for wheat crop and 11.9q/farm of paddy. For other kharif crops it was found to be 18.23q/farm. In this zone 58 per cent of the respondents reported that they have not resorted to burning of the straw, with maximum number of small farmers denying the practice.

The third zone of the state is the cotton belt with cotton as main kharif crop. In this zone on an average residue generated of wheat crop was 13.97q/farm. With small area under paddy, the residue generated was also less i.e. 2.28q/farm. In case of cotton crop it was estimated to be 12.56 q/ farm. In this zone 77.48 per cent of the respondents denied the practice of burning the residue.

For the state as a whole, 67.47 per cent of the total sampled farmers reported not burning the residue of the crops. On the whole, residue generated of wheat crop was about 14.31q/farm, 5.78q in case of paddy and 16.37q/farm for other crops but 75.67 per cent of the small farmers, 65.32 per cent of medium farmers and 57 per cent of large farmers denied the burning of crop residues.

Residue Disposal

With mechanized harvesting residue is left in the fields. While about 75 per cent of wheat straw is collected as fodder for animals, rice straw is considered poor feed for animals due to its high silica content. Therefore, management of paddy straw is more serious problem than that of wheat (Ladha *et al*, 2000). Added to this there are factors like shorter time gap between harvesting of paddy and sowing of wheat, scarcity of labour as well as lack of proper technology of crop residue management. With lesser options available at the farm level farmers are reluctant to clear the fields with chopper as it adds to their cost. So, burning of crop residue seems the quickest and cheapest option to clear the fields in the absence of strict implementation of the law against this practice. Presently, more than 80 per cent of total rice straw produced annually is being burnt by the famers in 3-4 weeks during October-November (Singh *et al*,2010).

Reasons for Burning of Crop Residue

Sampled farmers resorted to multiple responses for justifying the practice of stubble burning. In zone 1, the reason that dominated for undertaking the practice was lack of State Government's assistance to dispose it off in any alternative way. One farmer also reported the shortage of labour and higher wages for disposing it off. Farmers also reported that there were no takers for the residue.

Table 1. Constraints regarding disposal of crop residue reported by sampled farmers.

Punjab	Small	Medium	Large	Total
Labour shortage and costly	10(4.50)	4(3.22)	2(14.09)	35(7.07)
Preparation for Next crop	27(12.16)	26(20.96)	38(25.50)	91(18.38)
Shortage of time	25(11.26)	14(11.29)	28(18.79)	67(13.53)
Lack of machinery	3(1.35)	3(2.41)	4(2.68)	10(2.02)
Costly Machines	2(0.90)	1(0.80)	5(3.35)	8(1.61)
Lack of buyers	41(18.46)	27(21.77)	25(16.77)	93(18.78)
Not easy mixing in fields	0(0)	1(0.80)	2(1.34)	3(0.60)
No Govt. help for sale of residue	19(8.55)	26(20.96)	28(18.79)	73(14.74)

Figures in parenthesis indicate the percentage to total.

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In zone 2, where highest number of farmers accepted that they are going in for burning of straw, gave the reason that they could not find the buyers for the residue especially of paddy. The haste to sow next crop was also cited as a reason by a large number of farmers. Shortage of time to clear the fields as well as shortage of labour was also quoted as the reasons for the practice. Again, lack of state help to dispose it off lucratively emerged as a major reason for burning it. Small number of respondents about, 1 per cent also found lack of proper machinery to dispose off the residue or if it is available it is very expensive.

In south-western zone (zone 3) of the state also, lack of buyers for the crop residue emerged as the major reason for burning it. Shortage of time and haste to clear the fields for next crop were the other important reasons. No assistance provided by the state government was given an important reason by the large number of farmers in this zone. They also quoted labour shortage as a reason for it. In the light of reasons quoted by respondents for stubble fires, the experts also support that mechanized harvesting has been adopted by the farmers, but when it comes to straw management machinery, they do not show any interest.

Punjab Agricultural University as well as state government has come up with machines like happy seeders, straw choppers and other harrow machines, but their prices run into lakhs of rupees. So, there is lack of technological support to the farmers in this aspect. Then, ignorance on the part of farmers regarding loss of soil fertility with this practice is also one of the major reasons. The National Farmers Empowerment Initiative (NFEI) is of the opinion that there was no short duration variety of wheat with optimum yield in the state. So, even a delay of one week in the sowing of wheat crop resulted in a loss of 375kg produce per hectare as the grain shriveled up in february-march due to rise in temperature. So, this adds to severity of problem in paddy crop, as farmers want quick clearance of their fields for wheat crop.

Suggestions regarding residue disposal

In zone I, 100 per cent of the sampled farmers were against burning to straw. The major suggestion given by about 35 per cent of the farmers was that dairy farmers should take away the residue and prepare it as an animal feed. 32 per cent opined that it should be utilized to generate energy. 28 per cent

Table 2. Suggestions regarding residue disposal by sampled farmers.

Suggestion	Small	Medium	Large	Total
It should not be burnt	222(100)	124(100)	149(100)	495(100)
Lack of buyers	8(3.60)	6(4.83)	5(3.35)	19(3.83)
Develop new variety	5(2.25)	3(2.41)	4(2.68)	12(2.42)
Subsidized machines for disposal	27(12.16)	15(12.09)	28(18.79)	70(14.14)
Industrial use like Card board factories	12(5.40)	4(3.22)	7(4.69)	23(4.64)
Power generation	21(9.45)	15(12.09)	10(6.71)	46(9.29)
Govt assistance to sell	68(30.63)	50(40.32)	62(41.61)	180(36.36)
Need for cheap Labour	2(0.90)	1(0.80)	2(1.34)	5(1.01)
Low price	0(0.0)	1(0.80)	0(0.0)	1(0.20)
Use to feed cattle	34(15.31)	16(12.90)	8(5.36)	58(11.71)
Mix in Soil	16(7.20)	18(14.51)	37(24.83)	71(14.34)
Use in dairy farms	80(36.03)	37(29.83)	25(16.77)	142(28.68)
Given free	47(21.17)	21(16.93)	17(11.40)	85(17.17)

Figures in parenthesis indicate the percentage to total

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of the respondents suggested that it should be sold to cardboard factories. 8 per cent were willing to give it without any change to any user. 6 per cent sought help of the government in disposal of straw, while 4 per cent stressed on development of new varieties generating less stubble and thus no need of burning it. The main suggestion put forward by majority of respondents i.e. 43 per cent in zone 2 was need of government assistance in crop residue disposal or the farmers showed their helplessness to dispose of the massive straw generated in this zone. About 20 per cent of the respondents were in favour of selling it to dairy farmers so that they can convert it into animal feed. 20 per cent were in favour of subsidy on the machinery that can dispose it off. In the absence of any buyers for the stubble, 17 per cent were willing to give it free if anybody can put it to same use. 14 per cent of sampled farmers favoured its mixing in the soil on scientific lines to improve the nutrient status of the soil. Nearly 3 per cent of respondents favoured the development of those varieties producing less stubble.

All the sampled farmers of zone 3 were against the burning of straw. Here also, the major suggestion given by 43.7 per cent of respondents was to convert it into animal feed by dairy farmers. 32 per cent of sampled farmers favoured government assistance to dispose it off. Due to lack of any takers more than 20 per cent of farmers were ready to dispose it off without any charge for any purpose, 20 per cent of the farmers also suggested mixing of residue in the soil as per recommendation. However, 7 per cent demanded subsidy on expensive machinery that generates lesser straw while harvesting, 6 per cent of the farmers proposed to generate energy from the straw and 3 per cent suggested that cardboard factories should utilize it.

So, it was found that all the sampled farmers were against burning of crop residue in principle, but majority of them could not find any solution at individual level and were seeking government assistance to dispose it off. About 29 per cent suggested utilizing it as animal feed and 14 per cent want subsidy on machines like 'Happy

seeder' generating lesser amount of straw during harvesting. As there was no useful alternative to the farmers, so in the absence of any buyer, 17 per cent were willing to give free to who so ever put it to any use. 4 per cent of the respondents suggested that it should be used by cardboard making factories, small proportion of respondents favour that new crop varieties should be developed producing lesser residue as well as lower wages to carry on manual harvesting rather than machined which, generates more residue.

CONCLUSION

Thus, it is clear that farmers were well aware about the environmental problems related to residue disposal and various concerns thereof. They highlighted the constraints regarding the issue on the basis of prevailing practices as well as their experience. Different suggestions were put forward by the respondents to tackle these concerns, involving government action whether co-operative or coercive. Some measures to deal with the problem can be creating awareness among farmers about eco-loss and significance of the problem itself at various fora, strict implementation of the law prohibiting the burning of crop residue, custom hiring of expensive machinery for chopping of stubble, off farm utilization as suggested by farmers in industry, power generation, compost making etc.

REFERENCES

- Ladha J K, Fischer K S, Hossain M, Hobbs P R and Hardy B (2000). Improving the Productivity and Sustainability of Rice-Wheat Systems of the Indo-Gangetic Plains: A Synthesis of NARS-IRRI Partnership Research. Discussion Paper No. 40. International Rice Research Institute, Los Baños Philippines
- Singh Y and H S Sidhu (2014). Management of Cereal Crop Residues for Sustainable Rice-Wheat Production System in the Indo-Gangetic Plains of India 2Proc Indian Natn Sci Acad 80 : 95-114
- Singh Y, Singh M, Sidhu H S, Khanna P K, Kapoor S, Jain A K, Singh A K, Sidhu G K, Singh A, Chaudhary D P and Minhas P S (2010). Options for effective utilization of crop residues. Directorate of Research, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, India.

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Diagnosis and Remedial Measures of Common Technological Problems in Bee Keeping

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of Krishi Vigyan Kendra (KVK) is to help the farmers in the command area in the field of agriculture and allied sectors. During the last 3 years i.e. from 2013 to 2015, a record of all the visiting farmers was maintained in the plant health diagnostic laboratory at the KVK, in which complete details of the farmer with address and contact number was maintained. Similarly, the purpose of visiting KVK was recorded date wise by the KVK scientist and at the end of each month, a summary was prepared and analysed. It was inferred that majority of the farmers enquired about management of wax moth and varroa mite which reveals that these are the most important pests of honey bees and their products and cause serious losses in commercial beekeeping. Out of total 71 farmers who visited the KVK with queries pertaining to the honey bees from January to December months, 43.7 per cent farmers (31 farmers) enquired about management of wax moth and 40.8 per cent farmers (29 farmers) enquired about management of varroa mite which confirms that these were the two most devastating pests of honey bees. The other problems faced by the farmers were colony collapse due to severe cold (4.2% farmers), management of honey bees during different seasons (4.2 per cent farmers) and problem of robbing (2.8% farmers).

Key Words: Diagnosis, Technological problems, Insect Pest, Diseases, Honey Bees.

INTRODUCTION

Bee keeping is a profitable enterprise that requires little investment. Punjab farmers have taken up bee keeping on a large scale. Punjab has the largest number of 3,00,000 colonies, followed by Haryana (10,500 colonies), Himachal Pradesh (50,000 colonies) and J& K (15,000 colonies). There are 30,000 bee keepers in Punjab and honey production in 14,000mt. A large number of factors affect honey bee and hence the production of honey like honey bee do not do well in coniferous forests, in deserts where there are long stretches of sand dunes, in heavy monsoon areas and in cropped areas where insecticides are applied extensively by ground or aerial spraying. Similarly, a large number of insects act as enemies of the honey bee, but their attack is not serious in all cases. Some, like the wax moths and varroa mite, are extremely damaging and can cause absconding and death of a colony. Wasps an hornet, near relatives of the honey bees,

actively prey upon them and also rob them of their brood, depleting colony strength to such an extent that bee keeping cannot be practiced in the area of their abundance.

As far as diseases are concerned, there are a number of serious diseases of immature stages and of adult honeybees. Some are contagious caused by pathogens, others are non-contagious caused by physiological disorders or by poisons in the environment. The pathogens include viruses, bacteria, fungi, protozoa, mites etc. For the last so many years, every year, a large number of farmers visited KVK, Kapurthala to have guidance from the scientists posted at the Kendra. It has been reported earlier that during different seasons in a year, number of farmers seeking technical guidance regarding agriculture and allied fields varied to a large extent (Kaur, 2016). Therefore, it was planned to ascertain the areas in which farmers made most of the queries so that the Kendra can make changes

in the action plan so that maximum farmers can be benefitted. Keeping in view the above facts, it was planned to classify the data pertaining to number of farmers who visited KVK campus in the plant disease diagnostic laboratory pertaining to honey bee keeping to get the problem solved with the advice of scientist posted at the Kendra.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

During the last 3 years i.e. from 2013 to 2015, record of all the visiting farmers was maintained in the plant health diagnostic laboratory at the KVK, in which complete details of the farmer with address and contact number was maintained. Similarly, the purpose of visiting KVK was recorded date wise by the KVK scientist and at the end of each month, a summary was prepared and analysed for severity of the attack of insect pest and diseases. The data were classified month wise and problem wise to note down the extent of damage caused by the insect pests, diseases or other agencies on honey bees. The samples were diagnosed using simple microscope, compound microscope and preparing slides of the diseased specimen to know the pathogen involved for diagnosis. Based on the results of the diagnosed specimen, the bee keepers were advised to follow the recommendations accordingly.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Insect pests of honey bees

Data (Table 1) showed that out of 71 farmers who visited the KVK campus with queries pertaining to honey bees, per cent values for the month of January, February, March, April, May, June, July, August, September, October, November and December were 2.9, 1.7, 15.4, 0.8, 1.2, 26.2, 6.7, 7.1, 2.5, 1.2, 5.9 and 28.4 per cent, respectively. It was inferred that majority of the farmers enquired about management of wax moth and varroa mite which reveals that these are the most important pest of honey bees and their products and cause serious losses in commercial beekeeping.

Attack of wax moth

Out of 71 farmers who visited the KVK with queries pertaining to the honey bees from January to December months, 43.7 per cent farmers (31 farmers) enquired about management of wax moth which confirms that it is the most devastating pest of honey bees. Secondly, a constant number of farmers visited the KVK with queries pertaining to its management in every month of the year which again confirms its devastating nature and its activeness throughout the year. Maximum number of farmers (12.9%) enquired about its management in the month of September because of the two reasons. Firstly, in this month, the colony was unable to defend itself due to its low strength which was due to shortage of bee flora. Secondly, the left over raised combs in the hive (due to weak strength of the colony) have to be removed and kept in storage for further use in the coming peak season when bee flora is maximum. The larvae of the wax moth destroy raised combs in storage also by tunneling through near the midrib of a comb in search of pollen, wax and protein of the pupal skins and the farmers do not know the right procedure of storage of these raised combs.

The farmers were advised to follow the prophylactic measures which are more effective in keeping an apiary free from this pestilence as controlling this pest inside a hive in active season is not so easy. The farmers were advised to keep the bee colony stronger as a stronger bee colony itself is able to manage this pest. The farmers were also advised to keep the bottom board clean and burn the collected debris from the bottom board as a large number of eggs are laid by the moth on bee wax or in debris on the bottom board, to keep cracks and crevices in the hive plugged and to remove extra empty combs from the colony and store them properly with fumigation as fumigation with a poisonous gas kills all stages of the wax moth.

Periodic fumigation was advised keeping in view its activeness throughout the year. In the

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hibernating season, the farmers were advised to pick the cocoons from inside the hives and destroy. Similarly, the farmers were advised to kill the sluggish moths by swatting. Once the colony have been taken over by the wax moths, the farmers were advised to shift the bee to new combs and uninfested frames.

Attack of varroa mite

During January to December months, 40.8 per cent farmers (29 farmers) enquired about management of varroa mite which confirmed that it is the second most devastating pest of honey bees after wax moth. A constant number of farmers visited the KVK with queries pertaining to its management almost every month of the year which showed that it is active throughout the year. Maximum queries regarding its management were obtained in the month of November (27.6%), December (20.7%) and January (13.8%). This may be because of the reason that during this time brood rearing on large scale has just been initiated by the hive due to abundance of bee flora because the life cycle is started by a fertilized female living on adult bee and entering an uncapped cell containing 5d old worker or drone larva where the mite first feed on the left over royal jelly remaining in the cells. She lays her first eggs 60 hr after the cell is capped and more eggs at various intervals of one day or so. Depending upon the amount of damage caused, the honey bee adults emerge with various degrees of body deformities.

Regarding its management, the farmers were advised to trap varroa on drone brood as it is more attracted to drone brood and to cut and destroy the infested drone brood comb part. Secondly, the placement of a sticky paper covered with 8 mesh screen on the bottom board make the fallen mite stuck to it and prevents their return to the brood combs. Thirdly, dusting finely ground sugar @ 20g/10 bee frame strength colony, uniformly between the inter-comb spaces in the late evening time reduces infestation of the mite. In the chemical methods, the farmers were advised to treat colonies

with formic acid (85%) @ 5 ml/d continuously for two weeks.

Colony collapse due to severe cold

Out of total farmers, 4.2 per cent farmers (3 farmers) enquired about management of honey bees in the winter season because their honey bee colonies get collapsed due to severe cold which prevails in the district usually during the month of December. From the discussion with the bee keepers, the reason for this was found to be same for all the bee keepers. The honey bee colonies of these bee keepers were very weak at the onset of winter. Weaker honey bee colonies are usually found because before the winter season i.e. in the autumn season scarcity of bee flora occurs which leads to their weaker strength and weak colonies are unable to pass the winter season as *Apis mellifera* are sensitive to cold and stop their field activity at 7°C.

To overcome this menace, the bee keepers were advised to unite the weak colonies with stronger ones, using newspaper method and very weak colonies can be united into single chamber using vertical queen excluder and thirdly the bee keepers were advised to shift colonies to Raya growing areas of Punjab, Haryana and Rajasthan to sustain bee activities and brood rearing.

Management of honey during different seasons

The next very problem, about which the bee keepers enquired the most, was the management of honey bees in different seasons. There are five different seasons in Punjab and management practices are usually different, except some, during different seasons. 2.8 per cent farmers enquired about the management of honey bees in the winter and spring seasons each whereas 1.4 per cent farmers asked about management of honey bees in the summer season. The beekeepers asked about the general management practices during the different seasons and no critical problem had been faced by the beekeepers during the respective season.

Table 1. Monthwise – per cent farmers visited KVK regarding problems in honey bee keeping. (average of 3 years)

Sr. No.	Problem	Total farmers	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Per cent farmers
1	Attack of wax moth	31	9.7	6.5	9.7	3.2	6.5	9.7	3.2	3.2	12.9	9.7	19.4	6.5	43.7
2	Attack of varroa mite	29	13.8	6.9	13.8	3.4	3.4	0.0	0.0	3.4	6.9	0.0	27.6	20.7	40.8
3	Management of honey bees in spring season	2	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.8
4	Problem of robbing	2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	50.0	50.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.8
5	Problem of laying workers	1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.4
6	Management in summer	1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.4
7	Management in winter	2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	2.8
8	Colony collapse due to severe cold	3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	4.2
	Total	71	2.9	1.7	15.4	0.8	1.2	26.2	6.7	7.1	2.5	1.2	5.9	28.4	100.0

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As most of the bee keepers were trained one and know about the general management practices which one has to follow during the respective season, this may be the reason that very less number of bee keepers enquired about the management practices in the different seasons. The only bee keepers who enquired about the management of bees in the different seasons were the beginners. Hence, for management during the winter season, the beginners were advised to move the colonies to sunny places and to provide inner packing to weak colonies with dry paddy straw (prali) wrapped in newspaper or polythene sheets and outer packing with polythene sheet.

The beginners were further advised to examine colonies only on some calm and sunny days during noon time, grow wind breaks, plug cracks and crevices, narrow down the hive entrance and to place the colonies with entrance facing south-east to protect bees from chilly winds because these are the management practices which help the bees to maintain their inside temperature in the hive during the winter season. As far as the management during the summer season is concerned, the beginners were advised to keep the colonies at raised place and clear the vegetation growing around the colonies because these practices help to improve ventilation in colonies and keep the hive cool.

Problem of robbing

The problem of robbing was observed in honey bee colonies which were weak ones. Out of total farmers, 2.8 per cent farmers (2 farmers) enquired about its management in the month of July and August. Very less number of farmers enquired about its management. Actually it is a problem related to the scarcity of bee flora and hence can be easily cured either by shifting the colonies to the places where the bee flora is abundant or by providing

supplementary sugar: water feeding to the honey bee colonies.

As most of the bee keepers were well aware of the type of bee behavior which the bees generally show when robbing takes place and they have also included providing the supplementary sugar: water feeding during the lean period in their management practice, hence it may be the reason that very less number of bee keepers asked about the management of this problem. One thing to note that the bee keepers who enquired about this problem were the beginners and small bee keepers who were unable to shift the colonies to places of abundant bee flora or were unaware to provide the supplementary sugar solution during the lean period. To get rid of this problem, the beginners were advised to provide sugar feeding in the evening, to make colonies bee proof, by plugging cracks and crevices and reducing the entrance to one-bee feeding and prevent spillage of feed in the apiary or outside the colonies.

CONCLUSION

Plant health clinic established at KVK, Kapurthala is a unique initiative tried by the Krishi Vigyan Kendra to link the farmers with the scientific knowledge. There is need for adopting innovative strategies and more importantly adopting multipronged initiative and timely diagnostic and management strategies from plant health clinic to combat attack from pests and environmental stress, manage plant health mitigate losses.

REFERENCES

Kaur Gagandeep, Singh Gurmeet, Sharma Manoj, Singh Gobinder and Manan Jatinder (2016). Use of Plant Disease Diagnostic Laboratory in Identifying Insect Pests and Diseases of Fruit and Vegetable Crops. *J Krishi Vigyan* 5(1) : 107-113.

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Eco Friendly Management of Arecanut Root Grub (*Leucopholis lepidophora* Blanchard) in Hilly Tracts of Uttar Kannada, Karnataka

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ABSTRACT

Amongst the several factors attributed for lower productivity of Arecanut, damage by root grubs is substantially important in Malnad belt of Uttar Kannada district. The root grubs cause damage to the arecanut tree by directly feeding on roots resulting in symptoms like yellowing of leaves, stem tapering at the crown region, reduced inter-node length, nut fall and ultimately leads to reduced vigour, yield and death of plant. To manage this insect, usually insecticides are recommended but farmers of this district are reluctant to use chemical pesticides due to the deleterious effects on soil health, fauna and flora. Indigenous technical knowledge followed by the farmers were documented in 15 villages of three taluks viz., Sirsi, Siddapur and Yellapur and based on scientific validation, an on farm trial was conducted to evaluate the feasibility and economic viability of aqueous extract of soap nut and neem oil 5 % mixture and entomopathogenic fungi, *Metarhizium anisopliae* 2 X 10⁸ conidia /g @ 20 g per palm tree against root grubs in arecanut during 2009-12 at farmers' fields. The results revealed that the recommended practice i.e. drenching with chlorpyrifos 20 EC @ 10 ml/l of water (3-4l of solution per palm tree) recorded highest grub mortality of 86.83 per cent as against 64.88 per cent in aqueous extract of soap nut and neem oil 5 % mixture treated palms. Appearance of new healthy green frond and improvement in the growth of the palms are the visual indicators. Neem oil and soap nut extract was the best alternative to chemical insecticides, locally available and is ecofriendly.

Key Words : Arecanut, Root grub, Neem oil, Soap nut, Eco-friendly.

INTRODUCTION

Arecanut (*Areca catechu* L.) cultivation in the valley forms the main feature of the Uttar Kannada district, Karnataka and cultivated in an area of 17,912 ha with a production of 43,864Mt. The district has a rich heritage of floral and faunal diversity. Arecanut crop is attacked by an array of insect and non insect pests. Amongst them, the root infesting scarabaeid white grub, *Leucopholis lepidophora* Blanch (Scarabaeidae : Coleoptera) is a major pest and is widely distributed in Western ghats area of Karnataka(Veeresh *et al*, 1982).

The root grubs cause damage to arecanut tree by directly feeding on roots resulting in symptoms like yellowing of leaves, stem tapering at the crown region, reduced inter-node length, nut fall and ultimately leads to reduced vigour, yield and death of

plant (Nair and Daniel, 1982). The probable reasons for root grub menace in Uttar Kannada district are conversion of paddy fields into arecanut gardens without proper drainage, difficulty in collection of emerging adults during July to August, unaware about the application of plant protection chemicals and lack of community approach in managing rootgrubs. Present management practices include synthetic insecticides as major component but the farmers in Uttar Kannada district are reluctant to use chemical pesticides to soil due to its deleterious effects on soil flora and fauna apart from soil pollution. Farming community of this region is well known for practicing indigenous farming technology for the management of insect pest and diseases. Hence, an on farm trial was planned to study the feasibility and economic viability

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of Indigenous technical knowledge (ITK) and entomopathogenic fungi against this insect pest in farmers fields of Uttar Kannada district.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Uttar Kannada district (13055' to 15032' N and 7406' to 7507' E) is situated in the North West part of Karnataka adjoining the state of Goa. The documentation of Indigenous Technology Knowledge (ITK) of farmers in Uttar kannada district for management of insect pests of arecanut was carried out through questionnaire method in Sirsi, Yellapur and Siddapur taluks of Uttar Kannada district. An OFT was planned based on the scientific validation of most effective ITK i.e. performance of soap nut and neem oil aqueous extract @5 % and the entomopathogenic fungi, *Metarrihizium anisopliae* (Metsch.) for three consecutive years 2009-12 in already infested arecanut garden of 15 to 18 years old at Vaddinakoppa village of Sirsi Taluk. The trials were conducted in five farmers' fields with four treatments. Twenty palms were maintained for each treatment. Before the experiment, the population of grubs in palm basins was ascertained by random sampling. The treatments were imposed in the month of September. The *M. anisopliae* with 2×10^8 conidia /g was applied @ 20 g per palm at

the root zone of arecanut along with 2 kg farm yard manure (FYM). The plant extract was prepared afresh before imposition of treatment. To prepare 5 % of aqueous extract, 500 g of dry soapnut fruits were soaked in 2.5l of water for 72 hr. Later the fruits were squeezed thoroughly to get profuse frothing. The solution was filtered and mixed with 500 ml of neem oil and volume made up to 10 liters. Ready solution of 3 liters was applied to the soil in root zone of areca nut tree by drenching around the tree trunk.

In case of recommended practice, chlorpyriphos 20 EC@ 10 ml of insecticide formulation in one liter of water was prepared and such three liters of solution was drenched to the soil around the tree. In farmers practice, chlorpyriphos solution was applied at varying concentration twice in a year. Observations on larval mortality was recorded at 60 days after treatment (DAT) imposition by digging the soil at the base of tree and counting the grubs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results (Table 1) revealed that recommended practice, Chlorpyriphos 20 EC at the rate of 10 ml per liter proved to be highly effective treatment with 86.83 per cent mortality of grubs at 60 days after treatment. Though the average grub mortality

Table 1. Efficacy of plant extracts and bio pesticide in the management of arecanut root grub (2009 to 2012).

Treatment	Per cent Larval mortality at 60 Days after treatment (DAT)			
	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12	Mean
T1 : Farmers practice, Untimely soil application of insecticides	40.6	54.82	45.65	47.02
T2 : Recommended practice, Drenching of soil with chlorpyriphos 20 EC @ 10 ml/l of water	83.85	91.65	85.00	86.83
T3 : Alternate practice, Drenching of soil with mixture of neem oil and soap nut aqueous extract 5%	60.15	72.00	62.50	64.88
T4 : Alternate practice, Application of <i>M. anisopliae</i> with 2×10^8 conidia /g @ 20 g per palm + 2 kg FYM	36.52	32.85	56.5	41.96

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was around 64.88 per cent in treatment drenching of soil with mixture of neem oil and soap nut aqueous extract 5 %, but found effective against farmers practice (47.02 % larval mortality) and application of *M. anisopliae* (41.96 % larval mortality) .

These results of neem oil and soap nut extract were in line with the work of Rakesha *et al* (2011) who reported 59.26 per cent larval mortality of areca root grubs under laboratory conditions. Prabhu *et al* (2011) also recorded 53.55 per cent root grub mortality under large scale trails in farmers fields at Sirsi taluk, Uttar Kannada district. The results of chlorpyrifos corroborate with the reports of Channakeshavamurthy *et al* (2010) and Subaharan *et al* (2001) . Since the yield levels of arecanut can not be compared with the larval mortality, but, the appearance of new healthy green frond and improvement in growth of the palms could be the visual indicators.

The reduced mortality of grub in farmers practice may be due to wrong time of application of insecticides and the dosage. Considering the emergence pattern of adults and oviposition, it was observed that application of plant protection measures after the monsoon i.e., during September and October would yield desirable results in case of areca nut root grub. This helps in toxic principles to reach the target site without being lost by way of leaching, runoff due to heavy monsoon showers.

CONCLUSION

Along with plant protection measures, proper management of drainage is also very important. Many entomopathogens *viz.*, *Metarrhizium* are also

effective against this insect pest. Still there is a need to demonstrate the integrated management package to areca growers to combat this deadly insect pest on community approach. In this context, mixture of soap nut and neem oil could be one of the best alternative against chemicals and for organic areca growers.

REFERENCES

- Channakeshavamurthy H, Naik M I and Manjunatha M (2010). Evaluation of certain new chemicals, bio agents and plant products for the management of arecanut root grub, *Leucopholis lepidophora* Blanch. *Mysore J Agril Sci* **44** (4) : 815-817.
- Nair C P R and Daniel M (1982). *Pests of Arecanut* In : K V A Bhavappa, M K Nair and T Premkumar (Eds.) *The Arecanut Palm (Areca catechu* Linn.) CPCRI, Kasargod (India). pp 162-184.
- Prabhu S T, Rakesha H S and Balikai R A (2011). Field evaluation of fungal pathogens and plant extracts against arecanut root grub, *Leucopholis lepidophora* Blanchard. *Pest Management in Hort Ecosystems* **17** (2) : 75-79.
- Rakesha H S, Prabhu S T and Balikai R A (2011). Laboratory evaluation of fungal pathogens and plant extracts against areca nut root grub, *Leucopholis lepidophora* Blanchard. *Insect Environment* **17** (2) : 10-11.
- Subaharan K, Vidyasagar P S P V and Mohammed Basheer B M (2001). Bioefficacy of insecticides against white grub, *Leucopholis lepidophora* Blanch infesting arecanut palm. *Indian J Plant Prot* **29** (1-2) : 25-29.
- Veeresh G K, Vijayendra M, Reddy N V M and Rajanna C (1982). Bio- ecology and management of arecanut white grubs (*Leucopholis spp*) (Coleoptera : Scarabaeidae ; Melolonthinae). *J Soil Biology and Eco* **2** (2) : 78-86.

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Effect of Finishing Treatment with Softeners on Performance properties of Deccani Woollen Blanket

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ABSTRACT

The present study was focused on impact of softening treatment on performance properties of Deccani woollen blanket procured from Medleri village. Optimization process for softening was carried out by varying the concentration of softeners, pH and temperature of bath, and treatment time. Tensile strength and GSM of the treated sample was considered as a factor for optimization process. Deccani woollen blanket was treated as per the optimized process and performance properties *i.e.*, bending length, crease recovery, drapability. The result revealed that there was an improvement in performance properties of the softener treated sample. The decrease in bending length, increase in drapability and crease recovery was observed for the Deccani wool samples treated with softeners. Among the three different softeners, silicon softener treated Deccani wool blanket sample attained better performance properties.

Key Words: Silicon softener, Cationic softener, Non ionic softener, Drapability, Drape coefficient, Crease recovery.

INTRODUCTION

In India, woollen textile and clothing industry is relatively small compared to the cotton and manmade fibre based industries. However, the woollen sector plays an important role in linking the rural economy with the manufacturing industry, represented by small, medium and large scale units. The product portfolio is equally divergent from textile intermediaries to finished textiles, garments, knitwears, blankets, carpets and an incipient presence in technical textiles.

Fabric tactile properties are important criteria for the consumer acceptance. The properties namely bending length, crease recovery and drapability are an indicator of fabric handle. Crease recovery angle can be treated as an index to predict the pressing performance of the fabrics. According to Hearle (1969) the major mode of deformation in draping is fabric bending. Treloar (1965) investigated the dependence of drape of the fabric on bending

stiffness and shear stiffness. Hence, the present investigation was undertaken to know the influence of the softening treatment on performance properties of the Deccani wool blanket.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study was carried out at College of Rural Home Science, University of Agricultural Sciences, Dharwad, Karnataka during the year 2013-15. The plain weave Deccani wool blanket of size 3½ ft × 9½ ft woven in a pit loom was used for the present investigation. The sample was procured from Medleri village of Haveri district.

Procedure of softening treatment

Softening treatment was carried out at Bombay Textile Research Association, Mumbai Maharashtra. The woollen blanket test specimen of size 1m×1m was conditioned for 24 hrs at standard atmospheric condition *i.e.*, 27±2°C and 65±2% relative humidity. The woollen blanket was treated

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with selected softeners viz., cationic, non ionic and silicon of 1 per cent concentration, keeping pH of bath 6, temperature 40°C treatment time 30 min and MLR 1:6.

Evaluation of bending length

The specimen was placed on the platform with the scale on the top of it lengthwise and the zero of the scale coinciding with the leading edge of the specimen. The specimen along with the scale was pushed slowly and steadily when the leading edges project beyond the edges of the platform. A protruding part of the specimen overhangs and starts bending on its own weight. When two inclined lines (inclined plane making an angle of 41.5° with the horizontal) of the tester coincide, the length of the overhanging portion from the scale was recorded. The test sample were tested as directed in BS test method 3356:1961

Evaluation of crease recovery angle

Fabric crease recovery was measured in order to examine the pressing performance. Small samples of treated and control sample were folded and crease pressed using standard cycle on crease recovery tester. The samples were trimmed back leaving one centimeter of fabric on one side of the fold. The creases were then allowed to recover for about 30 min and the angle of the crease measured. The angle was measured after recovery under standard conditions (65% RH, 25°C).

Evaluation of Drape coefficient

Drape is the fabric’s ability to deform in space when bent under its own weight. A specimen was cut by means of circular template, sandwiched between two horizontal discs of smaller diameter and the unsupported annual rings of fabric was allowed to hang down on drape meter. On switching the lamp, it gives a circular parallel beam of light and falls on the cloth. The ammonia sheet (printing paper) of known dimension was placed on the base platform with sensitive side up, laying flat. The line of vision was kept along the baseboard and the height of the lower fringes of specimen was adjusted to 4 min,

the green pilot lamp lit up, when buzzer alarm rings, the ammonia paper was removed, rolled and placed in the developing box where strong ammonia solution was kept. The lid was shut airtight. After 4 minutes the drape pattern was ready. The statistical tool ANOVA and correlation was used to draw valid conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It was observed (Table 1) that, untreated and treated samples possessed higher warp way bending length compared to weft way bending length. Irrespective of softener treatment, all the treated samples exhibited decrease in bending length for both warp and weft way. Among the treated samples, silicon softener treated Deccani wool blanket sample indicated least bending length both on warp way and weft way. The reduction in bending length of all treated samples is attributed to decrease in inter fibre and inter yarn forces which leads to the formation of polymer film on the fibre surface due to softener treatment. These results were at par with the results of *Shakyawar and Behera (2007)*.

Table 1. Effect of softeners on bending length (cm).

Sr. No.	Treatment	Bending length (cm)	
		Warp	Weft
1.	Control	1.61	1.27
2.	Cationic softener	1.22	1.07
3.	Non-ionic softener	1.24	1.23
4.	Silicon softener	1.18	0.84

Source		SeM± 5%	CD		CV%
			1%		
Cationic	Warp	0.03	0.52	0.72	0.02
	Weft	0.03	0.54	0.76	0.03
Non ionic	Warp	0.03	0.53	0.74	0.03
	Weft	0.03	0.81	0.58	0.04
Silicon	Warp	0.03	0.57	0.79	0.03
	Weft	0.03	0.59	0.82	0.05

It was noticed (Table 2) that all the softener treated samples showed greater crease recovery

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angle over treated samples. Silicon treated samples attained higher crease recovery (170°). The higher crease recovery can be correlated with the lower bending length of treated samples. Softener treatment leads to the formation of elastic polymer on the surface of the fibres which aids in increase in the elastic property of the fabric and may have contributed for increase in crease recovery and the fabric becomes more pliable.

Table 2. Effect of softeners on cloth recovery angle (degree).

Sr. No.	Treatment	Crease recovery		Cloth recovery(°)
		warp	weft	
1.	Control	137.75	142.25	139.96
2.	Cationic softener	155.13	161.87	158.45
3.	Non-ionic softener	148.25	150.50	149.35
4.	Silicon softener	168.00	172.75	170.34

Source	SeM±	CD		CV%
		5%	1%	
Crease recovery(°)	1.22	3.41	4.78	1.77

Drapability

Drapability is expressed in terms of drape coefficient and number of nodes i.e., higher the drape coefficient, poorer the drapability or greater the number of nodes, better the drapability. It means, that drape coefficient and the fabric drape are inversely related. It was observed (Table 3) that all treated samples exhibited lower drape coefficient than the control. It means treated samples were more pliable. The decrease in drape coefficient of all treated samples may be because of the removal of dirt materials. Decrease in bending length and increase in cloth recovery indirectly indicated an improvement in the drapability. This can be proven with the existence of higher correlation between drape coefficient and crease recovery (Table 4) and between drape coefficient and bending length (Table 5 and 6a & b). Behera and Mishra (2006) in their

investigation also reported that crease recovery and bending length is correlated with drapability of the fabric.

Table 3. Effect of softeners on drape coefficient .

Sr. No.	Treatment	Drape coefficient (%)
1.	Control	60.48
2.	Cationic softener	57.84
3.	Non-ionic softener	59.05
4.	Silicon softener	56.94

Source	SeM±	CD		CV%
		5%	1%	
Drapability (%)	0.01	0.30	0.42	0.04

Table 4. Correlation between fabric thickness (mm) and thermal resistance (K.m2/W).

Sr. No.	Treatment	Fabric thickness (mm)	Thermal resistance (K.m2/W)
1.	Control	2.23	0.063
2.	Cationic softener	2.82	0.087
3.	Non-ionic softener	2.46	0.088
4.	Silicon softener	2.83	0.099

Correlation = 0.8547

Coefficient of determination R2 = 73.06%

Table 5. Correlation between crease recovery angle (degree) and drape coefficient.

Sr. No.	Treatment	Crease recovery (°)	Drapability (%)
1.	Control	139.96	60.48
2.	Cationic softener	158.45	57.84
3.	Non-ionic softener	149.35	59.05
4.	Silicon softener	170.34	56.94

Correlation = -0.987

Coefficient of determination R2 = 97.445%

Table 6a. Correlation between warp bending length (cm) and drape coefficient.

Sr. No.	Treatment	Bending length (cm) Warp	Drapability (%)
1.	Control	1.61	60.48
2.	Cationic softener	1.22	57.84
3.	Non-ionic softener	1.24	59.05
4.	Silicon softener	1.18	56.94

Correlation = 0.890

Coefficient of determination R² = 79.226%

Table 6b. Correlation between weft bending length (cm) and drape coefficient.

Sr. No.	Treatment	Bending length (cm) Weft	Drapability (%)
1.	Control	2.58	60.48
2.	Cationic softener	2.19	57.84
3.	Non-ionic softener	2.40	59.05
4.	Silicon softener	1.72	56.94

Correlation = 0.929

Coefficient of determination R² = 86.35%

Among three softeners, silicon softener treated sample showed better performance properties. It may be because of Silicon which forms a stable covalent bond with carbon leading to a class of materials known as organosilanes, when combined with chlorine and water, forms silanols. Condensation of silanols results in siloxane linkages. Dimethyl dichlorosilane will form linear polysiloxanes which are water clear oils having

good lubricating properties. Due to silicones Inorganic – Organic structure and the flexibility of the silicone bonds, silicones show some unique properties including thermal oxidative stability and high compressibility. Hence, resulted in the improvement in aforementioned properties of silicon treated Deccani wool sample.

CONCLUSION

The softening treatment increases pliability of the Deccani wool blanket. The bending length and Drape coefficient of the softener treated samples to certain extent decreased. The crease recovery angle of the Deccani wool blanket sample was also exhibited more when compared with control sample. Overall the performance properties of the softener treated samples were improved compared to untreated sample. The further studies can be carried out in this arena with different blends.

REFERENCES

- Behera B K and Mishra R (2006). Effect of crease behaviour, drape, and formability on appearance of light weight worsted suiting fabrics. *Indian J Fibre and Textile Res* **32**: 319-325.
- Hearle J W S (1969). *Structural Mechanics of Fibres, Yarns and Fabrics*, Vol.1, edited by J W S Hearle, P Grosberg and S Backer (Wiley-International, New York), Ch. 12.
- Shakyawar D B and Behera B K (2007). Influence of softening treatments on hand value of wooven fabrics produced from Indian wool and their blends. *Indian J Fibre Textile Res* **34** : 76-80.
- Treloar L R G (1965). The effect of test-piece dimensions on the behaviour of fabrics shear, *J Text Inst* **56** (1) :33-50.
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Effect of Integrated Nutrient Management on Production Potential and Quality of Summer Mungbean (*Vigna radiata L.*)

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ABSTRACT

An experiment was conducted during summer seasons of 2014 and 2015 to find out the effect of integrated nutrient management on crop growth, yield attributes, yield and quality of summer mungbean. Increasing the fertility level significantly increased the growth, yield attributes, yield, protein content and nutrient uptake by mungbean. Application of RDF+VC 5 t/ha registered maximum growth attributes, number of nodules, nodules dry weight, yield attributes and produced 8.42 and 5.1 per cent higher seed yield (1060.6 kg/ha) over RDF (978.1kg/ha), and RDF+VC 2.5 t/ha (1009.6 kg/ha), respectively. Fertility level RDF+VC5 t/ha similarly registered highest protein content (22.3%), protein yield (238.4 kg/ha) and nutrient uptake (85.65:9.47:75.33::N:P:Kkg/ha). Mungbean produced maximum response with biofertilizer + Mo 1.0 +Co 1.0 kg/ha in respect to growth, yield attributes, nodule number, nodule weight and 41.2 per cent higher grain yield over control (841.3kg/ha). Protein content (24.21%), protein yield (287.8kg/ha) and nutrient uptake (100.47:11.34:87.62::N:P:K kg/ha) were also recorded maximum with biofertilizer + Mo 1.0 + Co 1.0 kg/ha.

Key Words: Cobalt, Molybdenum, Mungbean, Phosphorus, Quality, Yield

INTRODUCTION

Mungbean (*Vigna radiata L.* Wilczek) is one of the protein rich pulse crop grown in India. The lack of productivity has contributed to food insecurity throughout the region and widespread malnutrition. Being a short duration crop, it fits well in many intensive crop rotations, prevents soil erosion, fixes atmospheric nitrogen through Rhizobial symbiosis and helps in improving soil fertility (Bansal, 2009).

Pulses like mungbean are generally grown in soils with low fertility status or with application of low quantities of organic and inorganic sources of plant nutrients, which has resulted in deterioration of soil health and productivity (Kumpawat, 2010). Organic manures provide a good substrate for the growth of microorganisms and maintain a favourable nutritional balance and soil physical properties (Chaudhary *et al*, 2004). The organic acids produced during decomposition of organic waste can exchange with adsorbed P and increase its

availability to plants. Application of FYM increased the activity of acid and alkaline phosphatase, phosphodiesterase, inorganic pyrophosphatase and dehydrogenase leading to faster hydrolysis of ester-bond P to plant available P (Dinesh *et al*, 2003).

Micronutrients play an important role in increasing legume yield through their effect on the plant itself, nitrogen fixing symbiotic process and effective use of major and secondary nutrients. Among micronutrients, cobalt and molybdenum are essential for the growth of *Rhizobium* and nitrogen fixation. Molybdenum is directly related to nitrogen fixation by legume. Molybdenum application plays a vital role in increasing the nitrogen fixation process by *Rhizobium* and, is responsible for the formation of nodule tissue and increase in N fixation (Roy *et al*, 2006). Cobalt is important in the plant world and constituent of cobalamine coenzyme and required for formation of leghaemoglobin

in nitrogen fixation. Cobalt also promotes many developmental processes including stem and coleoptiles elongation, opening of hypocotyls hooks, leaf disc expansion and development (Kandil, 2007). Keeping these facts, a field experiment was conducted to investigate the effect of integrated nutrient management on production potential and quality of spring mungbean.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A field experiment was carried out in the Instructional Farm of Krishi Vigyana Kendra, Buxar (25°34'6.33"N, 83°59'0.18" E and 63 m above sea level). The soil of the experimental farm is clay loam in texture with pH 7.8 and 0.48% organic carbon. The N, P₂O₅ and K₂O, Mo and Co content are 218.8, 17.9 and 145.3 kg/ha, 0.07 mg/kg and 0.10 mg/kg, respectively. The treatments comprised of three levels of fertility viz. F1: RDF (20 N, 40 P₂O₅ and 30 K₂O kg/ha), F2:RDF+VC 2.5 t/ha, F3:RDF+VC 5.0 t/ha and seven levels of biofertilizer + micronutrients viz., M1:Control (No FYM, No fertilizer), M2:Biofertilizer (*Rhizobium* + PSB) M3:Mo 1.0 kg/ha M4:Co 1.0 kg/ha M5:Biofertilizer +Mo 1.0 kg/ha M6:Biofertilizer + Co 1.0 kg/ha M7:Biofertilizer+Mo 1+Co 1 kg/ha. The treatments were replicated thrice and the experiment was laid out in split plot design. Fertilizers were applied as basal through urea, diammonium phosphate and muriate of potash. Molybdenum and cobalt were applied through ammonium molybdate and cobalt chloride, respectively. Vermicompost was applied before one month of sowing as per treatments and seeds were treated with biofertilizer (*Rhizobium* + PSB) except control. Mungbean variety "Samrat" was used as the test crop. Seeds were sown during last week of March and harvested at physiological maturity during both the years. All the cultural practices were followed as per package of practice. The data on various growth and yield attributes, nodule, seed and straws were recorded under various treatments. Before sowing composite soil samples representing the whole field and after harvest plot wise samples were collected. The

organic carbon, pH, available N, P and K were analyzed as per the method described by Jackson (1973), DTPA extractable Co was determined following Lindsay and Norvell (1978), available molybdenum by ammonium oxalate extraction method (Jackson, 1973). The representative dry samples of seed and straw were analyzed for ascertaining the nutrient (N, P and K) content. Nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium content in seed and stover were determined by modified Kjeldahl method, vanadomolibdophosphoric yellow colour method, flame photometer and turbidimetric method, respectively. Statistical analyses of all the data were done as per the methodology of Gomez and Gomez (1984).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Crop Growth

Beneficial effect of fertility levels and biofertilizer + micronutrient on growth and development of mungbean has been clearly brought out in this investigation. Perusal of the data (Table 1) revealed that application of RDF+VC 5.0 t/ha recorded maximum plant height, number of branches/plant, dry weight, nodule number and nodule dry weight and significantly superior to RDF. The RDF+VC 2.5 t/ha was next best treatment in these respect. The higher values of these growth parameters with this fertility level might be due to supply of all the essential mineral nutrients in a balanced amount. These results were in conformity with the findings of Choudhary *et al* (2011) and Tiwari *et al* (2011).

The seed inoculation with biofertilizers helped in increasing all the growth characters recorded over control (Table 1), which might be due the beneficial effect of the *Rhizobium* and PSB in enhancing the nutrient supply to the plant. Combined application of micronutrients and biofertilizers was found synergistic in enhancing the growth attributing characters. The significant variations created by the addition of Mo are attributed to higher availability and absorption of nutrients and, Co application

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improving the nodulation and high population of Rhizobia in the rhizosphere (Jena *et al*, 1994).

Yield and yield attributes

The yield attributing characters namely number of pods/plant, pod length, number of grains/pod and 1000 grain weight increased with addition of VC in RDF and recorded maximum with RDF+VC 5 t/ha. This might be due to combination of organic and inorganic nutrition provides better soil environment for root growth, nodule formation, availability and absorption of nutrient from soil. Seed inoculation resulted in greater number of pods/plant, pod length, number of grains/pod and 1000 grain weight. This may be attributed to increased nodulation and nitrogen fixation, more solubilization of native P and production of secondary metabolites by the bacteria. Combined application of biofertilizers along with micronutrients (Mo + Co) resulted in significant improvement in yield attributes (Table 1). Application of these micronutrients along with the inoculations might have a synergistic effect, which enhanced the activity of nitrogenase, in turn supplied more nitrogen by fixation for better growth and yield attributes. Similar results were also reported by Singh *et al* (2010) and Choudhary *et al* (2011).

Grain yield of mungbean crop is a function of cumulative effect of various yield components, which are influenced by genetic make-up of variety, various agronomic practices and environmental conditions. The application of RDF+ VC 5 t/ha produced higher seed and stover yield over RDF and RDF+VC 2.5 t/ha. An enhancement in seed yield is attributed to cumulative effect of number of pods/plant, pod length, number of grain/pod and seed weight. This result is also in close conformity with the findings of Singh *et al* (2010), Tiwari *et al* (2011), Choudhary *et al* (2011) and Meena *et al* (2016).

Seed and stover yield was enhanced by seed inoculation with biofertilizer and micronutrient application. Combined application of micronutrient

and seed inoculation resulted higher seed and stover yield over control and alone application of Mo and Co. This might be due to molybdenum have a synergistic effect, which enhances the activity of nitrogenase in turn supplied more nitrogen by fixation for better growth and finally increased yield (Biswas *et al* 2009; Biyan *et al*, 2014) and Co application has been attributed to promotion of many developmental processes such as stem and coleoptiles elongation, opening of hypostyle hooks, leaf disc expansion and bud development (Ibrahim *et al*, 1989).

Quality

Protein content and protein yield was significantly influenced by different fertility levels (Table 3). Maximum protein content (25.2%) and protein yield (107.6 kg/ha) was recorded under RDF+VC 5 t/ha. This was mainly due to higher biological production under these treatments which increase the nutrient uptake. Application of Mo + Co along with biofertilizer recorded maximum protein content and protein yield. The minimum protein content and protein yield was recorded under control. Similar result was observed by Khan *et al* (2002) and Jain *et al* (2007).

Nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium uptake by crop was also relatively higher with RDF+ VC 5 t/ha (Table 3). This was mainly due to higher biological production under these fertility levels. Nutrient uptake increased significantly with biofertilizer + Mo + Co treatment. The increased uptake with the application of biofertilizers and micronutrients might be due to enhanced effect of Rhizobium in nitrogen supply (Bhattacharyya and Pal, 2001). The increased uptake of P by phosphobacteria (*Bacillus*) could be attributed to its greater P-solubilization potentiality in the presence of organic matter. Organic fertilizer provides significant cation exchange capacity to hold cations such as K⁺. The change in cation exchange capacity of organics by acidification might have enhanced K availability (Kumar *et al*, 2009 and Jat *et al*, 2011).

Table 1. Effect of phosphorus, molybdenum and boron on growth, yield attributes and yield of mungbean

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	No branches/plant	Dry weight (g/row length)	No of nodules/plant	Nodule dry weight (mg)	No of pods/plant	Pod length (cm)	No of grains/pod	Test weight (g)
Fertility level									
F1:RDF	39.53	6.76	39.33	26.43	55.50	18.86	6.64	8.83	28.11
F2:RDF+ VC 2.5 t/ha	40.94	6.94	40.49	28.29	67.89	19.57	6.69	9.07	28.80
F3:RDF+ VC 5.0 t/ha	43.16	7.31	42.36	30.14	75.36	20.50	6.80	9.67	30.48
CD (P=0.05)	2.97	0.50	2.95	1.94	4.32	1.41	NS	0.65	2.08
Biofertilizer+Micronutrient									
M1:Control	35.23	5.80	39.28	19.67	46.10	16.7	6.00	8.67	26.90
M2:Biofertilizer	37.17	6.43	40.27	29.67	69.43	18.3	6.60	9.00	29.10
M3:Mo 1.0 kg/ha	38.90	6.53	38.23	23.33	54.63	18.0	6.40	8.33	26.89
M4:Co 1.0 kg/ha	41.67	6.63	40.07	23.00	53.80	18.7	6.50	8.33	27.03
M5:Biofertilizer + Mo 1.0 kg/ha	42.27	7.23	41.33	33.67	78.90	20.0	6.87	9.17	29.64
M6:Biofertilizer + Co 1.0 kg/ha	45.10	7.80	41.63	32.33	75.77	20.8	7.00	9.67	30.93
M7:Biofertilizer+Mo 1+Co 1 kg/ha	48.13	8.13	44.25	36.33	85.10	25.0	7.60	11.17	33.43
CD (P=0.05)	1.51	0.26	1.49	1.07	2.51	0.7	0.25	0.32	1.06

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Table 2. Interaction effect of phosphorus, molybdenum and cobalt on dry matter accumulation, number of nodules, grain and protein yield of mungbean

Treatment	Dry weight (g/row length)			Protein yield		
	RDF	RDF+ VC 2.5 t/ha	RDF+ VC 5.0 t/ha	RDF	RDF+ VC 2.5 t/ha	RDF+ VC.0 t/ha
Biofertilizer+Micronutrient						
M1:Control	36.85	38.40	42.60	167.57	175.35	184.63
M2:Biofertilizer	38.00	39.50	43.30	193.20	205.52	217.81
M3:Mo 1.0 kg/ha	37.50	38.00	39.20	191.10	198.58	205.67
M4:Co 1.0 kg/ha	39.50	40.20	40.50	192.66	202.47	211.93
M5:Biofertilizer +Mo 1.0 kg/ha	40.80	41.30	41.90	236.74	253.65	266.24
M6:Biofertilizer + Co 1.0 kg/ha	41.20	41.50	42.20	252.45	245.58	276.95
M7:Biofertilizer+Mo 1+Co 1 kg/ha	41.44	44.50	46.82	274.08	283.94	305.35
CD (P=0.05)	Biofertilizer+Micronutrient at same fertility level		2.59	14.46		
	Fertility level at same/different biofertilizer+micronutrient		3.75	20.49		
Biofertilizer+Micronutrient						
	Seed yield (kg/ha)			Total N uptake (kg/ha)		
M1:Control	810.0	840.0	874.0	63.10	66.52	69.97
M2:Biofertilizer	920.0	970.0	1025.0	72.33	77.10	82.16
M3:Mo 1.0 kg/ha	910.0	940.0	965.0	72.49	74.84	79.05
M4:Co 1.0 kg/ha	912.0	950.0	980.0	73.12	75.80	80.86
M5:Biofertilizer +Mo 1.0 kg/ha	1070.0	1140.0	1180.0	82.90	86.77	90.19
M6:Biofertilizer + Co 1.0 kg/ha	1080.0	1045.0	1160.0	91.04	87.06	93.10
M7:Biofertilizer+Mo 1+Co 1 kg/ha	1145.0	1180.0	1240.0	97.03	100.18	104.19
CD (P=0.05)	Biofertilizer+Micronutrient at same fertility level		65.11	5.22		
	Fertility level at same/different biofertilizer+micronutrient		92.96	7.44		

Interaction effect

The interaction between fertility levels and micronutrient + biofertilizer was found significant in case of dry weight, grain yield, protein yield and total N uptake (Table 2). Maximum dry weight, protein yield, seed yield and total N uptake by crop were recorded under RDF+VC 5 t/ha along with Mo +Co + biofertilizer. The next best treatment in these respect was RDF+VC 2.5 t/ha. This may be attributed to increased nodulation and nitrogen fixation, more solubilization of native P and production of secondary metabolites by the bacteria resulting; these facilitate a greater economic sink capacity as the yield has a highly significant correlation with yield attributes (Patra and Bhattacharya, 2009). The application of molybdenum and cobalt with biofertilizer was found effective in enhancing the dry weight, seed yield, protein yield and total N uptake in all the fertility levels.

CONCLUSION

On the basis of results drawn it may be recommended that application of RDF+VC 5 t/ha along with biofertilizer+Mo1.0+Co1.0 kg/ha in combination should be superimposed over no application (control and seed must be inoculated with rhizobium for realizing economic optimum yield.

REFERENCES

- Bansal R K (2009). Synergistic effect of Rhizobium, PSB and PGPR on nodulation and grain yield of mungbean. *J Food Leg* **22**(1): 37-39.
- Bhattacharyya J and Pal A K (2001). Effect of Rhizobium inoculation, phosphorus and molybdenum on the growth of summer greengram (*Vigna radiata* L. Wiczek). *J Interacad* **5**(4): 450-457.
- Biswas P K, Bhowmick M K and Bhattacharya A (2009). Effect of molybdenum and seed inoculation on seed inoculation on nodulation, growth and yield in urdbean [*Vigna mungo* (L.) Hepper]. *J Crop and Weed* **5**(1): 147-150.
- Biyan S C, Dhuppar P and Rao D S (2014). Integrated nutrient management assessment for increased mungbean crop yield. *Crop Res* **48** (1,2&3):38-41.
- Chaudhary D R, Bhandari S C and Shukla L M (2004). Role of vermicompost in sustainable agriculture: A review. *Agril Rev* **25**:29-39.
- Chaudhary H R, Sharma O P, Yadav L R and Choudhary G L (2011). Effect of organic sources and chemicals fertilizers on productivity of mungbean. *J Food Leg* **24**:324-326.
- Dinesh R, Ganeshamurthy, A N, Choudhuri S G and Prasaad S G (2003). Dissolution of rockphosphate as influenced by farm yard manure, fresh poultry manure and earthworms in soil of an oilpalm plantation. *J Indian Soc Soil Sci* **51**:308-312.
- Gomez K A and Gomez A A (1984). *Statistical Procedure for Agricultural Research*. John Wiley and Sons, New York.
- Ibrahim A, Abd SOEL and El AS (1989). A possible role of cobalt in salt tolerance of plant. *Egyptian J Soil Sci* **359**-370.
- Jackson M L (1973). *Soil Chemical Analysis*. Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.
- Jain A K, Sudhir Kumar and J D S Panwar (2007). Response of mungbean (*Vigna radiata*) to phosphorus and micronutrients on N and P uptake and seed quality. *Legume Res* **30**(3): 201 – 204.
- Jat R S, Dayal D, Meena H N, Singh V and Gedia M V (2011). Long-term effect of nutrient management and rainfall on pod yield of groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea*) in groundnut-based cropping systems. *Indian J Agron* **56**:145-149.
- Jena P K, Karmakar S, Ghatak S, Barik A, Naybri A, Sounda G, Mukher A K and Saren B K (1994). Effect of cobalt and rhizobium on yield, oil content and nutrient concentration in irrigated summer groundnut. *Indian J Agril Sci* **64**(1): 630 – 632.
- Kandli H (2007). Effect of cobalt fertilizer on growth, yield and nutrient status of faba bean (*Vicia faba* L.) plants. *J Applied Sci Res* **3**(9): 867-872.
- Khan M A, Aslam M, Tariq-Sultan and Mahmood I A (2002). Response of phosphorus application on growth and yield of inoculated and un-inoculated mungbean (*Vigna radiata*). *International J Agril Bio* **4**(4): 523-524.
- Kumar R P, Singh O N, Singh Y, Dwivedi S and Singh J P (2009). Effect of integrated nutrient management on growth, yield, nutrient uptake and economics of french bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*). *Indian J Agril Sci* **79** (2): 122-8.
- Kumpawat B S (2010). Integrated nutrient management in blackgram (*Vigna mungo*) and its residual effect on succeeding mustard (*Brassica juncea*) crop. *Indian J Agril Sci* **80**(1):76-79.

Effect of INM on Summer Mungbean

Table 3. Effect of phosphorus, molybdenum and cobalt on quality of mungbean

Treatment	Protein content (%)	Protein yield (kg/ha)	Seed yield (kg/ha)	Stover yield (kg/ha)	Total nutrient uptake by crop (kg/ha)		
					N uptake	P uptake	K uptake
Fertility level							
F ₁ :RDF	21.89	215.40	978.14	2665.57	78.86	8.73	70.19
F ₂ :RDF+ VC 2.5 t/ha	22.04	223.58	1009.29	2712.71	81.18	8.98	72.00
F ₃ :RDF+ VC 5.0 t/ha	22.34	238.37	1060.57	2822.57	85.65	9.47	75.33
CD (P=0.05)	NS	15.86	72.37	151.78	5.79	0.60	5.10
Biofertilizer+Micronutrient							
M ₁ :Control	20.90	175.85	841.33	2350.00	66.53	7.05	58.98
M ₂ :Biofertilizer	21.15	205.51	971.67	2680.00	77.20	8.37	68.55
M ₃ :Mo 1.0 kg/ha	21.15	198.45	938.33	2643.33	75.46	8.27	67.72
M ₄ :Co 1.0 kg/ha	21.35	202.35	947.33	2652.67	76.60	8.58	68.39
M ₅ :Biofertilizer +Mo 1.0 kg/ha	22.31	252.21	1130.00	2759.33	86.62	9.80	76.44
M ₆ :Biofertilizer + Co 1.0 kg/ha	23.58	258.33	1095.00	2898.33	90.40	10.02	79.87
M ₇ :Biofertilizer+Mo 1+Co 1 kg/ha	24.21	287.79	1188.33	3151.67	100.47	11.34	87.62
CD (P=0.05)	0.81	8.35	37.59	90.13	3.01	0.34	2.67

Lindsay W L and Norvell W A (1978). Development of DTPA soil test for zinc, iron, manganese and copper. *Soil Sci Soc America J* **42**: 421-8.

Meena S, Swaroop N and Dawson Jay (2016). Effect of integrated nutrient management on growth and yield of green gram (*Vigna radiata L.*). *Agric. Sci. Digest* **36**(1):63-65.

Patra P K and Bhattacharya C (2009). Effect of different levels of boron and molybdenum on growth and yield of mungbean [*Vigna radiata (L.) Wilczek*] cv. Baisakhi mung in red and laterite zone of West Bengal. *J Crop and Weed* **5**(1): 119-121.

Roy R N, Finck A, Blair G J, Tandon HLS (2006). *Plant nutrition for food security. A guide for integrated nutrient management. FAO fertilizer and plant nutrition bulletin* **16**. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome, Italy. p368.

Singh G, Aggarwal N and Khanna V (2010). Integrated nutrient management in lentil with organic manures, chemicals fertilizers and bio-fertilizers. *J Food Leg* **23**:149-151.

Tiwari D, Sharma B B and Singh V K (2011). Effect of integrated nutrient management in pigeonpea based intercropping. *J Food Leg* **24**:304-309.

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Effect of Microwave Radiation on Shelf Life of *Paneer* for Rural Market

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ABSTRACT

An attempt was made to enhance the shelf life of paneer by microwave irradiation. Standard plate count; coliform count; yeast and mold count; proteolytic count; acid producers count; staphylococcus count and sensory evaluation on a nine point Hedonic scale of each product i.e. treated and untreated products stored at ambient condition (30°C) and at refrigerated condition (5 - 7°C) was done at 0 , 2nd , 5th , 7th day and onward till they were acceptable based on organoleptic test and consumer acceptance. The shelf life of paneer was extended by 8d at room temperature and 15d at refrigeration temperature. Use of microwave radiation of indigenous milk products is suggested to enhance the shelf life of the product.

Key Words : Microwave, shelf-life, *Paneer*.

INTRODUCTION

Indian dairy industry has witnessed rapid progress in the last four decades. About 40-50 per cent of the total milk produced is converted into different varieties of traditional milk products using processes such as heat and acid coagulation, heat desiccation and fermentation. Out of this an estimated 5 per cent of milk produced in India is converted to paneer (Chandan, 2007). Paneer is mainly used for various culinary preparations. In the last few decades, the popularity of paneer has spread from the north to all over the country. The simplest way to enhance the keeping quality of milk and milk products is boiling. Many thermal processes i.e. pasteurization, sterilization and UHT have gained a lot of popularity. However, many drawbacks are also related to these processes of heat treatment viz. degradation of flavour and colour, nutrients, etc.

Microwave treatment is an intense thermal treatment, which is now widely used to extend the shelf life of food products. It is well established that the microflora of liquid milk could be reduced

by microwave treatment. It has also been observed that in pasteurized milk with microwave, microbial population was lower than untreated milk and has longer shelf life. Villamiel *et al* (1996) concluded that continuous microwave processing might be an efficient and mild method for the pasteurization of milk. They also concluded that shelf life of microwave treated milk was longer than that of milk heated on hot electric plate. Kindle *et al* (1996) also reported that colony counts of all microorganisms were significantly decreased by microwave heating. Hence, study was conducted to increase shelf life of *paneer* through microwave irradiation.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Samples of *Paneer* were procured under aseptic conditions from the local market. All the samples were separately packed in polypropylene pouches (75µ thickness and dimension 4 " X 3") aseptically, as suggested by Mathur *et al* (1992). Two container of each sample were microwave treated and other two were kept as control. *Paneer* samples were treated at power level 60 (i.e. 600w) for 32s. Power

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level and time combination was chosen based on their effect on taste, body and texture. The treated samples were kept under refrigerated condition (5°C) and under ambient temperature (30°C).

Standard Plate Count, Coliform Count, Yeast and Mold Count according to the methods of BIS (1960); Proteolytic Count (Harrigan and McCance, 1976), Acid Producers Count (AOAC), *Staphylococcus* Count (Chapman, 1960) and Sensory evaluation on a nine point Hedonic Scale was done for each product i.e. treated and untreated products stored at ambient condition and at refrigerated condition at 0, 2nd, 5th, 7th day and onward till they were acceptable based on organoleptic test and consumer acceptance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of microwave treatment on the microbiological quality of *paneer*

Standard Plate Count

In general the total plate count decreased due to microwave treatment and increased both in treated and untreated sample during storage (Table 1). The total plate count in fresh *paneer* sample was 12.4×10^4 cfu/gm. Maximum bacterial growth took place in untreated sample. Untreated fresh *paneer* (12.4×10^4 cfu/gm) was unacceptable organoleptically after 5d and 10d of storage respectively, under ambient and refrigerated condition. However, the shelf life of treated *paneer* was extended up to 8d and 15d under ambient and refrigerated conditions, respectively. It was observed that after microwave treatment the reduction in total plate count was 59 per cent. Similar results were observed by Kindle *et al* (1996). Bacteria destruction up to 5000 fold was reported by Kindle *et al* (1996) in infant milk food.

Effect on coliform count

The coliform count of fresh sample of *paneer* was nil (Table 1). Reduction in coliform count by microwave treatment was not examined as *paneer* from market had no coliform count, effect on coliform by microwave irradiation could not

be determined. Hammad (1998) observed that no viable coliform were detected in raw milk after microwave heating at 600W for 4 min.

Table I. Effect of Microwave Treatment on *Paneer*.

Sr. No.	Parameter	Before (cfu/g)	After (cfu/g)	Reduction (%)
1.	Standard Plate Count	124,000	51,000	59
2.	Coliform count	NIL	NIL	NIL
3.	Yeast and Mold Count	150	100	34
4.	Proteolytic Count	500	150	70
5.	Acid producers count	130	50	62
6.	<i>Staphylococcus</i> count	NIL	NIL	NIL

Effect on yeast and mold count

There was no significant change in yeast and mold count as compared to other microbial count due to microwave treatment of different indigenous dairy products. Yeast and mold count of *paneer* before treatment were 15×10^4 cfu/gm and it was observed that after irradiation, the percent reduction was 34 per cent in *paneer*. Similar results were observed by Culkin and Fung (1975) who reported that microwave heating at 2450 MHz caused little or no destruction of *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Rhizopus* etc. in foods.

There was a little effect of microwave heating on yeast and mold count in controlling their growth during storage. Yeast and mold count increased in both treated and untreated sample during storage. Fresh *paneer* having 15×10^4 cfu/gm yeast and mold count was spoiled by 5d stored at room temperature (count increased to 4.7×10^2 cfu/gm) and spoiled by 8d of storage under refrigerated condition (count increased to 38×10^4 cfu/gm). It was also observed that treated sample initially having 10×10^4 cfu/gm became unacceptable after 10d of storage under ambient condition (Yeast & Mold count increased to 47×10^4 cfu/gm) and 15d of storage under refrigerated condition (Yeast & Mold count increased to 42×10^4 cfu/gm).

Shelf Life of *Paneer*

Table 2. Effect of microwave treatment on *paneer* during storage.

Parameter	Sample	Paneer	
		Count at 0 day	Count at the day of spoilage
SPC	Untreated (at room temp.)	12.4 X 10 ⁴	51X10 ⁴ @5day
	Untreated (at refrigeration temp.)	12.4 X 10 ⁴	51 X 10 ⁴ @10 day
	Treated (at room temp.)	5.1 X 10 ⁴	59 X 10 ⁴ @8 day
	Treated (at refrigeration temp.)	5.1 X 10 ⁴	57 X 10 ⁴ @15day
Coliform	Untreated (at room temp.)	0	0@5day
	Untreated (at refrigeration temp.)	0	0@10 day
	Treated (at room temp.)	0	0@8 day
	Treated (at refrigeration temp.)	0	0@15day
Yeast & mold count	Untreated (at room temp.)	150	360@5day
	Untreated (at refrigeration temp.)	150	470@10 day
	Treated (at room temp.)	100	380@8 day
	Treated (at refrigeration temp.)	100	420@15day
Proteolytic count	Untreated (at room temp.)	500	31X 10 ² @5day
	Untreated (at refrigeration temp.)	500	52 X10 ² @10 day
	Treated (at room temp.)	150	24 X10 ² @8 day
	Treated (at refrigeration temp.)	150	52 X10 ² @15day
Acid Producers count	Untreated (at room temp.)	130	420@5day
	Untreated (at refrigeration temp.)	130	440@10 day
	Treated (at room temp.)	50	350@8 day
	Treated (at refrigeration temp.)	50	450@15day
Staphylococcus count	Untreated (at room temp.)	0	0@5day
	Untreated (at refrigeration temp.)	0	0@10 day
	Treated (at room temp.)	0	0@8 day
	Treated (at refrigeration temp.)	0	0@15day

Effect on Proteolytic count

The proteolytic count was lower in microwave treated sample than in untreated sample. It was observed that proteolytic count was inhibited by microwave treatment as fresh paneer, having proteolytic count of 5 X 10² cfu/gm and treated paneer, having proteolytic count of 1.5 X 10² cfu/gm was spoiled by 5d at room temperature (count increased to 31 X 10² cfu/gm) and by 10d at refrigerated condition (count increased to 52 X

10² cfu/gm); and untreated sample spoiled by 8d at room temperature (count increased to 24 X 10² cfu/gm) and by 15d at refrigerated condition (count increased to 52 X 10² cfu/gm). It was observed that reduction rate of proteolytic bacteria due to microwave treatment was 70 per cent in *paneer*.

Effect on Acid Producers Count

Acid producers count also reduced due to microwave treatment. The acid producers count of

fresh *paneer* was 130 cfu /gm and after microwave treatment it was reduced to 50 cfu /gm (62%). During storage, it was observed that the number of acid producers colonies in fresh *paneer* (13 X 10² cfu/gm) increased to 42 X 10² cfu/gm after 5d when stored at room temperature and to 44 X 10² cfu/gm after 10d under refrigerated condition. The count at microwave treated (600W for 30sec.) was 5 X 10² cfu/gm and increased to 35 X 10² cfu/gm after 8d when it stored at room temperature and to 45 X 10² cfu/gm after 15d under refrigerated condition (Table 2)

Effect on *Staphylococcus* count

Microwave treatment had a significant effect on survival of *Staphylococcus* spp.

No *staphylococcus* was detected in fresh *paneer*.

Sensory evaluation

The sensory score for flavour, colour, consistency and appearance of microwave treated *paneer* samples were observed to be same as compared to untreated products.

On the basis of organoleptic evaluation it was observed that the quality of *paneer* before and after treatment were almost same. During storage the overall acceptability of control sample was decreased to a greater extent than those of microwave treated sample.

CONCLUSION

Control sample of *paneer* was evaluated for 10d whereas treated *paneer* was evaluated for 15d. Control sample of treated *paneer* was evaluated for 28d. During storage, colour and appearance, smell of both the product was more affected than body and texture. Colour and appearance more quickly deteriorated due to mold growth and taste and flavour deteriorated due to acid producers bacterial growth.

It has been reported that microwave treatment of *paneer* up to 115°C for 5m did affect the body and texture and flavour attributes of the product and increase the shelf life and can be effectively utilized for fulfilling the local rural market demand.

REFERENCES

- BIS (ISI) (1960). *Bureau of Indian Standard*. Manak Bhawan, New Delhi; IS: 1449: Part.I Method of test for examination of dairy products.
- Chandan R C (2007). *Manufacture of paneer*. In: Gupta S, Gupta S, editors. Dairy India 2007. 6. New Dehli: Dairy India Yearbook, A Dairy India publication; 2007. pp. 411–412.
- Chapman G H (1946). A single culture medium for selective isolation of plasma- coagulating staphylococci and for improved testing of chromogenesis, plasma coagulation, mannitol fermentation, and the Stone reaction. *J Bacterial* **51**: 409-410.
- Culkin K A and Fung D Y C (1975). Destruction of *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella typhimurium* in microwave cooked soup. *J Milk Food Technol* **38**, 8-15.
- Hammad A A I (1998). Efficiency of domestic microwave oven in eliminating pathogenic bacteria from fresh foods and milks. *Asian J Agri Sci* **29**(3): 19-32.
- Harrigan W F and McCance M E (1976). *Laboratory Methods in food and Dairy Microbiology*. Academic Press, London, pp 358.
- Kindle G, Busse A, Kampa, D, Meyer- Koning U and Daschner F D (1996). Killing activity of microwave in milk. *J Hospital infection* **33**(4):279 – 278.
- Mathur B N, Vijay Kumar, Thompkinson D K and Goyal G K (1992). *Preservation of indigenous milk products employing microwave processing*. Annual Report, p. 96, NDRI, Karnal.
- Villamiel M, Lopez-Fardino R, Corzo N, Martinez-Castyro I, Olano A and Fardin R L (1996). Microwave pasteurization of milk in a continuous flow unit. Effect on cheese making properties of goat's milk. *Milchwisenschaft* **52**(1): 29 – 32.

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Effect of Spacing on Growth, Yield and Quality of Mango

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ABSTRACT

A field experiment was conducted at NARP, Ganeshkhind, during 1992 to 2013 to study high density planting of mango variety Kesar. Accordingly plant density studies in mango was laid out in the year 1992 with spacing of 5 X 5 m, 5 X 10 m and 10 X 10 m, in randomized block design at Ganeshkhind, Pune. The growth, yield and quality parameters were recorded for three years and pooled data (2010-2012) was analyzed statistically. The results were significant and the yield and monetary returns were 125 per cent more over conventional spacing. The recommendation of planting of mango cv Kesar at spacing of 5 X 5 m with light pruning (15 – 20 cm terminal shoot) after harvest of fruits every year is recommended for higher fruit yield and monetary returns in mango growing area of Maharashtra.

Key Words: Spacing, Growth, Yield, Quality, Mango

INTRODUCTION

Mango (*Mangifera indica* L.) is an important fruit crop in the tropical and subtropical regions of the world. High planting density is a technique that has been widely used in mango orchards worldwide to increase earliness to improve handling and cultural practices and to reduce costs (Oosthuysen, 2009). In mango orchards, some studies support the use of this technology in different countries with fruit yield reaching around 20 MT/ha/year in the third harvest (Oosthuysen, 2009). This value is almost three times higher than the world mean yield (Nath *et al*, 2007). Plant response to planting density depends on intrinsic variables related to the plants themselves such as rootstock, vigor, canopy age and extrinsic variables, including soil and climate (Yamakura *et al*, 2008). Therefore, high density planting has been standardized for the popular cultivars of Mango e.g., 2.5 x 2.5m for 'Amrapali' (Majumder *et al*, 1982), 6 x 6m for 'Mallika' and 3.0 x 2.5m for 'Dashehari'; Ram *et al*, 1997). It was felt necessary to standardize it for most popularly grown mango cv Kesar in Maharashtra. Hence, the objective of this study was to find out suitable spacing for mango cv Kesar for optimum growth and yield per unit area under Western Maharashtra plain zone conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present investigation was carried out at National Agriculture Research Project (Plain Zone) Ganeshkhind, Pune during the year 2010-2012. Veneer grafted plants of cv Kesar on local stalk were planted in deep black alluvial soil at three different spacing's viz. 10 X 10m, 10 X 5m and at 5 X 5m during 1992. Thirty plants of each cultivar were used for study, ten plants being a unit of a replication. The experiment was laid out in randomized block design with three replications. Observations on plant height, East West spread, North South spread, trunk girth at 30 cm above the ground, number of fruits/tree/year, yield/tree/year, fruit dimensions, TSS, acidity (%) and disease and pests incidence were recorded. Ten fruits were randomly harvested from each replication for recording the observations. Total soluble solids (TSS) were measured by a refractometer. Titrable acidity was determined by titrating a known quantity of blended (homogenized) pulp, diluted with distilled water, against NaOH solution (1N), using phenolphthalein as indicator and the results were expressed as percentage of citric acid (Ranganna, 1986). The data were analyzed as methods suggested by Panse and Sukhatme (1985).

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of pooled data of three trials (2010-2012) have been given in Table 3. There were significant differences for all the characters under study.

Growth parameters

There was significant difference for plant height. Significantly highest plant height (7.0m) was recorded in the spacing 10 X 10m which was statistically higher than other two spacing. In case of trunk girth, the maximum (98.5cm) trunk girth was attended in spacing 10 X 10m, while the plant spread (EW and NS) was significantly higher in 10 X 10m spacing. The light pruning operation was performed after fruit harvest every year.

Vegetative variables of 'Kesar' mango trees showed significant changes in response to higher planting density. In general, plants grown under traditional wide spacing (10 X 10m) showed greater vegetative growth than those grown under narrow spacing (10 X 5m and 5 X 5m). As the area for each plant was decreased, there was a decrease in plant height, trunk girth, canopy spread (East – West and North - South). The reduction in vegetative variables in 'Tommy Atkins' mango trees grown under increased planting density had already been reported by Sousa *et al* (2012). Similar trends in indigenous cultivars were observed by Nath *et al* (2007). A possible explanation is the competition for water and soil nutrients (Policarpo *et al*, 2006), but mainly for light (Policarpo *et al*, 2006), since under higher planting density plant canopies overlap into the rows, reducing light incidence on leaves. Other variables, such as trunk girth, which confirmed the trend of reduced growth under high planting density, in all studies (Nath *et al*, 2007), plant height can decrease with increase in plant density as occurred with 'Dashehari' mango (Ram and Sirohi, 1991).

In higher planting densities, East - West and North – South spread showed reduction due to the restrictions of light. This probably occurred overlapping of branches. Reduced mango tree growth under high planting density was to some extent an expected result (Nath *et al*, 2007).

Yield parameters

Significantly the highest (347.1) number of fruits per tree was recorded in spacing 10 X 10m, while the maximum fruit weight (271.1 g) was observed in the same spacing. The yield per tree was highest in the spacing 10 X 10m but the yield per hectare was higher (216 MT) in the spacing 5 X 5m. As with vegetative variables, reproductive variables were also negatively affected by planting density. The smaller the area available to plants, the higher the tendency to decrease the number and percentage of flower shoots, and the number and yield of fruit per plant.

As a consequence of the higher planting densities was the reduction of the number and percentage of flowering shoots. Plants grown under lower planting density may produced flowers in all quadrants of the canopy, while those grown under increasing planting density (5 X 5 m) might produced flowers only in the two quadrants of the canopy.

Fruit weight was negatively co-related with plant density, it is among the variables that changed more often due to high planting density (Souza *et al*, 2012). Consequently, there were reductions in the number and yield of fruits/plant. In the planting densities of 100 (10 X 10m) and 400 (5 X 5m) plants/ha, the number of fruits produced represented only about 76 per cent of those produced in the lowest planting density, with 100 plants/ha.

However, planting density of 400 plants/ha (5 X 5 m) showed estimated fruit yield of 21.36 MT/ha/year, representing an increase of approximately 125 per cent over the yield obtained at the planting density of 100 plants (10 X 10m)/ha, which was 9.46 MT/ha/year. These results were in accordance with Joglekar *et al* (2013) for indigenous cultivars and Sousa *et al* (2012) with respect to Tommy Atkins.

Quality parameters

The significant differences were noticed for the fruit length and breadth. In the spacing 10X10m recorded highest fruit length, breadth, TSS and acidity (10.72 cm, 7.42 cm, 19.62 oBrix and 0.18 %

Effect of Spacing in Mango

respectively). The pulp per cent was significantly higher (63.2%) in the spacing 10 X 10m but it was at par with the spacing 10 X 5m. According to Policarpo *et al* (2006), under high planting density, besides the changes in the quantity and quality of intercepted light, the partitioning of assimilates between vegetative and reproductive shoots may be responsible for the effects on fruit quality. Decrease in fruit diameter with increase in plant density is reported by Sousa *et al* (2012).

Pest and disease reaction

The data (Table 1) show that incidence of mango hoppers/inflorescence and powdery mildew/inflorescence was maximum (23.4 and 16.4 as PDI, respectively) in 5 x 5m planting. It was obvious to have more incidence of insect and pest attack in dense planting.

Table 1. Effect of different spacings on pest and disease incidence of mango cv Kesar (Pooled 2010-12).

Sr. No.	Spacing (m)	Mango hopper incidence per inflorescence	Powdery mildew per inflorescence (PDI)
1.	5 X 5	23.4	16.4
2.	10 X 5	20.4	16.3
3.	10 X 10	15.8	16.3

Economics

The data (Table 2) reveal that, per hectare economics for all the spacing were worked out and it was observed that, the highest monetary returns (Rs. 3,72,312/- ha) and the highest (3.3)

B:C ratio was recorded in the spacing 5 x 5m and it was followed by the spacing 5x10 m (2.5). These results were in confirmation with findings of Ram *et al* (1997).

CONCLUSION

In the density studies in mango cv kesar, on hectare basis the highest fruit yield (21.4 MT) was produced in closer spacing of 5 X 5m. However the highest fruit yield per tree was recorded in the wider spacing of 10 X 10m.

LITERATURE

- Joglekar V, Chivate D and Pujari K H (2013). High density planting technique in dry region for 'Kesar' mango cultivation - a Savlaj pattern. *Acta Hort* **992**: 233-235
- Johnson P R and Robinson D M (2000). The tatura trellis system for high density mangoes. *Acta Hort* **509**:359-364
- Majumder P K, Sharma D K and Singh R N (1982). Study on high density orcharding on mango (*Mangifera indica* L.). *Punjab Hort J* **22**:123-27
- Nath V, Das B and Rai M (2007). Standardization of high-density planting in mango (*Mangifera indica*) under sub-humid Alfisols of Eastern India. *Indian J Agrli Sci*, **77**: 3-7.
- Oosthuyse S A (2009). Management of a 'Tommy Atkins', ultra-high density orchard and recognized benefits associated with small tree mango orchards. *Acta Hort* **820**:335-338.
- Panse V G and Sukhatme P V (1985). *Statistical Methods for Agricultural workers*. 4th ed. ICAR New Delhi.
- Policarpo M, Talluto G and Bianco R L (2006). Vegetative and productive responses of 'Conference' and 'Williams' pear trees planted at different in-row spacings. *Scientia Horticulturae* **109**: 322-331.
- Ram S and Sirohi S C (1991). Feasibility of high density orcharding in Dashehari mango. *Acta Horti* **291**: 207-212,

Table 2. Effect of plant spacing on economics of mango cv Kesar (Pooled 2010-12)

Sr. No.	Spacing (m)	Yield MT/ha	Production cost/ha (Rs.)	Gross returns Rs./ha	Net profit Rs/ha	B:C ratio
1.	5 x 5	21.4	1,61,687	5,34,000	3,72,312	3.30
2.	10 x 5	14.8	1,46,437	3,69,500	2,23,062	2.52
3.	10 x 10	9.4	1,32,911	2,35,750	1,02,838	1.77

Sale rate: Rs. 25,000/MT

Table 3. Effect of plant spacing on growth, yield and quality of mango cv Kesar (Pooled 2010-12).

Sr. No.	Spacing (m) (plants/ha)	Plant height (m)	Trunk girth (cm)	Plant spread (EW)	Plant spread (NS)	Fruit length (cm)	Fruit breadth (cm)	Fruit weight (g)	No. of fruits/tree	Yield (kg/tree)	Yield (MT/ha)	Pulp (%)	TSS (O B)	Acidity (%)
1	5 x 5 (400)	6.24	80.8	6.20	6.30	9.5	6.20	201.30	264.80	53.40	21.40	60.80	18.90	0.17
2	10 x 5 (200)	6.45	87.9	6.80	6.50	10.5	6.80	234.90	312.90	73.90	14.80	62.20	19.20	0.18
3	10 x 10 (100)	7.02	98.5	8.90	8.70	10.7	7.40	271.67	347.10	94.30	9.40	63.20	19.60	0.18
	SE +	0.09	1.49	0.18	0.15	0.11	0.10	2.49	9.94	2.53	0.57	0.49	0.16	0.002
	C.D.at 5 %	0.27	4.28	0.52	0.44	0.32	0.28	7.14	28.52	7.27	1.65	1.41	0.46	0.005

Ram S, Singh C P and Kumar S (1997). A success story of high density orcharding in mango , *Acta Hor*, **455** :375-382

Ranaganna S (1986). *Handbook of Analysis and quality control for fruit and vegetable products* (2nd Edn) Tata McGraw Hill, New Delhi, p. 180-390

Singh G, Singh A K and Mishra D (2007). High density planting in guava. *Acta Horti* **735**:235-241.

Singh Sanjay, Yadav G S and Hooda MN (2006). High density planting in ‘ Amrapali’ mango (*Mangifera indica*). *The Indian J Agril Sci* **71**: 381-383

Sousa Carlos Antônio Ferreira de , Cavalcanti Maria Irisvalda Leal Gondim and Da Silva José Algaci Lopes (2012). ‘Tommy Atkins’ mango trees subjected to high density planting in subhumid tropical climate in northeastern Brazil. *Pesq Agropec Bras Brasília* **47**(1):36-43.

Yamakura T, Hosomi A and Hirayama D(2008). Effect of tree spacing on vegetative growth and reproduction in an early growth stage in two cultivars of *Ficus carica* L. *J Japanese Soc for Hort Sci* **77**:7-16.

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Effect of Sulphur and Vermicompost on Growth, Yield and Quality of Garlic (*Allium sativum* L.)

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ABSTRACT

A field experiment was conducted during the rabi season of 2013-14 to find out dose of sulphur and vermicompost to obtain better growth, yield and quality of garlic (*Allium sativum* L.). Sixteen treatment combinations of 4 levels of sulphur (0, 25, 50 and 75 kg S/ha) and 4 levels of vermicompost (0, 2, 4 and 6 t/ha) were tested. Application of 50 kg sulphur and 4.0t vermicompost / ha individually recorded significantly higher plant height, number of leaves per plant, neck thickness of bulb, polar diameter of bulb, equatorial diameter of bulb, number of cloves per bulb, fresh weight of 20 cloves, fresh weight of bulb, dry weight of bulb, bulb yield, TSS, volatile oil content and sulphur content of bulb. This combination significantly increased the bulb yield by 25.7 and 20.69 per cent over their respective control.

Key words: Bulb yield, Garlic, Sulphur, Quality and Vermicompost

INTRODUCTION

Garlic (*Allium sativum* L.) is an important cash crop of Madhya Pradesh but its yield is very low i.e. 5t/ha. The main constraints of low productivity of garlic are imbalance use of fertilizers and decline soil productivity. Like other bulb crops, garlic also requires adequate sulphur fertilization. Sulphur (S) is essential for growth and development of plants and if soil is deficient in S then full potential of a crop cannot be realized. However, there is a need for integrated application of alternate sources of nutrients for sustaining the desired crop productivity. In integrated nutrient supply system, vermicompost is one of the important organic manure source which can be used to increase the soil fertility. Hence, the present investigation was undertaken to study the effect of vermicompost and sulphur on growth, yield and quality of garlic.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The field experiment was carried out during the *rabi* season of 2013-14 at Research Farm, College of Horticulture, Mandsaur. The soil was light black, loamy in texture, normal in reaction

(pH 7.2), low in nitrogen (243.2 kg/ha), medium in available phosphorus (19.8 kg/ha), high in available potassium (448.0 kg/ha) and sulphur (8.2 kg/ha). A total of 16 treatments were tested in randomized block design. The experiment comprised of 16 treatment combinations consisting of 4 levels of sulphur (0, 25, 50 and 75 kg S/ha) and 4 levels of vermi-compost (control, 2, 4 and 6 t/ha) with 3 replications. The G-282 variety of garlic was sown with full recommended dose of fertilizer i.e. 100 kg N + 50 kg P₂O₅ + 50 kg K₂O/ha. Garlic was sown in rows, 15 cm apart, on 19 November, 2013 and harvested on 23 April, 2014.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of Sulphur

The plant height, number of leaves per plant, neck thickness of bulb, polar diameter of bulb, equatorial diameter of bulb, number of cloves per bulb, fresh weight of 20 cloves, fresh weight of bulb, dry weight of bulb and bulb yield /ha of garlic were significantly affected with varying levels of S application (Table 1). This increase in yield attributes and yield were significant for each

levels of S as compared to control. Application of 50 kg S/ha significantly increased the bulb yield by 25.7 per cent over control. Increased yield may be due to role of S in improving uptake of nutrient by root system, increased chlorophyll content, photosynthesis activity and protein content in crop plants. Similar results were also reported by Verma *et al* (2013) and Chaudhary *et al* (2014).

A perusal of data indicated that higher level of S was significantly superior over lower levels with respect to TSS, volatile oil content and S content of bulb. With the application of S a large amount of organic bound S containing amino acids i.e. cysteine and methionine are formed which are essential for synthesis of protein and improvement in quality of garlic. Banafar and Gupta (2005) reported that the application of 50 kg S/ha has improved nitrogen content, protein content, volatile oil, crude fiber percentage, ash percentage and TSS to a considerable extent.

Effect of Vermi-compost

It was evident (Table 1 and 2) that plant height, leaves per plant, neck thickness, cloves per bulb, fresh weight of 20 cloves, polar diameter of bulb, equatorial diameter of bulb, fresh weight of bulb, dry weight of bulb, bulb yield, volatile oil, TSS and S content increased significantly due to application of vermicompost. Application of 4 t vermicompost/ha significantly increased the bulb yield by 20.7 per cent over control. The above finding clearly indicated that vermicompost played a significant role in enhancing the growth and yield of garlic. Due to application of vermicompost in soil improved nutrient availability and improvement in physical condition of soil which provides balanced nutritional environment both in soil rhizosphere and plant system. The increase in bulb yield with application of vermicompost were in conformity with the earlier findings of Suthar (2008), Shashidhar *et al* (2009), Rodriguez *et al* (2012) and Verma *et al* (2013).

Table 1. Effect of sulphur and vermi-compost on yield and quality of garlic.

Treatment	Cloves per bulb	Fresh weight of 20 cloves (g)	Fresh weight of bulb (g)	Dry weight of bulb (g)	Bulb yield (q/ha)	TSS content of bulb (%)	Volatile oil content of bulb (%)	Sulphur content of bulb (%)
Sulphur (kg S/ha)								
0	32.4	31.2	44.7	27.3	69.4	30.0	0.46	1.11
25	35.5	33.1	48.5	29.9	81.7	33.2	0.49	1.24
50	38.0	34.4	51.5	30.9	87.2	35.3	0.52	1.31
75	39.8	35.7	52.7	31.1	89.4	36.3	0.53	1.33
S. Em. +	0.75	0.45	0.55	0.35	0.8	0.36	0.006	0.01
CD 5%	2.17	1.30	1.60	1.03	2.32	1.05	0.017	0.03
Vermi-compost (t/ha)								
0	30.2	29.2	42.3	27.3	71.4	31.3	0.46	1.17
2	34.7	33.0	49.1	29.0	81.7	33.5	0.49	1.25
4	39.5	35.7	52.2	31.0	86.2	34.6	0.52	1.28
6	41.4	36.5	53.7	31.8	88.4	35.3	0.53	1.29
S. Em. +	0.75	0.45	0.55	0.35	0.8	0.36	0.006	0.01
CD 5%	2.17	1.30	1.60	1.03	2.32	1.05	0.017	0.03

Effect of Sulphur and Vermi Compost in Garlic

Table 2. Effect of sulphur and vermi-compost on growth of garlic.

Treatment	Plant height			Leaves per plant			Neck thickness (mm)	Polar diameter of bulb (cm)	Equatorial diameter of bulb (cm)
	30 DAS	60 DAS	90 DAS	30 DAS	60 DAS	90 DAS			
Sulphur (kg S/ha)									
0	32.6	41.8	71.9	5.8	6.4	7.5	10.3	3.79	4.58
25	33.8	45.1	74.7	6.1	6.9	7.9	10.8	4.05	4.92
50	35.4	47.1	77.2	6.4	7.2	8.4	11.3	4.31	5.09
75	36.6	48.7	78.2	6.6	7.4	8.7	11.7	4.45	5.18
S. Em. +	0.39	0.55	0.72	0.09	0.09	0.13	0.17	0.08	0.05
CD 5%	1.15	1.59	2.10	0.27	0.27	0.37	0.49	0.25	0.16
Vermi-compost (t/ha)									
0	32.3	42.5	68.6	5.6	6.2	7.3	9.6	3.61	4.52
2	34.2	45.0	74.5	5.9	6.9	8.0	10.9	3.95	4.91
4	35.5	46.9	78.6	6.5	7.3	8.5	11.6	4.40	5.08
6	36.5	48.3	80.3	6.7	7.5	8.9	12.1	4.62	5.23
S. Em. +	0.39	0.55	0.72	0.09	0.09	0.13	0.17	0.08	0.05
CD 5%	1.15	1.59	2.10	0.27	0.27	0.37	0.49	0.25	0.16

Application of vermi-compost significantly improved in higher volatile oil, TSS and S content in the garlic bulb. It also resulted in vigorous vegetative growth and greater accumulation of food material which ultimately increased the quality of bulb. The similar results have been reported by Gowda *et al* (2007) and Singh *et al* (2012) in garlic.

CONCLUSION

It may be concluded that application of 50 kg S and 4.0t vermicompost / ha recorded significantly higher plant height, number of leaves per plant, neck thickness of bulb, polar diameter of bulb, equatorial diameter of bulb, number of cloves per bulb, fresh weight of 20 cloves, fresh weight of bulb, dry weight of bulb, bulb yield, TSS, volatile oil content and sulphur content of bulb.

REFERENCES

Banafar R N S and Gupta N K (2005). Influence of soil and foliar application of sulphur on growth, yield and quality on onion. *Proc. National Seminar on Agro-technology, Quality, Processing and Export of Spices*, March 20-21, 2005. J.N.K.V.V. Jabalpur. pp. 67.

Chaudhary P, Jhajharia A and Kumar R (2014). Influence of sulphur and zinc fertilization on yield, yield components and quality traits of soybean (*Glycine max L.*) *The Bioscan* **9** (1):137-142.

Gowda M C, Vijayakumar M and Gowda A P M (2007). Influence of integrated nutrient management on growth, yield and quality of garlic (*Allium sativum L.*) cv. G-282. *Crop Res* **33**(1/3):144-147.

Rodriguez R A, Migliarina A M, Ayastuy M E, Lobartini J C, Dagna N, Greco N, Konijnenburg A and Fernandez J A (2012). The effect of different organic fertilization on garlic (*Allium sativum L.*) in Bahia Blanca Region, Argentina. *Acta Hort.* **933**:187-194.

Shashidhar T R, Mannikeri I M and Chavan M L (2009). Influence of different organic manures on growth and yield of garlic (*Allium sativum L.*). *J Ecob* **25**(3):235-239.

Singh P C, Saravanan R and Singh S R (2012). Effect of NPK with different doses of organic manures on growth and yield of garlic (*Allium sativum L.*) var Yamuna Safed-2 (G-50). *Env Ecol* **30**(2):329-331.

Suthar S (2008). Impact of vermicompost and composted farmyard manure on growth and yield of garlic (*Allium sativum L.*) field crop. *Int J Plant Prod* **3**(1):1735-6.

Verma S, Choudhary M R, Yadav B L and Jakhar M L (2013). Influence of vermicompost and sulphur on growth and yield of garlic (*Allium sativum L.*) under semi arid climate. *J Spices Arom Crops* **22**(1):20-23.

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Effect of Training on knowledge and Adoption of Value addition Technology

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ABSTRACT

Value addition in agriculture predominantly offers a means to increase, rejuvenate, and stabilize farm income. The aim of the study was to know the effect of KVK training programmes on knowledge and adoption by rural women of value addition technology. The present study was carried out at KVK, Kollam, 150 beneficiary and non beneficiary rural women were selected for the study. The present investigation was based on the experimental design of social research considering beneficiary as experimental group and non-beneficiaries as a control group. The data revealed that majority of trained women had high level of knowledge with respect to making vegetable cutlet, chicken cutlet, grape wine, lemon pickle and fish pickle than the untrained participants. It was concluded that there is significant role of KVK in promotion of improved production practices of value added products and ensuring their adoption.

Key Words: Value addition, Training, Knowledge level, Adoption level.

INTRODUCTION

Training is the process of improving the knowledge and skills, changing the attitude of an individual for doing a specific job. Along with the changing situation, the people also need to acquire new knowledge, skills and attitude to keep up with the changing environment. Rural women spend much of their time in unpaid activities like working in the family, farm and other domestic work (Sharma *et al*, 2013). Therefore, training has been considered as the most important for developing an individual and improving his/her work efficiency. One of the main tasks of Krishi Vigyan Kendra (KVK) is to provide and improve the level of knowledge of the trainees about the improved farm practices (Gupta and Verma, 2013). KVK, Kollam conducted many training programmes exclusively for rural women with the aim to make them competent in performing various activities related to home science and agricultural sciences. Hence, the present study was designed to know the effect of KVK training programmes on knowledge and adoption of value addition technology by the rural farm women.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The study was conducted in Kollam district of Kerala state where the Krishi Vigyan Kendra is situated. The present investigation was based on the experimental design of social research considering beneficiary as experimental group and non beneficiary as a control group. The investigation is confined to purposively selected trainees trained under State plan board project funded under the project "Establishment of Agro processing cum training centre" and KVK trainees during 2014-2016. For the selection of respondent, 100 trainees (beneficiary) for knowledge level and adoption level were selected randomly from the list of beneficiaries who participated in the training programmes on value addition of fruits and vegetables. After selecting beneficiaries 50 numbers of non beneficiaries were also selected randomly as control group to measure knowledge and adoption level. Thus in all 150 respondents constituted the sample of this study. The role of KVK was assessed in terms of gain in knowledge and adoption by the beneficiary as a result of demonstration and training imparted to them compared to non-beneficiary. The

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Table 1. Knowledge and adoption of different value added products by the respondents.

(N=150)

Sr. No	Particulars	Knowledge		Adoption	
		Beneficiary (%)	Non- beneficiary (%)	Beneficiary (%)	Non- beneficiary (%)
A	Syrups				
1	Naruneendi	95	20	56	4
2	Banana Pseudostem	96	22	72	8
3	Mango(unripe)	98	36	86	14
4	Pine apple	97	42	81	22
5	Bilumbi	92	28	79	12
B	Jam				
1	Mixed fruit	95	8	65	2
2	Pine apple	96	22	89	14
3	Banana	99	24	82	12
C	Cutlet				
1	Banana blossom	97	22	92	14
2	Tender jack fruit	93	12	86	6
3	Vegetable	100	36	100	18
4	Chicken/ Cutlet	100	30	100	14
D	Halwa				
1	Banana	96	24	72	12
2	Carrot	91	4	56	2
3	Jack fruit	98	30	81	14
E	Wine				
1	Grapes	100	10	96	4
2	Banana	96	4	56	0
3	Pine apple	98	6	72	2
F	Pickle				
1	Banana Pseudostem	99	4	75	0
2	Lemon	100	54	100	54
3	Fish	100	30	100	30

role was measured in terms of impact index with the help of following formula

Impact index = $\frac{[\text{MIK of beneficiary} - \text{MIK of non- beneficiary}] [\text{MIA of beneficiary} - \text{MIA of non- beneficiary}]}{2}$

MIK = Mean Index of Knowledge ; MIA = Mean Index of Adoption

Impact (%) change = $\frac{\text{Sum of difference of index of knowledge adoption}}{2}$

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Adoption of Value Addition Technology

Table 2. Effect of trainings in terms of knowledge and adoption.

Sr. No.	Particular	Beneficiary	Non - Beneficiary	Difference
1	Mean knowledge index	97.04	22.28	74.76
2	Mean adoption index	40.30	6.14	34.16
	Total	137.42	28.42	108.92
3	Impact (per cent) = $\frac{\text{Sum of difference of index}}{2}$ $= \frac{108.92}{2} = 54.46\%$			

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Knowledge about different value added products and their adoption level was measured for the beneficiary and non-beneficiary respondents using a questioner.

The data (Table 1) revealed that all the beneficiary farmers had knowledge about for making vegetable cutlet, chicken cutlet, grape wine, lemon pickle, and fish pickle whereas, the corresponding knowledge level for the same products for non beneficiaries were 36 , 30 , 10 , 54 and 30 per cent , respectively.

In case of adoption, cent percent beneficiary farmers had adopted Vegetable cutlet, chicken cutlet, grape wine, lemon pickle and fish pickle. Whereas, in case of non-beneficiary adoption was highest for lemon pickle preparation (54 %) this was followed by pseudo stem pickle (99 %), pine apple wine (98 %), Pine apple jam (98 %) and syrup of un ripe mango (98 %). For beneficiaries the least adopted product was Naruneendi syrup (56 %). In case of non- beneficiaries, banana wine and pseudo stem pickle was not adopted at all.

Change in term of knowledge and adoption

The effect of KVK trainings as a whole was computed as the sum total of the differences of both the indices i.e., mean index of knowledge and adoption divided by two. The data thus obtained have been presented in Table 2.

It was evident (Table 2) that there was an effect

of KVK trainings and demonstration up to 54.46 per cent over the existing knowledge and adoption by the beneficiary which was found to be substantial over the non-beneficiary farmers. Therefore, it could be stated that there was a remarkable effect of the trainings and demonstration on those respondents who attended the training programme and participated in demonstrations conducted by KVK Kollam in terms of the knowledge about value added products and its adoption by them as compared to their counterparts i.e. the respondents who did not participate in the training programmes and demonstrations.

CONCLUSION

It was thus concluded that there is significant role of KVK in promotion of value added products of fruits and vegetables and ensuring their adoption. It was also ascertained that there was substantial effect of training and demonstrations over the existing knowledge and adoption of the beneficiary respondents than the non-beneficiary respondents.

REFERENCES

- Sharma P, Singh G P and Jha S K(2013). Impact of training programme on knowledge and adoption of preservation technologies among farm women- A comparative study. *Indian Res J Ext Edu* **13**(1): 96-100.
- Gupta S and Verma S(2013). Impact of KVK on knowledge level of farm women. *J Rural Agric Res* **13**(2): 87-89
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Effect of Variety and Method of Sowing Adopted by Farmers on Wheat Yield in District Kapurthala

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ABSTRACT

A survey was conducted on different wheat varieties and method of sowing adopted by the farmers in the district and its effect on wheat yield obtained. The results revealed area under wheat variety HD 2967 was reduced by 23 per cent and increased by 20 per cent under HD 3086. Regarding age and education of the farmers, fertilizer application decreased with the increase of literacy level of the farmers, while yield levels remained static. Data regarding different methods of sowing followed by the farmers revealed that area under wheat sown with seed cum fertilizer drill reduced during 2015-16 and increased under zero till seed drill, broadcasting, use of rotavator and happy seeder as compared to the year 2014-15.

Key Words: Cultivars, DAP, Urea, Kapurthala, Method of sowing, Wheat, Yield.

INTRODUCTION

Wheat was cultivated in Punjab on an area of 35.5 lakh ha with the average productivity of 43.04 q/ha (Anonymous, 2016). The preference for different varieties of wheat and method of sowing varies from farmer to farmer, as per their ease and management. The socio-economic factors such as age and education had impact on farmer's package of practices followed and wheat yield obtained. Taking the above issues in consideration, a survey was planned to understand the preference of different varieties of wheat along with method of sowing opted by farmers in district Kapurthala. In the present study, a comparison was also made regarding varietal preferences and method of sowing used by the farmers during the year 2014-15.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The survey was conducted during Rabi 2015-16 in district Kapurthala. The grain market of different blocks of Kapurthala was visited to collect the information on wheat. A total of 146 farmers with wheat cultivated on 365 ha were selected. A questionnaire on wheat was developed using different parameters including variety sown,

method of sowing, age and education of the farmer, fertilizer input added and wheat yield obtained. The data thus collected were tabulated and analyzed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Diversity in wheat cultivation

The data (Table 1) revealed that during the year 2014-15, wheat cultivar HD 2967 sown on maximum (96%) area followed by WH 1105 (2.6%) and PBW 621 (1.4%), respectively (Manan et al, 2015). During 2015-16, HD 2967 covered 72.9 per cent of the total area in the district followed by HD 3086 (20.0%), WH 1105 (4.9%), PBW 550 (1.3%) and PBW 677 (0.9%), respectively. The major shift in area from HD 2967 to HD 3086 was observed with marginal increase in area under WH 1105 and PBW 677 (a new variety released by PAU, Ludhiana). Overall, HD 2967 still have been sown on maximum area as compared to other wheat varieties. This was in line with the findings of Brar (2014).

Age and education in relation with fertilizer use and wheat yield

Data in Table 2 revealed that most of students with education level up to 10th were of age more

Table 1. Diversity in wheat cultivation.

Variety	2014-15		2015-16	
	Per cent area covered	Yield (q/ha)	Per cent area covered	Yield (q/ha)
HD 2967	96.0	34.3	72.9	47.2
HD 3086	--	--	20.0	46.7
WH 1105	2.6	35.0	4.9	48.0
PBW 550	--	--	1.3	45.5
PBW 677	--	--	0.9	43.7
PBW 621	1.4	38.8	--	--

than 30 yr and farmers with education level of more than 10th were of age less than 45 yr. Maximum area was covered by farmers with education level of 10th and of age more than 45 yr followed by farmers with education level of 12th and were in age group of 30-45 yr.

Regarding fertilizer use, the use of urea and diammonium phosphate (DAP) decreased with the education of the farmers, irrespective of farmer age in different groups, while there was marginal effect on wheat yield with the variation in education, age and fertilizer application etc.

Method of sowing in relation with wheat yield

Data gathered in Table 3 revealed the area covered under different methods of sowing during last 2 years. It was evident that during the year 2014-15, major area covered under seed cum fertilizer drill (39.1%) followed by zero till seed drill (31.5%), broadcasting (22.9%) and use of rotavator (6.5%), respectively (Manan et al, 2015). During 2015-16, the maximum area under wheat was sown by zero till drill (38.8%) followed by broadcasting (27.3%), seed cum fertilizer drill (14.6%), rotavator (12.3%) and happy seeder (7.0%), respectively. Zero till seed drill was getting popularity because intensive

Table 2. Effect of age and education level of farmers on fertilizer levels and yield of wheat.

Education level	Age (Years)	Number of farmers	Per cent area covered	Urea applied (kg/ha)	DAP applied (Kg/ha)	Yield (q/ha)
Up to 5th	<30	--	--	--	--	--
	30-45	2	0.3	312.5	187.5	45.0
	>45	12	2.8	302.0	156.2	46.2
6-10th	<30	--	--	--	--	--
	30-45	12	5.8	298.0	143.7	46.5
	>45	54	39.7	272.5	146.7	46.5
10-12th	<30	8	1.6	250.0	140.5	48.2
	30-45	38	33.6	276.2	127.7	47.2
	>45	--	--	--	--	--
Collegiate	<30	6	4.0	250.0	125.0	47.5
	30-45	14	12.2	214.2	126.7	46.7
	>45	--	--	--	--	--

Effect of Variety and Method of Sowing on Wheat Yield

Table 3. Effect of method of sowing on wheat yield.

Method of sowing	2014-15		2015-16	
	Per cent area covered	Yield (q/ha)	Per cent area covered	Yield (q/ha)
Zero till seed drill	31.5	32.3	38.8	47.2
Broadcasting	22.9	36.0	27.3	48.0
Seed cum fertilizer drill	39.1	34.2	14.6	47.0
Rotavator	6.5	37.9	12.3	48.2
Happy seeder	--	--	7.0	46.2

tillage may not be necessary for wheat crop in paddy-wheat rotation and there is sufficient scope to reduced tillage operations for seed bed preparation of wheat crop. Overall, zero tillage sowing was found to be most time, energy saving by the farmers and it also reduced cost of production as compare to conventional method of sowing (Papu et al, 2012).

The shift in method of sowing was probably due to adoption of happy seeder technology by the farmers and increase in area under use of rotavator was probably due to easiness of using rotavator as compared to seed cum fertilizer drill. The increase in grain yield with rotavator and broadcasting as compared to row sowing was observed during both the years under study. Similar results were also reported by Abbas et al(2009).

CONCLUSION

Considering diversity in wheat cultivation, the shift in area under HD 3086 was observed from HD 2967 along with increased area under PBW 550 (late sown) and PBW 677 (new variety). Taking into account the education level and age of the

farmers, use of fertilizers was reduced. Considering the method of sowing in wheat, shift in area under rotavator and happy seeder was observed from seed cum fertilizer drill, as compared to last year. Overall, farmers preferred new varieties and technologies. With the ease in technology, the adoption level increased as in case of zero till seed drill and broadcasting methods of wheat sowing.

REFERENCES

- Abbas G, Ali M A, Abbas G, Azam M and Hussain I (2009). Impact of planting methods on wheat grain yield and yield contributing parameters. *The J Anim & Plant Sci* 19(1): 30-33.
- Anonymous (2016). Package and Practices of Rabi crops 2016-17. Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana. pp 1.
- Brar R S (2014). Wheat variety HD 2967 gains popularity among farmers. *Hindustan Times*, Nov 10th , 2014.
- Manan J, Sharma M, Singh G and Singh G (2015). Package of practices followed by farmers and its effect on wheat yield in district Kapurthala. *J Krishi Vigyan* 4(1): 67-71.
- Papu S, Singh S and Singh B R (2012). Performance of zero-till drill for wheat cultivation at farmer's fields. *Int J Sci & Res ISSN (Online): 2319-7064*.

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Efficacy of Granular Insecticide against Yellow Stem Borer (*Scirpophaga incertulas*) on Basmati Rice

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ABSTRACT

Field experiments were conducted during *kharif* 2014-15 and 2015-16 seasons on Pusa Basmati 1121 to evaluate the efficacy and economy of granular insecticide against stem borer. The efficacy of 5 insecticides, viz., regent 0.3G (fipronil) @ 15 kg/ha, ferterra 0.4 GR (chlorantraniliprole) @ 10kg/ha, padan 4G (cartap hydrochloride) @25kg/ha, foratox 10G (phorate)@ 12.5kg/ha, dursban 10 G (chlorpyrifos) @10kg/ha besides insecticidal check dursban 10 G (chlorpyrifos) @10kg/ha and untreated control was evaluated against Yellow Stem Borer. The stem borer infestation, i.e. white ears varied between 5.54 to 8.20 per cent over the *kharif* seasons. The results on stem borer infestation and yield indicated that all the granular insecticidal treatments were significantly superior to untreated control but these insecticides differed from each other with respect to their cost. Regent 0.3G (fipronil) @ 15 kg/ha followed by the ferterra 0.4 GR (chlorantraniliprole) @ 10kg/ha and padan 4G (cartap hydrochloride) @25kg/ha with 5.88, 6.48 and 6.68 average YSB infestation; and 19.87, 18.25 and 17.125q/ha average grain yields, respectively, were effective against YSB on basmati rice and increasing its yield but regent 0.3G had its additional advantage over ferterra 0.4GR and padan 4G as far as its cost of application in the field was concerned. The average cost of application of regent 0.3G, ferterra 0.4G and padan 4G comes out to be Rs. 1163/-ha, Rs. 1975/-ha and Rs. 2000/-ha i.e. one has to spend this much amount of money to get rid of the pest from an area of one hectare and hence, regent must be recommended to farmers keeping in view its efficacy.

Key Words: Granule Insecticides, Rice, Stem borer, Crop pest.

INTRODUCTION

Basmati occupies a special status in rice cultivation. Its rice is known for excellent cooking and eating qualities. However, basmati varieties occupy about 50-55 per cent rice area in the Haryana state. The infestation of yellow stem borer in Ambala district is more pronounced compared to other insect's larvae. It has attained major pest status with the introduction of high yielding basmati varieties and particularly in areas of high fertilizer use. Stem borers are responsible for significant losses (Shafique and Anwar, 1986). The yellow stem borer (*Scirpophaga incertulas*) is widely distributed throughout South and Southeast Asia (Heinrichs *et al*, 1985).

Among the insect pests, the yellow stem borer (YSB), *Scirpophaga incertulas* is the most important and devastating insect pest of basmati/aromatic rice varieties. The insect is widely distributed throughout the rice growing areas in India. The insect has a number of host plants. The larva feed inside the stem causing drying of the central shoots or dead hearts in young plants. The insect causes drying of the panicles or white ears in older plants. The pest remains active throughout the year except between April and May and between October and November. The eggs are oval, flattened, and transparent at first and turn black before hatching. The caterpillars are tiny; black headed which bore into the stem from the growing point downward. The female is four

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winged. Colour is orange yellow with prominent black spots. Yellow stem borer causing yield losses to the tune of 27-34 per cent every year.

The economic threshold level for YSB have been determined to be in between 5 and 10% larval infestation levels (Prasad *et al*, 1992). The larvae of the stem borers, after hatching, bore into the rice plant and cut out the food supply to the upper part of affected stem, while the lower plant part remains green. The larval stage of stem borer mostly remains concealed inside the stem and is difficult to control.

As there is no full proof method to get rid of YSB either through a resistant variety or through certain biological agents, the use of insecticides becomes unavoidable. For quick knock down effect, the application of judicious dose of granular insecticides is desired to save the crop from toll of insects. Keeping in view of the above, in the present study, an attempt has been made to evaluate the efficacy and economy of new promising granular insecticides against YSB in basmati rice.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The field experiments were conducted in randomized block design with four replications during *kharif* seasons 2014-15 and 2015-16. The plot size was (5x4) m² with 1.0 m replication border and 0.5 m treatment border between the plots. The experimental plots have been separated by raising bunds of about 0.6m height all around each plot. The basmati variety used in the present study was *Pusa Basmati 1121*, released from IARI (New Delhi) of 145 days duration and sown in the first fortnight of June. About 25-30d old seedling having 5 to 6 leaf stage was transplanted in first fortnight of July. Transplant two-three seedlings per hill in line at spacing of 20x15 cm (33 hills/sq. m). The crop was raised following standard agronomic practices of irrigation and Nitrogen (N₂) and Phosphorus (P₂O₅) fertilizers were applied @ 90:30 kg/ha. All P₂O₅ and 1/2 N₂ was applied at the time of transplanting and rest of N₂ were applied at panicle initiation stage. The cultural practices were performed uniformly and equally to all the plots.

Six treatments included control with 5 granular insecticides *viz.*, regent 0.3G (fipronil) @ 15 kg/ha, ferterra 0.4 GR (chlorantraniliprole) @ 10kg/ha, padan 4G (cartap hydrochloride) @25kg/ha, foratox 10G (phorate)@12.5kg/ha, dursban 10 G (chlorpyriphos) @10kg/ha were used at vegetative and panicle formation stage respectively in recommended doses. All were replicated four times. Each demonstration was conducted in the farmer's field of 4 villages of Saha block of the Ambala district in agro-climatic zone-I of Haryana in irrigated condition on medium soils with low to medium fertility. To record the infestation of YSB, each plot was divided into 3 equal units for observation before harvesting. An area of 0.25 m² was selected from each unit and total panicle bearing tillers and YSB infested tillers, i.e. white ears (WE) were counted. Thus, a total of 20-27 hills (56-112 tillers) were sampled in each plot and infestation of YSB as per cent white ears have been worked out. Harvesting was done by the end of November. The yield data was recorded by excluding 2 border rows from all sides for each plot separately. The data have been analyzed statistically.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results regarding YSB infestation and yield were summarized in table 1. The YSB infestation varied from 6.22 to 7.74 and 5.54 to 8.20 per cent during *Kharif* seasons 2014-15 and 2015-16, respectively. The results on YSB infestation revealed that all the granular insecticidal treatments significantly superior to untreated control during the two *kharif* seasons. During the year 2014-15, regent 0.3G (fipronil) @ 15 kg/ha was most promising with 6.22 per cent YSB infestation. It was followed by the ferterra 0.4 GR (chlorantraniliprole) @ 10kg/ha and padan 4G (cartap hydrochloride) @ 25kg/ha with 6.60 and 6.70 per cent YSB infestation, respectively. These were comparable to check granule insecticide dursban 10 G (chlorpyriphos) @10kg/ha with 7.37 per cent YSB infestation and significantly superior to untreated control with 7.74 per cent YSB infestation.

Efficacy of Granular Insecticide on Basmati Rice

Table1. Comparative efficacy and economy of new granular insecticides on YSB infestation in basmati rice.

Treatment			Yellow stem borer (% WE)			Yield (q/ ha)			Cost of application Rs./ha
Insecticide	Formulation	Dose (kg / ha)	2014-15	2015-16	Pooled	2014-15	2015-16	Pooled	Average
T1-Regent (Fipronil)	0.3G	15	6.22	5.54	5.88	19.50	20.25	19.87	1163
T2-Ferterra (Chlorantraniliprole)	0.4 GR	10	6.60	6.36	6.48	17.75	18.75	18.25	1975
T3- Padan (Cartap hydrochloride)	4G	25	6.70	6.66	6.68	17.25	17.00	17.12	2000
T4-Foratox (Phorate)	10G	12.5	7.92	6.30	7.11	15.75	16.50	16.12	938
T5-Dursban (Chlorpyrifos)	10 G	10	7.37	7.08	7.22	13.25	13.75	13.50	1000
T6- Control			7.74	8.20	7.97	12.25	13.50	12.87	-
C.V.			28.18	24.56		15.03	11.42		-
C.D.			10.60	9.29		3.64	2.88		-

However during the year 2015-16, regent 0.3G (fipronil) @ 15 kg/ha followed by the ferterra 0.4 GR (chlorantraniliprole) @ 10kg/ha and padan 4G (cartap hydrochloride) @25kg/ha with 5.54, 6.36 and 6.66 per cent YSB infestation, respectively, were most promising and significantly superior over untreated control with 8.20 per cent YSB infestation. The check granule insecticide dursban 10 G (chlorpyrifos) @10kg/ha was also effective with 7.37 and 7.08 per cent YSB infestation, respectively, during the year 2014-15 and 2015-16. Thus on an average the pooled data indicated that regent 0.3G (fipronil) @ 15 kg/ha, ferterra 0.4 GR (chlorantraniliprole) @ 10kg/ha and padan 4G (cartap hydrochloride) @25kg/ha with 5.88, 6.48 and 6.68 per cent YSB infestation, respectively, were most promising insecticides.

The grain yield data also revealed that all the granule insecticidal treatments were significantly superior to untreated control and comparable to check insecticide dursban 10 G (chlorpyrifos) @10kg/ha. The yield data indicated that regent

0.3G (fipronil) @ 15 kg/ha followed by ferterra 0.4 GR (chlorantraniliprole) @ 10kg/ha and padan 4G (cartap hydrochloride) @25kg/ha with 19.50, 17.75 and 17.25 q/ha grain yields, respectively, were significantly superior to untreated control with 12.25 q/ha yields during 2014-15. However during the year 2015-16, regent 0.3G (fipronil) @ 15 kg/ha followed by ferterra 0.4 GR (chlorantraniliprole) @ 10kg/ha and padan 4G (cartap hydrochloride) @25kg/ha with 20.25, 18.75 and 17.00 q/ha grain yields, respectively, were significantly superior to untreated control with 13.50 q/ha grain yields.

The average grain yield of two seasons indicated that regent 0.3G (fipronil) @ 15 kg/ha, ferterra 0.4 GR (chlorantraniliprole) @ 10kg/ha and padan 4G (cartap hydrochloride) @25kg/ha were most promising with 19.87, 18.25 and 17.12 q/ha average grain yields, respectively, in comparison to check granule insecticide dursban 4G @10 kg/ha and untreated control with 13.50 and 12.87 q/ha average grain yields, respectively.

There must be two criteria based on which the insecticide should be selected for application in the field i.e. besides its efficacy, the cost of its application should also be taken into account. As far as the efficacy of the mentioned granular insecticides is concerned, all were found effective but these insecticides differed from each other as far as their cost of application in the field was concerned. The average cost of application of Regent 0.3 G, Ferterra 0.4G and Padan 4G comes out to be Rs. 1163/ha, Rs. 1975/ha and Rs. 2000/ha i.e. one has to spend this much amount of money to get rid of the pest from an area of one hectare.

CONCLUSION

It may be concluded that although regent 0.3G (fipronil) @ 15 kg/ha, ferterra 0.4 GR (chlorantraniliprole) @ 10kg/ha and padan 4G (cartap hydrochloride) @25kg/ha were effective

in controlling YSB on basmati rice variety and increasing its yield but regent 0.3G had its additional advantage over ferterra 0.4GR and padan 4G as far as its cost was concerned and it must be recommended to farmers keeping in view its efficacy.

REFERENCES

- Heinrichs E A, Medrano F G and Rupasas H R (1985). *Genetic evaluation for insect resistance in rice*. International Rice Research Institute, Los banos, Laguana, Philippines, 356 pp.
- Prasad S S, Gupta P K and Singh R B (1992). Economic threshold level for yellow stem borer, *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) in deepwater rice. *Nat Acad Sci Letters* **15** : 235-236.
- Shafiq M and Anwar M(1986). Effect of transplanting time on the borer attack and yield and yield of rice cultivars. *Proc Pakistan Congr Zool* **6**: 89-92.

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Enhancement in Production of Sunflower in North India through Conductance of Cluster Front line Demonstrations

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ABSTRACT

The domestic requirement of the oilseed had been manifold as of a modern living standard which has been fulfilled through the imports that leads to imbalance the Indian economy. To fulfill the domestic demand and to boost the production and productivity, front line demonstrations (FLDs) on sunflower were conducted at farmer's field in 2 KVKs of Punjab and 1 KVK of Haryana during spring season 2015-2016. In KVKs at Jalandhar, Kapurthala and Yamunanagar, 20, 20 and 10 FLDs were conducted on an area of 8.00, 8.00 and 4.00 ha respectively. The technologies i.e. improved variety; IPM, seed treatment and head rot management were followed to demonstrate the FLDs. Thus, 9.82 and 15.53 per cent higher yield was recorded over the local check in Punjab and Haryana. From demonstrations it was concluded that the vegetable oil production could be boosted by encouraging the farmers through recommended technologies which were followed in the FLDs.

Key Words: American bollworm (*Helicoverpa armigera*), FLD, Sunflower, Grain yield, IPM

INTRODUCTION

Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) is regarded as an important source of vegetable oil and has become the fourth most important oilseed crop in India. In Punjab and Haryana it is grown in spring season as of its short duration crop characteristics and it fits well in multiple cropping systems. Generally, potato and sugarcane based cropping system suits well for sunflower cultivation. The availability of early and medium duration varieties and sunflower hybrids, responsive to high input management and its relatively less thermo- and photo-insensitivity renders sunflower an ideal crop for all seasons. Due to its wider adaptability, the crop is ideally suited for intercropping system. It is estimated that about 10 per cent of the area of sunflower is under intercropping. In India it is cultivated on an area of 672 thousand ha with an annual production and productivity of 504 thousand MT and 750 kg/ha, respectively during 2013-14 (Anonymous, 2017). It has been reported that sunflower oil is good source of nutrients, vitamins, minerals and antioxidants. The sunflower oil is gaining more importance as

it is free from acid and rich in Vitamin-A, roasted sunflower seeds are also used as snacks. Because of increment in domestic consumption of sunflower edible oil, its cultivation is in critical situation in India. To fulfill this domestic requirement 40 per cent of the oil had been imported. To sustain this production and consumption system, the Department of Agriculture, Cooperation & Farmers Welfare (DAC&FW) had sanctioned the project "Cluster Frontline Demonstrations on Rabi Oilseed 2015-16" to ICAR-ATARI, Ludhiana through National Mission on Oilseeds and Oil Palm (NMOOP), a scheme sponsored by central government. This project was implemented in Krishi Vigyan Kendras (KVKs) of Zone-1 with main objective to boost the production and productivity through Frontline demonstrations (FLDs) with latest and specific technologies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present investigation of FLDs was conducted during spring season 2015-16 by the KVKs of northern states i.e. Punjab and Haryana in different

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blocks of the selected districts in Zone-I (Table 1). The FLDs were conducted with the objectives (i) self reliance in edible oils (ii) reduction in import of edible oil (iii) to raise oilseed production. The KVKs were funded by the ICAR-ATARI, Zone-I, Ludhiana. The funds provided to the KVKs were Rs.6,000/-ha for providing the quality inputs to the farmers in sunflower cultivation. The inputs i.e. recommended variety seed along with material of demonstrated technology was provided by the KVKs for conducting FLDs to the farmers (Table 1). The input materials provided to the farmers and they were trained to follow the package and practices for sunflower cultivation as recommended by the State Agricultural Universities.

The farmers followed the full package of practices like seed treatment, bio fertilizer inoculation, fertilizer application, water and weed management, insect-pest management etc. In case of local check, the traditional practices were followed in existing varieties by the farmers. The yield data were collected from both FLD plots as well as farmers practice plot (local check) and compiled results has been given in Table 2.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The total number of twenty Frontline demonstrations on sunflower variety PSH-1962 was laid out in an area of 8 hectares in farmer's field in Nurmahal, Shahkot and Mehatpur blocks of Jalandhar district in Punjab. The inputs provided to the farmers for laying the demonstrations were Thiram @ 2gm/kg seed and application of 200 ml Nuvan and 1 liter Dursban 20 EC and for controlling the tobacco caterpillar and American bollworm

insect that cause head rot disease in sunflower. The recorded yield in the demonstrations was 24.21 per cent higher than the local check in Jalandhar district

In Kapurthala, PSH 1962 variety was demonstrated on 8 ha area at twenty farmers' fields in Sultanpur lodhi and Kapurthala blocks of the district in Punjab. This, variety gave the average yield of 19.5 q/ha in district. After the improved treatment with Thiram 2g/kg of seed and ridge sowing by dibbling method was applied for sowing. Pre-emergence herbicide stomp @ 2.5l/ha was applied and 125 kg urea + 187.5 kg SSP. The farmer's fields were regularly monitored by the scientists for applications of suitable technologies.

Sadaura, Radaurand and Mustafabad blocks of Yamunanagar district in Haryana were selected to demonstrate Pioneer 64A57 variety of sunflower in four hectares at 10 farmers' field. The crop was sown after potato and sugarcane during the last week of February and first week of March. The results of the demonstrations, 15.53 per cent higher yield was recorded than the local check 16.1q/ha. This improvement in yield might be due to the application of DAP @125, Urea @125, gypsum @500kg/ha at time of sowing and after 3rd irrigation application of Chorpyriphos@1875ml/ha for control of *helicopter armigera* insect in sunflower crop.

Use of SSP and micronutrient

As an oilseed crop, sunflower needs more application of sulfur containing nutrient and micro nutrients. So, KVKs were allowed to concentrate to distribution of SSP and micronutrient as an input.

Table 1. Details of Frontline demonstrations conducted by the KVKs of sunflower in different districts during summer 2015-16.

KVK	Variety	Demonstrated technology	Block
Jalandhar	PSH 1962	Improved variety, IPM	Nurmahal, Shahkot and Mehatpur
Kapurthala	PSH 1962	Full Package of Practices	Sultanpurlodhi and Kapurthala
Yamunanagar	Pioneer 64A57	Improved variety, Sulphur (Gypsum)	Sadaura, Radaurand, Mustafabad

Production of Sunflower in North India

Table 2. Details of yield of FLDs conducted of sunflower during summer 2015-16

KVK	FLDs (No.)	Area (ha)	Demo yield (q/ha)	Local Check yield (q/ha)	Per cent increase
Jalandhar	20	8.00	11.80	9.50	24.21
Kapurthala	20	8.00	19.50	19.00	2.63
Total	40	16.00	15.65	14.25	9.82
Yamunanagar	10	4.00	18.6	16.1	15.53
Total	10	4.00	18.6	16.01	15.53

Constraints faced while conducting FLDs

The Frontline demonstration yields obtained by farmers have always been lower than those potential yields attainable under best practices. The farmers' yields are affected by various environmental and socio-economic factors like irregular supply of power for irrigation, non-availability of quality seed, poor quality of inputs, prevalence of biotic stress (mustard aphid, white rust, *Alternaria* blight and *Sclerotinia* rot), abiotic stress (rain, hail and abrupt rise in temperature in the months of February-March) causes severe yield loss, delayed sowing of the crop after harvesting of Kharif crops leads to lower yield, lack of sowing implements like Ridger Seeder for raya sowing in limiting moisture, use of recommended dosage of fertilizers, especially Sulphur is not practiced leading to decline in productivity and production. These constraints are being faced by the scientists working with the farmer's fields.

CONCLUSION

It was concluded that the yield gap between demonstration yield and local check can be

minimized through the wider publicity of the improved package of practices through various extensions activities organized in FLDs programmes in the farmer's fields. So, for fast and wide dissemination of technologies generated by SAUs a large number of FLDs should be conducted and the scientific visits to the fields should be augmented with the training to the farmers by Krishi Vigyan Kendras who are working at grass root level with the farmers. However, it has reported been that as per the constraints in oilseed production can be reduced by providing the quality inputs and scientific knowledge to the farmers.

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REFERENCES

Anonymous (2017) <http://icar-iior.org.in/db/apy2/index.php>.

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Evaluation of Exotic Cultivars of Gerbera (*Gerbera jamesonii* L.) under Naturally Ventilated Polyhouse in Western Odisha

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ABSTRACT

An endeavor was made during 2014-16 to evaluate and identify superior and most promising commercial variety in respect of important morphological and economic trait amongst 18 exotic cultivars of gerbera under naturally ventilated Poly house in Western Odisha. Variations in different growth parameters were prominent. Among vegetative parameters, 'Dreamer' recorded least mean value in terms of plant height, leaf area, number of leaves per plant, length and breadth of leaf, plant spread, number of lobes per leaf, fresh weight, vase life and yield per sq. m among quality parameters. Higher leaf area was found in 'Shimmer' followed by 'Paradiso' while 'Dune' has intermediate plant height and plant spread. 'Power Play' exhibited more number of leaves per plant with higher petiole length and more number of suckers per clump. With respect to flower and quality characters, the cultivar 'Diablo' found superior with respect to plant height, disc diameter and neck thickness and higher fresh weight. Minimum number of ray florets per flower with thicker petals were recorded in 'Colt', while 'Artist' have recorded highest number of ray florets with lesser petal thickness. 'Prime rose' had maximum flower diameter with minimum disc diameter and maximum length of ray floret. 'Universal' and 'Pink Power' recorded longest and shortest stalk length respectively. 'Amulet' had maximum stalk diameter and longer vase life (19.5 days). The cultivar 'Jaffer' recorded highest number of flowers per sq.m. Followed by 'Yucador' and 'Blind Date'. 'Shimmer' took lesser days from flower bud formation to flowering however 'Alex' and 'Colt' recorded maximum shelf life.

Key Words: Gerbera, Polyhouse, Shelf life, Vase life.

INTRODUCTION

Gerbera (*Gerbera jamesonii* L.) belongs to family Asteraceae is an important cut flower regarded as latest sensation to commercial floriculture industry on account of its remarkable form, magnificent colour variation, unsurpassed beauty and potentialities in the local, domestic and international market. It ranks fourth in the international cut flower market and a popular cut flower in Holland, Germany and USA. Choudhury *et al* (2000). There are many excellent varieties of gerbera with magnificent flowers in exhaustive range of colours, different shades and size and wide

range of keeping quality. The success of commercial cultivation of gerbera is mainly cultivar specific. All the gerbera varieties have their own characteristic features and suitability to a particular region. Gerbera is produced in 6 ha of land with 88 lakh stems in odisha condition which shows the infancy stage of this crop. Mohanty *et al* (2016). Due to the existence of extensive diversity in the crop will pave the way for selecting a suitable genotype performing best under Odisha condition particularly western central table land zone of Odisha. To meet the qualitative and quantitative standards, hybrid cultivars have to be grown under protected conditions Magar *et*

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al (2010). Although general cultural information for this crop is available, few studies describe the flowering habit and yield potential of various cultivars. Therefore, a systematic attempt was made to evaluate 18 varieties for their performance under naturally ventilated poly house.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present investigation was carried out in instructional farm, College of Horticulture, Chiplima during the year 2014-16. The experiment consisted of eighteen variety of gerbera viz., 'Diabolo', 'Paradiso', 'Blind Date', 'Dune', 'Power Play', 'Prime Rose', 'Colt', 'Pink Power', 'Alex', 'Rosalin', 'Amulet', 'Sunway', 'Yucador', 'Shimmer', 'Universal', 'Artist', 'Jaffer' and 'Dreamer' were bought from Kumar Florist (KF-Bio plants), Pune. The genotypes were evaluated in randomized block design (RBD) replicated three times. Raised beds of 30 cm height 70cm width and 16metre long were prepared inside a naturally ventilated poly house of 400sq.m (20mX20m.). Recommended dose of neem cake, FYM were applied at the time of planting. Tissue cultured plants of above mentioned varieties were planted on 6th November 2014 at a spacing of 30 X 30 cm in two rows in each bed. The data recorded on 21 parameters consisting of morphological trait, floral trait and quality traits from three randomly tagged plants in each plot. The data obtained were analyzed statistically and the significance level among the treatments was compared at 5 per cent of probability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Vegetative parameter

Plant height

The growth economic character displayed a wide range of variation and showed significant differences among genotypes (Table 1). The interpretation of analyzed data revealed that the cultivar 'Diablo' recorded maximum plant height (47.9 cm) and remained superior over others while

'Dreamer' being the short stature recorded minimum plant height (27.3cm). A similar variation in plant height among gerbera cultivars was observed by Reddy *et. al.* (2003).

Leaf area and number of leaves

Higher leaf area was found in shimmer (114.0 cm²) followed by Paradiso (101.2cm²) least being in 'Dreamer' (34.5 cm²). 'Power play' exhibited more number of leaves per plant (35.3) with higher petiole length (13.7 cm) and more number of suckers per clump(5.0), while 'pink power' exhibited poor suckering habit(2.0).

Plant spread

'Artist' has recorded maximum plant spread with (55.8cm) minimum length of petiole (4.3cm). This difference among the cultivars may be due to bigger sized leaves produced by respective cultivars. The results were in accordance with the findings of Singh and Ramachandran (2002) and Thomas *et. al.* (2004). Higher length and breadth and number of lobes (39.1cm, 10.5cm, 9.0cm), respectively was registered by 'Yucador' while lowest recorded in 'Dreamer' (24.6cm, 2.6cm, 4.7cm respectively). The marked variation in vegetative characters may be due to differential characters of individual varieties that expressed their genetic characters. These results were in conformity of findings of Kumari *et al* (2010); Wankhede and Gajbhiye (2013); Sarmah *et al* (2014) and Deka (2015) who reported significant difference among gerbera varieties with regards to vegetative characters like plant height, plant spread, and number of leaves, petiole length and number of lobes on leaves.

Floral attributes

Number of flower per square meter

The cultivar 'Jaffer' recorded highest number of flowers per sq.m. Followed by 'Yucador' and 'Blind Date'. The yield potential of particular variety might be due to inherent genetic potential of that variety also better vegetative growth of the variety which enable the plant for transformation of accumulated stock of photosynthesis to reproductive sinks

Evaluation of Exotic Cultivars of Gerbera

Meeramanjusha *et al*, (2003); Kumar and Kumar, (2001). This appreciably good yield might be due favorable conditions under protected conditions. Malik *et al*, (2013).

Days from flower bud initiation to flowering

‘Shimmer’ and ‘prime rose’ took less number of days from flower bud initiation to flower opening and remain at par with each other, however, slow development of flower after initiation of buds were marked in ‘Diabolo’

Shelf life

Significant variation was observed in case of shelf life of cultivars; however, ‘Alex’ and ‘Colt’ recorded maximum shelf life. In general, both shelf life and vase life of flower greatly depend on the general condition of the mother plant. The varieties which exhibit longer shelf life and vase life might possess better water uptake capacity and higher accumulation of metabolic sugars (reducing and non-reducing) in the plant as well as in the petal cells (Deka *et al*, 2015).

Quality parameter

Flower diameter and length of ray florets

The diameter of flower and length of ray florets varied significantly among the cultivars evaluated. Maximum flower diameter with longer ray florets was observed in ‘Prime rose’ (101.8mm) followed by ‘Shimmer’ (99.2 mm). They also exhibited the maximum length of ray florets (5.5cm and 5.2cm) respectively. However, ‘Alex’ showed minimum flower diameter (80.6mm) and length of ray florets (3.7cm). The size of these flowers may be due to bigger ray florets and the inherent characters of individual varieties.

Number of ray florets and petal thickness

Minimum number of ray floret per flower (65.0) with thicker petals (0.6mm) was recorded in ‘colt’, while ‘Artist’ has recorded higher number of ray florets (522.7) with lesser petal thickness (0.4mm).

Disc diameter

The mean value with respect to disc diameter remain at par with each other as observed in ‘Diabolo’ (22.8mm) and ‘Blind Date’ (21.8mm), whereas, ‘Prime rose’ (13.5mm) had smallest concealed disc followed by ‘Alex’ (13.9mm). Similar trend was noticed by Megokhono and Alila (2008).

Stalk length

Stalk length is an important factor while assessing a cultivar for cut flower. Long stalk with considerable girth and neck thickness imparts mechanical strength to flowers which helps in better handling, keeping quality and transportation. The stalk length is a genetic factor and therefore, it is expected to vary among the cultivars. Considerable variation was observed in stalk length of cultivars under study. ‘Universal’ and ‘Pink Power’ recorded longest (67.0cm) and shortest stalk length (41.7cm), respectively. These differences in cut flower quality characters may be due to the presence of additive genes present in the individual cultivar. The results were in conformity of findings of Ahlawat *et al* (2012); Chobe *et al* (2010); Malik *et al* (2013) and Deka *et al* (2015).

Fresh weight

Observations on fresh weight of flowers indicated that the cultivar ‘Diablo’ was found superior over all other varieties (40.3g) followed by ‘Rosalin’ (17.5g) whereas ‘Dreamer’ exhibited least weight (16.9g) which might be due to bigger size of flower, more stalk length. The difference in quality character might be due to inherent characters of the individual cultivars and presence of additive genes present in the individual cultivar. Similar results were observed by Kankana (2015) who reported the existence of large differences in quality parameters of Gerbera.

Vase life

The vase life of flowers (days) in 2 per cent sugar solution under ambient conditions was found to vary significantly. It was observed that ‘Amulet’

TABLE 1. Growth Parameters

Name of Variety	Plant Height (cm)	Leaf Area (cm ²)	No of Leaves/ Plant	Length (cm)	Breadth (cm)	Plant Spread (cm)	Petiole Length (cm)	No of Lobes	No of Sucker
DIABOLO	47.9	67.5	15.3	30.2	6.8	44.3	5.5	8.3	3.0
PARADISO	36.3	101.2	12.3	30.4	6.9	44.7	8.3	5.7	4.0
BLIND DATE	41.1	49.0	10.3	38.8	9.0	46.0	10.0	6.7	3.0
DUNE	42.7	85.2	15.7	34.8	7.3	48.9	10.4	6.3	4.3
POWER PLAY	33.6	96.2	35.3	31.4	6.8	38.0	13.7	6.3	5.0
PRIMEROSE	29.7	95.4	35.0	30.7	6.8	47.9	6.4	7.3	3.3
COLT	34.0	100.9	13.0	31.2	8.7	45.6	6.5	6.3	3.3
PINK POWER	28.3	70.9	19.7	31.6	7.0	39.5	10.4	6.3	2.0
ALEX	32.0	57.8	25.7	27.9	3.4	46.9	10.0	6.3	3.7
ROSALIN	31.0	83.1	16.7	29.4	5.5	38.0	8.9	6.0	3.0
AMULET	41.3	85.3	16.0	29.9	4.1	45.1	6.7	5.0	4.3
SUNWAY	37.5	70.1	18.3	30.9	4.8	47.4	6.2	7.3	2.7
YUCADOR	36.0	91.3	16.7	39.1	10.4	41.6	10.2	9.0	3.0
SHIMMER	37.0	114.0	16.3	33.0	6.0	41.1	6.8	7.0	3.3
UNIVERSAL	35.2	54.4	13.0	25.8	5.1	47.0	5.4	5.3	2.7
ARTIST	29.7	81.8	14.3	28.6	4.1	55.8	4.2	6.7	3.7
JAFFER	29.0	70.0	17.0	29.5	4.5	42.0	6.5	5.7	4.7
DREAMER	27.3	34.5	21.0	24.6	2.6	28.6	8.8	4.7	3.7
MEAN	34.9	78.1	18.4	31.0	6.1	43.7	8.1	6.5	3.5
CD at 5%	6.343	7.0	8.3	6.2	2.3	7.2	3.0	2.3	1.6
SEm	3.1	3.5	4.1	3.0	1.1	3.5	1.5	1.2	0.8

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TABLE 2. Flowering and Quality Parameters

Name of Variety	Flower diameter (mm)	Disc diameter (mm)	Stalk length (cm)	Stalk diameter (mm)	Neck thickness (mm)	Petal thickness (mm)	No. of ray floret (cm)	Length of ray floret (cm)	Days from bud initiation to flowering (Days)	Duration of flowering (Days)
DIABOLO	91.8	22.8	59.0	6.4	5.6	0.4	383.3	4.5	18.8	11.1
PARADISO	98.8	17.3	50.7	5.7	4.3	0.5	287.7	4.9	15.5	10.9
BLIND DATE	87.4	21.8	57.7	5.3	4.3	0.5	213.3	4.3	17.5	18.7
DUNE	97.0	18.0	50.0	6.5	3.5	0.4	250.0	4.9	15.2	15.5
POWER PLAY	83.0	17.3	53.3	5.4	5.2	0.5	420.0	4.6	13.3	16.9
PRIMEROSE	101.9	13.5	50.0	6.1	5.3	0.4	303.3	5.5	9.6	14.3
COLT	85.4	21.7	43.3	6.2	4.6	0.6	65.0	4.2	12.7	20.7
PINK POWER	91.7	21.8	41.7	5.8	4.6	0.4	247.7	4.4	17.9	15.3
ALEX	80.6	14.0	57.7	5.8	4.3	0.6	222.0	3.7	17.0	21.3
ROSALIN	96.0	16.6	54.0	4.9	3.7	0.4	341.3	4.5	14.8	18.9
AMULET	89.5	15.3	51.0	6.7	3.8	0.4	234.0	3.9	17.0	17.7
SUNWAY	94.8	20.7	56.7	6.0	4.4	0.5	283.3	4.5	18.4	14.1
YUCADOR	98.9	26.0	54.0	4.6	4.4	0.5	148.0	4.9	15.4	14.2
SHIMMER	99.2	15.5	52.3	4.9	4.9	0.4	233.7	5.2	9.5	15.7
UNIVERSAL	84.4	17.2	67.0	4.9	4.4	0.6	242.3	4.1	14.8	17.4
ARTIST	95.9	22.3	59.0	5.6	4.7	0.4	522.7	4.3	17.7	15.9
JAFFER	94.6	15.5	58.7	6.7	4.9	0.4	425.3	4.4	12.7	14.1
DREAMER	83.4	15.8	56.3	5.6	3.4	0.5	74.0	5.0	14.8	14.1
MEAN	91.9	18.5	54.0	5.7	4.5	0.5	298.3	4.5	15.1	15.9
CD at 5%										
SE(m)	9.7	4.2	7.7	1.3	1.3	0.0	108.0	0.6	0.9	1.8

TABLE 3. Quality Parameters

NAME OF VARIETY	Fresh weight(gm)	Vase life(Days)	Yield/m ² /year
DIABOLO	40.3	15.3	116.7
PARADISO	28.9	13.6	203.0
BLIND DATE	25.1	18.6	261.0
DUNE	18.5	14.5	250.0
POWER PLAY	24.6	11.1	255.7
PRIMEROSE	21.0	12.5	152.0
COLT	25.4	13.0	202.0
PINK POWER	20.1	13.8	251.0
ALEX	23.1	11.7	222.3
ROSALIN	17.5	14.0	157.0
AMULET	19.8	19.6	148.7
SUNWAY	19.3	9.5	208.0
YUCADOR	27.7	15.7	281.7
SHIMMER	20.8	10.0	159.7
UNIVERSAL	24.1	8.9	247.0
ARTIST	21.9	9.8	263.3
JAFFER	25.3	9.4	372.0
DREAMER	17.0	5.3	143.0
MEAN	23.4	12.6	216.3
CD at 5%	2.3	1.3	41.4
SE(m)	1.1	0.6	20.4

having higher stalk girth (6.7mm) followed by 'Dune' (6.5mm) have recorded highest vase life (19.6d) followed by 'Blind Date'(18.6d) while 'Dreamer' recorded minimum in vase life (5.3d). These distinct variations could be due to increase or decrease in stalk length and amount of food material reserved in flower stalk Kandpal *et al* (2003); Wankhede and Gajbhiye (2012) and better water uptake capacity and higher accumulation of metabolic sugars (reducing and non-reducing) in the plant as well as in the petal cells (Deka *et al*, 2015).

CONCLUSION

'Diablo' found superior with respect to plant height, disc diameter and neck thickness and higher fresh weight. 'Primerose' had maximum flower diameter with minimum disc diameter and maximum length of ray floret thus suitable for exhibition purpose. 'Universal' recorded longer stalk length. 'Amulet' has maximum stalk diameter and longer keeping quality which could be a very popular choice in the wholesale market. The cultivar 'Jaffer' recorded highest number of flowers per sq.m. Flowers remain fresh in plant itself for longer

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period in 'Alex' and 'colt'. 'Dune' has average growth and flower quality. 'Dreamer' is completely rejected due to low flower yield and quality point of view.

REFERENCES

- Ahlawat T R, Barad A V, Jat Giriraj (2012). Evaluation of gerbera cultivars under naturally ventilated poly house. *Indian J Hort* **69**:(4) 606 -608.
- Chobe R R, Pachankar P B and Wanade S D (2010). Performance of different cultivars of gerbera under poly house condition. *The Asian J Hort* **2**: 333-335.
- Choudhary M L and Prasad K V (2000). Protected cultivation of ornamental crops-an insight. *Indian Hort* **45**(1): 49-53.
- Deka Kankana and Talukdar M C (2015). Evaluation of gerbera (*Gerbera jamesonii* Bolus) cultivars for growth and flower characters under Assam conditions. *J Agri and Vety Sci* **8**(4) 28-30.
- Kandpal K, Kumar S, Srivastava R and Chandra R (2003). Evaluation of gerbera cultivars under Tarai condition. *Ornamental Hort* **6**: 252-255.
- Kumar D and Kumar R (2001). Effect of Modified environments on gerbera J. *Ornamental Hort* **4**(1): 33-35
- Kumari Anup, Patel K S and Nayee D D (2010). Evaluation of different cultivars of gerbera (*Gerbera jamesonii* Bolus ex hooker F.) for growth, yield and quality grown under fan and pad cooled green house conditions. *The Asian J Hort* **5** (2): 309-310.
- Magar S D, Warade S D, Nalge N A and Nimbalkar C A (2010). Performance of Gerbera (*Gerbera jamesonii*) under naturally ventilated poly house condition. *Int. J. Plant Sci* **5** (2): 609-612.
- Malik Abid Mahmood, Ahmad Naveed and Muhammad Saleem Akhtar Khan (2013). Comparative evaluation of growth, yield and quality characteristics of various Gerbera (*Gerbera jamesonii* L.) cultivars under protected condition. *J Ornamental Plants* **3**(4): 235-241.
- Meeramanjusha A V, Patil V S and Mathews Dalia (2003). *Evaluation of gerbera genotypes*. National symposium on recent advances in Indian floriculture. pp:285-288
- Megokhono Meyase and Alila P (2008). Varietal performance of gerbera under the foot hill conditions of Nagaland. *The Hort J* **21**: 136-139.
- Mohanty C R, Shasikala Beura and Das T K (2016). *Strategy for development of commercial floriculture in Odisha*, Souvenir on national seminar on horticultural diversity for prosperity. 203-208.
- Reddy B S, Kulkarni B S Manjunath H K and Shiragur M (2003). *Performance of gerbera cultivars under naturally ventilated greenhouse*. Paper Presented in All India Seminar on Potential and Prospects for Protective Cultivation, pp. 91-92.
- Sarmah Dipika, Kolukunde Swathi and Mandal Tapas (2014). Evaluation of gerbera varieties for growth and flowering under poly house in the plains of west Bengal. *Int. J Scientific Res* **3**(12):135-136.
- Singh K P and N Ramachandran (2002). Comparison of greenhouse having natural ventilation and fan and pad evaporative cooling systems for gerbera production. *J Ornamental Hort* **5** (2): 15-19
- Thomas D A, Suhatha K, Jayanthi R and Sangama A (2004). Comparative performance of sucker and tissue culture propagated plants of gerbera under poly house. *J Ornamental Hort* **7**(1): 31-37.
- Wankhede S and Gajbhiye R P (2013). Evaluation of Gerbera varieties for growth and flowering under shade net. *Int. J Hort* **3** (9): 42-45.

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Factors Responsible for Supply Chain Operating in Management of Inputs for Mushroom Enterprise

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ABSTRACT

Supply chain management evolves and expands with the spread of the enterprise and quantum of production. In case of mushroom production, even though spawn is the major critical input, there are certain other inputs like chemicals, polythene, spraying and cutting equipments which are external in nature. In order to know the types of supply chain operating in management of inputs in the study area and factors responsible for supply chain operating in management of inputs for mushroom enterprise focused group discussions were organized at six different locations in the study area. Along with quality and price, factors like timeliness in supply and ease in availability defines the efficiency of the agencies. Ease and timeliness in availability, price and quality of inputs vary with the source and mode of its flow from producer to the farmer was studied. The study revealed that the Centre of Tropical Mushroom Research and Training (CTMRT) secured 1st position followed by Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Farmers, Promoters, Farmers association, Private spawn producer, Middleman/ business man and Horticulture department.

Key Words: Supply chain, Mushroom, Inputs, Businessman.

INTRODUCTION

Supply chain management is the oversight of materials, information and finances as they move in a process from the sources to producer to aggregator and the ultimate consumer through the chain of agents. It involves co-coordinating and integrating the flows and actors both within and among. Strengthening the important actors and eliminating undesirables in the supply chain may improve the efficiency of input feeding mechanism and earn better profit to the producer without disturbing the interest of the consumer. In case of agricultural commodities, though not organized, a definite chain exists both in the supply of production inputs and also in marketing of the produce. The chain evolves and expands with the spread of the enterprise and quantum of production. With the up-scaling of the enterprise, there is a definite growth of input requirement there by creating a demand and need to access distant sources, which indirectly

increase the number of actors involved in the process. Similar hypothesis applies to marketing of produce. The number of entrepreneurs along with production volume decides the chain appropriate for a specific area.

In case of mushroom production, even though spawn is the major critical input, there are certain other inputs like chemicals, polythene, spraying and cutting equipments which are external in nature. Certain other input like straw and feeding materials though internal to the locality, with increase in volume of demand, there becomes a necessity to access the external sources.

Therefore, in order to know the types of supply chain operating in management of inputs in the study area and factors responsible for supply chain operating in management of inputs for mushroom enterprise, present study was undertaken.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was undertaken in three districts namely Bhadrak, Dhenkanal and Puri of Odisha state. The districts were purposively selected considering the spread and intensity of the enterprise among the farm families. Two blocks from each district, three *grampanchayat* from each blocks and 15- 20 numbers of respondents from each *panchayat* comprising total respondents is 300. In order to know the types of supply chain existing in the study area, focused group discussions were organized at six different locations, one each at the sample block, consolidating the outputs obtained during the focus group discussion the chain actors involved The data were collected through a brief interview schedule, personal discussion, observation and focus group discussion and tabulated and analyzed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Source of getting spawn

Spawn is the most critical input for mushroom production. Identifying the sources of spawn and getting it for the purpose without any hurdle is equally important which needs due attention of all those who are directly or indirectly involved in the mushroom production activity. In the existing chain for supply of spawn, three sources have been identified as primary supplier or producer i.e Centre of Tropical Mushroom Research and Training (CTMRT) KVKs and Private Spawn producer, from whom all intermediaries obtain the spawn. Even sometimes the farmer himself access primary sources for getting this input.

Table1. Sources of getting spawn.

Sr. No	Source	Frequency	Percentage
1	Krishi Vigyan Kendra	15	5.00
2	Spawn producer (Inside the district)	51	17.00
3	Spawn producer (Outside district)	99	33.00
4	Horticulture department	6	2.00
6	Farmer's promoter	210	70.00
7	Middleman	38	12.67

The data (Table 1) revealed that, maximum 70 per cent of respondents got the spawn from the farmer promoters followed by 33 per cent from spawn producer (outside the district), 17 per cent from spawn producer (inside the district), 12.67 per cent from middleman and 5 per cent from KVK.

Source of getting straw

In Odisha, paddy straw as an agricultural bi-product is available in plenty. Though at present, other materials like compost, banana leaf, cotton, rice husk, maize and sugarcane stack are used as a medium for mushroom production, Paddy straw always remain a first preference for mushroom grower in Odisha (Table 2).

Table 2. Sources of getting straw. (N=300)

Sr. No	Source	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Own farm	273	91.00
2.	Own village	208	69.33
3.	Near by village	95	31.67
4.	Block farmer	15	0
5.	District Farmer	3	0
6.	Middleman	35	11.67

It was observed that about 91per cent of the respondents, who are growing mushroom, do manage themselves to get straw from their own farm, yet some of them including others to the tune of 69 per cent, manage to get paddy straw from others in their own village and 31.67 per cent from nearby village. Only 11.67 per cent got it through middlemen. All the data clearly represent

(N = 300)

Management of Inputs for Mushroom Enterprise

the dependency upon own source for getting straw as an important input by most of the respondents and the least under this category was middlemen as source.

Sources of getting feeding material

Pulse powder and wheat bran are sometimes used as feeding material for getting healthy mushroom. The important point which needs due attention of mushroom growers is the source from where the feeding material can conveniently and comfortably be procured (Table 3).

Table 3. Sources of getting feeding material. (N=300)

Sl. No	Sources	Frequency	Percentage
1	Village input shop	45	15.00
2	Block input shop	176	58.67
3	District input shop	249	83.00
4.	Farmer promoters	42	14.00
5	Business Man/ Middleman	9	3.00

It was observed that majority of the respondents (83%) procured feeding material from district level input shop followed by 58.97 per cent from block input shop and 15 per cent from village input shop. In this context the role of middlemen was almost negligible and equally the farmer promoter does not involve himself very much in the supply of feeding material.

Sources of getting polythene

Polythene is required to cover the mushroom bed for maintaining temperature and humidity inside the bed. This polythene is not available in rural areas and mostly farmers go to block and district level to get such material. Farmer promoters and middlemen also supply polythene at door steps. Like feeding material polythene is also a kind of much needed material is required badly by the mushroom growers (Table 4).

Table 4. Sources of getting polythene. (N=300)

Sr. No	Source	Frequency	Percentage
1	Village input shop	0	0
2	Block input shop	44	14.67
3	District input shop	276	92.00
4	Farmer promoters	128	42.67
5	Business Man/ Middleman	11	3.67

It was noticed that polythene dealers doing business at district head quarter were the main source of supply of polythene followed by farmer promoter and block level polythene dealer. The reason was quite obvious considering the bulk purchasing attitude in the context of supply and demand situation. The village level in general and individual level in particular is less exploited because they normally do not keep stock of such huge quantity.

Sources of getting chemicals

The proverb 'prevention is better than cure' holds good for mushroom growers where they wish to take preventive measures by the way of sterilizing paddy straw as well as the production surrounding in order to avoid disease and contaminations. Farmers are using chemicals like formalin and bleaching powder for sterilization of cultivation sheds and rooms. Formalin with Bavistin are used for sterilization of straw and calcium carbonate used in the straw for maintaining moisture and preventing attack of harmful fungus. The supply chain of chemicals from different sources is presented in the Table 5.

It was evident that majority of respondents (48.67%) were getting chemicals from outside district followed by 46.33 per cent of respondents from farmer promoters, 6.33 per cent from KVK, 3.67 per cent from businessman and 1.67 per cent from own district. The chemicals required for mushroom cultivation are not always available

Table 5. Sources of getting chemicals.**(N=300)**

Sr. No	Source	Frequency	Percentage
1	Own district	5	1.67
2	Outside district	146	48.67
3	Farmers promoter	139	46.33
4	Businessman	11	3.67
5	KVK	19	6.33

everywhere. Primarily few druggists, chemist and pesticide shops, who normally make their business in chemicals and medicines do keep these chemicals. The scenario is justified with the statistical data presented in the above table that to a great extent as sample respondents to the extent of 48.67% depend upon these shops operating in district head quarter (Khurda, Cuttack) and also 46.33% of the respondents depend upon who do volunteers himself (farmer promoter) for purchasing such chemicals on behalf of mushroom growers in order to sustain his relationship. The other reason which may be attributed for poor dependency on own district level shop are the poor knowledge regarding the chemicals used and less number of chemical shops existing in home district of sample respondents.

Opinion about the sources of input

Even though a number of agencies and media are involved in the activities of supply of inputs, several factors other than quality are important to speak for the efficiency of the source or agent. Added to quality, price of the input is very important which decides the cost of production. Even though, price of supply of commodity varies with source, the farmer preference varies with quantum of requirement, time of requirement and acquaintance with source etc. Along with quality and price, factors like timeliness in supply and ease in availability defines the efficiency of the agencies. Easy in availability, timeliness in availability, price and quality of inputs vary with the source and mode of its flow from producer to the farmer. For some inputs which are required in bulk quantity, sometimes the farmers

prefer to get the material at their door steps even though the price is little bit high.

To know the opinion of the mushroom growers about the input sources, the respondents were asked to express their views pertaining to critical parameters of efficiency as discussed earlier. Their overall opinion regarding the input sources were consolidated averaging out their opinion regarding all the parameters. However, variable numbers of respondent have responded and given their opinion about different input sources considering their interaction and acquaintance with those organizations. The data so obtained were presented in table 6.

The private spawn producer, those who produce the spawn has got the sole intension to sell the produce i.e. spawn to the end users. Many a time a series of agents are involved in purchasing spawn from the input producers to make it available to the farmers. They usually sell the spawn through the sales person appointed by them, by which they enhance easy availability of the spawn to the farmers at their door steps. As spawn is considered to be the most critical input, in this regard the private spawn producers have secured 1st position followed by Middle men, Farmer Promoters and Farmer Association.

Farmer promoters and farmer association participate very intimately with their fellow producers who are venturesome in this direction. They know the importance of time and do never hesitate to make it available in proper time. The middlemen are involved in the process to procure the spawn from different spawn producers and make it available to the farmer and thereby earn their livelihood. Many a time they compete with the spawn producer in reaching out a number of farmers and in fact maintain parallel outfit as indicated (Table 6).

Beyond spawn producer and middlemen, farmer promoters are coming up who engage themselves not only in supply of spawn but also in spirit of

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Table 6. Opinion about the Input sources. (N=300)

Sr. No	Organization	No. of Respondents	Easy Availability			Timely Availability			Reasonable price			Good Quality			Overall performance		
			Score	Mean score	Rank	Score	Mean score	Rank	Score	Mean score	Rank	Score	Mean score	Rank	Score	Mean score	Rank
1	CTMRT	58	68	1.17	VI	80	1.37	VI	168	2.89	I	166	2.86	I	120.50	2.07	I
2	KVK	134	192	1.43	V	211	1.57	V	364	2.71	II	368	2.74	II	283.75	2.04	II
3	Horticulture department	69	80	1.15	VII	89	1.28	VII	145	2.10	III	137	1.98	V	112.75	1.62	VII
4	Farmers promoter	289	566	1.95	III	589	2.03	I	576	1.99	V	593	2.05	IV	581.0	2.0	III
5	Private spawn producer	293	627	2.14	I	579	1.97	II	513	1.75	VI	603	2.05	IV	580.50	1.97	V
6.	Farmers association	32	60	1.87	IV	60	1.87	IV	64	2.0	IV	72	2.25	III	64.00	1.99	IV
7	Middle men	289	617	2.13	II	545	1.88	III	431	1.49	VII	541	1.87	VI	533.50	1.84	VI

all production inputs along with technical advice. Farmer promoters are primarily mushroom growers who serve the fellow farmer utilizing the spare time. As the farmer promoters and middlemen do undertake input supply and produce procurement activity they ensure easy availability of the inputs.

Even though KVKs and Horticulture department operate at the district level and supply the inputs primarily spawn to the farmers, because of their limited outreach as compared to other agencies and individuals, they are placed towards lower rank of preference in the opinion scale developed for the purpose with regard to ease in availability. Similarly in making input available at appropriate timing, no doubt an important activity against which the farmer promoters occupy 1st position. Farmer promoter being basically a farmer, does understand the accuracy of timing for the requirement of inputs and supplies accordingly. Even though spawn producers and middlemen do undertake similar activity, they do have a business orientation focusing less on timely availability rather concentrate on volume of their transaction. Farmers association even though has been responded by fewer numbers of respondents (32) has took 4th position in the rank with respect to parameter of timely availability following the position occupied by private spawn producer and middle men.

With regards to price of the production inputs, the respondents have indicated that, CTMRT, KVKs and Horticulture department are in descending order of their preference. As CTMRT is purely a research institute and is producing quality spawn in limited scale, the spawn so produced are sold to the farmers at their own center at Bhubaneswar, Odisha. Because no transportation cost is involved in the process, the price is reasonable for farmers.

Mostly KVKs and in some of the districts, Horticulture department do have their own laboratory to produce quality spawn. With little involvement of transportation cost, their sale price is higher than CTMRT. However, in some cases, line department like Horticulture Department,

procure spawn from KVKs to make it available to the farmers through departmental network. With little involvement of transportation cost, their sale price is higher than KVK. Following the list, govt. organizations, farmers association, farmer promoters, private spawn producer and middlemen have been placed in descending order of scoring with regard to price of the production inputs.

CONCLUSION

A clear conclusion can be drawn from the list in order regarding the business / service motive of these entities and individuals. Farmers association being a body of the farmers takes maximum care and keeps minimum profit followed by farmer promoters which are also having the motive of helping the fellow farmers. Private spawn producer and middlemen purely operate with business motives and keep comparatively larger share in the price of the inputs as compare to others in the list. As revealed from the Focused Group Discussion organized at different places of study area, three agents in the supply chain i.e. Farmers association, Farmer promoters, and middlemen do supply other inputs (polythene, feeding material, chemicals, cutting & spraying equipments), where as govt. sources like CTMRT, KVKs, Horticulture department and also private spawn producers to larger extent concentrate in the supply of spawn.

Next parameter is the quality of the input, which is very much maintained by the CTMRT. However the overall scores help CTMRT to occupy 1st position irrespective of all the four parameters. Following CTMRT, KVKs being a research institute producing

spawn under the direct supervision of scientists takes utmost care to maintain the quality and occupy the second position. Farmers' association and farmer promoters realizing the importance of quality, switch over to different sources producing quality spawn. They have the liberty to choose for the organization or agency to maintain quality and accordingly occupy the third and fourth position respectively in this regard.

In overall performance, CTMRT found to occupy 1st position, when availability of good quality of mushroom spawn and reasonable price is concerned. It always takes the pride and rank 1st by the mushroom growers. The reason behind this phenomenon is that, the CTMRT is under administrative control of OUAT. Funds are diverted both for research and extension activity, infrastructure and technical sophistication which added value to the output given by the said organization in form of different services. Hence it is possible to sale their produce at reasonable price for the greater benefit of mushroom growers in general and mushroom entrepreneurs in particular.

Where as in contrast middlemen ranked last and obtained very low score with regard to the overall performance. As in case of CTMRT, middlemen by nature functions with moderate risk at opportune movement and normally hesitate to show any extra smartness until and unless warranted. When other organizations as source of inputs play their respective role with their utmost efficiency and effectiveness, very little space is available for such middlemen to function.

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Increasing Yield of Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* Linn.) through Improved Production Technology in Kalaburagi District of Karnataka

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ABSTRACT

Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* Linn.) is most important pulse crop in Karnataka state. The productivity of chickpea is low because of non adoption of available technologies by the farmers. Hence, Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Kalaburagi conducted 149 demonstrations at farmers' field during the last 6 years showing improved production technology. The results revealed variation in the yield obtained probably due to variation in agro-climatic parameters under rainfed condition. The highest yield of FLDs plots of chick pea achieved by adopting improved production technology was 12.87q/ha compared to farmers' practice (10.06 q/ha). Adoption of improved production technology increased yield by 27.80 per cent over farmers' practices. The average technological gap, extension gap and technological index were calculated as 7.13 q/ha, 2.81 q/ ha and 35.65 per cent, respectively. The economical parameters indicated that net profit of Rs. 33,213/- ha was recorded under FLDs plot over farmer practices Rs 24,095/-ha.

Key Words: Chick pea, Technology gap, Technology index, Extension gap, Yield, Economics.

INTRODUCTION

Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* Linn.) is a major rabi pulse crop grown in India. Among the pulses, chickpea occupies 30 per cent of area with 38 per cent of annual production in India. In Karnataka state, occupying about an area of 4.79 lakh ha with a production of 2.81 lakh tones and productivity of 618 kg/ha. It is a good source of carbohydrates and protein and protein quality is considered to be better than other pulses. Even though many technologies for chickpea cultivation have been evolved for increasing the productivity but farmers have hardly adopted a few of them and those in a non scientific manner. Singh and Bajpai (1996) reported that fertilizer and plant protection were most critical inputs for increasing seed yield of chickpea. Keeping this in view, front line demonstrations of chickpea were conducted in order to demonstrate the productivity potential and economic benefit of improved technologies under farmers' conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Frontline demonstrations (FLD) were organized on farmers' field to demonstrate the impact of integrated crop management technology on chickpea productivity over six years during rabi 2010 to 2016. Each FLD plot was laid out on 0.4 ha area and adjacent 0.4 ha was considered as control for comparison (farmer's practice). The integrated crop management technology comprised the improved variety, proper tillage, seed rate, pre emergent weedicide application, seed treatment, proper nutrient and pest management (Table 1). The FLD was conducted to study the technological gap between the potential yield and demonstrated yield, extension gap between demonstrated yield and yield under existing practice and technology index. The yield data were collected from both the demonstration and farmers practice by random crop cutting method and analyzed by using simple statistical tools. The technology gap, extension gap

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Table1. Improved production technology and Farmers practices of chick pea under FLD.

Sr No.	Technology	Improved practices	Farmers practice	GAP (%)
1	Variety	JG 11	A 1	Full gap
2	Land preparation	Ploughing and harrowing	Ploughing and harrowing	Nil
3	Pre emergent herbicide	Pendimethalin (@ 2.5 l/ha)	No herbicide	Full gap
4	Seed rate	50 kg/ha	62 kg/ha	Higher seed rate
5	Sowing method	Line sowing	Line sowing	No gap
6	Seed treatment	Biofertilizers and Trichoderma	No seed treatment	Full gap
7	Fertilizer dose (NPK kg/ha)	5:10:0	10:20:0	Partial gap
8	Plant protection	Integrated pest management	Indiscriminate application	Full gap
9	Grading the produce	Grading followed	Not followed	Full gap

Technology gap = Potential yield – Demonstration

Yield Extension gap = Demonstration yield – Farmers yield

Technology index = ((Potential yield - Demonstration yield) / Potential yield) X 100

and technological index (Samui et al, 2000) were calculated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the study period it was observed that the demonstration trials have increased the yield over the farmers' practices (Table 2). Full gap observed in most of production technology was the reason of not achieving potential yield. Farmers were not aware about recommended technologies.

Yield

The results revealed that due to FLD on chick pea an average yield was recorded 12.87 q/ ha under demonstrated plots as compared farmers' practice (10.06 q/ha). The highest yield in the FLD plot was 13.95 q/ha during year 2012-13 and in farmers' practice, it was 10.80 q/ha in the same year and lowest yield was recorded in the year 2015-16. The average yield of chick pea increased by 27.80 per cent. The results clearly indicated that the higher average seed yield in demonstration plots over the years compared to local check was due to knowledge and adoption of full package of practices i.e. appropriate varieties such as JG11, timely sowing,

seed treatment with bio fertilizers *Rhizobium* spp and phosphorus solubilizing bacteria (PSB), *Trichoderma* @4g/kg of seed, use of balanced dose of fertilize, method and time of sowing with proper spacing, timely weed management, irrigation water management, pulse magic spray at flowering and pod development stage, need based plant protection and grading of the seeds. The above findings were in agreement with the findings of Singh et al (2014) and Tomar (2010). The higher yield of chickpea under improved technology was due to use of latest high yielding varieties, integrated nutrient management and integrated pest management.

Technology gap

The technology gap means the differences between potential yield and yield of demonstration plot. The demonstration plot yields (Table2), were 7.5, 7.2, 6.05, 6.65, 6.12, and 9.26 q/ha during 2010-11, 2011-12, 2012-13, 2013-14, 2014-15 and 2015-16, respectively. On an average technology gap under six year FLD programme was 7.13 q/ ha. The technology gap observed may be attributed to dissimilarity in the soil fertility status, crop production practices and local climatic situation.

Increasing Yield of Chickpea

Table 2. Performance of chick pea (JG-11) through demonstration of Integrated Crop management technologies

Year	No of Demon.	Area (Ha)	Yield (q/ha)			Percent increase in yield	Techno-logical gap (q/ha)	Extension gap (q/ha)	Technological index (%)	Net Return (Rs/ha)		B:C	
			Potential yield	Demon yield	Farmers practice					Demon	Farmer practice	Demon	Farmer practice
2010-11	20	8	20	12.50	10.10	23.76	7.50	2.40	37.50	24000	17240	5.00	3.50
2011-12	48	20	20	12.80	10.20	25.49	7.20	2.60	36.00	34280	24520	3.90	3.00
2012-13	24	10	20	13.95	10.80	29.17	6.05	3.15	30.25	41110	29840	4.40	3.70
2013-14	15	7	20	13.35	10.20	30.88	6.65	3.15	33.25	38390	29810	4.50	3.90
2014-15	12	5	20	13.88	10.40	33.46	6.12	3.48	30.60	24168	17652	5.10	3.60
2015-16	30	12	20	10.74	8.66	24.02	9.26	2.08	46.30	37330	25510	3.28	2.43
Average	24.83	10.33	20	12.87	10.06	27.80	7.13	2.81	35.65	33213	24095	4.36	3.36
Total	149	62	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Extension gap

Extension gap means the differences between demonstration plot yield and farmers yield. Extension gap of 2.4, 2.6, 3.15, 3.15, 3.48 and 2.08 q/ha (Table 3) were observed during 2010-11, 2011-12, 2012-13, 2013-14, 2014-15 and 2015-16, respectively. On an average extension gap under six year FLD programme was 2.81q/ha which emphasized the need to educate the farmers through various extension means i.e. front line demonstration for adoption of improved production and protection technologies, to revert the trend of wide extension gap. More and more use of latest production technologies with high yielding varieties will subsequently change this alarming trend of galloping extension gap.

Technology Index

Technology index indicates the feasibility of the evolved technology in the farmers' fields. Lower the value of technology index, higher is the feasibility of the improved technology. The technology index varied from 30.25 to 46.30 per cent (Table 2). On an average technology index was observed 35.65 per cent during the six years of FLD programme, which showed the efficacy of good performance of technical interventions. This will accelerate the adoption of demonstrated technical intervention to increase the yield performance of pigeon pea.

Economic return

Data in table 2 revealed that the cost involved in the adoption of improved technology in chick pea varied and was more profitable. The cultivation of chick pea under improved technologies gave higher net return of Rs. 24,000/-, 34,280/-, 41,110/-, 38,390/-, 24,168/- and 37,330/- ha, respectively, as compared to farmers practices (Rs 17,240/-; 24,520/-; 29,840/-; 29,810/-; 17,652/- and 25,510/- per ha in 2010-11, 2011-12, 2012-13, 2013-14, 2014-15 and 2015-16, respectively). An average net return and B: C of demonstration field was Rs. 33,213/-ha and 4.36, respectively as compared to farmers practice (Rs 24,095/- ha and 3.36). Similar findings were reported by Singh *et al* (2014). The

benefit cost ratio of chick pea cultivation under improved practices has higher than farmers' practices in all the years and this may be due to higher yield obtained under improved technologies compared to local check (farmers' practice). This finding was in corroboration with the findings of Mokidue *et al* (2011) and Tomar (2010).

CONCLUSION

It is concluded from the study that there exists a wide gap between the potential and demonstration yields in wilt tolerant chick pea mainly due to technology and extension gaps and also due to the lack of awareness about new technology. The FLD produced a significant positive result and provided the researcher an opportunity to demonstrate the productivity potential and profitability of the latest technology (Intervention) under real farming situation, which they have been advocating for long time. This could be circumventing some of the constraints in the existing transfer of technology system in the district, Kalaburgi of Karnataka. The productivity gain under FLD over existing practices

of pigeon pea cultivation created greater awareness and motivated the other farmers to adopt suitable production technology of pigeon pea in the district.

REFERENCES

- Mokidue I, Mohanty A K and Sanjay K(2011). Corelating growth, yield and adoption of urd bean technologies. *Indian J Ex Edu* **11**(2): 20-24.
- Samui S K, Mitra S, Roy D K, Mandal A K and Saha D (2000). Evaluation of front line demonstration on groundnut. *J Indian Soc Costal Agril Res* **18** (2) : 180-183
- Singh V K and Bajpai R P(1996). Effect of crop production inputs on gram (*Cicer arietinum*) in north eastern hills zone of Madhya Pradesh. *Indian Agron* **44** (4), 655-656.
- Singh D, Patel A K, Baghel S K, Singh M S, Singh A and Singh A K(2014). Impact of front line demonstration on the yield and economics of Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) in Sidhi District of Madhya Pradesh. *J Agri Search* **1**(1): 22-25.
- Tomar R K S (2010). Maximization of productivity for chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* Linn.) through improved technologies in farmers field. *Indian J Natul Produ Resou* **1**(4): 515-517.

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Influence of Micronutrients on Growth and Yield of Banana

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted by Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University during 2011-12 to study the effect on application of different micronutrient formulations on growth, yield and quality of banana cultivar poovan. The four different formulation T1: No application of micronutrients, T2: Foliar Application of FeSo_4 0.20%, ZnSo_4 0.5%, CuSo_4 0.2% and borax 0.1% at 3, 5, 7 months after planting, T3: Soil Application of NRCB banana Sakthi at the rate 10g per plant on 3MAP. T4: Application Arka banana special @ 250 ml of 0.5% solution to the soil followed by foliar application of 0.5%, on 5,6,7,8 months after planting in five farmers field at Kammandadu village of Pudukkottai district during June, 2011. The results revealed that the highest pseudostem height of 2.48m, pseudostem girth of 76 cm, number of leaves per plant (18 nos.), leaf area index(4.72), finger weight (123g) bunch weight (20.10kg) and TSS (16.6° Brix) were recorded with application of Arka banana special micronutrients followed by foliar application micronutrients and soil application. The Arka banana special application through soil application 250 ml solution (%) on 45days after planting, followed by foliar application 0.5% on 5,6,7 and at shooting on hands recorded significantly highest yield (45.23 t/ha) over other two micronutrient application.

Key Words: Soil application, Foliar application, Zinc, Iron, Copper, Boron.

INTRODUCTION

Banana is one of the major fruit crops in India, occupies 8.03 lakh hectares with the production of 29.7mt and 37t of productivity per hectare. The area under cultivation in Tamil Nadu is 1.18 lakh hectares, with the production of 56 lakh tones and 47.9 t of productivity per hectare. In Pudukkottai district is cultivated 3,426 ha with the production of 2.19 lakh t and productivity 38 t/ha. The major soil type of this district is red lateritic having low in nitrogen, medium in phosphorus and high in potassium content. The most of the cultivable land soil is deficient in micronutrients viz., zinc, iron, magnesium and boron. An average the banana crops removes 6 kg of iron, 125 kg of magnesium, 4.70 kg of zinc, 12.0 kg of manganese 0.37kg copper and 1.27 kg of boron from one hectare. To meet the required micronutrients demand, external application is necessary to get maximum yield. There are different recommendation available for banana but not followed

by the farmers. Hence the present investigation was taken up to study the effect of three recommended micronutrient application as technology capsule for obtaining higher yield in banana.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The trial was conducted during 2011-12 at five farmers' field in Kammandadu village of Pudukkottai district. There were four treatments viz. T1: No application of micronutrients, T2: Foliar application of ZnSo_4 0.5%, FeSo_4 0.20%, CuSo_4 0.20%, Borox 0.10% at 3,5,7 months after planting (MAP) recommended by TNAU, Coimbatore. T3: Soil application of NRCB banana sakthi @ 10g/plant on 3 months after planting. T4: Soil and Foliar application of Arka banana special (IIHR, Bengaluru) @250 ml 0.50 % solution per plant on 45 days after planting followed by foliar application of 0.5% on 5,6,7 MAP and on bunches and leaves after one month of shooting.

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The planting was taken up during June 2011 in randomized block design with five replication. The pits of one and half foot cubic size were dugout at 2.1 x 2.1m and filled with organic manure 10kg, 250g neem cake, 50g lindane, *Pseudomonas fluorescens* 25g/plant. Biofertilizers *Azospirillum* and *Phosphobacteria* each 20g/plant. The growth parameters viz pseudostem girth, pseudostem height, number of leaves per plant, leaf area index, days to shooting, yield and quality parameters viz., number of hands/bunch, number of fingers/hand, bunch weight, finger weight and total soluble solids content in ripened fruits were recorded. The data obtained were statistically analyzed for analysis of variance. The soil type was red lateritic with pH of 6.7 and EC was 0.9. The available nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium content is 127, 13, 210 kg/ha, respectively. The soil contains zinc 1.42ppm, iron 5.74ppm, manganese 3.24ppm, copper 0.26ppm of micronutrients.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the experiment revealed that the highest pseudostem height of 2.48m was recorded with the application of Arka banana special through soil and foliar followed by foliar application of

micronutrients (T3) followed by application NRCB banana sakthi through soil.

The pseudostem girth was also proportionately increased to give strength to the plant to withstand the bunch weight. The highest pseudostem girth of 76cm was found with the application of micronutrients through soil and foliar application of Arka banana special micro nutrients. Kumar and Jeyakumar (2001) reported increased pseudostem girth and height with application of micronutrients. The more number of leaves per plant (18 nos.) was registered with the application of Arka banana special through soil and foliar followed by foliar application (17 nos.) alone and soil application (16 Nos.) alone. The maximum leaf area index of 4.72 was recorded in application of micronutrients (T4) through soil and foliar followed by 4.69 in foliar application of micronutrients. Yadlod and Kadam (2008) also observed that the number of leaves and leaf area index increased due to micronutrients application in banana.

The application of micronutrients through soil and foliage resulted in maximum pseudostem girth, pseudostem height, numbers leaves with maximum leaf area were also reflected in floral bud differentiation which resulted in early shooting

Table 1. Effect of micronutrients on growth and yield parameters of banana.

Sr. No.	Character	T1	T2	T3	T4	S.Ed.	C.D. (0.05)
1.	Pseudostem girth (cm)	52	62	71	76	2.40	4.82
2.	Pseudostem height (m)	1.82	2.06	2.38	2.48	0.02	0.04
3.	No. of leaves /plants	16	16	17	18	-	NS
4.	Leaf area index	4.64	4.66	4.69	4.72	0.10	0.20
5.	Days to shooting	243	238	235	230	1.50	3.22
6.	No. of hands/bunch	11	11	11	11	-	NS
7.	No. of fingers /hand	14	14	14	14	-	NS
8.	No.of fingers/bunch	160	161	162	164	1.50	3.20
9.	Finger weight (g)	101	106	113	123	2.6	5.4
10.	Bunch weight (kg)	16.12	17.22	18.24	20.10	0.60	1.22
11.	TSS (obrix)	16.1	16.3	16.4	16.6	-	NS
12.	Yield (t/ha)	36.27	38.75	41.04	45.23	2.24	4.18

Micro Nutrients on Growth and Yield of Banana

(230 days) followed by delayed shooting (235 days) of the plants in foliar application of micronutrients (Table 1)

The number of hands per bunch, number of fingers per hand and bunch were not recorded significant values with the application of micronutrients through soil and foliar, foliar alone and soil alone. The maximum finger weight (123 g), bunch weight (20.10 kg) and yield (45.23 t/ha) were recorded with (T4) soil and foliar application of Arka banana special @ 250ml of 0.5 per cent solution to soil on 45 days after planting, foliar application on 5,6,7,8 months after planting followed by foliar application (T3) of ZnSO₄ 0.5%, FeSO₄ 0.2%, CuSO₄ 0.2%, borax 0.1% on 3,5,7 months after planting.

The quality of banana fruit was assessed by total soluble solid content. The maximum value of 16.6° brix was recorded with the soil and foliar application of micronutrients followed by foliar application alone. Pathak *et al* (2011) also reported the earliness in shooting, higher finger weight and bunch weight due to the application of micronutrients in banana.

CONCLUSION

The results revealed that the highest pseudostem height of 2.48m, pseudostem girth of 76 cm, number

of leaves per plant (18 nos.), leaf area index(4.72), finger weight (123g) bunch weight (20.10kg) and TSS (16.6° Brix) and highest yield (45.23 t/ha) were recorded with application of Arka banana. The Arka banana special application through soil application 250 ml solution (%) on 45days after planting, followed by foliar application 0.5% on 5,6,7 and at shooting on hands over other two micronutrient application.

REFERENCES

- Kumar N and Jeyakumar P (2001). Influence of micro nutrients on growth and yield of banana *Musa sp cv. Robusta* (App.) In: *Plant Nutrition – Food Security and sustainability of agro ecosystem*. pp: 354-355. Kluwer Academic publishers, Netherlands.
- Pathak M, Bauri F K, Misra D K, Bandyopadhyay B and Chakraborty K (2011). Application of micronutrients on growth, yield and quality of banana. *J Crop and weed* 7 (1): 52-54.
- Yadlod S S and Kadam B A (2008). Effect of plant growth regulators and micronutrients on growth, yield and storage life of banana (*Musa spp.*) cv. Shrimanti. *The Asian J Horti* 3(2): 409-411.

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Knowledge and Adoption Level of Plant Protection Schedule and Certified Seed by Potato Growers

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ABSTRACT

The present study was carried out during the year 2012-13 in Surguja district of Northern Hilly zone of Chattisgarh. Finding of the study were that before FLD, majority of respondents belonged to low level of knowledge regarding plant protection schedule, time or schedule of use of insecticide/pesticide for storage pests (74.3), whereas, after FLD, maximum number of respondents were having medium level of knowledge about seed treatment, time of schedule of fungicide and other chemicals for diseases control and use of insecticide/ pesticide for storage pest (51.4%). In case of adoption level, before FLD maximum number of respondents belonged to low level of adoption about seed treatment and time or schedule of use of insecticide/ pesticide for storage pests (77.1%). While after FLD, maximum numbers of respondents were having medium level of adoption were about use of insecticide/ pesticide for storage pests (54.3 %). Regarding use of certified seed of potato before FLD, majority of respondents belonged to low level of knowledge about source of availability of certified seed of potato (82.9%). However, after FLD maximum respondents belonged to medium level of knowledge were about time of sowing (62.9%). Level of adoption regarding use of certified seed of potato before FLD majority of respondents belonged to low level of adoption were seed rate (85.7%), while adoption level after FLD maximum respondents belonged to high level of adoption were time of sowing (60.0%). In case of problems faced by respondents regarding use of certified seed maximum respondents having problems of more demand of local red variety of potato by consumer and cost of seed potato (100.0%) both followed by non availability of certified seed of potato in market and lack of facility of cold storage (94.3%) both.

Key Words: Adoption level, Certified seed, FLD, Knowledge level, Potato

INTRODUCTION

Improper plant protection schedule leads to increased infestation of many insect pests as well as attack of diseases in unfavorable condition. Likewise local variety didn't perform better for higher yield. The present system such as seed/soil treatment and recommended plant protection schedule, use of certified seed of suitable variety, sprays of recommended plant protection chemicals for control of major insect-pests and diseases were varying from farmer to farmer. In this context, front line demonstrations (FLD) on assessment of plant protection schedule and use of certified seed of potato conducted during the year 2012-13 at block Surajpur of Surguja District. Total number of

beneficiaries were 35 from obtained farmers list of FLD with following objectives to study the level of knowledge level, adoption and constraints regarding use of plant protection schedule and certified seed by potato growers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study carried out in Surguja district of Chattisgarh. FLD on assessment of use of plant protection schedule and certified seed were conducted in the village-Pando nagar, block Surajpur, district Surguja during the year *rabi* 2012-13. For collecting information semi structured interview schedule designed on the basis of available literature. Data have been collected by personal

interview or discussion with all respondents. The data analyzed by using appropriate statistical framework such as frequency, mean and percentage.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Plant protection schedule of potato

The data in (Table 1) revealed that before FLD, majority of respondents belonged to low level of knowledge regarding various aspects of use of plant protection schedule i.e. 74.3 per cent of respondents follow time or schedule of use of insecticide for storage pests, seed treatment (71.4%), Use of insecticide for storage pests (68.6%) , time or schedule of use of insecticide (69.0%), use of insecticide (60.0%) & time or schedule of use of fungicide or other chemicals for diseases control (57.1%), respectively. While after FLD, medium level of knowledge regarding various aspects of plant protection schedule i.e. 51.4 per cent of respondents use fungicide or other chemicals for diseases control. In case of low level of knowledge after FLD maximum number of respondents were

use of Insecticide, time or schedule of use of insecticide (28.6%) both.

The data in Table 2 revealed that before FLD, maximum number of respondents was having low level of adoption about seed treatment and time or schedule of use of insecticide/ pesticide for storage pests (77.1%) both. In case of medium level of adoption maximum respondents were use of fungicide or other chemical for diseases control (37.1 %) followed by use of insecticide / pesticide (31.4%), time or schedule of use of fungicide or other chemical for diseases control, use of insecticide/ pesticide for storage pests (28.6 %) while high level of adoption regarding plant protection schedule were 11.4 per cent regarding time or schedule of use of fungicide or other chemical for diseases control. After FLD, maximum number of respondents were having medium level of adoption regarding use of insecticide/ pesticide for storage pests (54.3%) followed by seed treatment, use of insecticide / pesticide, time or schedule for use of fungicide or other chemicals for disease control, respectively. While high level of adoption regarding plant

Table 1. Per cent knowledge level regarding plant protection schedule of potato.

Sr No	Particular	Knowledge level before FLD			Knowledge level after FLD		
		Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High
1	Seed Treatment	71.4	28.6	0.0	20.0	51.4	28.6
2	Use of insecticide	60.0	31.4	8.6	28.6	48.6	22.8
3	Time or schedule of use of insecticide	65.7	22.8	11.5	28.6	45.7	25.7
4	Use of fungicide or other chemicals for diseases control	57.1	42.9	0.0	25.7	40.0	34.3
5	Time or schedule of use of fungicide or other chemical for diseases control	69.0	31.4	5.6	20.0	51.4	28.6
6	Use of insecticide for storage pests	68.6	28.6	2.8	25.7	51.4	22.9
7	Time or schedule of use of insecticide for storage pest	74.3	25.7	0.0	20.0	45.7	34.3

Knowledge and Adoption Level

Table 2. Per cent adoption level regarding plant protection schedule of potato.

Sr No	Particular	Knowledge level before FLD			Knowledge level after FLD		
		Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High
1	Seed Treatment	77.1	22.9	0.0	14.3	51.4	34.3
2	Use of insecticide	65.7	31.4	2.9	25.7	51.4	22.9
3	Time or schedule of use of insecticide	71.4	22.9	5.7	28.6	37.1	34.3
4	Use of fungicide or other chemicals for diseases control	62.9	37.1	0.0	20.0	42.9	37.1
5	Time or schedule of use of fungicide or other chemical for diseases control	60.0	28.6	11.4	14.3	51.4	34.3
6	Use of insecticide for storage pests	71.4	28.6	0.0	14.3	54.3	31.4
7	Time or schedule of use of insecticide for storage pest	77.1	22.9	0.0	17.1	48.6	34.3

protection schedule were 34.3 per cent about seed treatment, time or schedule of use of insecticide, time or schedule of use of fungicide or other chemical for diseases control, time or schedule of use of insecticide for storage pests, respectively.

Certified seed of potato

Data (Table 3) revealed that level of knowledge regarding use of certified seed of potato before FLD, majority of respondents was medium about time of

sowing (54.3%) followed by earthing up (48.6%) and time of harvesting (45.7 %), respectively. However low level of knowledge were about source of availability of certified seed of potato (82.9%), spacing (65.7%), seed rate (60.0 %), application of fertilizer (57.1 %), respectively. After FLD, majority of respondents were having high level of knowledge about time of harvesting (57.1%), followed by spacing (51.4%), application of fertilizer (48.6%) and seed rate (42.9%), respectively.

Table 3. Per cent knowledge level regarding use of certified seed of potato.

S r No	Particular	Knowledge level before FLD			Knowledge level after FLD		
		Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High
1	Source of availability	82.9	17.1	0.0	8.6	48.6	34.8
2	Variety	82.9	17.1	0.0	5.7	54.3	40.0
3	Seed rate	60.0	37.1	2.9	14.3	42.9	42.9
4	Spacing	65.7	31.4	2.9	8.6	40.0	51.4
5	Time of sowing	31.4	54.3	14.3	5.7	62.9	31.4
6	Application of fertilizers	57.1	34.3	8.6	20.0	31.4	48.6
7	Earthing up	28.6	48.6	22.8	0.0	60.0	40.0
8	Time of harvesting	28.6	45.7	25.7	2.9	40.0	57.1

Table 4. Per cent adoption level regarding use of certified seed of potato.

Sr. No.	Particular	Knowledge level before FLD			Knowledge level after FLD		
		Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High
1	Source of availability	82.9	17.1	0.0	20.0	54.3	25.7
2	Variety	82.9	17.1	0.0	20.0	51.4	28.6
3	Seed rate	85.7	14.3	0.0	14.3	48.6	37.1
4	Spacing	54.3	31.4	14.3	2.9	57.1	40.0
5	Time of sowing	48.6	37.1	14.3	8.6	31.4	60.0
6	Application of fertilizer	28.6	65.7	5.7	5.7	42.9	51.4
7	Earthing up	28.6	48.6	22.8	0.0	60.0	40.0
8	Time of harvesting	28.6	54.3	17.1	0.0	54.3	45.7

Table 5. Problems faced by respondents regarding use of certified seed.

Sr. No.	Problem	Yes	No
1	Non availability of certified seed of potato in market	94.28	5.72
2	More demand of local red variety of potato by consumer	100.00	-
3	Lack of facility of cold storage	94.28	5.72
4	More cost of seed potato	100.00	-

Data presented in Table 4 depicted that before FLD, respondents having medium level of adoption about application of fertilizer (65.7%), time of harvesting (54.3%), earthing up (48.6%), respectively. While majority of respondents have low level of adoption about seed rate (85.7%) followed by source of availability of certified seed of potato and variety (82.9%), respectively. Singh *et al* (2010) also reported that 82 per cent of the growers had low or medium adoption of commercial potato cultivation practices.

In case of problems faced by respondents given in Table 5 regarding use of certified seed, maximum respondents having problems of more demand of local red variety of potato by consumer and more cost of seed potato (100.0%) followed by non availability of certified seed of potato in market and lack of facility of cold storage (94.3%).

CONCLUSION

The present study reveals that the intervention of FLD on use of plant protection schedule and certified seed of potato by KVK facilitated the acquisition of knowledge and enhances the adoption regarding plant protection schedule and certified seed of potato. Finding of this study will help to researcher to plan, conduct & guideline them to draw research programme or strategies of farmers benefit.

REFERENCES

- Singh B K, Singh Dhiraj Kumar, Yadav V P S and Singh Lotan (2010). Adoption behaviour of commercial potato growers in district ghaziabad (up). *Indian Res J Ext Edu* **10** (3):5-9
- Huque M M, Rashid M H, Rahman M L(1996). Adoption of improved practices by potato farmers. *Bangladesh J Agric Econ* **XIX** (1 & 2): 59-69.

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Knowledge Level of Farmers Regarding Safety Issues of Pesticides

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ABSTRACT

Pesticides are an important aspect of agricultural practice in both developed and developing countries. This paper focuses on the farmers knowledge of pesticides and patterns of safety measures followed. The study revealed that majority of farmers have poor knowledge of pesticide safety labels and wear no proper protective clothing during spraying. This indicates the need for promoting greater awareness among farmers about pesticides through health education programs and need for promotion of use of protective clothing and equipment suitable for the tropical climate

Key Words: Pesticide, Spraying , Protective equipment, Knowledge level.

INTRODUCTION

Over the last 50 years, agriculture has deeply changed with a massive use of pesticides and fertilizers to enhance crop protection and production, food quality and food preservation. Pesticides are an important aspect of agricultural practice in both developed and developing countries and, despite the many technological advances brought by the modern intensification of agriculture, the increased yields were achieved primarily through the use of fertilizers and pesticides. Despite their popularity and extensive use, pesticides cause serious concerns about health risks arising from the exposure of farmers when mixing and applying pesticides or working in treated fields and from residues on food and in drinking water for the general population have been raised . These activities have caused a number of accidental poisonings, and even the routine use of pesticides can pose major health risks to farmers both in the short and the long run and can degrade the environment. Being the principle polluters and victims of pollution, farmers are at the top risk. Moreover, Singh (2013) indicated that most of the recommended brands of the pesticides were not available in the market. As a result of which farmers were helpless in adopting

the recommended spray schedule for the control of attack of various insect pest and diseases on various crops.

The World Health Organization (WHO) and the United Nations Environment Program estimate pesticide poisoning rates of 2-3 per minute, with approximately 20,000 workers dying from exposure every year, the majority in developing countries (Dasgupta *et al*, 2005). Therefore, the objectives of the present study were to evaluate the knowledge of farmers regarding the use of pesticides and pattern of use of preventive measures for the safe use of pesticides.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in three Mandals i.e. Kowthalam, Aluru and Holugunda mandals of Kurnool district covering 21 villages where the major crops grown were cotton and chillies. Cotton is one of the major agricultural systems on which small holder farmers use substantial proportion of pesticides and there is high level of pesticide usage in these mandals. The technique of stratified random sampling was used covering sample size of 300 farmers involved in pesticide application. Data were gathered using structured interview schedule

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Table 1: Distribution of farmers based on the knowledge of pesticide safety labels.

Sr. No.	True message of safety label	Correct	Partially correct	Wrong
1.	Expiry date	17	18	65
2.	Alert on possible danger of death	10	10	80
3.	Wear glasses to protect eyes	16	20	64
4.	Put on leg boots	10	20	70
5.	Put on hand gloves	12	19	69
6.	Protect nose and mouth	20	20	60
7.	Keep securely out of reach of children	10	10	80
8.	Proper method of spraying	2	5	93
9.	Wash after pesticide operation	3	20	77
10.	Wear breathing apparatus	0	3	97
	Average	10	14	76

and also direct field observations which analyzed using SPSS – 20 version.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Knowledge of pesticide safety labels

The assessment of farmers knowledge on pesticide labels indicated that majority (76%) of the farmers have misinterpreted the safety labels especially knowledge on proper methods of spraying and wearing breathing apparatus while spraying is very poor. The labels that advice to protect nose and mouth was interpreted correctly by 20 per cent of farmers which is the highest among the correctly interpreted labels. Overall the knowledge on safety labels is very poor only 10 per cent of the farmers had awareness. Ninety per cent of the farmers consult dealers for any information on pesticides use. In terms of training Agri input companies have organized training sessions which focused on pesticide dosages, spraying operations etc. The findings in Table 1 indicate that a health education program promoting greater awareness among farmers and labourer about pesticides was highly needed. This awareness should tap the belief system. It should include relevant information that explicitly takes into account farmers beliefs and perceptions about pesticides and specific details of how pesticides can enter the body, who are those at

risk and how they can reduce their exposure.

Method of application

Ninety percent of the respondents were using motorized Knapsack sprayer due to its easy availability and utility or suitability for their crops in spraying whose cost ranges from Rs 2,000/- to Rs 16,000/-. Only 5 per cent of the farmers were using hand operated Knapsack sprayer whose cost ranged between Rs 300/- to Rs 1,900/-.

Storage of pesticides

Figure: 1

As depicted in figure 1 majority of farmers store pesticides in house in lofts and corners along with other articles which are not regularly used. 6 per cent of the farmers store along with house hold items which is very dangerous and not recommended. 6 per cent of the farmers avoid storage due to its easy availability

Knowledge Level of Farmers

Pesticide container disposal practices

The survey included questions mostly related to the management and disposal of left over pesticides and empty (used) pesticide container. Proper rinsing is necessary so that it may not contaminate the surrounding atmosphere and ground water. Most of the pesticide applicators (62%) sold the empty containers without proper rinsing/washing which is not acceptable. Whereas 22% of the respondents were using empty containers for domestic purpose after well rinsing, which is also not a healthy practice. The remaining respondents left empty containers in the field after use, which is also not acceptable.

Protective clothing and Safety measures

Only 40 per cent of the farmers recognized the consequences of spraying against the wind or when the speed of wind is high. They took precautionary measures to observe the direction of the wind before they begin spraying. Rest 60 per cent did not follow right direction with respect to wind direction which may increase their exposure to pesticides.

Fig 2

Majority (70 %) reported to be not wearing any form of protective clothing. They wore only *Lungi* and *Banian*. In 20 per cent of cases they tied a

towel / Hand kerchief around the mouth and nose to prevent from pesticide exposure. Only 10 per cent protected themselves by wearing shirt and pant with long sleeves. There is no incident using of gloves and masks due to discomfort in hot weather and economic reasons. Poor protective clothing that exposed farmers to potential health risks cannot be attributed to lack of information alone, but on other factors such as accessibility and cost of procuring protective equipments.

CONCLUSION

Many farmer and labourer are exposed to pesticide hazards, which they could reduce if they had more information about health hazards and appropriate safety measures. A health education program promoting greater awareness among farmers about pesticides is highly needed. There is scope for both government and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) to work on this issue and even the pesticide industries should also provide information on pesticide hazards and precautionary measures. In addition to safety issue, the promotion of integrated pest management (IPM) which has potential to reduce the quantity of pesticide use may help reduce the risks. Similarly, use of protective equipment suitable for tropical climate should be promoted.

REFERENCES

- Dasgupta S, Meisner C (2005). Health effects and pesticide perception as determinants of pesticide use: Evidence from Bangladesh World Bank Policy Research Working Paper 3776, November 2005
- Singh Gurmeet, Kaur Gagandeep, Sharma Manoj, Kaur Gurpreet and Singh Gobinder 2013. Use and availability of recommended pesticides in district Kapurthala. *J Krishi Vigyan* 2(1) : 64-72.

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Livelihood Security of Tribal Farmers by Integration of Different Enterprises

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ABSTRACT

To enhance income and employment of small and marginal farmers, Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Kanker introduced multi-enterprises model. Six different models were developed at Kulgaon and Aturgaon villages on the small and marginal farmer's fields on their need basis. Out of the different farming system models, rice + vegetable + maize + fish + duck + backyard poultry + goat was found more remunerative. The net return from this model was Rs 1.13 lakh from 1.5 ha land holding. Also found suitable from the point of employment generation per unit utilization of resources. It provided about 826 mandays throughout the year.

Key Words: Livelihood, Integrated farming system, Enterprises, Tribal.

INTRODUCTION

Uttar Bastar Kanker is tribal dominated district, about 78 per cent population lives in the villages and 70 per cent of total population belong to ST/SC. Rainfed rice is the major crop of the district which is growing in 1.71 lakh hectare and average size of land holding was declined to 1.86 during 2011-12 from 2.19 ha in 2001-02. The sustenance of increased productivity must emphasize on the development of strategies aimed at maintaining improved yields without depleting natural resources or destabilizing the environment. Integrated farming (or integrated agriculture) is a commonly and broadly used word to explain a more integrated approach to farming as compared to existing monoculture approaches. It refers to agricultural systems that integrated livestock and crop production. Integrated farming system has revolutionized conventional farming of livestock, aquaculture, horticulture, agro-industry and allied activities (Chan, 2006). It could be crop-fish integration, livestock-fish integration, crop-fish-livestock integration or combinations of crop, livestock, fish and other enterprises (Thy, 2006).

The approach aims at increasing income and employment from small-holding by integrating

various farm enterprises and recycling crop residues and by products within the farm itself. Farming system approach is one of the important solutions to face this peculiar situation as in this approach the different enterprises can be carefully undertaken and the location specific systems are developed based on available resources which will result into sustainable development (Dashora and Singh, 2014). Therefore, present investigation was undertaken to study integration of different enterprises for livelihood security of tribal farmers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A study was conducted on integrated farming system at Kulgaon and Aturgaon villages of Kanker block under irrigated condition during 2012 to 2014 involving cropping (rice, maize, and vegetables), fishery, poultry, piggery, goat azolla and vermicompost as the integrated system. Six farmers were selected, a thorough PRA were conducted of selected farmers. Synergy of different schemes with line department helps in providing critical inputs for IFS model development. Training on integrated farming system, demonstrations of technologies and field visit understands the problems and cause of low output from the fields.

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Six farm families of two villages namely Kulgaon and Aturgaon were selected for development of farming system model. Six different models of 1.5 ha each were developed in the small and marginal farmers fields on need basis as follows

Model 1 - Crop+ backyard poultry + goatry + vermi compost + azolla+ fish + duck+ piggery

Model 2 - Crop + backyard poultry + goatry + vermi compost + azolla + piggery

Model 3 - Crop + goatry + vermi compost + azolla+ piggery + backyard poultry

Model 4 - Crop+ backyard poultry + Piggery + fish + gotary

Model 5 - Crop+ piggery + backyard poultry + goatry + vermi compost + azolla+ fish

Model 6 - Crop + backyard poultry+ goatry + fish+ piggery

To sustain the productivity the residues obtained in the system was recycled. Observations on the productivity and economics of individual components and the farming system as a whole

and employment generation and water requirement were recorded as per the standard procedure. Since, the study includes diversified enterprises like fish, poultry and goat, the yield was converted into rice equivalent yield as suggested by Singh *et al* (2005).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The integration of crop with fish, poultry, piggery and goat resulted in higher productivity than adoption of conventional method of rice mono cropping. Mono cropping of rice generates employment of 233 mandays throughout the year, whereas integrated farming system provides on an average 730 mandays per year (Table 1), which helps in reducing migration of rural youth to urban areas. Also adopting IFS model, one can use efficiently family labour and conservation, preservation and utilization of farm biomass including non-conventional feed and fodder resource.

Out of the different farming system models (model 1 to 6) rice + vegetable + maize + fish + duck + backyard poultry + goat+ Piggery was found more remunerative (net return Rs 1.13

Rice Cultivation

Vegetable cultivation

Goat rearing

Fish + Duck production

Pig rearing

Poultry3

Livelihood Security of Tribal Farmers

Table 1: Comparative economics of mono cropping and IFS model

Sr. No.	Farming system	Cost of production (Rs./ha)	Gross return (Rs./ha)	Net return (Rs./ha)	Employment man days/year
1	Mono crop rice	36350	68400	32050	233
2	Crop+ backyard poultry + goatry + vermi compost + azolla+ fish + duck+ piggery	75350	188540	113190	826
3	crop + backyard poultry + goatry + vermi compost + azolla + piggery	71230	176460	105230	768
4	crop + goatry + vermi compost + azolla+ piggery	68390	162500	94110	686
5	crop+ backyard poultry + piggery + fish + goatry	66500	152340	85840	626
6	crop+ + backyard poultry + goatry + vermi compost + azolla+ fish + piggery	74250	186210	111960	817
7	crop + backyard poultry+ goatry + fish + piggery	67200	157325	90125	657

lakh from 1.5 ha land holding) from the point of employment generation (826 mandays per year), per unit utilization of resources (Table 1).

CONCLUSION

Integrated farming systems offer unique opportunities for maintaining and extending biodiversity. The emphasis should be on small livestock such as chicken, duck, pig, goat in accordance with constant income. Addition of organic residues in the form of animal and plant wastes could also help in improving the soil – health and thereby productivity over a longer period of time with lesser environmental hazards.

REFERENCES

- Chan G L (2006). Integrated Farming System. What Does Integrated Farming System Do? <http://www.scizerinm.org/chanarticle.htm>.
- Dashora L N and Hari Singh (2014). Integrated Farming System-Need of Today. *Int J App Life Sci and Eng* 1(1) 28-37.
- Singh, J P, A Salaria, K Singh and B Gangwar (2005). Diversification of rice-wheat cropping system through inclusion of Basmati rice, potato and sunflower in trans-gangetic plains. *J. Fmg Syst Res Dev* 11: 12-18.
- Thy S (2006). Management and Utilization of Biodigesters in Integrated Farming Systems. <http://www.aidg.net/index.php?option=com>.

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Menace of Anaemia among Adolescent Girls in Shaheed Bhagat Singh Nagar District in Punjab

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ABSTRACT

Anaemia is the most prevalent nutritional deficiency disorder in the world. It is very common in the developing countries as a result of inadequate diet or poor absorption. Among all the age groups, adolescents girls are the most vulnerable. District Level Household Survey indicated that about 99 per cent of adolescent girls in Punjab suffer from anaemia. Among all the districts it is quiet prevalent in Shaheed Bhagat Singh Nagar district. The present study focused on the anaemia levels of the adolescent girls calculated from the hemoglobin test of 150 school going adolescent girls in SBS Nagar district. The study indicated that all the adolescent girls tested for haemoglobin in the present study suffered from some form of anaemia. The prevalence was higher in urban areas and those who belong to nuclear families and had 3rd or 4th ordinal position in the family. The study also focused on the source of drinking water and eating patterns of the adolescent girls.

Key Words: Menace, Anaemia, Adolescent, Girls.

INTRODUCTION

Anaemia is a condition in which the haemoglobin count of the blood is lower than the normal as a result of deficiency of one or more essential nutrients and can occur at all stages and among both sexes. It is very common in the developing countries as a result of inadequate diet or poor absorption. Infants, children up to 2 years of age, adolescent girls and pregnant women are more prone to anaemia. Adolescence is a crucial phase of growth in the life cycle of an individual. It is period of transition between children and adulthood occurring between 12 to 18 years of age. Adolescent girl form a crucial segment of the population and acts as a “bridge” between the present generation and the next.

Prevalence of Iron Deficiency Anaemia among Adolescent Girls

In India, 75 per cent adolescent girls are anaemic and are at a risk of mortality and morbidity. Adolescence is the vulnerable period in the human life cycle for the development of nutritional anaemia as it is the shaping period of life when maximum amount of physical, psychological and behavioural

changes take place. (Chaudhary and Dhage, 2008). The state level data from the District Level Household and Facility survey (DLHS) conducted in 2006 indicates that as high as 99 per cent of the adolescents girls in Punjab in the age group of 10-19 years had some form of deficiency pertaining to their anaemia levels; 17 per cent of them were mildly anaemic, 48 per cent were moderately anaemic and 34 per cent had severe anaemia. The recent findings on anemia as indicated by DLHS 4 (2015) had reported that 48.6 per cent of adolescent girls suffer from anaemia and 3.2 per cent of them suffer from severe anaemia (Table 1).

The data reveal that the proportion of females living in rural areas in the age group of 6-10 years and belonging to SC category suffering from anaemia is higher as compared to their counterparts. Further district wise data indicates that the prevalence of anaemia is highest in districts Hoshiarpur (57.5%), Muktsar (57.4 %) followed by districts Mansa, Ludhiana (54 % each) and Jalandhar (53 %). Shaheed Bhagat Singh (SBS) Nagar district is also one of the districts where the proportion of adolescent girls

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Table 1. Percentage of school going population classified as having iron deficiency (anaemia) by degree of anaemia and by selected background characteristics, Punjab

Background characteristics	Anaemia status by haemoglobin level			
	Mild anaemia (10.0-10.9 g/dl)	Moderate anaemia (7.0-9.9g/dl)	Severe anaemia (<7 g/dl)	Any anaemia <11.0 g/dl)
Age group (in years)				
6-10	20.6	29.2	4.0	53.8
11-14	19.9	26.7	2.9	49.5
15-16	19.1	24.0	2.7	45.8
17-19	16.5	22.5	2.8	41.8
Sex				
Male	18.0	23.7	2.9	44.7
Female	20.7	29.1	3.6	53.4
Place of residence				
Rural	19.4	26.6	3.4	49.4
Urban	18.9	25.3	2.9	47.1
Education				
Non-Literate	20.5	30.8	5.1	56.4
Less than 5 years	20.0	28.7	3.6	52.3
5-9 years	19.6	25.8	2.9	48.4
10 or more years	17.0	21.8	2.5	41.3
Religion				
Hindu	19.8	26.4	3.4	49.5
Muslim	20.1	25.3	2.7	48.1
Christian	21.6	28.7	3.5	53.8
Sikh	18.9	26.0	3.1	48.0
Jain	22.5	10.6	0.0	33.1
Others	21.7	34.6	4.9	61.2
Caste/Tribes				
Scheduled Castes	19.7	28.0	3.8	51.5
Scheduled Tribes	18.2	28.1	2.3	48.6
Other Backward Castes	20.5	25.4	3.0	48.8
Others	18.3	23.9	2.6	44.8
Punjab	19.2	26.1	3.2	48.6

Source: District Level Household Survey (2015).

Menace of Anaemia

Table 2. Percentage of adolescents classified as having iron-deficiency (anaemia) by degree of anaemia in districts of Punjab, 2012-13

Districts	Any Anaemia (<11.0 g/dl)	Severe Anaemia (<7 g/dl)
Gurdaspur	49.1	5.6
Amritsar	50.9	3.5
Kapurthala	47.9	2.4
Jalandhar	53.3	2.0
Hoshiarpur	57.5	3.8
SBS nagar	50.2	1.9
Rupnagar	48.9	2.5
Fatehgarh Sahib	38.6	2.3
Ludhiana	54.5	4.7
Moga	52.0	3.7
Ferozpur	51.2	3.1
Muktsar	57.4	5.6
Faridkot	47.0	4.3
Bathinda	47.4	3.0
Mansa	54.1	3.5
Sangrur	38.7	2.0
Patiala	43.2	1.7
SAS Nagar	46.3	3.3
Barnala	39.0	2.8
Tarn Taran	47.2	1.9
Punjab	48.6	3.2

Source: District Level Household Survey, 2015

suffering from anaemia is the higher than the state average (Table 2). One-half of the adolescent girls suffer from some form of anaemia. About 48.6 per cent of adolescent girl in SBS Nagar district have anaemia levels of <11.0g/dl while 1.9 per cent of them suffer from severe anaemia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Keeping in view the high anaemia levels in the State especially among the adolescent girl a study was conducted in SBS Nagar district wherein 150 adolescent girls studying in government school were included in the study. Blood test to check the haemoglobin (Hb) levels of adolescent girls

were conducted by the health officials from health department. Blood tests were conducted after obtaining consent from the adolescent girls. Data on socio-economic background of respondents, source and treatment of drinking water and eating habits was collected using interview schedule.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The primary data reveal that all the adolescent girls tested for haemoglobin suffered from some form of anaemia. About seven out of every ten girls had moderate level of anaemia which means that their hb levels were from 8 g/dl to 10 g/dl. About one-fifth of them suffer from severe anaemia (19

%) with hb levels as low as between 6 g/dl to 8 g/dl and only three per cent of them had mild anaemia i.e. the hb levels were between 10 g/dl to 12 g/dl.

Socio-economic Indicators

The majority of adolescent girls who suffer from severe or moderate anaemia were in the age group of 14 to 16 years. Further the data revealed that among the adolescent girls who had severe or moderate anaemia, a majority resided in urban areas. (69 % in cases of severe anaemic and 63 % in case of moderately anaemic). Among the social indicators caste is an important factor as it has bearing on the food intake of the family and in turn the nutritional status of the family members. Anaemia is directly affected by dietary intakes so it is interesting to know the differences in the prevalence of anaemia among the SCs and non-SCs. The state level NFHS-4 data indicated that the prevalence of both mild and moderate anaemia among the SCs was high in Punjab. The data of the present study in SBS Nagar district is in line with the state level data and indicates that about eight out of every ten adolescent girls who suffered from severe and moderate anaemia belonged to SC category (Table 3).

Joint family system is rapidly being replaced with nuclear family system. This is probably due to urbanization along with migration especially in case of SBS Nagar which belongs to the NRI belt and most of the family members are NRIs which has led to disintegration of joint family system in this belt. The data of the present study indicates that majority of the respondents suffering from any type of anaemia lived in nuclear families. The data on the number of members in the family in the present study indicates that the majority of adolescent girls who suffer from anaemia had 5-7 members in the family. Their proportions being as high as 57 per cent in case of adolescent girls having moderate anaemia, 52 per cent in the case of severe anaemia, closely followed by 50 per cent of the adolescent girls suffering from mild anaemia.

Ordinal position is the position of the adolescents according to the place or rank of her birth in the family. Three out of every ten adolescent girls who suffered from severe anaemia were the fourth child in the family. Similar proportions of adolescent girls (34 %) were at the third ordinal position in the family. The present study points that probably the ordinal position has certain influence on the anaemia levels of the individuals as a majority of the respondents who suffered from mild anaemia were the first child in the family.

Adolescent girls suffering from severe anaemia had monthly family income of less than Rs. 6000/- per month. Further half of them had family income between Rs.3,000/- to Rs. 6,000/- and about three out of every ten had family income less than Rs. 3,000/- per month.

Thus in the present study the adolescents who suffer from severe and moderate anaemia were in the age group of 14-16 years, resided in urban areas, belonged to nuclear families, had 5-7 members in the family and were either 3rd or 4th child in the family. They had monthly family income of less than Rs.6000/- per month. A similar study conducted by Chellan and Paul (2010) indicated that household standard of living also shows gradual decline in anaemia level among adolescent girls in the country. The prevalence of moderate to severe anaemia as indicated in the study by Chellan and Paul is high among girls with low standard of living and SC membership. The study also reveals that severity of anaemia was higher among adolescent girls belonging to urban areas than rural areas. Contrary to the common perception anaemia not only affects the lower strata as such but has its mark on well-off sections of the society as well.

Hellen Keller Institute for Girls (1996) estimated that 83.9 per cent girls between the age 12 to 18 years in rural India were found to be anaemic, the levels is high among girls with no schooling (92.7 %). The study conducted by Basu *et al* (2005) indicated that anaemia was significantly less among the urban school going children as compared

Menace of Anaemia

Table 3. Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents.

Socio-Economic Indicators	6 to 8 (Severe)	8 to 10 (Moderate)	10 to 12 (Mild)
Age (in years)			
11 to 13	34	41	43
14 to 16	59	53	43
17 to 19	7	6	14
Residence			
Rural	31	37	50
urban	69	63	50
Caste			
General	17	18	86
SC	83	82	14
Type of family			
Nuclear	66	74	86
Joint	34	26	14
Family members (Number)			
Upto to 5	27	30	36
5 to 7	52	57	50
7 to 9	21	13	14
Ordinal Position			
1	10	19	36
2	21	30	14
3	24	34	14
4	31	12	29
5	7	3	7
6	7	2	0
Monthly Family Income (in Rs.)			
<3000	28	30	7
3000-6000	52	41	28
6000-9000	14	10	21
9000-12000	3	10	28
>12000	3	9	14

Source: Field Survey

to the rural school going ones. Socio-economic and demographic factors have a bearing on the prevalence of anaemia. In the study conducted by Deshpande *et al* (2013), 60 per cent of the adolescent girls were found to be anaemic with a

very high percentage belonging to lower socio-economic strata. These findings were similar to the study conducted by Gawarka *et al* (2006) where the prevalence was 96.5 per cent in the weaker income group and 65.18 per cent in middle or higher middle

Table 4. Source of Drinking Water and Methods of Purification of Water

Sr. No.	Source of drinking water	6 to 8 (Severe)	8 to 10 (Moderate)	10 to 12 (Mild)
1.	Well	3	2	14
2.	Running water	90	96	78
3.	Storage tank	7	2	8
	Water purification			
4.	Yes	24	3	14
5.	No	76	97	86

Source: Field Survey

group. Kapoor *et al* (1992) also reported 56 per cent in lower middle and 46 per cent in high socio-economic strata were observed to be anaemic with 2 and 28 being suffering from mild and moderate anaemia.

Source of Drinking Water

Safe drinking water is essential for the health and well being of the individuals. It is also important while studying anaemia as drinking contaminated or untreated water may lead to worm infestation which is one of the major causes of anaemia. The data revealed that the main source of drinking water of the respondents was the running water from the municipality tank. Almost all of the adolescent girls who suffer from moderate anaemia did not purify drinking water. Even among those who suffer from severe anemia three-fifths of the adolescent girls did not purify water. Among those who purify water, 16 per cent use filter for water purification and rest boil the water only during illness.

Eating Patterns of the Respondents

Eating habits are changing rapidly especially among the adolescents. With attractive packaging and easy availability of junk food adolescents are attracted towards it. This type of food provides them with instant energy and fulfills their requirements of calories but the need of other nutrients is not met from such kind of food. It is recommended that adolescents must eat green leafy vegetables and fruits daily to meet their daily requirements of vitamins and minerals. In order to ascertain eating

habits among the adolescent girls, the frequency of eating different foods respondents was assessed. The data (Table 5) indicate that about one-fourth of the adolescent girls who suffer from severe anaemia eat junk food daily. Around 36 per cent of the adolescent girls who had moderate or mild anaemia reported that they eat junk food only once in a month.

Green leafy vegetables which are rich iron sources are preferred once a week in diet by 38 per cent of the adolescent girls who suffer from severe anaemia. While their proportions were half in case of adolescent girls who had moderate levels of anaemia. In case of adolescents who had mild anaemia a majority (three out of every ten) preferred to eat green leafy vegetables twice a week. Milk was never consumed by 34 per cent of the adolescent girls who suffer from severe anaemia while 54 per cent of those who had moderate anaemia never consumed it. Only 14 per cent of the girls having mild anaemia consumed milk daily. Non-vegetarian foods are one of the richest sources of iron. These food items were never consumed by 45 per cent adolescent girls having severe anaemia, 76 per cent of adolescent girls having moderate anaemia and 43 per cent of those having mild anaemia.

Midday meal is provided to the adolescents to improve the school drop out rates and also to provide at least one healthy meal in a day. The study indicates that 33 per cent girls bring lunch from home and they had midday meal also and 11 per cent neither bring lunch from home nor had midday

Menace of Anaemia

Table 5. Eating Patterns of Respondents

Sr. No.	Frequency of Eating Food Items	6 to 8 (Severe)	8 to 10 (Moderate)	10 to 12 (Mild)
A.	Junk food			
1.	Never	14	20	22
2.	Once in a month	10	35	7
3.	Twice in a month	14	13	14
4.	Once in a week	10	19	21
5.	Twice in a week	31	13	36
6.	Daily	21	-	-
B	Green leafy vegetables			
7.	Never	3	1	
8.	Once in a month	14	5	29
9.	Twice in a month	7	4	14
10.	Once in a week	31	3	22
11.	Twice in a week	38	37	14
12.	Daily	7	50	21
C	Fruits			
13.	Never	7	4	21
14.	Once in a month	28	9	36
15.	Twice in a month	10	4	14
16.	Once in a week	21	10	14
17.	Twice in a week	17	43	7
18.	Daily	17	30	8
D	Milk			
19.	Never	34	54	36
20.	Once in a month	14	1	14
21.	Twice in a month	10	2	14
22.	Once in a week	21	6	7
23.	Twice in a week	14	10	15
24.	Daily	7	27	14
E	Non-vegetarian food			
25.	Never	45	76	43
26.	Once in a month	17	14	21
27.	Twice in a month	14	2	7
28.	Once in a week	10	14	7
29.	Twice in a week	7	4	14
30.	Daily	7	14	7

Source: Field Survey

meal a school, thus they are deprived of nutrition at a very crucial stage of their life.

CONCLUSION

The study indicated that all the adolescent girls tested for haemoglobin in the present study suffered from some form of anaemia. Seven out of every ten girls had moderate level of anaemia, about one-fifth of them suffer from severe anaemia. The adolescent girls who suffer from severe and moderate anaemia were in the age group of 14-16 years, resided in urban areas, belonged to nuclear families, had 5-7 members in the family and were either 3rd or 4th child in the family. They had monthly family income of less than Rs.6000/- per month. Almost all of the adolescent girls who suffer from moderate anaemia did not purify drinking water. Even among those who suffer from severe anemia three-fifths of the adolescent girls did not purify water. Eating patterns of the respondents indicate that about one-fourth of the adolescent girls who suffer from severe anaemia eat junk food daily. In case of adolescents who had mild anaemia a majority (three out of every ten) preferred to eat green leafy vegetables twice a week. Non-vegetarian foods were never consumed by 45 per cent adolescent girls having severe anaemia. The study indicates that 33 per cent girls bring lunch from home and they had midday meal also and 11 per cent neither bring lunch from home nor had midday meal a school, thus they are deprived of nutrition at a very crucial stage of their life.

REFERENCES

- Basu S, Basu S, Hazarka R and Parmar P (2005). Prevalence of Anaemia among School Going Adolescents of Chandigarh. *Clinical Med* **42** : 595-597.
- Chaudhary S M and Dhage V R (2008). Anaemia levels among the adolescents. *Int J Community Med* **33** (4): 243-245.
- Challen R and Paul L (2010). Prevalence of Iron Deficiency Anaemia in India: Results from Large Scale Nationwide Survey. *J Pop and Soc Studies* **19** (1): 59-80.
- Seshadri S (1999). *Department of Food and Nutrition WHO collaborating Centre for Nutrition Research, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara, India.*
- Trivedi P and Palta A (2007). Prevalence of Anaemia and Impact of Iron Supplementation on Anaemia Adolescent School Girls. *Health and Population Perspective and Issues* **30** (1): 45-55.
- Girija (2001). Anaemia among Women and Children of India: Present Scenario. *European J Zoological Res* **3** (1): 32-36.
- Tara N S (2003). *India's Anaemia Woes: A Study, International Institute of Population Studies.*
- Deshpande N S, Karve D, Agarkhedkar S and Deshpande S (2005). Prevalence of Anaemia in Adolescent Girls and its Correlated with Demographic Factors. *Int J Med and Public Health* **3**: 235-9.
- Gawarika R, Gawarika S and Mishra A K (2006). Prevalence of Anaemia in Adolescents belonging to Different Economic Group. *Indian J Community Med* **31** (4):48-62
- Kapoor G and Aneja S (1992) Nutritional Disorders in Adolescent Girls. *Indian Pediatrics* **29**: 969-973.
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Methodologies for Livelihood Support through Fish Farming at High Altitudes of Arunachal Pradesh

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ABSTRACT

Aquaculture in the hilly regime of eastern part of Himalayas could not make much headway due to lack of awareness, perspective, technical skills and low risk-taking capacity of the farmers. Simple attention to basic requirements in fish farming may spell a big difference in raising the production level by many folds, for which easier technologies are readily available. For proper land utilization, aquaculture was supported with free of cost critical inputs from various agencies for economic well being of the community. An attempt was, thus made here to evaluate the effect of awareness generation, skill dissemination and sustained level of follow up action over extended period, in transforming the aquaculture scenario of Chug village, Dirang Block of West Kameng district of Arunachal Pradesh. Study revealed that 500 farmers developed skill from fisheries training programmes, on-farm trials and Frontline Demonstrations; more than 1000 farmers gained knowledge from kisan goshies and exhibitions; 1000 fish farmers were distributed fish seeds and other critical inputs. 30 fish pond holders of Chug village adopted the technology on scientific lines with recommended dietary protein level for raising the fish production from a negligible quantity to a level of 0.4-0.6 kg/m² unit area.

Key Words: Aquaculture, coldwater, *Monpas*, Chug village, Arunachal Pradesh

INTRODUCTION

Chug village is situated 10 Km north-east of Dirang township and 52 Km from district headquarter Bomdila. The village is located at an altitude of 1450 m msl approximately with a temperature range from 5°C – 30°C. The village has a total of 58 farm families with a population of 268 belonging to schedule tribe community (Census of India, 2011) and the literacy rate is 24.3 per cent. The village is surrounded by lofty mountains, covered with forests, bestowed with a roaring river and numerous small streams, and rich diversity of flora and fauna characterizing the landscape.

Farming is the mainstay of livelihood for the people and both men and women contribute equally in agriculture and household activities. Aquaculture development could not make much headway because farmers have low risk-taking capacity, lack of awareness, perspective and technical skills. This

clearly showed that the farmers were in need of help and technical assistance for a change of attitude and cast away the traditional practices in order to reap the benefit of technological advancements in aquaculture and other production technologies. The first step to make a stride in aquaculture development in rural areas lies in involving the grass root level farmers in large number and also aiming at bringing more and more available water bodies under aquaculture. Simple attention to basic requirements like stocking density, species composition, reasonable culture duration, effective manuring and liming only may spell a big difference in raising the production level by many times, for which easier technologies are readily available (Sharma *et al*, 2010). An attempt was, thus made here to evaluate the effect of awareness generation, skill dissemination and sustained level of follow up action over extended period, in transforming the aquaculture scenario in the village.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

Need-based extension programmes were organized for a decade by the Krishi Vigyan Kendra, West Kameng district of Arunachal Pradesh at Chug village of Dirang Block with the objectives (i) to raise the status of aquaculture in terms of expansion of cultivable area and income generation through mass participatory approach (ii) to maximize productivity per unit of water area. Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) method ascertained the status and potential of fish farming in the village and therefore leading to initiation of a developmental programme with 10 numbers of farmers at the first stage. Free inputs supported with technical guidance from various institutes, organizations, financing agencies and state departments, following different extension tools led to success in dissemination of fish farming technology and its mass adoption among the villagers in the following years in a hilly regime of Arunachal Pradesh.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The aquaculture scenario

Although fish is an accepted delicacy in the region, there was a big gap in the demand and supply. The local people are largely dependent on fish imported from other states like Andhra Pradesh, West Bengal and Assam. Profession level of fish farming remained a low key affair until the recent past and traditional to extensive culture methods using mixed riverine fish seeds was in vogue. Participatory Rural Appraisal conducted in the year 2006 by a team of scientist from Krishi Vigyan Kendra (KVK) of West Kameng district determined the status and potential of existing culture area which was found to be small yielding with extremely low fish production. Lack of awareness, skill and access to technology hindered the pace of progress to a considerable extent in the past. The villagers were totally unaware as to whom to approach for guidance and technical back up to venture in to a new economic activity. The PRA helped to witness a few numbers of unutilized fish ponds in the village which triggered the idea

to promote fish culture in the area, provided fish farmers of the village are technically guided and supported with critical inputs in the form of fish seeds and feeds for startup incentive to take up the venture.

Intervention

Based on the findings of the PRA, the possibility of reclaiming the waste land and unused water bodies was felt in order to improve productivity and to generate income from the village ponds, by suitably adopting fish farming with the existing structures and resources, which was further intensified with horticulture and animal husbandry. In pursuance to the above fact, 10 numbers of unutilized ponds were identified (Fig. 1 & 2) and villagers owning them were asked for their consent to adopt the venture of fish farming. But nothing was possible without the technical and financial support from institutes and financing agencies. Therefore, in order to make the programme a successful one, approach was made by the Kendra during 2006-07 to National Research Centre on Coldwater Fisheries (now ICAR-Directorate of Coldwater Fisheries Research), Bhimtal, Uttarakhand and Office of the District Fishery Development Officer, Govt. of Arunachal Pradesh, Bomdila for financial assistance for preliminary renovation of the identified 10 numbers of unutilized ponds and purchase of critical inputs such as fish seeds, fish feeds, chemicals and fertilizers. Much of the effort was relieved when consent was received from ICAR-DCFR for providing financial assistance for the preliminary cost of pond repair (Fig. 3 & 4), fish seed, fish feed and necessary chemicals whereas the District Fishery Development Officer (DFDO), Bomdila agreed to provide fish seeds and fish feeds through his office supplier at the cost remitted by ICAR-DCFR, Bhimtal. Action oriented programmes with sustained technical back-up, skilled training, trials and demonstration were conducted in the village for the year to motivate and to generate awareness among the rural people in order to take fish culture on scientific lines for income generation and livelihood development.

Livelihood support through Fish Farming

Methodologies for aquaculture adoption and expansion at high altitudinal regions.

1. Training programmes

Training is the process of acquiring specific skills to perform a job better. Analyzing the technology gap and need of the farmers, more than 20 training programmes in aquaculture were organized for farmers, farm women, rural youth and school drop-outs both on and off campus. Emphasis was given mainly on fish culture practices suited for mid-hill conditions. Approximately, 500 farmers were benefited from the training programmes in the district and minimum of 100 farmers from the Chug village. Financial assistance was rendered by National Fisheries Development Board, Hyderabad; NABARD, Regional Centre, Itanagar; National Horticulture Board, Gurgaon; and ATMA, Arunachal Pradesh in conducting many of these programmes.

2. On-Farm Trials (OFT)

On-Farm Trial is an important tool for identifying technologies in terms of location specific sustainable land use systems. Considering the topography and climatic conditions of the area, trials were conducted at the selected 10 numbers of farmers' ponds at Chug village on the technology of "Composite culture of carps" for the first time in order to determine the growth pattern and survival of the stocked Indian Major Carps (IMC) and Chinese carps at mid-altitudes region of the eastern Himalayas. Fish seeds were supplied from the Office of DFDO with the financial assistance from ICAR-DCFR as discussed above. Encouraging results were achieved in the growth of 3-pronged Chinese carps viz., silver carp (*Hypophthalmichthys molitrix*), grass carp (*Ctenopharyngodon idella*) and common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) whereas success rate was much lower in case of IMCs viz., catla (*Catla catla*), rohu (*Labeo rohita*), mrigal (*Cirrhinus mrigala*) due to slower growth in cold regime. From the OFT, it was concluded that rearing of fish at this altitude is possible with Chinese carps alone, devoid of IMCs in polyculture system.

3. Frontline Demonstrations

Seeing the affirmative results of OFT in carp farming, many more farmers approached to adopt fish farming in the village and nearby areas. Based on the guidelines of KVK, another methodology was followed known as Frontline Demonstration to generate production data and feedback information from technology on "3-pronged Chinese carp culture at high altitudes" by its mass adoption and expansion. Altogether, 30 fish pond holders of Chug village came forward and adopted the technology. Interestingly, the farmers renovated their existing structures as well as excavated new ponds at their own cost. The only requirement was to provide them with quality fish seeds. Therefore, quality seeds were purchased from a private hatchery belonged to Mr. Neelam Dutta, a resident of Pavo village at Biswanath Chariali of the neighbouring state Assam, and the seeds were later distributed to the fish farmers free of cost. The technique of preparation of fish feeds was taught to the farmers by the then Fisheries Scientist of the KVK by utilizing the farmer's own household resources such as maize powder or maize flour, rice bran, soybean meal, vegetable or household waste, banana leaves etc., supported with the knowledge of feeding schedule and feeding techniques. Three species of Chinese carps viz., silver carp (*Hypophthalmichthys molitrix*), grass carp (*Ctenopharyngodon idella*) and common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) of 60 mm size were stocked in combination with a density of 3-4 fishes/m² and recommended supplementary diet was provided under low temperature conditions. The performance of each fish species in terms of growth, survival and contribution to total biomass were studied and found to be quite remarkable with a production range of 0.4-0.6 kg/m².

4. Celebration of Fish Farmers' Day and Field Days

Celebrating important days such as Farmers' Day and Field Days are a method of motivating the people to adopt a new practice by showing what has actually been achieved by applying the practice under field conditions. All these important

days were organized at farmers' fields. On the Fish Farmers' Day, approximately 15,000 numbers of fish seeds were distributed free of cost to the selected beneficiaries (approximately 100 persons) every year procured either from the Regional Fish Nursery under Office of DFDO, Bomdila or from the neighbouring state Assam. Fish harvest was generally conducted with the help of the fish farmers in their own ponds to observe the production and successful results of fish farming.

5. Exhibitions

An exhibition is a systematic display of models, specimens, charts, photographs, pictures, posters, information etc. in a sequence around a theme to create awareness and interest in the community. The major segment of the display was with the fish aquariums, museum specimens on important fishes, posters and charts. The farmers also bring fishes and other sellable products on the occasion and are much benefited. More than thousands of people were benefited from the exhibitions in terms of gaining knowledge and technical know-how in high-altitude fish farming practices.

6. Kisan gosthies and farmers-scientist Interactions

Such programmes were arranged at a selected location under Government Administration or at farmers' field. More than 12 such meets were organized in the district since 2006 benefiting more than 500 farmers inclusive of the Chug villagers in the subjects of agriculture, horticulture, fisheries, animal husbandry and home science etc. The queries and issues raised by the farmers were answered and solved on the spot by the experts and scientists from various organizations. These meets are very effective as farmers from different villages get a platform to exchange their views and farming techniques and therefore support in expansion of innovative ideas.

Promotional activities for sustained aquaculture in the village

The coldwater fisheries occupy a prominent

position especially in West Kameng district of Arunachal Pradesh. In order to make fish farming sustainable in a hilly regime amid of several constraints, it was felt to take initiation in binding the farmers in one frame so as to reduce much of their human drudgery, overcome financial inability and improving livelihood. The steps taken were as follows;

a. Formation of farmers' clubs

Farmers' Clubs were formed with financial assistance from NABARD, Arunachal Pradesh Regional Office, Itanagar and under the guidance of KVK West Kameng during 2008-2010. Two numbers of Farmers' Clubs viz., Mani Dungjur Farmers' Club (Male members) and Changpa Women Farmers' Club (Female members) were constituted at Chug village with 15 members in each club. The members resolved to deposit a sum of INR 100.00 each on every month. A joint savings account was opened at the nearest State Bank of India, Dirang Branch for each of the clubs. On completion of a year, a part of the deposited amount was disbursed as loan to individual members based on their requirement. The members discussed the issues on each month in a group meeting to undertake new farm-based initiatives and to mitigate the financial crunches by disbursing the loan amount at a minimal interest rate. The clubs performed well and the members were much benefited in terms of procurement of critical inputs as well as marketing of commodities in mass. The club members also support other villagers in undertaking fish farming by personally involving themselves in pond construction and repairing as well as lending loans in starting the venture. This led to a dramatic change in their livelihood pattern as the farmers could now avail to purchase the household commodities, afford for children education etc from the sell produce of their farm unit.

b. Association with other organizations for financial and livelihood support

(i) Seed distribution programme in collaboration with the Office of DFDO, Bomdila

Livelihood support through Fish Farming

Survey was conducted during 2006-08 to identify the existing fish ponds and tanks of entire Dirang and Nafra block and a list of names of the fish farmers were proposed to DFDO, Bomdila for providing free inputs in the form of carp seeds each year. As the entire region is devoid of a fish seed hatchery, fish seeds were purchased by the Office of DFDO, Bomdila from the neighboring state Assam which were stocked initially at their Regional Fish Nursery at Salari village for acclimation. A part of these fish seeds were later procured by the KVK and were distributed free of cost to the farmers based on the estimated requirements (minimum 15000 numbers) every year. This helped to mitigate the problem of fish seed unavailability in the village and the locality.

(ii) Indo-Tibetan Border Police Force (ITBPF), 4th BN for aquaculture promotion under Border Area Development Programme (BADP)

The KVK West Kameng district and Indo-Tibetan Border Police Force (ITBPF), 4th BN, Dirang, West Kameng district, Arunachal Pradesh had initiated a collaborative fisheries demonstration programme on “Economic and livelihood development of rural population through freshwater aquaculture in hill region” in the year 2010-11, giving priorities to the locals who have common interest and stake in coldwater sector development. The aim of the programme was to prepare a blueprint for a relevant, economical and viable coldwater fisheries package of practice which can easily be implicated in the hill region of the district. More than 200 farmers adopted fish farming along with raising horticulture crops (vegetables and fruits) and animal husbandry (poultry and pig), ornamental fish keeping and aquarium making, fish processing under this programme.

(iii) PRAGYA (NGO) – A volunteer organization for livelihood development

The approach of PRAGYA - a Gurgaon based NGO was well supported by the KVK in conducting On-Field Demonstration & Free input distribution

programme on the title “Occupational skills in Pisciculture” during 2009 to the farmers of Chug and nearby villages (Sangti, Khaso, Namchu etc.) so as to develop livelihood options in hill regions by practicing fish farming on scientific lines. About 1000 numbers of farmers were benefited by receiving fish seeds, feeds, chemicals and fish nets from the NGO and technical guidance from the KVK.

Establishment of method demonstration unit in collaboration with ICAR-National Research Centre on Yak, Dirang

In the year 2008, KVK West Kameng initiated to establish a demonstration unit in the unutilized tank of 600m² area at the premises of ICAR-National Research Centre on Yak, Dirang in collaborative mode with an objective to demonstrate the production and productivity of composite carp culture in pond fisheries at high altitudes with pre-decided protein percentage of fish feed ration. The KVK hold responsibility for implementing the work plan on scientific fish culture and its operational demonstration to the farmers whereas ICAR-NRC on Yak took charge of the financial and manpower based managerial issues. The income generated from the harvest was deposited as revenue in the account of ICAR-NRC on Yak. Approximately 10 numbers of trainings were imparted and demonstration programmes were conducted by KVK during the trial period benefiting more than 300 farmers, farm women and school drop-outs of the district. Field demonstrations comprised of feed preparation, feeding methodology, stocking procedure, liming and manuring techniques, management of water quality and fish health, harvesting etc which were very useful for easy understanding and skill development among the farmers. From the trials, the average fish production achieved was @ 334 kg/ 600m²/ 8 months. In a span of 8 months, silver carp (15%), grass carp (30%), common carp (30%) and other carps (25%) recorded a maximum individual average weight of 250g, 500g, 900g and 375g respectively. An

Fig. 1 & 2: A few unmanaged fish ponds of Chug village farmers before scientific intervention

Fig. 3 & 4: Self motivated fish farmers with their newly excavated ponds

Fig. 5: Distribution of fish seeds through Office of DFDO, Bomdila

Fig. 6: Fish seed release on the occasion of Fish Farmers' Day at farmers' ponds

Livelihood support through Fish Farming

Fig. 7: Happy fish farmers of Chug village on receipt of fish seeds

Fig. 8: A fish farmer with fish seeds for release in his pond at Chug village

Fig. 9: Field demonstration at ICAR-NRC on Yak pond premises

Fig. 10: Fish harvest and sell from demonstrating unit of ICAR-NRC on Yak

experimental trial on comparative study on growth performances of carps supplemented with different dietary protein levels resulted into a production of 485 kg/ 600m²/ 8 months @ 35% dietary protein level as compared to 381 kg/ 600m²/ 8 months @ 30% dietary protein level (Baruah *et al*, 2015). The experiment concluded for inclusion of higher range of protein percentage (35%) in fish feeds for higher productivity in colder regime.

Productivity and profitability status

The fish production from each of the pond in Chug village in a decade rose from a negligible level up to 3000-4000 kg/ha/yr, which was sold at

the local market @ Rs. 200-300/kg fish. The village with 58 farm families, and not known for any reasons has now gained much popularity for their endeavor in fish farming in the region. Establishing a fish seed hatchery in the locality and a feed mill for ready availability of critical inputs round the year will reduce much of their effort in fish farming. The success of Chug village has led to adoption of fish farming as a true vocation of livelihood in the recent times in other villages of the district viz., Khellong, Nafra, Saddle, Khoina, Rahung, Tenga, Rupa, Shergaon, Sangti, Khaso etc. The unemployment problem in these regions is growing, not because there is lack of opportunities but

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because the unemployed youth have failed to take advantage of the opportunities available. Therefore, few initiatives like forming Farmers' Clubs, SHGs, organizing regular training and demonstration programmes, OFTs and FLDs, organizing field days, farmers' meets and distribution of critical inputs in agriculture, horticulture, fisheries, animal husbandry and allied subjects has already been taken in these villages alike Chug village and hopefully progress visibility will be achieved in the coming years to come. The perception of species diversification based to altitudinal regime needs much attention today and attempts must be made for the best utilization of the available resources and conserving the environment at the same time.

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REFERENCES

- Census of India (2011). *District Census Handbook*, West Kameng, Arunachal Pradesh, Series 13, Part XII-B, Directorate of Census Operations, Pp. 1-109.
- Baruah D, Das S K, Baruah K K, Ahmed F A and Saikia A (2015). Growth performance of Chinese carps on feeding varying levels of protein under coldwater farming system in Arunachal Pradesh, North-east India. *Indian J Fisheries* **62**(3): 113-117.
- Sharma D, Baruah D and Mahanta P C (2010). Performance of three pronged Chinese carp farming in mid Himalayas of West Kameng district, Arunachal Pradesh. *J Inland Fish Soc India* **42** (2): 48-51

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Mortality Pattern in Crossbred Calves of Dairy Cattle

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted at Cattle Breeding Farm, Nagpur Veterinary College, Nagpur. A record of 64 crossbred calves died during 2000-2015 was used for the study. The period-wise distribution of calf mortality showed that highest mortality rate was recorded in period P1 and the lowest in period P2. Age-wise distribution revealed that calf mortality was highest in 0 to 1 month age group in both sexes and lowest was in 1 to 3 months of age group. Sex-wise it was 19.05 per cent for male calves and 11.00 per cent in female calves. Season-wise distribution showed that the highest calf mortality (40.30%) was found in calves borne during the winter season. The overall mortality rate due to parity of dam was 39.34, 16.67, 33.33 and 31.94 per cent, respectively for first, second, third and fourth calving. The highest mortality in crossbred calves was recorded due to gastroenteritis followed by pneumonia.

Key Words: Causes, Calf mortality, Calving, Mortality rate, Pneumonia.

INTRODUCTION

Calf plays an important role in the development and profitability of a dairy farm, as future of dairy herd solely depends on the successful raising of the young calves. Healthy calves are not only essential for sustenance of dairy farm but also necessary for preserving the good quality germplasm. According to Sreedhar *et al* (2010) high survival rate in a dairy farm helps to increase the selection pressure which is one of the main factors controlling genetic gain and profitable returns. Calf care is not only essential for sustenance of the dairy herd, but also essential in the wake of preserving and maintaining proven germplasm. Tiwari *et al* (2007) noted that the growth performance of calves in rural dairies revealed poor health condition, which indicated lack of awareness among farmers on scientific management. Verma and Thakur (2013) reported that production efficiency traits can be utilized for the selection of future dairy cows for both production and reproduction potential and profitability. Hence

there is a need to study the commercial dairy farms in terms of calf mortality with emphasis on calf management practices being adopted by the dairy farmers.

Mortality among dairy cattle results in financial loss, including the value of the lost cattle, cost of replacement, loss of milk production, and extra labour. Several herd-level risk factors for mortality have been identified, such as herd size, herd management, and milk yield. Mortality patterns in organized dairy herds serve as a useful indicator for assessing the status of herd health and the efficacy of management programs. A rise in mortality among a group of cattle can indicate suboptimal health and welfare. Calf mortality in every dairy and breeding farm results in financial and genetic loss. Therefore, reductions in morbidity and mortality rate are the first and foremost targets of dairy farm management. Identification of factors that are responsible for the death of cattle is an important prerequisite for avoiding excessive mortality.

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Table 1. Calf mortality according to period of the year.

Period	Male			Female			Overall mortality		
	No. of Birth	Total no. of death	Mortality Per cent	No. of Birth	Total no. of death	Mortality Per cent	No. of Birth	Total no. of death	Mortality Per cent
P1	16	11	68.75	23	10	43.48	39	21	53.85
P2	17	4	23.53	17	1	5.88	34	5	14.71
P3	44	18	40.91	32	8	25.00	76	26	34.21
P4	28	6	21.43	28	6	21.43	56	12	21.43
Chi-square value	4.89NS			4.65NS			8.33*		

*Significant at $P < 0.05$; NS= non significant

Therefore, the present study was conducted to investigate the calf mortality with special reference to better management practices in a dairy farm.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Data

The data of present study were collected from the records of Sahiwal x Jersey crossbred cattle herd, maintained at Cattle Breeding Farm, Nagpur

Veterinary college, Nagpur, Maharashtra, covering a period of 16 years from 2000-2015. Information on the date of birth, sex, breed, date of death, parity of dam and causes of death were collected from the farm records at the individual animal level. The collected data were analyzed to study mortality pattern in different age groups.

Data classification

The total period of the calf mortality was divided

Table 2. Calf mortality according to age and sex in crossbred calf.

Age (Month)	Male			Female			Overall mortality		
	No. of Birth	Total no. of death	Mortality Per cent	No. of Birth	Total no. of death	Mortality Per cent	No. of Birth	Total no. of death	Mortality Per cent
0-1	105	20	19.05	100	11	11.00	205	31	15.12
1-3	85	6	7.06	89	4	4.49	174	10	5.75
3-6	79	4	5.06	85	6	7.06	164	10	6.10
6-9	75	9	12.00	79	4	5.06	154	13	8.44
Overall	37.14			25			31.22		
Chi-square value	8.54*			3.19NS			10.64*		

*Significant at $P < 0.05$; NS= non significant

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Table 3. Calf mortality according to season of birth.

Period	Male			Female			Overall mortality		
	No. of Birth	Total no. of death	Mortality Per cent	No. of Birth	Total no. of death	Mortality Per cent	No. of Birth	Total no. of death	Mortality Per cent
Summer	29	5	17.24	24	1	4.17	53	6	11.32
Monsoon	43	15	34.88	42	16	38.10	85	31	36.47
Winter	33	19	57.58	34	8	23.53	67	27	40.30
Chi-square value	5.04NS			6.11*			6.99*		

*Significant at $P < 0.05$; NS= non significant

into four groups (P1=2000 to 2003; P2=2004 to 2007; P3=2008 to 2011; P4=2012 to 2015). The year was divided into three seasons (summer = March-June; monsoon=July-October; winter=November-February). The parity of dam was determined as first (Pty-1), second (Pty-2), third (Pty-3) and fourth onwards (Pty-4). Calf mortality records kept at the farm were used for the study. Number of calves born in this period was 205 of which 64 died (31.22%). The percent of animal disposed from the herd due to different reasons was calculated by proportion

using descriptive statistics.

Table 4. Calf mortality according to season of death.

Season	Number of calves died	Percentage
Summer	6	9.38
Monsoon	31	48.44
Winter	27	42.18
Total	64	100

Table 5. Calf mortality according to parity of dam in crossbred cattle.

Period	Male			Female			Overall mortality		
	No. of Birth	Total no. of death	Mortality Per cent	No. of Birth	Total no. of death	Mortality Per cent	No. of Birth	Total no. of death	Mortality Per cent
Pty-1	33	16	48.48	28	8	28.57	61	24	39.34
Pty-2	21	3	14.29	21	4	19.05	42	7	16.67
Pty-3	16	7	43.75	14	3	21.43	30	10	33.33
Pty-4	35	13	37.14	37	10	27.03	72	23	31.94
Chi-square value	3.49NS			0.47NS			3.41NS		

*Significant at $P < 0.05$; NS= non significant

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mortality rate during different period of the year

The pattern of calf mortality showed that the highest mortality rate (53.85%) was recorded in P1 (2000 to 2003), which included 68.75 and 43.48 per cent in male and female calves respectively, whereas, the lowest (14.71%) was determined in P2 (2004 to 2007), which included 23.53 and 5.88 per cent in male and female calves, respectively (Table1). Mishra *et al* (2015) observed highest mortality rate in P4 and lowest in P2. The lowest percentage of calf mortality in second phase of establishment of herd might be due to small number of population in the dairy herd. The period had significant effect ($P < 0.05$) on the overall mortality rate in calves. Rawal and Tomar (1994) showed significant effect of period on mortality rate in Sahiwal female whereas, Gupta *et al* (2016) found the effect of period on mortality as non significant ($P > 0.05$) in murrha buffaloes. The highest mortality rate in P1 might be a combined effect of season, parity and herd size.

Table 6. Calf mortality rate (%) according to causes of disease.

Cause	Number of calves died	Percentage
Pneumonia	12	18.75
Gastroenteritis	21	32.81
Septicemia	8	12.50
Cold Shock	7	10.94
Hydrocephalus	1	1.55
uremia	2	3.13
Pasturellosis	3	4.69
Other	10	15.63
Total	64	100

Mortality rate according to age and sex

The maximum percentage (15.12%) of calves died at the first month of age observed in the study (Table 2) was in agreement with the findings of Islam *et al* (2005) who found comparatively larger

percentage of calf mortality (84.0% and 35.2% respectively) during first month of age. Mortality was decreased with the increase in age of calves. These results revealed that first 30d are more sensitive for calves rearing and special care and management should be maintained during this period. The overall mortality percentage in 1 to 3m of age group was 5.75 per cent (7.06% in male and 4.49 % in female). Mishra *et al* (2015) in Gir calves reported lower estimates than the present findings. The overall mortality rate in 3 to 6m of age group was 6.10 per cent. The percentages of mortality in male and female calves were calculated to be 5.06 and 7.06 per cent. However, lower estimates than present finding was recorded by Kumar *et al* (2002a) in organized dairy farms of Andhra Pradesh.

The mortality rates from 6 to 12m of age were also calculated and the values were 8.44 per cent (12.00% in male and 5.06% female calves, respectively). Kambaj *et al* (2006) in buffalo calves had reported an overall mortality rate of 14.59 per cent which is higher than that of our present finding. Sex-wise distribution of calf mortality indicates that out of a total 105 male calves, 39 calves (37.14%) died, whereas, out of 100 female calves, a total of 25 calves (25.00%) were reported to be dead. The reason for higher percentage of death in male calves than in females, might be due to want of milk, better care and management practices adopted for raising of females, whereas, male calves might have ignored. In the present study, the overall mortality in cross-bred calves was found to be 31.22 per cent, however, Sreedhar *et al* (2010), Mishra *et al* (2015) found a lower mortality rate (19.5%) in buffaloes and (15.09%) in Gir calves, respectively.

Mortality rate according to season of birth

Season-wise distribution showed that the highest calf mortality rate (40.30%) was determined in those calves born in the winter season (November to February). The percentage of mortality in male calves was recorded as 57.58 per cent whereas, that of female calves was 23.53 per cent during winter season. The lowest (11.32%) percentage

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of mortality was recorded during summer season (March to June). The higher percentage of mortality during winter season was also recorded by Kumar *et al* (2002b) and Mishra *et al* (2015) in Ongole and Gir calves, respectively. The effect of season had significant effect ($P < 0.05$) on the overall mortality and in female calves.

Mortality rate according to season of death

Greater percentage of calves was died in monsoon. Data presented in table 4 showed that out of 64 died calves, 31 were died in monsoon (48.44%), 27 in winter (42.19%) and 6 in summer season (9.38%). Mortality rate was higher during monsoon (48.44%), which revealed that monsoon was most susceptible season to calf disease and mortality. Moist and humid conditions along with heavy rainfall may be suitable for growth and proliferation of disease causal agents. Similar pattern of mortality have been reported by other workers (Islam *et al* (2005). However, Shahi and Kumar (2014), Mishra *et al* (2015) reported higher mortality rate in winter for crossbred and Gir calves respectively.

Mortality rate according to different parity of dam

The overall mortality rate due to parity was found to be 39.34, 16.67, 33.33 and 31.94 per cent in Pty-1, Pty-2, Pty-3 and Pty-4 and onwards parities, respectively (Table 5). Highest mortality (39.34%) was observed in first parity and least (16.67%) mortality was observed in second parity. The highest mortality in first parity was observed by Mishra *et al* (2015) and Gupta *et al* (2016) in Gir calves and Murrah buffalo calves, respectively. The effect of parity on mortality was established to be non-significant ($P > 0.05$) in cross-bred calves. Similar findings were reported by Gupta *et al* (2016) in murrah buffalo calves whereas, Mishra *et al* (2015) reported that the parity of dam had significant effect on the mortality rate in Gir female calves.

Mortality rate according to cause of diseases

The highest mortality in crossbred calves was recorded due to gastroenteritis (32.81%) followed by pneumonia (18.75%), other (15.63%) and septicemia (12.50%). The highest mortality rate in crossbred calves was recorded due to delayed feeding of colostrums to the calves (Table 6). Similar findings were reported by Mishra *et al* (2015), Shrivastava *et al* (2013), Sreedhar and Sreenivas (2015). In our study, pneumonia was found to be the second important cause of calf mortality with 18.75 per cent. Similar findings were observed by Mishra *et al* (2015) in Gir calves. High incidence of mortality due to gastroenteritis in calves might be due to bacterial and/or viral infection or due to delayed feeding of colostrum to the calves.

CONCLUSION

Intensive health care and management is the prerequisite for young calves especially in winter and monsoon season to minimize mortality due to gastroenteritis and pneumonia problems which will facilitate maximizing intensity of selection among calves born out of elite mating. Thus, the availability of male and females with high genetic merit for future production can be increased.

REFERENCES

- Gupta N M, Mehra M L and Malhotra P (2016). Studies on effect of non-genetic parameters on mortality pattern in Murrah buffaloes. *Buffalo bull* **35**(3): 365-370.
- Islam S, Safiqlul A, Reza A, Ayesha A, Nargis K and Mohamad B A (2005). Causes and consequences of calf mortality in a dairy farm of Bangladesh. *J Anim and Vet Adv* **4**(2):260-264.
- Kambaj, M L, Joshi B K, Ghansham S and Shiv P (2006). A study on calf mortality in Nili-Ravi Buffalo calves. *Indian J Dairy Sci* **95**(3):181-184
- Kumar C R, Moorthy P R, Rao K S and Naidu K V (2002a). Calf mortality pattern in relation to age and sex in organized livestock farm in Andhra Pradesh. *Indian J Anim Sci* **72**(10): 921-923.
- Kumar C R, Moorthy P R S and Rao K S (2002b). Effect of birth weight and weaning on calf mortality. *Indian Vet J* **78**:1134-1137.

- Mishra A K, Rawat N S, Nanawati S and Gaur A K (2015). Studies on the calf mortality pattern in Gir breed. *Int J Livestock Pro* **6**(4):47-51.
- Rawal S C and Tomar S S (1994). Inherited variations in mortality and culling rates in Sahiwal female calves up to maturity. *Indian J Anim Sci* **64**(11):1286-1287.
- Shahi B N and Kumar D (2014). Studies on mortality and culling rate among female calves of Sahiwal and Jersey crossbred cattle. *Indian J Vet and Anim Res* **43**(6):454-457.
- Shrivastava M, Nanavati S, Yadav D S and Mishra A K(2013). Studies on incidences and causes of buffalo calf mortality in Malwa region of Madhya Pradesh. *Int J Agri Sci and Vet Med* **1**(2):69-72.
- Sreedhar S and Sreenivas D (2015).A study on calf mortality and managerial practices in commercial dairy farms. *Livestock Res Int* **3**(4):94-98.
- Sreedhar S, Ranganadham M and Madan Mohan E (2010). Calf mortality in indigenous Buffaloes. *Indian Vet J* **87**:197-198.
- Tiwari R, Sharma M C and Singh B P (2007). Buffalo health care in commercial dairy farms: A field study in Uttar Pradesh (India). *Livestock Res Rural Dev* **19**(3):62-64.
- Verma N and Thakur Y P (2013). Effect of genetic and non-genetic factors on production efficiency traits of Red Sindhi x Jersey crossbred cows maintained under sub temperate Indian conditions. *Livestock Res Int***1**(2):58-60.

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Nutrient Requirement of Papaya (*Carica papaya* L.) for Yield Optimization and Commercial Cultivation Under Kerala Conditions

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ABSTRACT

Papaya has gained commercial importance over the years because of its varied uses, mainly for table purpose. One of the reasons for low production in papaya is inadequate nourishment. As the export of papaya from India is rapidly increasing, there is a pressing need to enhance its productivity and improve the fruit quality. The present experiment was undertaken to study the response of major plant nutrients viz., nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium on growth, yield and quality of papaya and also to find out the optimum dose of NPK for commercial cultivation of papaya under Kerala conditions. The trial was conducted in confounded factorial randomized block design. Different levels of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium (200, 250 and 300) gram per plant per year were tried in six equal splits. Results revealed that application of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium at the rate of 250:250:500g per plant per year in six equal splits, at two months interval was economically viable and improved the growth, yield and quality of papaya.

Key Words: Papaya, Nitrogen, Phosphorus, Potassium, Yield.

INTRODUCTION

Papaya (*Carica papaya* L.) has gained commercial importance over the years because of its varied uses. In Kerala it is grown in an area of 16,640 ha with an annual production of 1,03,420t and with average productivity of 6.2t/ha (FIB, 2016). The major production constraint encountered in papaya is difficulty in maximizing yield with in unit time. Balanced nutrition plays a vital role on plant growth, yield and fruit quality. Papaya is very responsive to the application of inorganic fertilizers along with organic manures. One of the reasons for low production in papaya is inadequate nourishment. Understanding the interrelationships among vegetative growth, yield and nutrient uptake will help to exploit the high yielding potential of papaya plants. As the export of papaya from India is rapidly increasing, there is a pressing need to enhance its productivity and improve the fruit quality. However under Kerala conditions, no systematic attempts have been made on the requirement of nutrition of papaya. The

experiment was carried out to study the response of balanced nutrition on yield and yield attributes of papaya and also to find out the optimum dose of NPK for commercial cultivation of papaya under Kerala conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out at College of Agriculture, Vellayani, using papaya variety CO-2. The experiment was conducted in confounded factorial randomized block design. Three different levels of nitrogen (200 (n₀), 250 (n₁), 300 (n₂) gram per plant per year), phosphorus (200 (p₀), 250 (p₁), 300 (p₂) gram per plant per year) and potassium (300 (k₀), 400 (k₁), 500 (k₂) gram per plant per year) were applied to papaya plants in six equal split doses at two months interval. Two month old seedlings were used for transplanting. Fertilizer application started thirty days after transplantation of seedlings to the main field. Urea, rock phosphate and muriate of potash were used as sources of Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Potassium.

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Table 1. Influence of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium on biometric characters of papaya

Treatment	Plant height (6MAP) (cm)	Plant height (12MAP) (cm)	Leaf number (6MAP)	Leaf number (12MAP)	Time for first flowering (days)	Time for harvest (days)
T1 (n0p0k0)	82.2	236.9	17.4	30.3	208.9	239.5
T2 (n0p0k1)	86.0	242.8	14.0	25.9	172.9	226.7
T3 (n0p0k2)	163.9	267.8	23.5	37.6	204.6	252.1
T4 (n0p1k0)	93.2	227.1	12.6	22.1	151.2	254.6
T5 (n0p1k1)	105.6	207.5	17.9	28.9	137.5	231.8
T6 (n0p1k2)	161.6	266.8	19.3	33.3	208.4	260.3
T7 (n0p2k0)	153.4	231.6	12.2	27.4	163.3	253.7
T8 (n0p2k1)	105.5	240.1	15.9	29.3	194.4	241.3
T9 (n0p2k2)	198.8	291.1	19.8	32.6	154.8	246.4
T10 (n1p0k0)	145.3	262.6	13.2	27.2	147.3	252.6
T11 (n1p0k1)	129.8	210.6	19.2	31.6	185.7	257.6
T12 (n1p0k2)	180.5	273.9	20.8	28.1	127.6	231.5
T13 (n1p1k0)	190.9	265.7	15.4	24.8	197.1	259.6
T14 (n1p1k1)	132.8	235.4	17.9	30.5	146.7	234.9
T15 (n1p1k2)	147.6	280.6	14.9	34.1	119.5	211.8
T16 (n1p2k0)	122.4	248.8	22.2	30.7	169.0	250.1
T17 (n1p2k1)	163.6	279.5	14.9	26.4	153.9	233.3
T18 (n1p2k2)	175.2	197.1	21.4	35.7	121.9	224.0
T19 (n2p0k0)	129.9	250.6	15.6	37.5	219.6	253.1
T20 (n2p0k1)	106.2	254.2	17.4	30.5	163.2	233.7
T21 (n2p0k2)	139.4	246.7	24.4	37.1	141.3	241.9
T22 (n2p1k0)	150.4	282.4	16.1	28.5	212.8	249.0
T23 (n2p1k1)	120.3	230.4	12.5	24.7	172.6	256.7
T24 (n2p1k2)	162.9	261.4	25.6	40.0	149.5	239.4
T25 (n2p2k0)	153.7	268.2	20.4	28.7	139.7	222.2
T26 (n2p2k1)	134.1	258.4	17.2	31.8	216.7	241.2
T27 (n2p2k2)	133.1	262.8	19.5	38.5	153.8	250.9
T28Control	69.8	163.2	11.2	21.7	224.3	266.5
SE	3.2	3.5	0.3	0.6	2.7	1.8
CD (0.05)	6.6	7.3	0.7	1.3	5.7	3.7

MAP- Months after planting

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The treatments involved 27 different combinations of Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Potassium at different levels, their interactions and control. Biometric characters like height of plants, girth of plants, number of leaves, time of first flowering and time of harvest were noted. Yield characters like number of fruits per plant, fruit weight, fruit length and girth, fruit volume, pulp percentage, total yield per

Table 2. Influence of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium on yield characters of papaya.

Treatment	Number of fruits per plant	Total fruit yield per plant (kg)	Papain yield (Kg/ha)	Fruit length (cm)	Fruit girth (cm)	Fruit weight (g)	Benefit: cost ratio
T1 (n0p0k0)	29.3	32.3	356.8	25.9	40.6	1163.7	2.1
T2 (n0p0k1)	21.3	19.8	415.9	21.9	38.1	959.2	1.8
T3 (n0p0k2)	16.8	22.5	397.6	26.7	42.9	1207.3	1.4
T4 (n0p1k0)	30.6	35.6	251.9	24.9	37.0	835.1	2.4
T5 (n0p1k1)	20.9	17.4	264.9	25.9	34.4	855.9	1.3
T6 (n0p1k2)	26.2	28.2	392.5	25.4	42.5	999.2	1.8
T7 (n0p2k0)	21.3	27.1	300.6	25.3	26.4	866.8	1.7
T8 (n0p2k1)	28.05	17.8	323.6	20.2	34.1	708.3	1.1
T9 (n0p2k2)	17.7	23.5	266.2	27.9	42.1	920.5	1.4
T10 (n1p0k0)	24.1	24.5	318.9	21.6	24.3	895.8	1.6
T11 (n1p0k1)	15.9	37.1	314.3	25.3	41.5	1246.7	2.3
T12 (n1p0k2)	35.0	27.7	605.6	23.7	36.9	899.5	1.8
T13 (n1p1k0)	26.1	19.2	323.5	22.7	33.8	1116.9	1.2
T14 (n1p1k1)	19.5	26.4	377.8	24.9	36.4	1018.8	1.6
T15 (n1p1k2)	43.6	59.8	674.6	32.9	42.3	1338.7	3.6
T16 (n1p2k0)	36.0	28.8	541.7	22.4	27.6	453.7	1.7
T17 (n1p2k1)	24.5	31.9	420.7	25.1	26.1	1238.2	1.9
T18 (n1p2k2)	32.2	20.6	569.0	23.4	29.4	927.5	1.2
T19 (n2p0k0)	20.0	32.6	390.10	22.8	35.3	1190.8	2.0
T20 (n2p0k1)	15.6	22.8	258.9	22.4	38.9	1152.5	1.4
T21 (n2p0k2)	28.7	27.5	268.7	20.9	32.8	719.5	1.6
T22 (n2p1k0)	24.2	21.8	346.2	23.9	35.4	936.2	1.3
T23 (n2p1k1)	29.5	39.1	272.9	24.3	27.4	854.7	2.3
T24 (n2p1k2)	24.7	36.2	339.9	23.6	35.3	849.1	2.2
T25 (n2p2k0)	30.8	27.7	402.4	27.6	30.9	911.6	1.7
T26 (n2p2k1)	34.5	35.4	276.4	22.1	29.4	658.2	2.1
T27 (n2p2k2)	26.7	27.7	347.3	26.6	42.1	1171.4	1.6
T28 Control	11.2	5.9	58.7	16.1	23.5	395.6	0.5
SE	1.4	1.7	21.7	2.	2.71	23.1	
CD (0.05)	2.9	3.4	45.1	NS	5.6	47.9	

plant and papain yield were recorded. Fruit quality characters were also recorded during the study. Benefit: Cost ratio was worked out. Shelf life of fruits was noted. Soil samples from the experimental area were analyzed before and after experiment for available nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium. Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Potassium content of leaf petioles were also assessed. Tissue samples were collected from recently matured petiole.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

NPK interaction had significant influence on plant height at all stages of growth. N0p2k2 gave maximum plant height in papaya (Table 1). The result of the present study was in conformity with the observations of Auxilia *et al* (2008) who observed that in papaya, lower dose of nitrogen combined with higher dose of phosphorus and potassium showed synergistic effect, thus resulting in increased height of plants. Potassium probably stimulated the efficiency of nitrogen utilization in respect of growth. Also it was seen that n2p1k2 resulted in maximum number of leaves. Lowest duration of flowering and harvesting was observed with nop1k1 while control plants registered maximum number of days for harvest.

N1p1k2 had increased the number of fruits/plant by way of mean effect as well as interaction effect of nutrients (Table 2). This result was in conformity with the findings of Cruz *et al* (2004) who observed that in papaya application of 500g potassium gave significantly more number of fruits/plant. Similar result was also reported by Garcia *et al* (2003) that in papaya variety Ranchi maximum number of fruits were obtained by applying nitrogen 200g, phosphorus 300g and potassium 500g per plant.

Maximum fruit girth was obtained from n0p0k2. Similar results were observed with fruit weight and papain yield. The possible explanation for higher yield in treatment n1p1k2 could be a favourable combination of NPK which provided better vigour to the plants. There is a close relationship between vigour of plant and yield. Canesin and Correa

(2006) also reported that in papaya application of potash increased yield significantly. Highest benefit: cost ratio (3.55) was obtained from the combination of n1p1k2.

Nitrogen and phosphorus application had no significant influence on TSS content of fruits. This finding is in conformity with the observations of Akinyemi and Akanda (2008) and Kumar and Gho (2003) who observed that in papaya, TSS was not affected by different levels of nitrogen. But potassium application had significant influence on TSS content of fruits. Highest dose of potassium (500 g/plant/year) gave highest TSS content of fruits. Highest carotenoid content was reported by the application of n0p2k2. The results from the experiment showed that nitrogen and phosphorus application had no significant influence on ascorbic acid content. While application of highest dose of potassium (500g/plant/year) resulted in highest ascorbic acid content in fruits. Highest total sugar and reducing sugar was obtained with application of n0p2k2. In the studies it was also observed that highest shelf life of fruits was obtained from combined application of n2p0k0.

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that application of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium increased plant height and number of leaves. Plants receiving a dose of nitrogen at 250 g, 300 g phosphorus and 500g potassium per plant took the shortest time for flowering. Combined application of nitrogen at 250 g/plant, phosphorus at 250 g/plant and potassium at 500g/plant considerably shortened the time for harvesting the first fruit increased fruit weight, number of fruits per plant, yield per plant and papain yield. Levels of nitrogen and phosphorus had no significant influence on TSS and ascorbic acid content of fruits. Nitrogen at 200g, phosphorus at 250 g and potassium at 500g/plant was found to increase the shelf life of fruits. The overall assessment of the effect of major plant nutrients on papaya indicated that the application of nitrogen,

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Table 3. Influence of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium on fruit quality characters of papaya.

Treatment	TSS (per cent)	Acidity (per cent)	Total carotenoids (mg 100g ⁻¹)	Ascorbic acid (mg 100g ⁻¹)	Total sugars (per cent)	Reducing sugars (percent)	Non reducing sugars (per cent)	Shelf life (days)
T1 (n0p0k0)	11.6	0.1	2.2	41.9	12.3	10.4	1.9	5.2
T2 (n0p0k1)	10.6	0.3	2.6	38.9	10.6	8.6	2.0	6.9
T3 (n0p0k2)	13.8	0.2	1.5	42.8	14.6	11.7	2.8	4.1
T4 (n0p1k0)	10.8	0.2	2.1	40.4	8.7	7.2	1.5	5.4
T5 (n0p1k1)	10.8	0.2	2.3	40.6	9.7	7.3	2.4	6.1
T6 (n0p1k2)	14.4	0.2	2.54	42.3	14.3	12.7	1.6	6.3
T7 (n0p2k0)	13.9	0.3	1.3	43.8	10.9	8.8	2.0	4.1
T8 (n0p2k1)	12.4	0.1	2.3	39.4	11.4	9.5	1.9	5.3
T9 (n0p2k2)	16.7	0.1	3.7	51.7	15.4	13.9	1.6	7.2
T10 (n1p0k0)	14.8	0.2	1.8	47.6	12.7	9.7	2.9	4.0
T11 (n1p0k1)	11.7	0.3	2.9	41.8	8.2	5.1	3.2	6.8
T12 (n1p0k2)	12.0	0.4	1.6	44.5	13.0	12.1	1.6	5.6
T13 (n1p1k0)	12.7	0.2	1.8	36.7	12.1	10.9	1.3	4.7
T14 (n1p1k1)	10.8	0.2	1.6	43.4	7.7	6.4	1.3	3.4
T15 (n1p1k2)	14.9	0.3	3.1	42.9	11.0	9.2	1.8	7.0
T16 (n1p2k0)	12.6	0.3	1.6	44.9	8.5	6.5	2.0	3.7
T17 (n1p2k1)	12.4	0.2	2.0	39.2	11.2	9.5	1.9	6.5
T18 (n1p2k2)	10.0	0.3	2.4	48.9	12.8	10.1	2.8	4.1
T19 (n2p0k0)	12.2	0.3	2.4	48.9	8.3	7.0	1.3	7.3
T20 (n2p0k1)	10.0	0.2	2.3	44.6	11.2	9.1	2.2	4.0
T21 (n2p0k2)	15.2	0.2	2.6	41.3	12.7	10.2	2.5	5.2
T22 (n2p1k0)	11.4	0.1	2.2	41.2	10.5	8.3	2.1	6.7
T23 (n2p1k1)	12.5	0.3	2.6	47.4	9.9	7.5	2.3	3.9
T24 (n2p1k2)	11.5	0.1	1.6	41.2	13.3	12.1	1.3	5.7
T25 (n2p2k0)	12.3	0.15	2.5	45.9	9.6	8.4	1.2	4.2
T26 (n2p2k1)	9.9	0.2	2.1	39.3	8.6	6.4	2.3	6.3
T27 (n2p2k2)	13.0	0.2	1.9	47.2	13.5	11.7	1.8	4.9
T28 Control	7.5	0.4	0.8	31.8	5.6	4.4	1.3	3.2
SE	1.0	0.1	0.3	2.5	0.2	0.4	0.3	0.1
CD (0.05)	NS	0.08	0.7	NS	0.5	0.2	NS	0.2

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phosphorus and potassium at the rate of 250 : 250 : 500 g/ plant/ year in six equal splits at two months interval was economically viable and improved growth, yield and quality of papaya under Kerala conditions.

REFERENCES

- Akinyemi S and Akanda M O (2008). Effect of organic and inorganic fertilizers on growth and yield of pawpaw (*Carica papaya* L.) *Interciencia* **29**: 274-270.
- Auxilia J, Balamohan TN and Nalina L (2008). *Standardisation of stage wise nutrient requirement of papaya*. Second International symposium of papaya p.99.
- Bertuzzi S M and Rodreguez V A (2006). Response of pawpaw to application of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium on a sandy soil in north western Corrientes *Horticultura Argentina* **15**: 65-66.
- Canesin R C F and Correa (2006) The use of manure associated with mineral fertilization of papaya seedling production. *Bras Fruitic* **28**:483-486.
- Cruz J L, Coelho and Santos M T (2004). Growth, dry matter and carbon partitioning papaya in response to nitrogen nutrition. *Bragantia* **63**: 351-361.
- FIB (2016). *Farm Guide*. Farm Information Bureau, Government of Kerala, Thiruvananthapuram, p 451.
- Garcia E J L, Sanchez G and Soto Hernandez (2003). Mineral and foliar fertilization on development and production of papaya cv Maradol. *Terra* **21**:161-167.
- Kumar K and Gho K M (2003). Nitrogen release from crop residues and organic amendments as affected by biochemical composition. *Commun Soil Sci Pl Anal* **34**: 2441-60.

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Obstacles in Practicing Organic Farming in Nyoma, Changthang Region in Ladakh

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ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted in the tehsil Nyoma of Ladakh, Jammu and Kashmir state during the year 2015 to know the obstacles faced by farmers practicing organic farming. The findings showed that major obstacles faced by the farmers were, unavailability of organic farming literature, inadequate availability of inputs like vermicompost, biofertilizers and organic manures, non availability of skilled labourer, lack of market information and market access, lack of minimum support price for the organic products, lack of skill about improved methods of compost making, inadequate knowledge of field functionaries about organic farming, non availability of recommended package of practice and laborious process involved in application of organic practices, lack of proper training about organic farming, difficulties in getting the organic manures compared to the chemical fertilizers, scarcity of FYM and other organic manures. The average FYM available was 5.2q which was maximum in Nidder village and the average minimum FYM available was 2.8q for Nyoma village. On the other hand, average FYM required for Nidder village was 8.1q and 5.0q for Nyoma. The average chemical fertilizer used was 36q. A maximum average chemical fertilizer used was in Nyoma village (42.25q) and minimum used in Nidder village(30.79q). Maximum pesticides used were in Mudh village followed by Henle and negligible in rest of the villages.

Key Words: Organic farming, Vermi-compost, Chemical fertilizers, Manure, Vermicompost.

INTRODUCTION

The relevance and need for an eco-friendly alternative farming system arose from the ill effects of the chemical farming practices adopted worldwide during the second half of the last century. People began to think of various alternative farming systems based on the protection of environment which in turn would increase the welfare of the humankind by various ways like clean and healthy foods, an ecology which is conducive to the survival of all the living and non-living things, low use of the non-renewable energy sources, etc. Organic farming is considered to be the best among all of them because of its scientific approach and wider acceptance all over the world.

Organic agriculture sustains the health of soils, ecosystems and people. It relies on ecological processes, bio-diversity and cycles adapted to local conditions, rather than the use of inputs with adverse effects. Organic agriculture combines tradition, innovation and science to benefit the shared environment and promote fair relationships and a good quality for all involved. According to Gill and Prasad (2009), organic farming aims at the minimizing cost of production, healthy food, augmentation of profit, improving soil health, counteract the climate change, minimize energy consumption and encourage natural habitats. According to Gill (2014), there was an urgent need to do follow the natural farming or zero budget

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farming by making use of the resources available at the farm itself. The use of bio-fertilizers, bio-dynamics formulations, recycling of crop residue, crop rotation, application of green manuring, farm yard manure, extracts of herbs, following bhumi sanskar, beej sanskar, use of bio agents not only would reduce the cost of production but simultaneously make the ecosystem more vibrant by making a choice of the various plantation crops based farming system.

Ayala (2001) was of the view that almost all benefits of high yielding varieties based farming accrue mostly in the short term and in the long term cause adverse effects. There is an urgent

need for a corrective action. The authors ruled out organic farming based on the absolute exclusion of fertilizers and chemicals, not only for the present, but also in the foreseeable future. There ought to be an appropriate blend of conventional farming system and its alternatives. The average yields under organic and conventional practices are almost the same and the declining yield rate over time is slightly lower in organic farming. The authors also quote a US aggregate economic model, which shows substantial decreased in yields on the widespread adoption of organic farming. Decreased aggregate outputs, increased farm income and increased consumer prices are other results the model gives.

Table 1. Obstacles expressed by farmers practicing organic (N=120)

Sr .No.	Constraint	Number of farmers		
		Frequency	Per cent	Rank
1.	Unavailability of organic farming literature in the village.	119	99.16	I
2.	Inadequate availability of inputs like vermicompost, biofertilizers and organic manures.	118	98.33	II
3.	Non availability of skilled labourer.	117	97.50	III
4.	Lack of market information and market access.	116	97.00	IV
5.	Lack of minimum support price for the organic products.	115	95.83	V
6.	Inadequate knowledge of field functionaries about organic farming	106	88.33	VI
7.	Non availability of recommended package of practice and laborious process involved in application of organic practices.	105	87.5	VII
8.	Farmers are not sure whether all the nutrients with the required quantities can be made available by the organic materials.	104	87.00	VIII
9.	Lack of proper training about organic farming	102	85.00	IX
10.	Difficulties in getting the organic manures compared to the chemical fertilizers.	98	82.00	X
11.	Lack of skill about improved methods of compost making	98	82.00	XI
12.	Insufficient training.	97	81.00	XII
13.	Scarcity of FYM and other organic manures.	95	79.16	XIII

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Table 2. FYM available, required and deficit at farmers' level. (N=24 in each village)

Sr . No.	Village	FYM available (in q)	FYM req (in q)	Deficit (Percentage)
1.	Nyoma	2.8±0.3 (1.0-7.0)	5.0±0.3 (2.0-9.0)	64
2.	Mudh	3.9±0.4 (1.0-10.0)	6.6±0.6 (2.0-15.0)	40
3.	Nidder	5.2±0.6 (1.0-11.0)	8.1±0.6 (3.0-14.0)	36
4.	Henley	3.3±0.2 (1.0-8.0)	5.8±0.2 (3.0-8.0)	43
5.	Chumathang	3.4±0.2 (2.0-6.0)	5.9±0.2 (4.0-7.0)	42
	Total	3.7±0.1 (1.0-11.0)	6.3±0.2 (2.0-15.0)	41

While the details about this US analysis are not known, its relevance to India where we already have the lowest yields of a number of crops under the conventional system appears to be open.

The present fertilizer consumption in J&K is 38.3 kg/ha as compared to 170 kg/ha in Punjab Chandra (2014). In contrast the estimated quantity of nutrients mined by crops in Kashmir is 48 kg/ha. Thus, there are better options for boosting organic production in J&K especially in the horticultural products, floriculture ,honey, basmati rice, aromatic and medicinal plants and have varied agro-climatic zones. The tehsil Nyoma is known for its excellence in animal husbandry thus makes more scope for farmers to go for organic farming. However, there are various obstacles being faced by the farmers of this region and all those have been delineated in this research paper.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out in tehsil Nyoma , Changthang ladakh at high altitude (4500m above sea level) in Jammu and Kashmir during the year 2015. Five villages in tehsil Nyoma namely Nyoma, Mudh, Nidder, chumathang and Henle were selected for investigation. Twenty four respondents were selected from each village, thus making a total of 120 respondents for the investigation. Data were collected through structured and pre-tested interview schedule. The collected data were coded, tabulated and analyzed and the results were interpreted accordingly.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Obstacles expressed by the farmers practicing organic farming

Results (Table 1) revealed that majority of respondents (99.2%) expressed problem of unavailability of organic farming literature in the village and was ranked at number 1 followed by inadequate availability of inputs like vermicompost, biofertilizers and organic manures (98.3%), non availability of skilled labours(97.5%), lack of market information & market access (97.0%), lack of minimum support prize for the organic products (95.8%) of the respondents.

It was obvious (Table 2) that the average quantity of farm yard manure (FYM) available was 3.7q while the required quantity was 6.3q, thus, there was a deficiency of 41.0 per cent. Maximum quantity of FYM (5.2q) was available in Nidder village and minimum (2.8q) in Nyoma village. However , the required quantity for Nidder village was 8.1q and for Nyoma village (5.0q) . Hence, there is need for more quantity of FYM in these villages to meet the agriculture demand of the farmers.

On the other hand, average chemical fertilizer used was 42.3q in Nyoma, 36.1q in Mudh, 30.8q in Nidder, 36.5q and in Henley it was 34.5q in Chumathang village. It was evident that maximum chemical fertilizers used was in Nyoma village and minimum Nidder village.

Table 3. Use of pesticides in different villages.

Sr . No.	Village	Use of pesticides	Organic control
1.	Nyoma	-	+
2.	Mudh	++	+
3.	Nidder	-	++
4.	Henley	+	+
5.	Chumathang	-	+

Where “-” indicates not used, “+” indicates slightly used and “++” indicates used by most.

It was obvious from the above table that out of five villages selected for the present study, maximum pesticides used by Mudh village followed by Henle and negligible in rest of the villages.

CONCLUSION

There is need to standardize the practices on participating basis and evolve package of practices related to organic farming. In order to motivate farmers to take up organic farming provision has to be made profitable by providing minimum support price for organic produce by the government. Tehsil Nyoma department of agriculture and other

institutions should give more stress on imparting training programmes to improve the skill of farmers, motivate the farmers to take up organic farming in future and efforts need to be taken towards minimum use of inorganic fertilizers, use of pesticides/insecticides, conserving natural resources, using indigenous knowledge and improving status of farmers through organic farming. Stress has to be given minimum use of inorganic fertilizers, minimum use of pesticides/insecticides.

REFERENCES

- Chandra Ratna (2014). Sustainability through Organic Agro-Biotechnology with special reference to Jammu & Kashmir scenario. *Int J Gen Eng and Biotech* **5** :169-178.
- Gill M S (2014). Organic farming based farming system and its role towards sustainability. *J Krishi Vigyan* **3**(1) : 54-57
- Gill M S and Prashad Kamta (2009). *Organic Agriculture – Concept, Status and strategies in Indian Perspective*. Compendium on Advances in Organic farming, project Directorate for Farming System Research, ICAR, Modipuram : pp 1-7.
- Sankaram Ayala, (2001). Organic Farming: Eco-Technological Focus for Stability and Sustainability, *Indian Farming* (June issue) :7-11.

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Performance of Different Coriander Varieties for Seed Yield

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ABSTRACT

The present investigation entitled “Performance of different coriander varieties for seed yield” was carried out during rabi season of the year 2013 at the College of Horticulture, Akola. The study consisted of eight coriander varieties using randomized block design and each treatment was replicated thrice. The varieties viz., Hissar Sugandh, Pant Haritima, Sadhana, Swati, CO 4, Hissar Anand, CO 2 and Rajendra Swathi were studied under investigation. The results revealed that variety Pant Haritima was found superior in seed yield (13.33 q/ha) but required more number of days for seed harvesting (131d). The yield contributing parameters like days required for seed harvesting, plant height; leaf area (73.9), number of umbels (20.5), number of umbellate (5.7), number of seed (30.4) and test weight (12.23 g) were observed with maximum numerical values in variety Pant Haritima, than rest of the varieties under study. Amongst the eight coriander varieties, Pant Haritima performed better in almost all the characters. Hence, this variety can be included in further breeding programme for improving the seed yield.

Key Words: Coriander, Pant Haritima, Seed, Yield, Varieties

INTRODUCTION

Coriander (*Coriandrum sativum* L.) is an important seed spices crop of family Apiaceae (Umbelliferae). The area, production and productivity of coriander during 2013 to 2014 in India were 447 thousand ha, 314 thousand mt and 0.7 MT per ha respectively, (Anonymous, 2014). In India it is mainly grown in Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh and Tamilnadu. India rank first in terms of area and production in the world (Datta *et al*, 2006). The productivity of coriander seed is about 1145.86 kg/ha only. The low seed yield in coriander is because it is mainly grown on marginal lands with poor management of soil fertility, irrigation, fertilizers, pests and the disease. Since improved varieties are not available the farmers are forced to use local material for sowing, which are variable in productivity and susceptible to various diseases.

For the improvement of seed yield in coriander, it is necessary to gather the information regarding the association of various quantitatively inherited characters with seed yield. Therefore, the present investigation was carried out with the objectives of to study the performance of different coriander varieties for seed yield and to find out suitable variety for seed yield.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present investigation was carried out at College of Horticulture, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola during rabi season 2013-2014. The experimental material (different varieties of coriander) was procured and collected from different sources (Table 1). The experiment was laid out in randomized block design with eight treatments and three replications. The soil of experimental site was medium black with clay

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soil, well levelled and uniform in topography with appropriate drainage. Land was ploughed once by soil turning plough and thrice with desi plough followed by planking to obtain fine tilth of soil. Well rotten farm yard manure was applied @ 20 t/ha. Neem cake @ 2t/ha was incorporated in the soil during the last ploughing as a preventive measure against termites and other soil insects.

A raised bed was prepared of plot size 1.8m x 2m. The seeds of different varieties were sown bed on 17th of December 2013, before sowing the seeds were pre-treated with thirum @ 2 g/kg seeds, treated seeds were sown apart 30cm between rows and 10cm between plants. The recommended dose of fertilizer 20:30:20 N:P:K kg/ha were applied at the time of field preparation. Full dose of phosphorus, potash and one third of nitrogen were applied at the time of sowing of seeds. Remaining two third dose of nitrogen was top dressed in two equal splits at 30-35 days interval. The growth, flowering and seed yield observation were recorded on five randomly selected plants in each plot. The data of various observations were subjected to statistical analysis as method suggested by Panse and Sukhatme (1957).

Table 1. Different coriander varieties and their sources.

Sr. No	Variety	Source
1	Hissar Sughand	CCS HAU, Hisar
2	Pant Haritima	GBPANT (GBPANT)
3	Sadhana	RRC-Lam (APAU),-Gunter
4	Swati	RRC-Lam (APAU),-Gunter
5	CO-4	Coimbatore (TNAU)
6	Hissar Anand	CCS HAU, Hisar
7	CO-2	Coimbatore (TNAU)
8	Rajendra Swathi	RRC. (RAU) Dolia, Bihar

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Growth attributes

There was significant difference among coriander varieties in plant height all the growth stages (Table1). At 30th DAS, variety CO 4 was found to be the tall variety (11cm), followed by Sadhana (10.4cm) which was statistically at par with variety Rajendra Swathi (10.3cm). The variety Hissar Anand was found to be the dwarf variety (6.9cm). At 60th DAS the variety Sadhana was found to be the tall variety (36.5cm), followed by CO 4 (34.6cm), Rajendra Swathi (32.8 cm). The variety Swati was found to be the dwarf variety (22.5cm). At 90th DAS, the variety Sadhana was found to be the tall variety (73.9cm), which was statistically at par with the variety Pant Haritima (73.5 cm), CO 2 (72.9cm), Swati (70.7cm), and variety Rajendra Swathi was recorded the dwarf variety (62.9cm). These differences in plant height among the varieties might be due to the genetic makeup of the plant and its expression to the growing soil and environmental conditions. The variation in plant growth of different coriander varieties were also observed by Carrubba *et al* (2002) in coriander, Kalidasu *et al* (2008) in Sadhana variety of coriander, Verma *et al* (2014) in coriander, Meena *et al* (2014) in Pant Haritima variety of coriander, which confirms the results of present investigation.

The average number of primary branches over all the eight varieties was (5.8). The maximum (7.7) number of primary branches was recorded in variety Hissar Anand, which was statistically at par with the variety Pant Haritima (7.4) whereas, the variety Swati produced less number of primary branches (4.8). The significant difference in early stages of growth was observed, as during germination and growth initiation process, the varieties might not have expressed their genetic potential. The findings of Moniruzzaman *et al* (2013) in CS004 variety of coriander, Verma *et al* (2014) in coriander, Meena *et al* (2014) in Pant Haritima variety of coriander, supports the results of present findings. The average

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number of secondary branches over all the eight varieties was found to be 15.3. The maximum (24.0) number of secondary branches were recorded in variety Hissar Anand, which was statistically at par with the variety Pant Haritima (23.5). Variety Swati was found to produce less number of secondary branches (8.3).

Regarding the character leaf area (cm²) for all the eight varieties a range of 11.7 to 21.8 cm² was observed. The average leaf area cm² over all the eight varieties was found to be (17.5 cm²). The leaf area was found maximum (21.8 cm²) in Hissar Anand, which was statistically at par with the variety Pant Haritima (21.6 cm²) and Hissar Sugandha (20.9 cm²). The variety Swati was found to produce less leaf area (11.7 cm²). These variations in leaf area among various varieties of coriander might be attributed to their inherent characters. Maximum leaf area might be helpful for more photosynthesis and making food for better yield potential character of plant growth and produce maximum yield. Similar results were obtained by Meena *et al* (2014) in coriander, which supported the present findings.

Flowering attributes

The data in respect of days required to 50 per cent flowering in coriander as influenced by different varieties are presented in table 2. The character, days to 50 per cent flowering for all the eight varieties ranged between 40.3d to 64d with the average of (53.3d) for 50 per cent flowering. The variety Sadhana required minimum (40.3d) 50 per cent flowering and the variety Hissar Anand required maximum (64d) to 50 per cent flowering, The genotypes Swati (42.7d), CO 2 (51d), CO 4 (52d), Rajendra Swathi (53 d) and Pant Haritima (61d), Hissar Sugandha (63.3d) which was numerically decreased over the variety Hissar Anand.

The significant differences among varieties were observed for number of umbel per plant. The maximum (20.5) numbers of umbel per plant were observed in variety Pant Haritima and the minimum (16.3) number of umbel per plant was observed in Swati. The varieties Hissar Sugandha (19.2), CO 2 (18.2), Hissar Anand (17.2), Sadhana (16.5), Rajendra Swathi (16.8), CO 4 (16.6), which was numerically increased over Swati. The number

Table 2. Performance of different coriander varieties in respect of growth attributes.

Sr. No.	Variety	Plant height (cm)			Number of primary branches	Number of secondary branches	Leaf area in (cm ²)
		30 DAS	60 DAS	90 DAS			
T1	Hissar Sugandh	8.0	23.8	64.1	6.7	17.9	20.9
T2	Pant Haritima	7.3	25.6	73.5	7.4	23.5	21.6
T3	Sadhana	10.4	36.5	73.9	4.9	14.9	14.0
T4	Swati	6.9	23.9	70.7	4.8	8.3	11.7
T5	CO-4	11.0	34.6	64.7	5.5	13.5	16.3
T6	Hissar Anand	7.9	22.5	65.1	7.7	24.0	21.8
T7	CO-2	8.9	28.8	72.9	5.4	10.9	14.8
T8	Rajendra Swathi	10.3	32.8	62.9	5.0	9.0	18.6
SE(m)+		0.083	0.225	1.520	0.23	0.30	0.749
CD at 5%		0.252	0.680	4.589	0.69	0.91	2.254

Table 3. Performance of different coriander varieties in respect of flowering attributes.

Sr. No.	Variety	Days to 50 per cent flowering	Number of umbel per plant	Number of umbellet per umbel
T1	Hissar Sugandh	62.7	19.2	4.5
T2	Pant Haritima	61.0	20.5	5.7
T3	Sadhana	40.3	16.5	4.7
T4	Swati	42.7	16.3	4.4
T5	CO 4	52.0	16.6	5.3
T6	Hissar Anand	64.0	17.2	5.5
T7	CO 2	51.0	18.2	4.3
T8	Rajendra Swathi	53.0	16.8	4.3
SE (m) +		0.295	0.46	0.179
CD at 5 %		0.892	1.39	0.539

of umbel per plant affects to seed yield when increase the umbel per plant. The similar variations in number of umbel per plant among different coriander varieties have reported by Kalidasu *et al* (2008) in sadhana varieties of coriander supports the results of present findings.

The significant differences were observed for number of umbellet per umbel. The highest number of umbellet per umbel which were recording variety Pant Haritima (5.7) was statistically at par with the variety Hissar Anand (5.5) and CO 4 (5.3).

Seed yield attributes

The data in respect of days to seed harvesting in coriander were significantly influenced by different varieties and are presented in table 3. The variety sadhana required minimum days to harvesting (94.3d) followed by the cultivar Swati (97.7d), CO 2 (103.3d), CO-4 (108.3d), Rajendra Swathi (110.3 d), Hissar Anand (116.3 d) and Hissar sugandh (117.3d). The cultivar Pant Haritima required maximum (131.3d) to harvesting. The differences in maturity period can be attributed to genetic differences among the cultivars and ecological as well as climatic condition, as climate during growth and development of plant plays a dominant role in growth, yield and quality of coriander. Similar trend of result was also observed and supports the

results of present findings by Kofidis *et al* (2008) in coriander, Meena *et al* (2010) in coriander.

The number of seed per umbel indicated significant differences among the different coriander varieties. The maximum number of seed per umbel were obtained in the variety Pant Haritima (30.4) which was found to be at par with the variety Swathi (28.5) and CO 2 (26.9). The less number of seed per umbel was obtained in the variety Hissar Anand (18.7). The variety Pant Haritima recorded maximum (12.3g) test weight followed by variety Swati (11.2g) and variety CO 2 (11.1g). The variety CO 4 and Rajendra Swathi recorded minimum (7.3g) test weight. It might be due to the fact that, genetic cause or responses of the particular genotype to the soil and climatic conditions might be reflected in such characters. Similar results were reported by Singh and Singh (2013), Dyulgerov and Dyulgerova (2013) which supports the results of present findings.

The data in respect of seed yields per plant (g) were significantly influenced by the different varieties of coriander (Table 3). The variety Pant Haritima recorded maximum yield per plant (13.4g) followed by cultivars Swati (11.9g), CO 2 (11.3g), Sadhana (10.9g), Hissar Sugandh (10.0g) and Rajendra Swathi (9.6g). The cultivar Hissar Anand

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produced minimum seed yield per plant (7.1g) followed by CO 4 (8.3g). The similar variations in seed yield per plant among different varieties have reported by Moniruzzaman *et al* (2013) in variety CS011 of coriander, Meena *et al* (2013) in coriander, which supports the results of present findings.

The data with respect of seed yield (q/ha) in coriander influenced by different varieties of coriander (Table 3). The results indicated that, the seed yield per hectare was significantly influenced due to different varieties under study. The cultivar Pant Haritima recorded maximum seed yield per ha (13.3q/ha). The cultivar Hissar Anand produced minimum (4.2q/ha) seed yield per ha followed by CO 4 (5.3q/ha). It was observed that, the varieties which performed better in a unit area were likely to perform better on large scale as the yield per hectare was calculated by multiplying yield per plot with hectare factor. The yield is the result of interaction of the variety to a given agro climatic and management factors. The variations in yield among the coriander varieties were also reported by several workers i.e. Yadav (1999) in coriander,

Singh and Singh (2013) in coriander, Meena *et al* (2013) in coriander, Moniruzzaman *et al* (2013) in variety CS011 of coriander which supports the results of present findings.

CONCLUSION

The evaluation of present investigation concluded that, the significant variations were observed in growth, yield and quality parameters of different variety of coriander. The variety Pant Haritima showed significantly superior performance in respect of seed production. Thus, it was concluded that, the various characters of different coriander varieties can be exercised on the varieties possessing more seed yield, more average test weight, number of umbel per plant and more yield useful in identifying the suitable variety.

REFERENCES

- Anonymous (2014). Database. Area, Producion, Productivity of major in India, National Horticulture Board Database.
- Carubba A, Calabrese I, Torre R and Kock O (2002). Cultivation trials of coriander (*Coriandrum sativum* L.) in a semi-arid Mediterranean environment. *Acta Hort* 576: 237-242.

Table 4. Performance of different coriander varieties in respect of flowering attributes seed yield attributes.

Sr. No.	Variety	Days to seed harvesting	Number of seed per umbel	Test weight (g) 1000 seed	Seed yield per plant (g)	Seed yield per plot (kg)	Seed yield (q/ha)
T ₁	Hissar Sugandh	117.3	23.9	9.0	10.0	0.4	11.4
T ₂	Pant Haritima	131.3	30.4	12.3	13.4	0.5	13.3
T ₃	Sadhana	94.3	22.7	10.2	10.9	0.3	9.2
T ₄	Swati	97.7	28.5	11.2	11.9	0.3	7.2
T ₅	CO-4	108.3	21.4	7.3	8.3	0.2	5.3
T ₆	Hissar Anand	116.3	18.7	8.2	7.1	0.2	4.2
T ₇	CO-2	103.3	26.9	11.1	11.3	0.4	10.3
T ₈	Rajendra Swathi	110.3	20.1	7.3	9.6	0.3	9.9
SE (m) ±		0.223	1.545	0.210	0.252	0.011	0.112
CD at 5 %		0.672	4.664	0.633	0.760	0.033	0.339

- Datta S, Chatterjee R and Satya (2006). Correlation and path analysis studies on Coriander (*Coriandrum sativum* L.). *Hort J* **19**: 65-67.
- Dyulgerov N and Dyulgerova B (2013). Variation of yield components in coriander (*Coriandrum Sativum* L.). *J Agric Sci and Tech* **5**(2): 160 – 163.
- Kalidasu G, Sarada C and Reddy T Y (2008). Efficacy of biofertilizers on the performance of rainfed coriander (*Coriandrum sativum* L.) in vertisols. *J Spices and Aromatic Crops* **17**(2): 98-102.
- Kofidis G, Giannakoulaand A, Ilias I F (2008). Growth, anatomy and chlorophyll fluorescence of coriander plants (*Coriandrum sativum* L.) treated with prohexadione-calcium and daminozide. *Acta Biologica Cracoviensia Series Botanica* **50**(2): 55–62.
- Meena M L, Kumar V, Kumar S, Yadav Y C and Kumar A (2010). Genetic variability, heritability, genetic advance, correlation coefficient and path analysis in coriander. *Indian J Hort* **67**: 242-246.
- Meena Y K, Jadhao B J and Kale V S (2014). Genetic analysis of agronomic traits in coriander. *SABRAO. J Br and Genet* **46**(2) 265-273.
- Moniruzzaman M, Rahman M M, Hossain M M, Sirajul K and Khaliq Q A (2013). Evaluation of coriander (*Coriandrum sativum* L.) genotypes for foliage yield and its attributes” *Bangladesh J Agric Res*, **38**(1): 175-180.
- Panse V G and Sukatme P V (1957). *Statistical methods for agricultural Workers*. 2nd Edn. PP. 152-157.
- Singh S J and Singh S K (2013). Genetic variability analysis in coriander (*Coriandrum sativum* L.). *J Spices and Aromatic Crops* **22**(1): 81–84.
- Verma P, Doshi V and Solanki R K (2014). Genetic variability assessed in Coriander (*Coriandrum sativum* L.) over years under environmental conditions of South Eastern Rajasthan (Hadoti Region) *Int J Seed Spices* **4**(2): 94-95.
- Yadav R K (1999). Variability in a collection of coriander (*Coriandrum sativum* L.) germplasm. *J Spices and Aromatic crops* **8**(1): 99.

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Performance of Mid Duration Variety of Pea (*Pisum sativum* L.) under FLD in Banka District of Bihar

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ABSTRACT

Pea (*Pisum sativum* L.) is the most important crop globally. Attempts were made to improve productivity and to increase area under vegetable pea by adoption of high yielding varieties (HYVs). In order to compare performance of conventional vegetable pea varieties with HVY, 34 front line demonstrations (FLD's) were laid out at farmers' field to show the worth of new variety over local check. Likewise, to facilitate the farmers through FLD's about potential of new improved production practices of vegetable pea for the adoption, knowledge enhancement and satisfaction were undertaken. The demonstrations resulted in enhancement in productivity. The yield was found to be increased from 98 (q/ha) in local check to 175 (q/ha) under FLDs. Similarly, the benefit: cost ratio was improved to 3.77 as compared to 2.11 in local check. Lack of market and support price (83.43) was observed to be major constraints in late sown pea cultivation.

Key Words: Knowledge, Adoption, Pea Cultivation, Improved production technology.

INTRODUCTION

Pea (*Pisum sativum* L.) is grown successfully in different districts of Bihar. In Banka district it is grown in Banka, Katoria Amarpur, Baunsi and Chandan blocks with approx. 106 ha area. It is harvested in immature conditions and cooked as fresh or canned for subsequent uses. The acreage under vegetable pea in Bihar did not increase during last five years. Banka district topography is undulated and rain fed. Land is low to medium upland. Farmers cultivate vegetable pea variety locally known as *Kushia* Mater. This variety is poor yielding, having lesser sweetness with low marketable price. The productivity of vegetable pea is low due to various constraints like unavailability of early to mid season variety to the farmers, use of traditional varieties, inadequate moisture availability at sowing time and late sowing of peas particularly in rice –fallow areas, broad casting

method of sowing and use of high seed rate, pod borer infestation and wilting in plants.

KVK's role in agriculture and its allied sector is crucial as it is ideally placed to facilitate field – tested proven technologies with appropriate modulation which addresses location specific problems and concern on the prevailing natural and socio –economic conditions, needs and priorities. Climatic conditions are suitable for pea cultivation, therefore trials were conducted to introduce new vegetable pea variety in Banka district to increase the profitability. Keeping the above point in view, FLDs on vegetable pea were conducted to compare the yield levels of local check with the improved variety, work out the economic feasibility of the crop, calculate technology satisfaction, know feedback for further improvement in extension programme and to note down various constraints in dissemination of technology.

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Table 1. Detail of vegetable pea grown under FLD and existing practices.

Sr. No.	Particular	Existing practice	Improved cultivation practice under FLD
1.	Use of seed	Local seed (Kushia Mater)	Azad Pea3 used for mid season sowing
2.	Seed quality	Medium bold, light green	Wrinkled , dark green colour
3.	Method of sowing	Broadcasting	Line sowing
4.	Fertilizer application	0:0:0 (kg N:P:K/ha)	55:20:40 (kg N:P:K /ha)
5.	Bio fertilizers	No use of Rhizobium spp.	Seed treatment with Rhizobium@10ml/kg of seed
		No soil application of Rhizobium spp.	Soil application of Rhizobium@ 3l/ha

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Front Line Demonstrations were conducted on 34 farmers' field on an area of 2.3 ha and cultivar Azad Pea 3 was used in FLD during the year 2015-16. Full recommended package of practices were followed under the FLD plots (Table 1). An interview schedule was prepared and administered to the respondents and data were analyzed. Preferential ranking technique was utilized to identify the constraints faced by the farmers in vegetable pea cultivation. The quantification of data was done by first ranking the constraints and then calculating the rank based quotient (RBQ) as given by Sabarathanam (1998), as mentioned below-

$$RBQ = \frac{f_i (n+1 - i)}{N \times n} \times 100$$

Where, f_i =Number of farmers reporting a particular problem under i th rank; N = number of farmers and n =number of problems identified.

Production and economic data for FLD's and local practices were collected and analyzed. The technology gap and technology index were calculated using the following formulas as given by Samui *et al* (2000).

Technology gap= Potential yield- Demonstration yield

Potential yield- Demonstration yield

Technology index= ----- x100

Potential yield

Knowledge level of the farmers about improved cultivation practices of the Azad Pea 3 variety before frontline demonstration and after implementation, was measured and compared by applying dependent 't' test. The selected respondents were interviewed personally with the help of a pre test and well structured interview schedule. Client satisfaction index was calculated by using formula as developed by (Kumaran and Vijayaragavan, 2005).

Client satisfaction index= $\frac{\text{Individual obtained score}}{\text{Maximum possible score}}$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A comparison of productivity levels between demonstrated variety and local check is shown in table 2. It was observed that in front line demonstrations, the improved pea variety Azad pea 3 recorded higher seed yield (175q/ha) as compared to local check variety (98 q/ha). The increase in yield over check was 78.6 percent. It was, thus, evident that improved high yielding variety Azad Pea 3 performed well as comparison to local check at different locations in the district. Yield of

Performance of Pea

Table 2. Yield, technology gap, technology index and economics of front line demonstration of vegetable pea.

Variables	Seed yield (q/ha)	(Per cent) increase over check	Potential yield (q/ha)	Technology gap (q/ha)	Technology index (%)	Cost of cultivation (Rs/ha)	Gross return (Rs/ha)	Net return (Rs/ha)	Benefit cost ratio
Local check (FP)	98					61000/-	196000/-	135000/-	2.21
FLD	175	78.6	200	25	12.5	66375/-	314000/-	247325/-	3.77

the demonstration and potential yield of the crop was compared to estimate the yield gap which were further categorized into technology index and harvest index. Potential yield for variety was 200 q/ha. The technology gap showed the gap in the demonstration yield over potential yield of 25 q/ha.

The observed technology gap was due to various constraints like low soil fertility, availability of low moisture content during sowing time, weather condition and climatic hazards etc. Hence to reduce the yield gap, there must be location specific recommendation for variety, soil testing and timely sowing appears to be necessary. Technology index showed the suitability of variety at farmer's field. Lower technology values indicated that feasibility of variety among the farmers was more. It was revealed (Table 2) that technology index (32.51%) was better than the local one. These results were in agreement with Singh and Kumar (2012).

The economic analysis of the yield performance revealed that front line demonstrations recorded higher gross return (Rs 314000/ha) and net return (Rs 247625/ha) with higher benefit cost ratio 3.77, compared to 2.21 over local check (Table 2).

Technology satisfaction among respondents

The extent of satisfaction level of farmers about performance of demonstrated varieties was measured by Client Satisfaction Index (CSI). It was observed that majority of the farmers indicated high (52.94 %) to the medium (26.47 %) level of adoption or satisfaction for improved cultivation practices and HYV of pea. Whereas, 20.58 percent

respondents expressed lower level of satisfaction with respect to improved vegetable pea variety and cultivation practices. The medium to higher level of satisfaction with respect to improved cultivation practices, linkage with farmers, services rendered etc. indicated stronger conviction, physical and mental involvement in the front line demonstration. Similar findings obtained by Tomar (2010) and Dudi and Meena (2012)

Knowledge gain regarding new variety and technology among respondents

Knowledge level of respondent farmers on various aspects of improved pea production technologies before conducting the front line demonstration (MS=23.6) and after front line demonstration (MS=85.6) was measured and compared by applying dependent 't' test. It was observed that farmers mean knowledge score increased to 85.6 after implementation of front line demonstrations. Mean difference recorded was 62.0 for pea growers. The increase in mean knowledge score of farmers was significantly higher as the computed value of 't' (4.54) at 5 percent probability level. It indicated that there was significant increase or gain in knowledge level of farmers that have resulted in higher adoption of improved farm practices.

Constraints with mid season vegetable pea variety

In the cultivation of mid season vegetable pea problems encountered and ranking given by the farmers are mentioned in table 3. A perusal of data

Table 3. Rank based quotient obtained by the vegetable pea respondents (n=34)

S. No.	Problem encountered	RBQ	Overall rank
1	Lack of market and support price	83.45	I
2	Disease and insect pest infestation	78.25	II
3	Lack of high yielding varieties of mid season pea	74.42	III
4	Lack of moisture availability in the field during sowing	73.68	IV
5	Low soil fertility	68.47	V
6	Weed infestation	62.14	VI
7	Lack of technical support	60.42	VII
8	Undulated topography of land	59.15	VIII
9	Lack of credit facilities	48.43	IX
10	Illiteracy among farmers	50.75	X
11	Damage by wild animals	30.75	XII

indicated that lack of market and support price ranked first by 34 respondent's with RBQ value (83.45). Disease and insect pest infestation, lack of high yielding varieties of vegetable pea, lack of moisture availability in the field during sowing, low soil fertility, pod borer and weed infestation were major constraints faced by the pea farmers. While lack of technical support, Undulated topography of land, lack of credit facilities, illiteracy among the farmers and crop damage by wild animals were also found as a constraints to reduce the production of mid season sown pea crop. The view was also supported by Singh *et al* (2007).

CONCLUSION

The productivity gain under FLD over existing practices of vegetable pea cultivation created greater awareness and motivated to the other farmers to adopt suitable production technology of vegetable pea in the district. The constraints faced by the farmers were different for different technologies. Efforts should, therefore, be made by the extension agencies in the transfer of technology programmes to consider the constraints as perceived by the farmers in this investigations as well as personnel. The effect of FLD showed that there was significant

improvement in knowledge level and satisfaction on the part of pea farmers.

REFERENCES

- Dudi A and Meena M L (2012). Adoption of improved mustard production technology in Pali district of Rajasthan. *Int J Ext Edu* **8**: 5-8.
- Kumaran M and Vijayaragavan K (2005). Farmer's satisfaction of agricultural extension services in an irrigated command area. *Indian J Ext Edu* **41** (3&4): 8-12.
- Sabarathanam V E (1998). "Manuals of field experience training for ARS Scientists". Hyderabad: NAARM.
- Samui S K, Maitra S, Roy D K, Mondal A K and Saha D (2000). "Evaluation of front line demonstration on ground nut (*Arachis hypogea* L.) in Sundarbans". *J Indian Soc Coastal Agric Res* **18** (2): 180-183.
- Singh K R and Kumar H (2012). On farm evaluation of front line demonstration on mustard in eastern plain zone of Uttar Pradesh. *Indian J Ext Edu* **8**:115-117.
- Singh S N, Singh V K, Singh R K and Singh K R (2007). Evaluation of on -farm front line demonstration on the yield of mustard in central plains zone of Uttar Pradesh. *Indian Res J Ext Edu* **3**: 79-81.
- Tomar R K S (2010). "Maximization of productivity for chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* Linn.) through improved technologies in farmer's fields". *Indian J Natural Products and Resources* **1** (4): 515-517.

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Pesticide Use Behavior of Farmers in Rice-Onion Production System

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ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted to assess the pesticide application behavior of farmers with respect to rice- onion production system in Sheikhpura district of Bihar. A total of 200 farmers were selected as respondents through three stage sampling procedure. The selected respondents were interviewed personally using pre-tested well structured interview schedule. Results of the study showed that almost all the farmers were dependent on chemical pesticides for the management of pests. The respondent farmers were using a variety of pesticide formulations. The most frequently used were insecticides followed by fungicides, weedicide, acaricide and bactericide. The data revealed that majority of farmers had low to medium knowledge on various aspects of pesticide use. A majority of the farmers were dependent mostly on input dealers, neighbourer and fellow farmers for their need of technical information.

Key Words: Farmers, Onion, Paddy, Pesticides, Production.

INTRODUCTION

Pesticides represent an important ingredient in current Indian agriculture. The crop loss from pests is estimated to be 18 per cent annually in India where insecticides are the most popular pesticide and are predominantly used on cotton. Since the 1980s, integrated pest management (IPM), the combination of various management methods gained importance in India through favorable policy and extensive programs in rice, sugarcane and some vegetables. However a lack of trained personnel, complex decision-making required on the part of farmers and farmer beliefs in relation to natural enemies have been identified as limitations to the widespread adoption of IPM in India (Singh *et al* 2003). Pesticides have been an integral part of the vegetable production process by reducing losses from the weeds, diseases and insect pests that can markedly reduce the amount of harvestable produce (Aktar *et al*, 2009).

To promote appropriate use of pesticides applications it is crucial to understand the current

use of pesticides among farmers. Therefore, this study was conducted to analyze the pesticide use and application behavior of farmers in rice-onion production system. The specific objective of this study was to investigate farmers' perception and the factors that influence their intention to apply pesticide to their crop for pest management with the purpose of improving the IPM extension program.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in Sheikhpura district of Bihar. A three stage sampling design was used to select the sample households. In first stage, Ariyari and Sheikhpura blocks of the Sheikhpura district where rice followed by onion is grown at a large scale was selected purposively. In second stage, four villages were purposively selected to ensure good representation of the selected block. Finally in third stage, a total of 200 farmers, representing households, were selected from the selected villages in proportion to the population in each selected villages. The selected respondent farmers

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were interviewed personally with the help of a well structured and pre-tested interview schedule.

Knowledge was operationalized as the information possessed by the farmers about pesticide use and handling practices with adequate understanding of the pesticides in use, choice of pesticides, recommended dose and time of application, quantity and method of application etc. The knowledge of the individual farmer was measured through a schedule prepared for the study purpose. The response of farmers was obtained on three point continuum i.e. fully correct, partial correct and incorrect, and scores of 2, 1 and 0 were assigned, respectively. Item wise scores of 2, 1 and 0 were assigned and thus total score was worked out. On the basis of mean knowledge score, the farmers were categorized into low, medium and high knowledge on the basis of equal intervals. Data thus collected were analyzed using statistical tools such as standard deviation (SD), percentage analysis wherever required.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the respondent farmers

Socio economic characteristics of respondent farmers were analyzed (Table 1). Majority of the

respondents (40.5%) belonged to middle age group followed by young age (39.0%) and old age (20.5%) group. The frequency distribution was highly skewed towards the younger farmers. Regarding the educational status of respondent, results showed that a majority (56%) of respondents were functionally literate up to middle class followed by high school (18.5%), illiterate (16.5%), higher secondary (6.5 %) and graduate and above (3.5 %). Data on land holding demonstrated that nearly 80 per cent of respondents were marginal (52.5 %) to small (27.0 %) farmers. It was also observed that majority (54%) of respondents were resource poor. A sizable portion of the sample had more than five years of farming experience.

Pesticide utilization

The study revealed that hundred per cent of the respondent farmers were dependent on the chemical pesticides for the management of pests and diseases. The respondent farmers were using a variety of pesticide formulation of different groups and for different purposes. Most of the respondents remember the pesticides by their trade names without any awareness of their technical names. Among them, the most frequently mentioned were insecticides followed by fungicides, herbicides,

Table1. Distribution of respondents based on their socio economic characteristics

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age(in years)	Young (18-35)	78	39.0
	Middle (35-50)	81	40.5
	Old (50 and above)	41	20.5
Education	Illiterate	33	16.5
	Primary	47	23.5
	Middle	63	32.5
	Matriculate	37	18.5
	Intermediate	13	6.5
	Graduate	7	3.5
Operational land holding	Marginal	105	52.5
	Small	54	27.0
	Medium	37	18.5
	Large	4	2.0

Pesticide use Behaviour of Farmers

Table 2. Types of pesticides used and the number of farmers using.

Types of Pesticide	Common name	Number of farmers	Per cent farmers
Fungicides	Carbendazim	196	98.0
	Carboxin	34	17.0
	Copper oxy chloride	165	82.5
	Hexaconazole	63	31.5
	Mancozeb	200	100.0
	Propiconazole	15	7.5
	Sulpher	175	87.5
	Tebuconazole	25	12.5
	Thiram	135	67.5
Bactericides	Streptomycin	106	53.0
	Acephate	93	46.5
	Carbaryl	100	50.0
	Carbosulfan	23	11.5
Insecticides	Chloropyriphos	59	29.5
	Cypermethrin	64	32.0
	Deltramethrin	38	19.0
	Dichlorvos	105	52.5
	Dimethoate	155	77.5
	Fenvalrate	72	36.0
	Fipronil	43	21.5
	Flubendamide	43	22.5
	Imidachloprid	156	78.0
	Lambda-cyhalothrin	82	41.0
	Malathian	165	82.5
	Methyl parathion	83	41.5
	Monocrotophos	75	37.5
	Phorate	136	68.0
	Phosphamidon	59	29.5
	Profenophos	112	56.0
	Thiomethoxam	53	26.5
	Triazophos	87	43.5
	Acaricides	Ethion	76
Dicofol		100	50.0
Dinocap		55	27.5
Weedicides	Pedimethalin	78	39.0
	2,4-D	169	84.5
	Isoproturan	136	66.5
	Bispyribac Sodium	145	72.5

Table 3. Knowledge of farmers on safe and proper use of pesticides.

Particular	Low		Medium		High	
	Number	Per cent	Number	Per cent	Number	Per cent
Pesticide in use	98	49	74	37	28	14
Choice of pesticide	96	48	78	39	26	13
Recommended dose and time of application	68	34	96	48	36	18
Handling of pesticide	60	30	104	52	36	18
Disposal and storage	44	22	110	55	46	23
Effects of pesticides on environment	64	32	88	44	48	24
Effects of pesticides on human and animal health	56	28	100	50	44	22

nematicides and bactericides as shown in Table 2. It was also observed that preference of farmers toward pesticide selection was primarily based on their efficacy rather than safety. Mancozeb, Carbendazim and Sulphur fungicides; Melathion, Imidachloprid and Phorate insecticides and 2,4-D herbicides were most commonly used by the respondent farmers.

Knowledge on pesticide use

On the major aspects regarding safe use of pesticides, the knowledge level of the respondents was assessed and results are presented in Table 3. The data revealed that had low or medium level of knowledge about pesticide in use, their toxicity, target pest, recommended dose and time of application, handling of pesticides, disposal and storage, effects of pesticides on environment and on the human health. Similar results were also reported by Nagenthirarajah and Thiruchelvam (2008). Hence, the extension services to farmers need to

be improved so that farmers can access the relevant information on the use of pesticides (Table 3).

Source of information

Different sources of information were used by the farmers to adopt a new technology and to solve their problems. It was expected that faith on certain information sources would influence the decision to purchase a pesticide as well as their application. Data indicated that the input dealer has been the major information provider on pesticide use for the majority of farmers (56%). On the other hand, extension personnel were mostly consulted by 24 per cent of the respondent followed by occasionally contacted by 19 per cent. Similarly extension literature was utilized rarely by majority (61%) of respondent. Thus, this depicts the risk of adoption of incorrect practices. Prior studies of Heong and Escalada (1999) also reported similar observation (Table 4).

Table 4. Source of information for farmers regarding pesticides use.

Source of information	Mostly		Occasionally		Seldom	
	Number	Per cent	Number	Per cent	Number	Per cent
Extension personal	48	24	38	19	114	57
Input dealer	112	56	56	28	32	16
Extension literature	30	15	48	24	122	61
Mass media	32	16	52	26	116	58
Neighbour, fellow farmers	70	35	80	40	50	25

Pesticide use Behaviour of Farmers

CONCLUSION

It may be concluded that farmers were dependent on chemical pesticides for the management of pests and diseases in crops and were using a variety of pesticide formulations. Some of the pesticides were extremely or highly hazardous. The choice of pesticide by farmer was primarily based on efficacy rather than safety. Lack of knowledge on various aspects of pesticides application made them to inappropriate use of pesticides. The input dealers were acting the role of major provider of information on pesticide use which causes the risk of adoption of incorrect practices. Thus, Agricultural extension need to be employed to follow a systemic, well planned and coordinated approach in the area for improving the knowledge status of farmers for the management of pests and diseases in the rice- onion production system.

REFERENCES

- Aktar M W, Sengupta D and Chowdhury A (2009). Impact of pesticides use in agriculture: their benefits and hazards. *Interdisciplinary Toxicology* **2**: 1-12.
- Rashid M A, Alam S N, Rouf F M A and Talekar N S (2003). *Socio economic parameters of egg plant protection in Jessore District of Bangladesh*. Technical Bulletin 29. AVRDC – The World Vegetable Center, Shanhua, Taiwan. 37 pp.
- Heong K Land Escalada M M (1999). Quantifying rice farmers' pest management decisions: beliefs and subjective norms in stem borer control. *Crop Protection* **18**: 315-322.
- Nagenthirarajah S and THiruchelvam S (2008). Knowledge of Farmers about pest Management Practices in Pambaimadu, Vavuniya District: An Ordered Probit Model Approach. *Sabaramuwa University J* **8**: 79-89.
- Singh A, Singh S and Rao S N (2003). "Integrated Pest Management in India." In KM Maredia (ed.) *Integrated Pest Management in the global arena*, CABI Publishing, Wallingford.

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Pre-Weaning Morpho-metric Measurements and Body Weights of Chhotanagpuri Sheep in its Breeding Tract

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ABSTRACT

Data on 142 Chhotanagpuri lambs (62 males and 80 females) belonging to Deoghar district of Jharkhand were used for the present investigation. The mean body length, height at withers, chest girth, paunch girth, ear length and tail length were estimated to be 28.06 ± 0.36 , 24.84 ± 0.38 , 27.61 ± 0.41 , 26.37 ± 0.42 , 7.28 ± 0.16 and 7.97 ± 0.16 cm respectively for male lambs. The corresponding values for female lambs were 27.77 ± 0.34 , 24.72 ± 0.29 , 25.95 ± 0.38 , 25.08 ± 0.38 , 7.15 ± 0.15 and 7.96 ± 0.12 cm respectively. The mean of above body bio-metric at the age of 3-months were recorded as 39.48 ± 0.59 , 38.61 ± 0.76 , 42.72 ± 0.64 , 43.91 ± 0.74 , 10.83 ± 0.36 and 11.82 ± 0.39 cm for male lambs and 38.60 ± 0.53 , 38.46 ± 0.61 , 40.41 ± 0.63 , 42.15 ± 0.72 , 9.71 ± 0.34 and 10.63 ± 0.28 cm respectively for female lambs. The mean body weight of male lambs at birth, 1-month, 2-months and 3-months were estimated to be 1.82 ± 0.05 , 3.49 ± 0.10 , 5.36 ± 0.23 and 7.62 ± 0.34 kg, respectively. The corresponding values for females lambs were 1.71 ± 0.04 , 3.11 ± 0.12 , 5.01 ± 0.21 and 6.72 ± 0.32 kg, respectively.

Key Words: Pre-Weaning, Measurements, Body weight, Chhotanagpuri Sheep, Breeding.

INTRODUCTION

Chhotanagpuri is well defined breed of sheep found in Jharkhand. The breed is distributed in the entire area of Jharkhand and adjoins districts of West Bengal (Purulia, Western part of Bankura and west of Medinapur district). The breed is mostly reared by weaker sections of the society specially schedule caste and schedule tribes. The breed is in small size and having straight nose, short drooping or horizontal ears and short tail. The utility of the breed is solely for mutton production. They produce coarse wool of poor quality, which may be utilized for carpet manufacturing. The information on Morpho-metric measurement and growth parameters on Chhotanagpuri under field condition is scanty. Growth performance is a key production indicator. It has implications in the reproductive efficiency of sheep. Fast growth performance allows sheep to breed early and contribute more lambs in their lifetime. Fast growth rate entails reaching market weight early and brings a quicker income to the farmer. Hence, this study was conducted to

estimate the pattern of growth in Chhotanagpuri sheep under prevailing natural and ecological conditions of Jharkhand, India.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data on 142 Chhotanagpuri lambs (62 males and 80 females) belonging to Deoghar district of Jharkhand were considered for the present study. The district extends from $24^{\circ} 03'$ and $23^{\circ} 38'$ N latitude and $86^{\circ} 28'$ and $87^{\circ} 04'$ E longitude. The average elevation of the district is 247 m above msl. Average annual rainfall is 1239 mm, mean summer maximum temperature is 43°C and mean winter minimum temperature is 8°C . The data was generated during survey of Mega Sheep Seed project of ICAR at Birsa Agricultural University, Ranchi, Jharkhand.

The Morpho-metric measurement and body weights were recorded. Six different body measurement and birth weight of the lambs were recorded immediately after the lambing and thereafter at monthly intervals up to the age of

three months. The body measurements recorded included body length (BL), height at withers (BH), chest girth (CG), pouch girth (PG), ear length (EL) and tail length (TL). The body measurements were taken for various age groups with a standard measuring tape of 1 mm accuracy after the animals were allowed to stand squarely on an even ground.

The weight was recorded with the help of 25 kg weighing balance with 50 g accuracy. All the observations were taken in the morning before grazing or being allowed feed or water to the animals. The season was divided into three: the main winter (November to February), summer (March-June) and monsoon (July-October). The animals were maintained only on grazing and allowed for 6-7 hours during day on natural grasses and shrubs. The data collected were analyzed by least-squares method (Harvey, 1990).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morpho-metric measurement of Chhotanagpuri lambs

The mean \pm SE of morpho-metric measurement for various traits under the study have been presented in the table. The body measurements indicate the skeletal growth of the animals. Body length and height at withers are the measures of bone growth while chest girth is a measure of development of muscles, bones and fat and it had close relationship with the live weight (Pomeroy, 1955). The mean \pm SE of body length, height at withers, chest girth, paunch girth, ear length and tail length were estimated to be 28.06 ± 0.36 , 24.84 ± 0.38 , 27.61 ± 0.41 , 26.37 ± 0.42 , 7.28 ± 0.16 and 7.97 ± 0.16 cm respectively for male lambs. The corresponding values for female lambs were 27.77 ± 0.34 , 24.72 ± 0.29 , 25.95 ± 0.38 , 25.08 ± 0.38 , 7.15 ± 0.15 and 7.96 ± 0.12 cm respectively.

Table 1. Mean \pm S.E. of Morpho-metric measurements (cm) and body weights (kg) of Chhotanagpuri sheep under field conditions.

Traits	Sex	BL	BH	CG	PG	EL	TL	BW
At Birth	M	28.06 ± 0.36	24.84 ± 0.38	27.61 ± 0.41	26.37 ± 0.42	7.28 ± 0.16	7.97 ± 0.16	1.82a ± 0.05
	F	27.77 ± 0.34	24.72 ± 0.29	25.95 ± 0.38	25.08 ± 0.38	7.15 ± 0.15	7.96 ± 0.12	1.71b ± 0.04
At one month	M	32.16 ± 0.38	33.39 ± 0.31	34.50 ± 0.45	34.44 ± 0.67	9.01 ± 0.20	9.92 ± 0.20	3.49a ± 0.10
	F	31.86 ± 0.36	32.26 ± 0.39	32.62 ± 0.39	31.75 ± 0.45	8.57 ± 0.15	9.38 ± 0.17	3.11b ± 0.12
At two month	M	37.25 ± 0.54	38.28 ± 0.46	40.66 ± 0.58	41.92 ± 0.62	10.67 ± 0.25	11.39 ± 0.42	5.36a ± 0.23
	F	36.18 ± 0.48	36.37 ± 0.51	38.16 ± 0.57	39.07 ± 0.75	9.30 ± 0.22	10.46 ± 0.27	5.01b ± 0.21
At three month	M	39.48 ± 0.59	38.61 ± 0.76	42.72 ± 0.64	43.91 ± 0.74	10.83 ± 0.36	11.82 ± 0.39	7.62a ± 0.34
	F	38.60 ± 0.53	38.46 ± 0.61	40.41 ± 0.63	42.15 ± 0.72	9.71 ± 0.34	10.63 ± 0.28	6.72b ± 0.32

Number of observations: male (62) and female (80) lambs

a, b mean values differ significantly ($p < 0.05$)

Body Weights of Chhotanagpuri Sheep

7.15 ± 0.15 and 7.96 ± 0.12 cm respectively for above mentioned traits. The mean ± SE for body measurements at the age of one month were found to be 32.16 ± 0.38, 33.39 ± 0.31, 34.50 ± 0.45, 34.44 ± 0.67, 9.01 ± 0.20 and 9.92 ± 0.20 cm for male lambs. However, the corresponding values for female lambs were observed as 31.86 ± 0.36, 32.26 ± 0.39, 32.62 ± 0.39, 31.75 ± 0.45, 8.57 ± 0.15 and 9.38 ± 0.17 cm respectively. Likewise at the age of two months for male and female lambs were estimated as 37.25 ± 0.54, 38.28 ± 0.46, 40.66 ± 0.58, 41.92 ± 0.62, 10.67 ± 0.25 and 11.39 ± 0.42 cm and 36.18 ± 0.48, 36.37 ± 0.51, 38.16 ± 0.57, 39.07 ± 0.75, 9.30 ± 0.22 and 10.46 ± 0.27 cm respectively. The mean ± SE of body length, height at withers, chest girth, paunch girth, ear length and tail length were found to be 39.48 ± 0.59, 38.61 ± 0.76, 42.72 ± 0.64, 43.91 ± 0.74, 10.83 ± 0.36 and 11.82 ± 0.39 cm for male lambs and for female lambs it was observed as 38.60 ± 0.53, 38.46 ± 0.61, 40.41 ± 0.63, 42.15 ± 0.72, 9.71 ± 0.34 and 10.63 ± 0.28 cm respectively.

Body weights of Chhotanagpuri lambs

The body weights of Chhotanagpuri lambs at various stages have been presented in the table 1. The body weights of lambs differ significantly at all stages. The mean ± SE of body weight male lambs at birth, 1 month, 2 months and 3 months were estimated to be 1.82 ± 0.05, 3.49 ± 0.10, 5.36 ± 0.23 and 7.62 ± 0.34 kg, respectively. The corresponding values for females were 1.71 ± 0.04, 3.11 ± 0.12, 5.01 ± 0.21 and 6.72 ± 0.32 kg, respectively. The lower values for body weights in Chhotanagpuri lambs were reported by Thanesh (2013) under farm conditions. Higher body weights at various stages were reported by Das et al (2002), Pattanayak et al (2003), Raman et al (2003) in different Indian breeds of sheep.

CONCLUSION

The present study was carried out in the breeding tract of Chhotanagpuri sheep. The mean body length, height at withers, chest girth, paunch girth, ear length and tail length were recorded as 28.06 ± 0.36, 24.84 ± 0.38, 27.61 ± 0.41, 26.37 ± 0.42, 7.28 ± 0.16 and 7.97 ± 0.16 cm respectively for male and 27.77 ± 0.34, 24.72 ± 0.29, 25.95 ± 0.38, 25.08 ± 0.38, 7.15 ± 0.15 and 7.96 ± 0.12 cm respectively for female lambs. The mean body weight of male at birth, 1-month, 2-months and 3-months were estimated to be 1.82 ± 0.05, 3.49 ± 0.10, 5.36 ± 0.23 and 7.62 ± 0.34 kg, respectively and 1.71 ± 0.04, 3.11 ± 0.12, 5.01 ± 0.21 and 6.72 ± 0.32 kg, respectively for female lambs. Significant effect of sex was observed in Chhotanagpuri lambs. Selective breeding may be followed for genetic improvement of Chhotanagpuri sheep in the breeding tract.

REFERENCES

- Das P., Sil B K and Samanta R (2002). Reproductive performance of Muzafarnagri X shahabadi cross- breed sheep under deep litter system of management . *Enviorn and Ecolo* **20**(4): 806-809.
- Harvey W R (1990). User guide for LSMLMW pc-1 version mixed model least-squares and maximum likelihood computer program. Columbus, Ohio, USA.
- Pattanayak G R, Patro B N, Das S K and Nayak S. (2003). Survey and performance evaluation of Ganjam sheep. *Indian J Small Ruminant* **9**(1): 47-49.
- Pomeroy R W (1955). *Progress in the Physiology of Farm Animals*. Vol.2: 395-429. Butter Worths Scientific Publication, London.
- Raman K S, Sundaraman M N, Haribhaskar S and Ganesakale D (2003). Biometrics and breed characteristics of Madras red sheep. *Indian J Small Ruminant* **9**(1): 6-9.
- Thanesh Oraon (2013). *Genetic architecture of Chhotanagpuri sheep in context of fecundity gene*. M.V.Sc. Thesis submitted to Birsa Agricultural University, Ranchi, Jharkhand.

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Silicon Nutrition for Sustainable Rice Production in Iron Toxic Laterite Soils of Kollam District in Kerala

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ABSTRACT

In iron toxic laterite soil of Kerala, the major soil related constraints affecting rice production are acidity and toxicity of metals like iron (Fe), aluminium (Al) and manganese (Mn). In Kollam district approximately 60 per cent of area under rice is coming under iron toxic iron laterite soil. The presence of high concentration of these metals in soil hinders the absorption of other nutrients leading to poor nutrient use efficiency. A suitable nutrient management system which reduces the toxic level of these metals prevalent in low pH soil, will certainly improve the yield of rice. The trial consisted of three technology options viz., farmers practice i.e., unscientific use of high analysis fertilizers (TO1), recommended practice i.e., 5 t/ha OM + 90:45:45 kg N:P:K/ha +600 kg lime/ha (TO2) and alternate practice i.e., 90:45:120 kg N:P:K/ha +OM 5 t/ha + 150 kg lime/ha+100 kg silica/ha (TO3). The study revealed that compared to the technology TO1 and TO2, the technology option TO3 (OM 5 t/ha+ 90:45:120 kg N:P:K/ha + 150 kg lime+100 kg silica) gave significantly higher grain and straw yield i.e., 6.61 t/ha (17.62%) increase in grain and 9.29 t/ha (20.65%) increase in straw over recommended practice (TO2). Benefit cost ratio was also highest for this treatment (2.26). The lowest incidence of pests was recorded in silica applied plots. This shows that in addition to yield enhancement, this technology has an additional benefit i.e., reduction of pest incidence. Hence the outcomes of this farmer participatory experiment emphasized the importance of the special nutrient package for yield increase in rice under iron toxic laterite soils. The feedback of the farmers who visited the trial plots was positive and they recorded that silica application has increased the growth and number of productive tillers. They also observed that silica application reduced the incidence of pests.

Key Words: Al, Fe, Grain yield, Incidence of pests, Mn, Toxicity, Rice, Silica, Straw yield.

INTRODUCTION

The rice farming sector in Kerala is facing a multitude of problems which led to drastic decline in area under cultivation and production. The main problem yet to be addressed in detail is soil related constraints. About 65 per cent of soils in Kerala is iron toxic laterite, which require special management package as the soils are low to medium in organic carbon, N and K, very low in Ca, Mg and B. Apart from low nutrient status, high acidity and toxicities of iron, aluminium and manganese are other major soil related constraints in iron toxic laterite soils of Kerala.

Silicon the wonder element can alleviate various abiotic stresses including, metal toxicity, drought

stress, nutrient imbalance, high temperature, freezing and so on as reported by Matichenkov and Calvert (2002), Ma, 2003; and Singh *et al*(2005). Though silicon is abundantly present in the earth crust, continuous and intensive monoculture of nitrogen responsive high yielding cultivars depletes the available silicon from soil. Nutrient management systems including silicon fertilizer which reduce the toxic levels of Al, Fe & Mn which is prevalent in low pH soil will certainly improve the yield. In this context, KVK, Kollam has conducted on farm testing to assess the feasibility of the alternate Kerala Agricultural University nutrient package that includes silicon fertilizer for yield enhancement

in iron toxic laterite soils in the selected farmer's fields of Kollam district of Kerala through a farmer participatory approach during 2012-2013.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The trial was carried out in 7 randomly selected farmer's fields at Elamadu and Thevannur panchayats of Kollam district during rabi season of 2012-13. Different farmers' fields were taken as replications. The variety selected was Uma. The plot size was 100 m² for each technology options. The soils are acidic in nature with a pH of 4.9 to 5.14. The fertility status of selected plots were medium in organic carbon, medium to high in available P and low to medium in available K. The iron content in soil before the experiment was analyzed and found that it was high in all plots.

The trial consisted of three technology options (TO); viz., farmers practice i.e., unscientific use of fertilizers (TO1), recommended practice i.e. 5 t/ha OM + 90:45:45 kg NPK/ha +600 kg lime/ha (TO2) and alternate practice i.e., 90:45:120 kg N:P:K/ha +OM 5 t/ha + 150 kg lime/ha+100 kg silica/ha (TO3). The technologies were evaluated by collecting data on plant height, total number of productive tillers, grain yield, straw yield, and incidence of pests and disease with farmer participation. The study also explored the feedback of visiting farmers of sample size 21 from different areas of Chadayamangalam block under ATMA exposure visit programme organized by Department of Agriculture, Kollam. The response of farmers on these technologies were recorded after observing the parameters on

growth, productive tillers and pest incidence, as, low, medium and high.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Growth and yield

The data on growth and yield parameters are given in Table 1. The results showed that growth, yield parameters and yield were high for TO3, it recorded the highest grain yield (6.61t/ha) nearly 17.62 per cent over the recommended practice (TO2). The same treatment recorded an increase in straw yield also i.e., 9.29 t/ha which was 20.65 per cent increase over the recommended practice (TO2). Application of silica helped to increase growth and yield attributes which in turn increased grain yield and straw yield.

The similar studies reported that important constraints limiting productivity of rice in the iron toxic laterite soils, viz., high acidity and toxicity of Al, Fe and Mn can be alleviated to a greater extent through the application of silicon fertilizer (Ma *et al*, 2006 and Matichenkov and Calvert (2002). The possible mechanisms through which Si alleviates the metal toxicity are: (1) Plant available silicon (PAS) increase the pH of acidic soil, (2) PAS can form ions with the toxic metals thereby precipitating it out of soil solution, (3) Silica deposition in roots reduce the binding sites for metals resulting in decreased uptake and translocation of salts and toxic metals from roots to shoot, (4) Another way is interaction between Si and Al occurs in the solution, presumably by the formation of Al-Si complexes, a

Table 1. Effect of nutrient management systems on growth and yield attributes of rice

Technology options	Plant height (cm) at harvest	No. of tillers/hill at harvest	No. of productive tillers/hill	Pest incidence (%)
Farmers' practice (TO1)	101.4	8.85	8.14	35.85
Recommended practice (TO2)	103	10.5	7.85	27.42
Alternate practice (TO3).	102.7	11.42	9.14	7.11

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non-toxic form (5) Silicon enhanced the oxidative power of rice roots, resulting in enhanced oxidation of Fe from ferrous iron to insoluble ferric iron. Similar mechanism is applicable for Mn also (Matichenkov and Calvert, 1999). In this trial also alleviation of metal toxicities proved to be the reason for enhanced productivity along with other positive benefits of silicon.

Pest incidence

The data on pest incidence is given in Table 2. Better reduction of pests was observed in silica applied plots (7.11%) whereas the pest incidence was 35.85 per cent in the plots under farmers practice. This may be due to the deposition of silica on epidermal layers that in turn offers a physical barrier to insects. Sucking pests and leaf eating caterpillars have a low preference for the silicic tissue than low silica containing succulent parts. Suppression of insect pests by the application of silicon was reported by many scientists (Ma and Takahashi, 2002).

Economics

The data on economics is given in Table 2. Among the different technology options, the maximum net return (Rs.76,900/-) and BCR (2.27) was observed for TO3 followed by TO2 (1.78). The lowest net income and BCR (1.36) was recorded by TO1.

Perception of farmers, who visited the experimental plots on the relative performance of crop

Feedback of farmers, who visited the experimental plots on the relative performance

of crops under different technological options were elicited and quantified (Table 3). 21 Farmers from Chadayamangalam block of Kollam district visited the experimental plots and recorded their observations. According to their opinion the number of tillers and productive tillers were more in silica applied plots. The disease and pest incidence was also lower in these plots i.e., plots under TO3.

Wide scale adoption of technology through ATMA, Department of Agriculture, Kollam

In active collaboration with the Department of Agriculture front line demonstrations of this technology were carried out for the previous three years (2013-2016) and covered 197 ha of rice field with severe iron, aluminum and manganese toxicity under 19 padasekharams. Outstanding yield was obtained from these plots (5.65 t/ha which was 32 per cent over the conventional method) i.e., adopting this new technology the farmers could harvest superior yield with reduced use of pesticides. The incidence of leaf folder and stem borer were reduced to 50% over traditional method. Hitherto rice fields of 17 panchayaths under 6 blocks have been successfully utilized the technology in Kollam district.

CONCLUSION

Silicon depletion coupled with Fe, Al and Mn toxicity and high acidity are more common in our tropical soil leading to poor productivity of rice. Approximately 60% rice area under Kollam district faces this problem. The outcomes of this farmer participatory experiment emphasized the importance of the alternate nutrient package including silica (OM 5 t/ha+ 90:45:120 kg N:P:K /

Table 2. Effect of nutrient management systems on yield and economics of rice

Technology options	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Net returns (Rs/ha)	B:C Ratio
Farmers practice (TO1)	4.47	7.5	23,470/-	1.36
Recommended practice (TO2)	5.62	7.7	51,100/-	1.78
Alternate practice (TO3).	6.61	9.29	76,900/-	2.27
CD(0.05)	0.463	0.804	-	-

Table 3. Perception of farmers visited the experimental plots, relative performance of crop

Technological Op- tions	Visual growth			Productive tillers			Pest incidence		
	Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High	Low	Medium	High
Farmers' practice (TO1)	7	14	0	19	2	0	0	0	21
Recommended prac- tice (TO2)	0	16	5	6	15	0	0	0	21
Alternate practice (TO3).	0	6	15	0	10	11	21	0	0

ha + 150 kg lime+100 kg silica) for yield increase in rice under iron toxic laterite soils. In addition to yield enhancement, the technology including silica has an additional benefit i.e., reduction of pest incidence. The response of the participating farmers on the technology option 3 was positive. The feedback of the farmers who visited the trial plots was also positive where they recorded that silica application has increased the growth and number of productive tillers. They also observed that silica application has reduced the incidence of pests. Hence the present investigation suggests the use of silica in the nutrient management programme of rice for enhanced productivity by alleviating the abiotic and biotic stresses along with beneficial effects of silicon fertilizer.

REFERENCES

- Ma J F and Takahashi E (2002). Silicon uptake and accumulation in higher plants. *Soil, fertiliser and Plant Silicon Res* **11**:8.
- Ma J F (2003). Role of silicon in enhancing the resistance of plants to biotic and abiotic stresses. *Soil Sci Plant Nutr* **50**(1): 11-18.
- Ma J F, Tamai K and Yamaji N (2006). *Nature* **440**: 688-691.
- Matichenkov V V and Calvert D V (2002). Silicon as a beneficial element for sugarcane. *J of American Society of Sugarcane Techno* **22**: 21-29
- Matichenkov V V and Calvert D V (1999). Silicon fertilizers for citrus in Florida. *Proc Fla State Hort S* **112**:5-8.
- Singh K K, Singh K, Singh R S and Chandel R S (2005). Silicon nutrition in rice- a review. *Agric Rev* **26**(3): 223-228.

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Study on Profile Characteristics of Women Self Help Group Members

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, SHGs have become significant institutions for rural development. It is now being increasingly realized that instead of targeting the individual in the process of development, it would be more useful to adopt the approach of group development. The group approach makes available the collective wisdom and combined resources for any task. With this background, a critical study of the evaluation of the profile characteristics of the SHGs and Non SHG members was carried out. The diagnostic study was confined to 10 villages from which 90 SHGs and 90 Non SHG respondents were selected for the study. The result revealed that the independent sample 'Z' test showed that there was significant difference in the mean values of SHG members and Non SHG members in case of education, family size, social participation, land holding, annual income, material possession, source of information, extension participation, achievement motivation, market orientation, risk orientation, innovativeness and attitude towards SHGs whereas, there was no significant difference in the mean values with respect to age, family type and marital status.

Key Words: SHG and Non SHG members, Self Help Groups, Profile characteristics

INTRODUCTION

In recent years self help groups (SHG) are emerging as alternative credit source to the poor. In self help groups, collective actions and solidarity is an important empowering mechanism. The empowerment of women through SHGs would lead to benefits not only to the individual woman and women groups but also for the family and community as a whole through collective action for development.

Self help groups also play a very vital and critical role towards empowering women in almost all the fields. In recent years the group approach to various poverty alleviation programmes is getting recognition in India. Mostly, women are mobilized into groups for undertaking mutually beneficial social and economic activities. The group provides women, a base for self-employment and empowerment through group dynamics. In India

the mutual help based groups are known as self help group. It is being realized in India that SHGs can establish relationship between the formal institutions and the poor for providing information, credit and other facilities.

It has been very well established that providing finance to the poor after organizing them into homogenous group commonly known as SHGs have given statutory results in India and other developing countries, especially among the rural poor women. Group approach to poverty alleviation is gaining momentum in India and other developing countries. This approach aims at inculcating the habits of saving even in small amounts, supplemented by borrowing from outside sources and rotation of saved and borrowed funds by lending within the group. Hence, present study was carried out to know the profile characteristics of SHG and non SHG members.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

Different five talukas of Amreli district were randomly selected where SHGs were formed under Integrated Watershed Management Programme. Two villages from each taluka were purposively selected where SHGs conducted their livelihood activities more than four years under IWMP. Villages having effective and coordinated working of SHG were also one of the criteria to select. In addition, from each village ninety women (n = 90) who were not members of SHG were studied for comparative purposes. SHG member and Non SHG member was the unit of analyses. The data were collected by personal interviews using a pre-tested structured schedule. The findings were tabulated, analyzed and presented in a different groups like socio, personal, economic, communicational and psychological characteristics of the SHG and Non SHG members.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile Characteristics of the SHG and Non SHG members

Age: Physical and psychological development of an individual is related to his age. It thus influences the interest and needs of an individual. It also plays a vital role in deciding future goals and expectations. It was evident from Table 1 that there was no significant difference in the mean values of SHG members (38.08) and Non SHG members (39.54) in case of age. This finding was in conformity with the finding of Naik *et al* (2012) and Shelke *et al* (2013).

Education: Education is a process of bringing desirable changes in knowledge, skill and attitude of an individual. Education in a society is a primary requirement for its socio-economic development. Formal education is helpful to the women to equip them to face difficulties and challenges in a better way. The data (Table 1) revealed the independent sample 'Z' test was highly significant difference in the mean values of SHG members (6.09) and Non SHG members (3.88) in case of education. In

general, it can be said in case of Non SHG members that women had poor and low economic status, rural social environment; poor education facilities during their childhood days and schools located in faraway were the contributing reason for low level of education. This finding was in conformity with those reported by Chandravadia (2009) and Gethanjali and Prabhakar (2013).

Family Size: Independent sample 'Z' test showed significant difference in the mean values of SHG members (5.87) and Non SHG members (6.43) for family size. This might be due to the fact that in case of SHG members' majority had nuclear family and aware about family planning as compared to Non SHG members and also because of the realization of the advantages of nuclear families in terms of educating their children, for saving money, assets, responsibilities, etc.

Social Participation: Membership in any social organizations provide platform to the women to exchange their views and feelings. It is believed that more social participation by the women in the family has greater influence on decision-making. Thus, to know the social participation of women in various organizations the information was gathered. In Table 1 the independent sample 'Z' test showed that there was highly significant difference in the mean values of SHG members (2.44) and Non SHG members (0.83) in case of social participation. It was observed during survey that most of the SHG members women were members in other SHGs groups' formation by ATMA as well as informal association including caste mandals, religious groups etc., which might have motivated them to take part in the social activities and to get the benefit of related to agriculture and livestock. This finding was supported by the results of George *et al* (2012).

Land holding: Land holding has been considered as one of the factors that determine the economic and social status. Size of land holding has also role in maintaining family and socio-economic development therefore, the variable land holding was included in present investigation. The

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independent sample 'Z' test showed that there was highly significant difference in the mean values of SHG members (1.47) and Non SHG members (1.00) in case of land holding. The finding is in agreement with the findings reported by Soni and Pandya (2007).

Material Possession: The independent sample 'Z' test showed that there was highly significant difference in the mean values of SHG members (27.77) and Non SHG members (15.81) in case of material possession. This could be attributed to the reasons like majority of the respondents belonged up to small land holding category and rest to landless category in case of Non SHG members. They cannot buy the improved agricultural implements

because of cost and feasibility of maintenance of implement. Hence the income level of respondents may restrict them to do so. These findings were in line with Devalatha (2005).

Annual Income: Annual income refers to the gross annual earning of family from all resources. It also indicated that socio-economic position of the individual affects the behaviour of them. Generally the sound and multipurpose activities can only be possible when money is available on hand. It was found from the Table 1 that there was significant difference in the mean values of SHG members (2.55) and Non SHG members (1.98) in case of annual income. Summarizing the findings it can be stated that overwhelming majority of the women

Table:1. Profile Characteristics of SHG and Non SHG members n=180

Sr. No.	Variables	Mean (SHG members)	Mean (Non SHG members)	Mean Difference	Z value
Socio-Personal Variables					
1	Age	38.08	39.54	1.467	1.523NS
2	Education	6.09	3.88	2.21	4.59**
3	Family type	1.42	1.50	0.08	1.04NS
4	Family Size	5.87	6.43	0.567	2.14*
5	Marital Status	1.97	1.98	0.011	0.451NS
6	Social Participation	2.44	0.83	1.61	6.259**
Economic variables					
7	Land holding	1.47	1.00	0.47	3.07**
8	Material Possession	27.77	15.81	11.96	6.577**
9	Annual Income	2.55	1.98	0.572	2.606*
Communication Variables					
10	Source of Information	24.93	13.62	11.31	12.45**
11	Extension Participation	8.62	3.49	5.13	18.79**
Psychological variables					
12	Achievement motivation	7.96	5.63	2.32	10.23**
13	Market Orientation	16.72	10.51	6.21	11.37**
14	Risk Orientation	3.03	2.34	0.689	7.41**
15	Innovativeness	9.03	5.83	3.20	12.54**
16	Attitude towards SHGs	66.89	36.86	30.03	27.23**

had low to medium annual income in case of Non SHG members because they were resources poor and having poor knowledge about the efficient use of resources to raise their income. This finding was in agreement with the findings of Soni (2009).

Source of Information: Information seeking was operationally defined as the frequency of contact or exposure of women to different sources for obtaining information regarding their enterprises. The independent sample 'Z' test showed that there was highly significant difference in the mean values of SHG members (24.93) and Non SHG members (13.62) in case of source of information. The probable reason might be that the majority of the respondents had low level of education, social participation, extension participation and mass media exposure in case of Non SHG members. This finding was in conformity with the finding reported by Devalatha (2005), Biradar (2008) and Sharma and Das (2012).

Extension Participation: Extension participation helps the women to acquire knowledge about their business, scientific practices in agriculture, animal husbandry and household activities to solve their problems with the help of extension personnel. There was highly significant difference in the mean values of SHG members (8.62) and Non SHG members (3.49) in case of extension participation. It can be pointed out that majority of the SHG members had medium level of extension participation. This type of result is attributed to, District Watershed Development Unit, Krishi Vigyan Kendra, ATMA activities and Krishi Mahostav programme. While in case of Non SHG respondents had in low level of extension participation this might be poor education, low social participation, low mass media exposure, etc. and also lack of awareness in different extension activities may also contribute for the above said observation. These findings were similar to those of Devalatha *et al* (2013).

Achievement motivation: It is defined as a value associated with women, which drives her to excel

in their business and related fields to reach a sense of personal accomplishment. A highly significant difference in the mean values of SHG members (7.96) and Non SHG members (5.63) in case of achievement motivation was observed. Hence, it can be concluded that overwhelming majority of the SHG members had medium to very high level of achievement motivation. Obviously it can be said that all of the SHG members involved in the entrepreneurial activities were with mentality of medium to high level of realistic estimation of progressive and prosperous life in future and might have understood and realized significance of their business to reach up to high level of progressive and prosperous life as compared to Non SHG members and in case of Non SHG respondents majority had low level achievement motivation due to poor educational level, low mass media exposure, low level of innovativeness and risk orientation, very less entrepreneurial activities had taken up, etc. The finding was in concurrence with the findings reported by George *et al* (2012).

Market orientation:

The market orientation is such a psychological trait that is associated with market related implementation to manage their business. This helps the respondents to analyze market intelligence to avail better price of their products. The independent sample 'Z' test showed that there was highly significant difference in the mean values of SHG members (16.72) and Non SHG members (10.51) in case of market orientation. Thus, it can be concluded that all the SHG members had medium to high level of market orientation as the SHG members had taken up entrepreneurial activities, where constant touch with market is must to recognize suitable place for selling the products at high rate as investment in the transportation and other input is more against high fluctuation in prices of products leads them to become more market oriented. While in case of Non SHG groups very less number of the respondents had involved in entrepreneurial activities and had landless, marginal and small farmers and that's why they had low level of market orientation.

Profile of Self Help Groups

Risk orientation

The risk orientation is described as the degree to which an individual is oriented towards the risk and uncertainty and has courage to face the problems in their business. This is one of the important qualities to manage risks. It could be seen (Table 1) that there was highly significant difference in the mean values of SHG members (3.03) and Non SHG members (2.34) in case of risk orientation. Hence it can be said that majority of the Non SHG members were low level of risk orientation. This might be up to primary level of education and illiteracy and the respondents were not in a position to withstand economic losses and entrepreneurial activities is taken by some of the Non SHG members and is somewhat risky business as perceived by them and Non SHG members might have preferred to take calculative risk to prevent loss in the business. This finding was in line with result reported by George *et al* (2012).

Innovativeness

It is orientation of individual to get linked or closing associated with change adopting innovative ideas and practices and hence, it plays an important role in influencing socio-economic change and their by empowerment of an individual. There was highly significant difference in the mean values of SHG members (9.03) and Non SHG members (5.83) in case of innovativeness. Thus, it can be concluded that in case of SHG members had more innovativeness as compared to Non SHG members. This might be due to poor economic condition, poor education, and low level of mass media exposure, low extension and social participation as compared to SHG members. This finding was in concurrence with the findings reported by Devalatha *et al* (2013) and Verma *et al* (2013).

Attitude towards SHGs

Attitude strength is an important determinant of the attitude-behavior relationship. Strong attitudes are based on past knowledge and may be retrieved, whereas weak attitude is often constructed on the

spot. Strong attitudes have more impact on behavior, are less susceptible to self-perception effects and are more stable over time (Holland *et al* 2002). Attitudes are relatively stable and once adopted, provide a long-term positive effect (Olgyaiova *et al* 2005). It was evident (Table 1) that there was highly significant difference in the mean values of SHG members (66.89) and Non SHG members (36.86) in case of attitude towards SHGs. It can be concluded that vast majority of the SHG members were high to very high level of attitude towards Self Help Groups. This is because of the most of the respondents had benefited a lot by the SHG under the project IWMP and due to improvement in their socio-economic condition. This finding was in line with the findings of Meena and Singh (2013) and Sangeetha *et al* (2013).

CONCLUSION

It could be concluded that the SHG members have been benefited by microfinance. It has helped them in their socio-economic upliftment. The women now feel that they can also be partners in the process of family welfare by joining the SHG movement. This study has also indicated that even though the members have joined the SHGs for various reasons, all of them have one common goal, which is seeking a better standard of living via a better organization that works for their benefits. Hence, it could be concluded that the SHGs have proved that they could serve as an alternative instrument of financial intermediation for the poor. Also, the microfinance services offered by them have helped to push back. SHG can contribute to changes in economic conditions, social status, decision making and increases women in outdoor activities. These SHGs play a very important role in social change

REFERENCES

- Biradar B N (2008). *A study on impact of income generating activities on sustainable rural livelihoods of kawad project beneficiaries*. MSc (Ag.) thesis, University of Agricultural Science, Dharwad.

- Chandravadiya K U (2009). *Role of SHG for empowerment of women*. MSc (Ag.) thesis, Junagadh Agricultural University, Junagadh.
- Devalatha C M (2005). *Profile study of women SHGs in Gadag district of Northern Karnataka*. MSc (Ag.) thesis, University of Agricultural Science, Dharwad.
- Devalatha C M, Hirevenkara G L V and Ramchandran V A (2013). Socio- economic and psychological status of self help group members in Northern Karnataka. *Agriculture Update* **8**(3):496-503
- Gethanjali R and Prabhakar K (2013). Economic Development of women through SHGs in YSR district, Andhra Pradesh, India. *Stud Home Com Sci* **7**(1): 25-34.
- George A Rajkamal, P J and Jiji R S (2012). Analysis of socio-personal profile of livestock based self help group members of Thrissur district. *J Ind Vet Assoc Kerala* **10** (1):38-42.
- Holland R W, Verplanken B and Knippenberg A (2002). On the nature of attitude behavior relations: The strong guide, the weak follow. *European J Social Psychology* **32**: 869–76.
- Meena M S and Singh K M (2013). Impact of self help groups on attitudes of members. *Indian J Agril Sci* **83** (9):971-976.
- Naik R M, Tandel B M and Chauhan N M (2012). Empowerment of rural women through SHGs. *Agriculture Update*, **7**(3 & 4):342-345.
- Olgyaiova K, Pongra'cz E, Mikkola T, Radoslav S, Kapa R and Keiski R L (2005). *Attitudes toward waste minimization in Finland and Czech Republic barriers and drivers*. In: Proceedings of the RESOPT Closing Seminar Waste Minimization and Utilization in Oulu Region: Drivers and Constraints. Oulu University Press, Oulu, pp 85–109.
- Sangeetha V, Bahal, R, Singh P and Venkatesh P (2013). Impact of NGO-led Self-Help Groups on the empowerment of rural women-experience from South India. *Outlook on Agri* **42**(1): 59-63.
- Sharma G N and Das D (2012). Micro finance, self help groups (SHGs) and the socioeconomic development of rural people (A case study with special reference to the Lakhimpur district of Assam). *Asian J Res in Business Econ and Management*. **2**(4): 145-159.
- Shelke S A, Gohad V V and Shinde P P (2013). Knowledge of the members about working of the self help groups. *Agriculture Update*. **8**(4):613-615.
- Soni (2009). *Socio-economic change in rural tribal women through self help groups*. In: seminar on Participatory approach and recent trends in rural development, Junagadh 31st August 2009. Junagadh Agricultural University, Junagadh. pp: 19.
- Soni A N and Pandya C D (2007). Socio-Economic change in Tribal farm women through Self Help Groups. *Gujarat J Ext Edu* **18-19**: 24-26.
- Verma N K, Pandey D K and Upadhyay A D (2013). Performance Evaluation of Fishery Based Self Help Groups in West Tripura. *Indian Res J Ext Edu* **13** (3): 15-18.

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Volatility in Price of Rubber Crop in Kerala

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ABSTRACT

Rubber is an important plantation crop cultivated in Kerala. The state holds a dominant position both in area and production. It is the main source of income for majority of farmers. Any volatility in the price of rubber put them in a miserable situation. Recent years witnessed unprecedented volatility in rubber price. Declining trend in the prices of rubber has pushed natural rubber production the lowest in the country. The study revealed that prices were so low so that the rubber cultivators cannot even pay workers wages and the recent unprecedented volatility in prices declined rubber production leads to the falling standard of living of the rubber farmers in Kerala.

Key words: Kerala, Price, Rubber, Cultivators, Volatility.

INTRODUCTION

Major rubber producing states in India are Kerala, Tamilnadu and Karnataka; other includes Tripura, Assam, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Manipur, Goa, Andaman and Nicobar Islands. Kerala is in the forefront and is one of the most plantation crop cultivated. Of the total rubber produced in the country 92 per cent, and in area 84 per cent is the contribution of Kerala.

Rubber cultivators in Kerala are mainly small growers and any financial constraints, fluctuations in price or backwardness in technology will affect the growers considerably. In the state, 10 lakh farmers directly and indirectly depended upon and the capital employment opportunity ratio the rubber providing is 40 per cent employment for one crore rupees and is a main source of tax to state governments. The manufacturing units using rubber were facing problems because of the volatility in the price of natural rubber. About 11 lakh small rubber growers are facing crisis due to fall in price. Price of natural rubber is determined by international market. In Kerala, the price of one kilogram of natural rubber had decreased from Rs. 245/- in 2011 to Rs. 102/- in 2016. However, the cost of cultivation in this sector is increasing. Therefore, the main objectives of the

study was to analyse the trend in volatility of price of rubber and its effect on rubber production and productivity and problems faced by small growers in Kerala.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study used both primary and secondary data. The primary data were collected through sample survey from Kerala with the help of a well structured questionnaire. The secondary data were collected from official website of Rubber Board, Rubber Board office and publications of Govt. of Kerala and India. Growth rate and percentages are used for data analysis. Compound Growth Rates (CGR) of area, production and productivity of rubber for the period were estimated with the following exponential model.

$$Y = abt$$

The growth rate (GR) has been computed using the formula: $GR = (\text{Antilog } b-1)100$

The F test has been applied to test the significance of b.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During 1960's, the first five main crops in terms of area were rice, coconut, tapioca, rubber

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and pepper in the descending order of shares to the total cropped area. But at present, rubber occupied second position in area compared to other crops. The percentage increase in area under rubber was 328; among the districts Thiruvananthapuram recorded highest percentage increase in area. The growth of rubber-output decomposed in real and monetary terms (Karunakaran, 2015) revealed the dominance of monetary growth over real growth; the overall growth is actually monetary growth rather than real growth.

Volatility in the price of rubber in Kerala

Natural and synthetic rubber is interchanged for various usages. When price of natural rubber rises automatically the demand for synthetic will increase. In addition, petro-chemical products used for making synthetic rubber also have an indirect effect on natural rubber price.

The average farm harvest price of rubber in Kerala during 2000 to 2015 is presented in Table 1. The highest price was noticed during the year 2011-

12; after that fast decline noticed.

Trend in the volatility in price of rubber in Kerala

The marketing and export of rubber is commonly adopted through different channels. The leading export markets are China, Malaysia, Indonesia, Turkey, Sri Lanka, Spain and Nepal. More than 90 per cent of the rubber produced in India is from Kerala. 80 per cent of the area under rubber in Kerala is accounted by small holdings and is generally grown in the midlands and highlands. The small holding under rubber in Kerala is mainly homestead planting and is lying adjacent to each other.

Data (Table 2) show the volatility in rubber price of Kerala in terms of growth rate during the period 1961-2015. It clearly revealed that there is an increasing and decreasing trend in price. Rubber price showed an increasing trend in 1991 and this continued up to 1995. Since then there was a negative trend in growth rate. After 2001,

Table 1. Average farm harvest price of Rubber in Kerala.

Sr. No	Year	Price (Rs/q)	Annual Growth rate (per cent)
1	2000-01	3,036	-
2	2001-02	3,228	1.92
3	2002-03	3,919	6.91
4	2003-04	5,040	11.21
5	2004-05	5,570	5.30
6	2005-06	6,699	11.29
7	2006-07	9,204	25.05
8	2007-08	9,390	1.86
9	2008-09	10,112	7.22
10	2009-10	11,498	13.86
11	2010-11	19,003	75.05
12	2011-12	20,805	18.02
13	2012-13	17,682	-31.23
14	2013-14	16,602	-10.80
15	2014-15	13,257	-33.45

Source: Computed from Rubber Board office, Kottayam, Kerala.

Rubber Crop in Kerala

Table 2. Growth rate of Rubber price in Kerala (1961-2015)

Sr. No	Year	Growth rate (in percent)
1	1961-1965	-2.75
2	1966-1970	6.67
3	1971-1975	8.11
4	1976-1980	4.31
5	1981-1985	6.07
6	1986-1990	4.44
7	1991-1995	9.31
8	1996-2000	-13.58
9	2001-2005	9.09
10	2006-2010	8.34
11	2011-2015	-8.66

Source: Computed from Rubber Board office, Kottayam, Kerala.

growth rate again increased; but the present trend is negative (-8.66 percent).

Effects of volatility in rubber price of Kerala

The analysis revealed unprecedented volatility in rubber price. So there was a sharp decline in rubber production and productivity in Kerala. Table

3, 4 show the area, production and productivity of rubber during 1960-61 to 2014-15. Production and productivity has declined during 2013-14 to 2014-15.

Originally rubber was introduced into areas with degraded forests; from there it spread all over. It replaced natural vegetation, tapioca, cashew nut, fruit trees and coconut (Chattopadhyay, 2015). The area, production and productivity of rubber crop had tremendously increased (Table 3, 4). From 2013-14 to 2014-15, production and productivity has declined tremendously due to sharp fall in price and consequent reduction of tapping by rubber growers.

The rubber farmers cultivate in more than 60 per cent of their land and considerable investment has been done to maintain the plantations. The major share of their income is from this crop. The expenditure for maintaining the holdings is increasing and the cost of cultivation is very high irrespective of the decrease in price. Decrease in income has compelled the farmers to reduce expenses on fertilizers and other inputs used. The analysis revealed certain important results: (i) the decrease in price reduced confidence among rubber growers which compelled them to shift to other crops, (ii) the wide fluctuations in the price of rubber and the consequent reduction in income of

Table 3. Area, production and productivity of Rubber in Kerala

Year	1960-61	1970-71	1980-81	1990-91	2000-01	2013- 14	2014- 15
Area (000 ha)	122.9	179.3	237.7	411.6	474.4	548.2	549.9
Production (000t)	23.0	78.7	140.3	307.5	579.9	648.2	507.7
Productivity (kg/ha)	187	439	590	747	1222	1182	923

Source: Computed from Rubber Board office, Kottayam, Kerala.

Table 4. Compound growth rates of area, production and productivity of rubber in Kerala.

Sr. No.	Item	1960-69	1970-79	1980-89	1990-99	2000-15	1960-2015
1	Area	3.65	1.99	6.49	1.41	1.08	3.08
2	Production	*	6.11	7.64	7.35	4.01	6.71
3	Productivity	10.73	3.82	1.09	5.85	3.02	3.20

* Significant at probability level 0.01

the farmers put them in a miserable situation. Some rubber growers were found unable to complete the construction of their house, marriage of children, education of children started, etc during the period due to decrease in price and (iii) when the price of rubber came below cost of production, cultivation became unprofitable to farmers.

Table 5. Income to farmers from rubber cultivation (in percent)

Sr. No	Amount (in Rs)	Percentage
1	Below 10,000	44
2	10,000-20,000	46
3	20,000-30,000	6
4	Above-30,000	4
5	Total	100

Source: primary data

Most of the farmers are tapping rubber trees between 100 to 200 numbers and rubber sheet is below 10 in number. 46 percentages of farmers are earning income between Rs. 10000-20000 and 44 percent below Rs. 10000 (table 5). The percentage of rubber cultivators using labour skill is very small. The efficiency of labour depends on the education

and training imparted to them and wages. Tapping wages constitute a major component of cost of production.

CONCLUSION

Rubber is an agro-industry based product in which 10 lakh farmers are directly involved. There is a scarcity of 2 lakh tonne of natural rubber in the world market today. The farmers in Kerala are facing many problems due to volatility in price; so a scheme that guarantees minimum price of Rs. 150/-kg. for natural rubber sheets produced was implemented by state government. The government should provide more incentives to protect the small rubber growers and also stop the import of natural rubber; otherwise there will be a shift from rubber growing to other crops.

REFERENCES

- Karunakaran N (2015), "Growth of crop output in Kerala: is it real or monetary", *Artha J Social Sci* **14**(4): 89-109.
- Chattopadhyay Srikumar (2015), *Environmental Consequences of Rubber Plantations in Kerala*, Discussion paper No. 44, CDS, Thiruvananthapuram: 1-54.

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Management of Mastitis in Dairy Cattle using Herbal Combination

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INTRODUCTION

Mastitis is the one the most commonly encountered economic problem in the field by the dairy farmers. Bovine mastitis, the inflammation of the mammary gland is primarily caused by pathogenic microorganisms, is a major health hazard for the dairy industry. Mastitis affects the quality and quantity of milk. Mastitis is a pervasive and costly disease that afflicts mammary glands worldwide. In the dairy industry, a clinical case of bovine mastitis can cost greater than Rs.5,000/- up to Rs.20,000/- in high-yielding cows due to milk yield losses, increased mortality, and treatment costs (Bar *et al*, 2008; Cha *et al*, 2011).

Mastitis is detrimental to the health of the cow, and its negative effects can impact cow reproduction, milk yield and shelf life of dairy products derived from the cow's milk (Schrack *et al*, 2001). Ethano veterinary medicines refer to people's belief, knowledge, skill and practice relating to care of their farm (Martin *et al*, 2001). Aloe vera has been used as an immune stimulant in both humans and animals with no adverse reactions. A review of controlled human clinical trials reported that Aloe vera gel applied topically to a wound site speeds the healing process and when taken orally can lower blood glucose in diabetic patients (Vogler and Ernst, 1999). The application of Aloe vera based herbal paste for treating the mastitis has been standardized by Directorate of Distance Education, Tamil Nadu University of Veterinary and Animal sciences. Hence, demonstration was taken to validate this

herbal combinations effectiveness against mastitis in dairy cattle and also to reduce the cost spend towards the treatment by cattle growers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Selection of animal

A total of 50 mastitis affected cattle were selected in Dharmapuri district to demonstrate the herbal treatment. Animals were selected irrespective of age, body weight, breed and type of mastitis. Mastitis diagnosed on the basis of abnormality of milk, hardening of udder, change in quality and quantity of milk. Physiological parameters in all the animals were in normal condition.

Preparation of herbal paste

The ingredients required for the preparation of herbal paste were 200 g Aloe vera (3 leaves), 50g turmeric powder (handful quantity) and 5g lime (size of tamarind seed). Three Aloe vera leaves had chaffed with leave blade into a 2 X 2cm small piece and grinded to became a bubble mixed greenish paste without adulteration of water. Then handful of turmeric powder along with tamarind seed size lime were added into the paste, further grinding of the ingredients to became reddish paste. This prepared paste was used for this study.

Application method

The affected udder was drained completely. It was rubbed using coir pith for cleaning of debris and other stained infectious material. The udder was washed with clean water.

A handful of paste was taken into to a bowel and diluted with 100 ml of pure water. The paste now became a herbal solution. This was applied over the both affected and normal udder. Three hours later the udder was cleaned and drained as stated previously and again the solution was applied over the udder. The same procedure was repeated for 8 times per day for 5 days. The herbal paste was prepared freshly for application everyday and old paste was discarded.

Parameter recorded

Random numbers of 10 milk samples were analyzed for pH, conductivity, California Mastitis Test (CMT), Somatic Cell Count (SCC) and microbial organism before and after the proposed herbal treatment by using standard procedure. Duration of normal secretions of milk (in days), reduction of size of affected udder (in days) and Economics (in percentage) were recorded and analyzed using statistical software SPSS 16.0

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result of the present study was present in table 1&2. In the present study grinding and mixture of Aloe vera, turmeric powder and lime had given good results for the management of clinical mastitis in dairy cattle as reported by Mooventhan et al (2016) where it has been documented the indigenous practices and its procedure for the

management of clinical mastitis in dairy cattle.

In the present study pH, conductivity and somatic cell count of mastitis milk were found higher compared to control whereas it was found lesser in the herbal treatment after 5d of post treatment .In the present study California Mastitis Test was found negative after treatment. This indicates the control of mammary infection. E. coli was found in control whereas Streptococcus and E.coli were found in demonstration samples. These results were in concurrence with results of Kiltte *et al* (2008). Nurdin *et al* (2011) reported that quality and quantity of the milk was increased in subclinical mastitis with supplementation of Black Cumin, Curcuma zeodharia, Curcuma mangga and Curcuma aeruginosa in dairy cattle. In the present investigation, the use of Aloe vera, turmeric and lime resulted in normal secretion of milk in 4.8 days whereas in control it takes 4.0 days. Reduction of size of affected udder in the present study was noticed after 3.3 days.

In the present study 100 per cent success was noticed without any post treatment complications in the herbal treatment demonstration. Compared to control group herbal paste application for mastitis had given good results with less input cost outcome and conventional treatment had required ten times higher cost than herbal treatment.

Table 1. Average change in milk pH, conductivity, California Mastitis Test (CMT), Somatic Cell Count (SCC) and microbial organism in control and mastitis cattle at different intervals.

Sr.No	Parameter	Normal milk	control	Herbal treatment
1	pH	6.4±0.14	7.4±1.12	6.6±0.69
2	Conductivity(µg/cm)	0.6±0.02	1±0.05	0.8±0.04
3	California Mastitis Test	No clump	Clumping noticed	No clump
4	Somatic Cell Count (cells/ml) in lakhs	1.5±0.12	2.75 ± 2.12	1.95 ± 1.18
5	Quality of Microbial organism	<i>E. Coli</i>	<i>Streptococcus</i> and <i>E.coli spp</i>	<i>Streptococcus</i> and <i>E.coli8 spp</i>

Management of Mastitis in Dairy Cattle

Herbal treatment for mastitis in dairy cattle of Dharmapuri district

Examination of udder and milk

Decolouration of milk

Application of herbal paste

Normal secretion of milk

Reduction of size of quarter

CONCLUSION

Mixture of Aloe vera (200g), turmeric powder (50g) and lime (5g) paste was found to be suitable to treat all type of mastitis without any adverse effects. The treated animal recovered within 5d after treatment. The conventional treatment needs ten times higher cost than herbal treatment for treating mastitis. The farmers can use this herbal treatment application as preventive strategy to treat the mastitis.

REFERENCES

- Bar D, L W Tauer, G Bennett, R N González, J A Hertl, Y H Schukken, H F Schulte, F L Welcome and Y T Gröhn (2008). The cost of generic clinical mastitis in dairy cows as estimated by using dynamic programming. *J Dairy Sci* **91**: 2205-2214. doi:10.3168/jds.2007-0573.
- Cha E, D Bar, J A Hertl, L W Tauer, G Bennett, R N González, Y H Schukken, F L Welcome and Y T Gröhn (2011). The cost and management of different types of clinical mastitis in dairy cows estimated by dynamic programming. *J Dairy Sci* **94**:4476-4487. doi:10.3168/jds.2010-4123.

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- Kilte A Y, Waghmare S P, Mode S G and Arun Handa (2008). Efficacy of indigenous herbal preparation on altered milk pH, somatic cell count and electrolyte profile in subclinical mastitis in cow. *Vety World* **8**:239-240.
- Martin M, McCordle C M and Mathisa E (2001). *Ethano veterinary medicine An annotated bibliography of community Animal Health care*. Intermediate Technology Development Group publishing, London.
- Mooventhan P, Manimaran A, Senthilkumar R, Sakthivel selvan A and Arul Prakash M(2016). Indigenous ethno veterinary medicinal practices for management of mastitis in dairy cattle. *Indian J.Anim Res* **50**:137-139
- Nurdin E, Amelia T and Makin M (2011). The effects of herbs on milk yield and milk quality of mastitis dairy cow. *J Indonesian Trop Anim Agric* **36**:104-108.
- Schrick F N, M E Hockett, A M Saxton, M J Lewis, H H Dowlen and S P Oliver(2001). Influence of subclinical mastitis during early lactation on reproductive parameters. *J Dairy Sci* **84**:1407-1412. doi:10.3168/jds.S0022-0302(01)70172-5.
- Vogler B K and E Ernst (1999). Aloe vera: a systematic review of its clinical effectiveness. *Br J Gen Pract* **49**:823-828.

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Innovative Way for Collection of Combine Harvested Paddy Straw

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INTRODUCTION

Janjgir –Champa district is mechanization area of state and agro-climatic zone is a called Chhattisgarh plain. The total geographical area of the district is 446674 ha. The average rainfall of the district is 1150mm while normal rainfall is 1477.8mm. The main crop which has been grown in this area is paddy and other crops are grown in considerable amount like wheat, gram, mustard, arhar, black gram and green gram.

The problem of unavailability of labour for crop cultivation is increasing day by day. Hence, now even in paddy now a day farmers using combine harvester for harvesting of paddy. The use of tractor operated and self propelled combine leaves behind enormous quantity of paddy straw which is difficult to arrange for every farmers of paddy nearly equal amount of straw remain in the fields which is normally burnt by the farmers. This practice damages the soil quality, create pollution and also affect on availability of feed paddy straw for cattle. To overcome this problems and save energy Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Janjgir-Champa conceptualized an efficient method to collect paddy straw. Hence in order to save energy, an efficient mechanism have been development to collect paddy straw after application of combine harvester.

Straw management

The combine harvesting has been taken up on large scale on custom hiring service. The use of tractor operated and self-propelled combines leaves behind enormous quantities of organic matter,

which is difficult to manage. For every four tones of rice and wheat , nearly 6-7t of straw produced which shows a huge amount of residue available for disposal every year. The total yield of paddy straw in combine-harvested paddy field is 10-12 t/ha and the yield of standing stubbles and loose straw are about 60 and 40 per cent, respectively (Anonymous, 2002). At present, the leftover straw and stubble is burnt to prepare the field for crops but this method damages soil quality and causes pollution.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this new innovative practice farmers required tractor, cultivator and steel mash having size 7 X 1ft or 8 X 1.1 ft. This mesh tied behind the cultivator through simple steel wire. This mesh keep just 5cm above the ground. Tractor in the field in one direction and collecting spreaded straw easily 3 to 4 places collect the straw which after lifted in trolley manually.

Design considerations

Farmers can collect easily with their available resources (Tractor & Cultivator). It should be economical in operation, variety should not affect the technology, no need of additional knowledge and field situation no bar.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In collection of harvested paddy straw from one hectare area required 300 minutes with 5 labours where as with tractor operation it can be collected within 45 minutes. In manual collection of straw

Jain and Shantaiya

Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Janjgir-Champa, Chhattisgarh have devised a way to collect leftover paddy straw from the fields by attached a simple steel-mesh to a tractor drawn cultivator.

Length: 7-8 ft
Width: 1.1 ft
Above the ground level: 5 cm or 2 inch
Cost of attachment: Rs.150/-

Table 1. Technical Specification of wire-mesh attached TD cultivator.

Particulars	Specification
Total length	2.13 to 2.20m or 7 to 8 ft
Width	0.30 m or 1.1ft
Above the Ground level height	5 cm or 2 inch
Cost of Technique	Rs.150/-

with there labours 8 hrs @ 200/- per day costing 625/- per ha where as in tractor operation cost just one third i.e., Rs.200/- ha. One hactare paddy produce near 30-40q paddy straw which is term of rupees near about Rs.700/- that additional income to farmers if collected instead of burning of straw.

Table 2. Results of different parameters of wire-mesh attached TD cultivator.

Technique	Manual	Cultivator attachment
Time required to collect straw/ha	300 minutes	45 minutes
Cost of operation (Rs. 200 /labour)	625/- (5 labours & 5 hrs)	200/- (Tractor rent)
Quantity of collected paddy straw	Nil	4 tonnes
Earned cost of paddy straw	Nil	Rs.7650/-

CONCLUSION

After observing results of this technology at KVK, farmers started to utilize in their field for collecting paddy straw by making use of this innovative technique.

REFERENCES

Anonymous (2002). Annual report of project, Mechanization of rice wheat cropping system for increasing the productivity 2001-02. Department of Farm Power and Machinery, PAU, Ludhiana.

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Udder and Teat Characteristics of Surti Buffaloes Maintained Under Farm and Field Conditions

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The information with respect to udder and teat characteristics of Surti buffaloes maintained under farm and field conditions are scanty. Therefore, an attempt have been made for evaluating and documenting Surti buffaloes for udder and teat characteristics during different lactations, maintained both under farm and field conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The data for this study were recorded on 80 Surti buffaloes maintained at Livestock Research Station, Vallabhnagar, and 260 Surti buffaloes maintained by farmers in the field. Buffaloes in advance pregnancy (≥ 7 months) and those calved recently (up to 1 months) were not included in the study. Eighty farm and 260 field surti buffaloes were evaluated for udder and teat characters during different lactation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The majority of surti buffaloes had straight as well as medium and small milk vein, bowl type udder, cylindrical teats, pointed teat tip. The shrinkage of udder was very low after first lactation but after three lactation the udder had 3-4 folds on the rear side.

Comparative udder and teat characteristics of Surti buffaloes maintained both at farm and field

are presented in Table 1. About 81 per cent of buffaloes at the farm has straight milk vein. Out of which 60.0 per cent were classified as medium and 21.3 per cent as small milk vein. In all 18.7 per cent buffaloes at the farm had large milk vein and convoluted. On the other hand, the Surti buffaloes maintained by the farmers had 6.92 per cent large and convoluted milk vein. Saini and Gill (1988) observed about 85.9 per cent of the buffaloes had straight milk-vein, where as 4.3 and 9.8 per cent of the buffaloes had convoluted and non-apparent milk-vein respectively in Murrah buffaloes. The frequency of buffaloes according to size of milk-vein across different lactations indicated that all the first and second calver had low to medium size milk-vein sometimes non-apparent, which is in evidence to low milk production during I and II lactations as compared to subsequent lactations. A well developed milk-vein reflects better production potential, which was observed for III and latter lactations in Surti and Surti type buffaloes maintained both at farm and field. In general, it may be concluded that milk- vein in buffaloes was not as prominent as in cattle.

At farm 98.7 per cent of the animals has bowl type udder. The respective values for Surti and Surti-type buffaloes maintained by the farmers were 78.7 and 88.7 per cent. The results also indicated

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Table –1 Comparative udder and teat characteristics of Surti- type buffaloes maintained at farm and field

Lactation	No. of observation Large	Milk vein			Udder shape			Teat shape				Teat Tip			
		Me- dium	Small	Bowl	Round	Goat type	Pen- du- lous	Cylin- dri- cal	Funnel shaped	Pear shaped	Bottle shaped	Point- ed	Round	Flat	
1	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
Pooled Farm	80	15 (18.7)	48 (60.0)	17 (21.3)	79 (98.7)	--	--	1 (1.3)	54 (67.6)	9 (11.2)	9 (11.2)	8 (10.0)	27 (33.7)	41 (51.3)	12 (15.0)
Field S	127	10 (7.9)	86 (67.7)	31 (24.4)	100 (78.7)	18 (14.2)	1 (0.8)	8 (6.3)	106 (83.4)	19 (15.0)	1 (0.8)	1 (0.8)	119 (93.7)	8 (6.3)	--
ST	133	7 (5.3)	83 (62.4)	43 (32.3)	118 (88.7)	11 (8.3)	1 (0.7)	3 (2.3)	130 (97.7)	03 (2.3)	--	--	126 (94.7)	6 (4.6)	1 (90.7)
Pooled field	260	18 (6.9)	169 (65.0)	73 (28.1)	218 (84.0)	29 (11.1)	3 (1.1)	10 (3.8)	237 (91.1)	21 (8.1)	1 (0.4)	1 (0.4)	244 (93.9)	13 (5.0)	3 (1.1)

Figures in parenthesis indicates percentage

S= Surti

ST= Surti type

Udder and Teat Characteristics of Surti Buffaloes

that animals with pendulous udder increased with increase in lactation number. Saini and Gill (1988) observed 76.6, 14.3, 1.6 and 7.4 per cent Murrah buffaloes had bowl, round, goat and flat type udder respectively.

The percentage of buffaloes with cylindrical, funnel, pear and bottle shaped teats was 67.6, 11.2 and 10.0, respectively in farm buffaloes whereas it was 83.4, 15, 0.8 per cent in Surti and 97.7, 2.3, 0.0 and 0.0 per cent Surti-type buffaloes maintained by the farmers. The percentage of buffaloes with cylindrical, funnel, bottle and pear shaped teats as 71.5, 24.2, 4.0 and 0.4, respectively was also reported by Saini and Gill, 1988.

CONCLUSION

Percentage of buffaloes with round, pointed and flat teat tip was 33.7, 51.3 and 15.0 at the farm, whereas it was 93.7, 6.0 and 0.0 in Surti and 94.7,

4.6 and 0.7 in Surti-type buffaloes at farmers herd. The observations on udder shape of dry buffaloes indicated that the shrinkage of udder was very low in buffaloes which had completed Just first lactation. The comparative shrinkage in subsequent lactations. The animals which had completed 3 or more lactations, had udders with 3-4 folds on the rear side. In most of the cases, the front attachment was showing the dry udder up to six months of pregnancy in non-lactating buffaloes, no variable change was observed with respect to udder development except few animals.

REFERENCES

Saini A L and Gill R S (1988). Milk production in relation to variation in size and shape of udder and teats in Murrah buffaloes. Proceeding of II world buffalo congress, vol. II, PP 70-75.

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Message

Dear readers,

Ushering this edition in the year 2017 with NAAS rating elevated from 2.77 to 4.41 in a year's span itself is complimentary and commendable to share. From the sidelines of political potpourri the drive which we all Indians, must join being a citizen of India is "Swatch Bharat".

I hereby do not endorse or promote any political agenda but believing that it has become a must, since we are the second most populated nation for the heck of good health of our future - for our children. We must have health and hygiene as our principle responsibility in all its measures.

Do we not need to keep our environment clean! What about unhealthy eating and littering habits! Government is trying through public media about use of toilets and sanitation but how far is its implementation.

Should we not come forward to monitor at least in area where we are working, residing or even commuting. Yes, Please lets be vigilant and police defaulters with bad habits of spitting on roads, puking here and there, throwing eats and surplus out in open. Smoking of cigarettes, bidies, tobacco for that matter must be banned if not possible then at least not be allowed in public. We need to leave a legacy of good habits mainly of clean thoughts , clean mind and clean environment.

I humbly pray that all Indians give it a due thought and make the nation worth living atleast for our future generations.

Wishing you all joining Swatch Bharat Campaign in your own way but to a meaning.

Thanks & Regards

A handwritten signature in black ink, consisting of stylized loops and a long horizontal stroke.

Shabnam Sharma, Principal,
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For Chapters in book

Barnabas A P and Lakshmiswaramma M (1980). “Assessment of Evaluation system for Rural development”. In: *Monitoring and Evaluation of Rural Development: Some Asian Experiences*. (eds Kuldeep Mathu and Inayatulloah) Kuala Lumpur U.N. Asian and Pacific Development Centre. Pp: 121-22.

Bray R A (1994). The leucaena psyllid. In: *Forage Tree Legumes in Tropical Agriculture* (eds. R C Gutteridge and H M Shelton). CAB International, Oxford. Pp. 283-91.

For proceedings of conferences/symposia etc.

Vivero J L P (2002). Forest is not only wood: the importance of non-wood forest products for the food security of rural households in Ethiopia. In: *Proceedings of the Fourth, Annual Conference forestry society of Ethiopia* 14-15 January 2002, Ethiopia pp 102.

Elangovan A V ,Tyagi P K, Mandal A B and Tyagi P K (2007). Effect of dietary supplementation of stain on egg production performance and egg quality of Japanese quail layers. *Proceedings of XXIV Annual Conference of Indian Poultry Science Association and National Symposium* , 25-27 April, Ludhiana, India, pp. 158 (Abstr.).

For theses

Fayas A M (2003). Viability of self help groups in vegetables and fruit promotion council Keralam- a multidimensional analysis, MSc (Ag.) thesis, Kerala Agricultural University.

For online (internet site) citation

FDA (2008). Effect of the use of antimicrobials in food producing animals on pathogen load: Systematic review of the published literature. www.fda.gov/cvm/antimicrobial/PathRpt.PDF Accessed January 11, 2012.

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